

Selfie Numbers With Binomial Coefficients, Triangular Numbers and Factorial

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Abstract

By *selfie numbers*, we understand that the numbers represented by their own digits by use of certain operations, such as, *basic operations, factorial, square-root, Fibonacci squence, Triangular numbers, etc.* These are by use of single variable. In two variables, we worked with *binomial coefficients type selfie numbers with basic operations, factorial and square-root.* This paper brings *binomial coefficient triangular type selfie numbers, i.e., binomial coefficients and triangular numbers together.* This is done by use of only *basic operations and factorial.* The work is in *digit's order and in reverse order of digits.* The work is up to 5-digits numbers.

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sectionIntroduction

Let’s analyse historical aspects of some numbers:

- (i) Consider the following classical number famous as **printer’s error** (Dudeney, 1917, pp. 379 [5]):

$$2592 := 2^5 \times 9^2 \tag{1}$$

Actually it is not a **printer’s error**, it a represents number in its own digits. The first number similar property is $25 = 5^2$, but is in **reverse order**.

- (ii) Let consider another examples (Madachy, 1966, pp.167-175 [11]):

$$34425 := 3^4 \times 425$$

$$312325 := 31^2 \times 325 \tag{2}$$

Above two are represented their own digits. Moreover, if we multiply by both sides by 10, they continued with property of same digits both sides. These kinds of numbers are famous as **number patterns**. Still there is another number with different property, i.e.,

$$27594 := 73 \times 9 \times 42 = 7 \times 3942 \tag{3}$$

In this case, the two expressions on right side of (4) are with same digits, but the total value is with different digits. This type of study is not under work.

- (iii) Madachy, 1966, pp.167-275 [11] also gave an interesting property with factorials know by **sum of factorials**:

$$1 := 1!$$

$$2 := 2!$$

$$145 := 1! + 4! + 5!$$

$$40585 := 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! \tag{4}$$

Above numbers also have the property of same digits on both sides, but with factorial and addition.

In all the three situations, we observe that we are dealing with numbers those have same digits on both sides, where one side is number another with same digits with certain operations. Based on above idea of numbers, the author studies numbers calling **selfie numbers**, i.e., numbers represented by their own digits by certain operations. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. Some studies in this direction can seen in the works of Friedman [6, 7] and Rose [2, 3, 4].

Below are some examples of **selfie numbers** extending the idea of equation (2) using the operations of addition and subtraction with **factorial**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 145 &= 1! + 4! + 5! & 352797 &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! \\
 733 &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! & 357592 &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! \\
 1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & 357941 &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1! \\
 5177 &:= 5! + 17 + 7! & 361469 &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\
 10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! & 364292 &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\
 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! & 397584 &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\
 80518 &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! & 398173 &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \\
 363239 &:= 36 + 323 + 9! & 408937 &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\
 363269 &:= 363 + 26 + 9! & 715799 &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9! \\
 403199 &:= 40319 + 9! & 720599 &:= -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9! \\
 317489 &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9!
 \end{aligned}$$

0.1 Selfie Numbers with Binomial Coefficients

See below some examples written in both ways, digit's order and reverse order of digits:

$$\begin{aligned}
 6435 &:= C(C(6, 4), 3 + 5) = C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4} + 6) \\
 15504 &:= C(15 + 5, 0! + 4) = C(4 \times 05, 5 \times 1) \\
 42504 &:= C(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4}) = C(4!, -05 + 24) \\
 54264 &:= C(5 + 4^2, C(6, 4)) = C(4! - 6/2, (\sqrt{4} + 5)!) \\
 74613 &:= C(7 \times 4 - 6, 1 \times 3!) = C(3! + 16, (-4 + 7)!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 12650 &:= C(-1 + 26, 5 - 0!) & 28 &:= C(8, 2) \\
 12870 &:= C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7 + 0!) & 792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7) \\
 14950 &:= C(-1 + 4! + \sqrt{9}, 5 - 0!) & 924 &:= C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!) \\
 18564 &:= C(18, (5 - 6 + 4)!) & 2024 &:= C(4!, 2 + (0 \times 2)!) \\
 19448 &:= C(19 - \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4} + 8) & 4845 &:= C(5 \times 4, 8 - 4) \\
 26334 &:= C(2 + C(6, 3), 3 + \sqrt{4}) & 00378 &:= C(C(8, \sqrt{7-3}), 0! + 0!) \\
 43758 &:= C(4! - 3!, 7 - 5 + 8) & 00792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7 - 0! - 0!) \\
 53130 &:= C(5^{3-1}, 3! - 0!) & 00924 &:= C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0! + 0!))
 \end{aligned}$$

The symbol C used for binomial coefficients is given by

$$C(m, r) = \frac{m!}{r! \times (m-r)!}, \quad m \geq r \geq 0, \quad m, r \in \mathbb{N}.$$

For more details refer author's work [22, 31]. Also refer [5, 11] for historical books on numbers. Some initial study on **selfie numbers** are given in [6, 7], and for extensions refer [2, 3, 4]. The last Section 3 is dedicated to the summary of **selfie numbers** done by author with different functions.

There are many ways of representing **selfie numbers**. They can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of basis operations along with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers, binomial coefficients, s-gonal values, centered polygonal numbers**, etc. Below is item-wise details of author's work on **selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order**, and in **reverse order of digits**:

Selfie numbers with:

1. **Basic Operations**; [29];
2. **Factorial**: [26, 27];
3. **Square-root**: [14, 15];
4. **Factorial and Square-root**: [14, 15, 16];
5. **Fibonacci sequence**: [23, 24];
6. **Triangular numbers**: [21, 32, 33];
7. **Fibonacci and Triangular numbers**: [24];
8. **Binomial coefficients**: [22];
9. **Binomial coefficients: Fibonacci**: [31];
10. **Binomial coefficients: Triangular**: [34, 35];
11. **S-gonal numbers**: [17];
12. **Centered Polygonal**: [17];
13. **Concatenation-Type**: [28];
14. **Quadratic numbers**: [25];
15. **Cubic numbers**: [29];

The last Section 3 is dedicated to summary of **selfie numbers** in different situations along with necessary references.

The aim of this paper is to bring **selfie numbers** by use of **binomial coefficients** and **Triangular numbers**. This can be done in three parts. One is by use of **basic operations**, second by use of **factorial** and third by use of **square-root**. This work is concentrated only with **square-root**. Work with basic operations and square-root can be seen in [34, ?].

1 Binomial-Coefficient-Triangular-Factorial-Type Selfie Numbers - Digit's Order

1.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** represented in symmetric way.

$$1330 := C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 0$$

$$1331 := C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 1$$

$$1332 := C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 2$$

$$1333 := C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 3$$

$$1334 := C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 4$$

$$1335 := C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 5$$

$$\begin{aligned}1336 &:= C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 6 \\1337 &:= C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 7 \\1338 &:= C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 8 \\1339 &:= C(T(T(1 \times 3)), 3) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6370 &:= C(T(6), 3) + 7! + 0 \\6371 &:= C(T(6), 3) + 7! + 1 \\6372 &:= C(T(6), 3) + 7! + 2 \\6373 &:= C(T(6), 3) + 7! + 3 \\6374 &:= C(T(6), 3) + 7! + 4 \\6375 &:= C(T(6), 3) + 7! + 5 \\6376 &:= C(T(6), 3) + 7! + 6 \\6377 &:= C(T(6), 3) + 7! + 7 \\6378 &:= C(T(6), 3) + 7! + 8 \\6379 &:= C(T(6), 3) + 7! + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12420 &:= 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 0 \\12421 &:= 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 1 \\12422 &:= 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 2 \\12423 &:= 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 3 \\12424 &:= 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 4 \\12425 &:= 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 5 \\12426 &:= 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 6 \\12427 &:= 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 7 \\12428 &:= 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 8 \\12429 &:= 12 \times T(C(T(4), 2)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}13230 &:= T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 0 \\13231 &:= T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 1 \\13232 &:= T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 2 \\13233 &:= T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 3 \\13234 &:= T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 4 \\13235 &:= T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 5 \\13236 &:= T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 6 \\13237 &:= T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 7 \\13238 &:= T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 8 \\13239 &:= T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}14630 &:= (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 0 \\14631 &:= (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 1 \\14632 &:= (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 2\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}14633 &:= (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 3 \\14634 &:= (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 4 \\14635 &:= (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 5 \\14636 &:= (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 6 \\14637 &:= (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 7 \\14638 &:= (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 8 \\14639 &:= (1 + T(4)) \times C(T(6), 3) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}20240 &:= C((T(2) + 0)!, T(2)) \times T(4) + 0 \\20241 &:= C((T(2) + 0)!, T(2)) \times T(4) + 1 \\20242 &:= C((T(2) + 0)!, T(2)) \times T(4) + 2 \\20243 &:= C((T(2) + 0)!, T(2)) \times T(4) + 3 \\20244 &:= C((T(2) + 0)!, T(2)) \times T(4) + 4 \\20245 &:= C((T(2) + 0)!, T(2)) \times T(4) + 5 \\20246 &:= C((T(2) + 0)!, T(2)) \times T(4) + 6 \\20247 &:= C((T(2) + 0)!, T(2)) \times T(4) + 7 \\20248 &:= C((T(2) + 0)!, T(2)) \times T(4) + 8 \\20249 &:= C((T(2) + 0)!, T(2)) \times T(4) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}20350 &:= (2 \times 0)! + C(T(T(3)), 5) + 0 \\20351 &:= (2 \times 0)! + C(T(T(3)), 5) + 1 \\20352 &:= (2 \times 0)! + C(T(T(3)), 5) + 2 \\20353 &:= (2 \times 0)! + C(T(T(3)), 5) + 3 \\20354 &:= (2 \times 0)! + C(T(T(3)), 5) + 4 \\20355 &:= (2 \times 0)! + C(T(T(3)), 5) + 5 \\20356 &:= (2 \times 0)! + C(T(T(3)), 5) + 6 \\20357 &:= (2 \times 0)! + C(T(T(3)), 5) + 7 \\20358 &:= (2 \times 0)! + C(T(T(3)), 5) + 8 \\20359 &:= (2 \times 0)! + C(T(T(3)), 5) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}21420 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 0 \\21421 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 1 \\21422 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 2 \\21423 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 3 \\21424 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 4 \\21425 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 5 \\21426 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 6 \\21427 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 7 \\21428 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 8 \\21429 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$21930 := T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9, 3)) + 0$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21931 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9,3)) + 1 \\ 21932 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9,3)) + 2 \\ 21933 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9,3)) + 3 \\ 21934 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9,3)) + 4 \\ 21935 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9,3)) + 5 \\ 21936 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9,3)) + 6 \\ 21937 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9,3)) + 7 \\ 21938 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9,3)) + 8 \\ 21939 &:= T(T(2)) \times T(1 + C(9,3)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25620 &:= (2 + 5!) \times C(T(6),2) + 0 \\ 25621 &:= (2 + 5!) \times C(T(6),2) + 1 \\ 25622 &:= (2 + 5!) \times C(T(6),2) + 2 \\ 25623 &:= (2 + 5!) \times C(T(6),2) + 3 \\ 25624 &:= (2 + 5!) \times C(T(6),2) + 4 \\ 25625 &:= (2 + 5!) \times C(T(6),2) + 5 \\ 25626 &:= (2 + 5!) \times C(T(6),2) + 6 \\ 25627 &:= (2 + 5!) \times C(T(6),2) + 7 \\ 25628 &:= (2 + 5!) \times C(T(6),2) + 8 \\ 25629 &:= (2 + 5!) \times C(T(6),2) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25740 &:= C(T(2) \times 5,7) \times 4 + 0 \\ 25741 &:= C(T(2) \times 5,7) \times 4 + 1 \\ 25742 &:= C(T(2) \times 5,7) \times 4 + 2 \\ 25743 &:= C(T(2) \times 5,7) \times 4 + 3 \\ 25744 &:= C(T(2) \times 5,7) \times 4 + 4 \\ 25745 &:= C(T(2) \times 5,7) \times 4 + 5 \\ 25746 &:= C(T(2) \times 5,7) \times 4 + 6 \\ 25747 &:= C(T(2) \times 5,7) \times 4 + 7 \\ 25748 &:= C(T(2) \times 5,7) \times 4 + 8 \\ 25749 &:= C(T(2) \times 5,7) \times 4 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29070 &:= C(T(T(2)!),9 - 0!)/7 + 0 \\ 29071 &:= C(T(T(2)!),9 - 0!)/7 + 1 \\ 29072 &:= C(T(T(2)!),9 - 0!)/7 + 2 \\ 29073 &:= C(T(T(2)!),9 - 0!)/7 + 3 \\ 29074 &:= C(T(T(2)!),9 - 0!)/7 + 4 \\ 29075 &:= C(T(T(2)!),9 - 0!)/7 + 5 \\ 29076 &:= C(T(T(2)!),9 - 0!)/7 + 6 \\ 29077 &:= C(T(T(2)!),9 - 0!)/7 + 7 \\ 29078 &:= C(T(T(2)!),9 - 0!)/7 + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$29079 := C(T(T(2)!),9 - 0!)/7 + 9$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29280 &:= T(2)!! + T(C(9, T(2))) \times 8 + 0 \\ 29281 &:= T(2)!! + T(C(9, T(2))) \times 8 + 1 \\ 29282 &:= T(2)!! + T(C(9, T(2))) \times 8 + 2 \\ 29283 &:= T(2)!! + T(C(9, T(2))) \times 8 + 3 \\ 29284 &:= T(2)!! + T(C(9, T(2))) \times 8 + 4 \\ 29285 &:= T(2)!! + T(C(9, T(2))) \times 8 + 5 \\ 29286 &:= T(2)!! + T(C(9, T(2))) \times 8 + 6 \\ 29287 &:= T(2)!! + T(C(9, T(2))) \times 8 + 7 \\ 29288 &:= T(2)!! + T(C(9, T(2))) \times 8 + 8 \\ 29289 &:= T(2)!! + T(C(9, T(2))) \times 8 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33250 &:= C(T(T(3)),3) \times 25 + 0 \\ 33251 &:= C(T(T(3)),3) \times 25 + 1 \\ 33252 &:= C(T(T(3)),3) \times 25 + 2 \\ 33253 &:= C(T(T(3)),3) \times 25 + 3 \\ 33254 &:= C(T(T(3)),3) \times 25 + 4 \\ 33255 &:= C(T(T(3)),3) \times 25 + 5 \\ 33256 &:= C(T(T(3)),3) \times 25 + 6 \\ 33257 &:= C(T(T(3)),3) \times 25 + 7 \\ 33258 &:= C(T(T(3)),3) \times 25 + 8 \\ 33259 &:= C(T(T(3)),3) \times 25 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34220 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)),T(2)) + 0 \\ 34221 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)),T(2)) + 1 \\ 34222 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)),T(2)) + 2 \\ 34223 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)),T(2)) + 3 \\ 34224 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)),T(2)) + 4 \\ 34225 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)),T(2)) + 5 \\ 34226 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)),T(2)) + 6 \\ 34227 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)),T(2)) + 7 \\ 34228 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)),T(2)) + 8 \\ 34229 &:= T(3 + T(T(4))) \times C(T(T(2)),T(2)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35280 &:= T(3)! \times C(T(5),2) - 8! + 0 \\ 35281 &:= T(3)! \times C(T(5),2) - 8! + 1 \\ 35282 &:= T(3)! \times C(T(5),2) - 8! + 2 \\ 35283 &:= T(3)! \times C(T(5),2) - 8! + 3 \\ 35284 &:= T(3)! \times C(T(5),2) - 8! + 4 \\ 35285 &:= T(3)! \times C(T(5),2) - 8! + 5 \\ 35286 &:= T(3)! \times C(T(5),2) - 8! + 6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35287 &:= T(3)! \times C(T(5), 2) - 8! + 7 \\ 35288 &:= T(3)! \times C(T(5), 2) - 8! + 8 \\ 35289 &:= T(3)! \times C(T(5), 2) - 8! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38760 &:= C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 0 \\ 38761 &:= C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 1 \\ 38762 &:= C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 2 \\ 38763 &:= C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 3 \\ 38764 &:= C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 4 \\ 38765 &:= C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 5 \\ 38766 &:= C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 6 \\ 38767 &:= C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 7 \\ 38768 &:= C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 8 \\ 38769 &:= C(T(3) \times 8 - T(7), 6) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 40950 &:= T(4! + 0!) \times C(9, 5) + 0 \\ 40951 &:= T(4! + 0!) \times C(9, 5) + 1 \\ 40952 &:= T(4! + 0!) \times C(9, 5) + 2 \\ 40953 &:= T(4! + 0!) \times C(9, 5) + 3 \\ 40954 &:= T(4! + 0!) \times C(9, 5) + 4 \\ 40955 &:= T(4! + 0!) \times C(9, 5) + 5 \\ 40956 &:= T(4! + 0!) \times C(9, 5) + 6 \\ 40957 &:= T(4! + 0!) \times C(9, 5) + 7 \\ 40958 &:= T(4! + 0!) \times C(9, 5) + 8 \\ 40959 &:= T(4! + 0!) \times C(9, 5) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42420 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) - 4) \times T(T(T(2))) + 0 \\ 42421 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) - 4) \times T(T(T(2))) + 1 \\ 42422 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) - 4) \times T(T(T(2))) + 2 \\ 42423 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) - 4) \times T(T(T(2))) + 3 \\ 42424 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) - 4) \times T(T(T(2))) + 4 \\ 42425 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) - 4) \times T(T(T(2))) + 5 \\ 42426 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) - 4) \times T(T(T(2))) + 6 \\ 42427 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) - 4) \times T(T(T(2))) + 7 \\ 42428 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) - 4) \times T(T(T(2))) + 8 \\ 42429 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) - 4) \times T(T(T(2))) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42480 &:= C(4!, 2) \times T(4!) - 8! + 0 \\ 42481 &:= C(4!, 2) \times T(4!) - 8! + 1 \\ 42482 &:= C(4!, 2) \times T(4!) - 8! + 2 \\ 42483 &:= C(4!, 2) \times T(4!) - 8! + 3 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42484 &:= C(4!, 2) \times T(4!) - 8! + 4 \\ 42485 &:= C(4!, 2) \times T(4!) - 8! + 5 \\ 42486 &:= C(4!, 2) \times T(4!) - 8! + 6 \\ 42487 &:= C(4!, 2) \times T(4!) - 8! + 7 \\ 42488 &:= C(4!, 2) \times T(4!) - 8! + 8 \\ 42489 &:= C(4!, 2) \times T(4!) - 8! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42570 &:= C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 0 \\ 42571 &:= C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 1 \\ 42572 &:= C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 2 \\ 42573 &:= C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 3 \\ 42574 &:= C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 4 \\ 42575 &:= C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 5 \\ 42576 &:= C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 6 \\ 42577 &:= C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 7 \\ 42578 &:= C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 8 \\ 42579 &:= C(T(4), 2) \times T(T(5) + T(7)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42630 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) + 6) \times T(T(3)) + 0 \\ 42631 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) + 6) \times T(T(3)) + 1 \\ 42632 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) + 6) \times T(T(3)) + 2 \\ 42633 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) + 6) \times T(T(3)) + 3 \\ 42634 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) + 6) \times T(T(3)) + 4 \\ 42635 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) + 6) \times T(T(3)) + 5 \\ 42636 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) + 6) \times T(T(3)) + 6 \\ 42637 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) + 6) \times T(T(3)) + 7 \\ 42638 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) + 6) \times T(T(3)) + 8 \\ 42639 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) + 6) \times T(T(3)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43450 &:= T(43) + C(4!, 5) + 0 \\ 43451 &:= T(43) + C(4!, 5) + 1 \\ 43452 &:= T(43) + C(4!, 5) + 2 \\ 43453 &:= T(43) + C(4!, 5) + 3 \\ 43454 &:= T(43) + C(4!, 5) + 4 \\ 43455 &:= T(43) + C(4!, 5) + 5 \\ 43456 &:= T(43) + C(4!, 5) + 6 \\ 43457 &:= T(43) + C(4!, 5) + 7 \\ 43458 &:= T(43) + C(4!, 5) + 8 \\ 43459 &:= T(43) + C(4!, 5) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44100 &:= C(T(4), 4)^{1+0!} + 0 \\ 44101 &:= C(T(4), 4)^{1+0!} + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}44102 &:= C(T(4), 4)^{1+0!} + 2 \\44103 &:= C(T(4), 4)^{1+0!} + 3 \\44104 &:= C(T(4), 4)^{1+0!} + 4 \\44105 &:= C(T(4), 4)^{1+0!} + 5 \\44106 &:= C(T(4), 4)^{1+0!} + 6 \\44107 &:= C(T(4), 4)^{1+0!} + 7 \\44108 &:= C(T(4), 4)^{1+0!} + 8 \\44109 &:= C(T(4), 4)^{1+0!} + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}45380 &:= T(T(4)) + C(T(5), T(3)) + 8! + 0 \\45381 &:= T(T(4)) + C(T(5), T(3)) + 8! + 1 \\45382 &:= T(T(4)) + C(T(5), T(3)) + 8! + 2 \\45383 &:= T(T(4)) + C(T(5), T(3)) + 8! + 3 \\45384 &:= T(T(4)) + C(T(5), T(3)) + 8! + 4 \\45385 &:= T(T(4)) + C(T(5), T(3)) + 8! + 5 \\45386 &:= T(T(4)) + C(T(5), T(3)) + 8! + 6 \\45387 &:= T(T(4)) + C(T(5), T(3)) + 8! + 7 \\45388 &:= T(T(4)) + C(T(5), T(3)) + 8! + 8 \\45389 &:= T(T(4)) + C(T(5), T(3)) + 8! + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}48620 &:= C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 0 \\48621 &:= C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 1 \\48622 &:= C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 2 \\48623 &:= C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 3 \\48624 &:= C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 4 \\48625 &:= C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 5 \\48626 &:= C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 6 \\48627 &:= C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 7 \\48628 &:= C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 8 \\48629 &:= C(T(4) + 8, 6 + T(2)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54360 &:= 5! - 4! + C(T(T(3)), 6) + 0 \\54361 &:= 5! - 4! + C(T(T(3)), 6) + 1 \\54362 &:= 5! - 4! + C(T(T(3)), 6) + 2 \\54363 &:= 5! - 4! + C(T(T(3)), 6) + 3 \\54364 &:= 5! - 4! + C(T(T(3)), 6) + 4 \\54365 &:= 5! - 4! + C(T(T(3)), 6) + 5 \\54366 &:= 5! - 4! + C(T(T(3)), 6) + 6 \\54367 &:= 5! - 4! + C(T(T(3)), 6) + 7 \\54368 &:= 5! - 4! + C(T(T(3)), 6) + 8\end{aligned}$$

$$54369 := 5! - 4! + C(T(T(3)), 6) + 9$$

$$\begin{aligned}55320 &:= 5! \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 0 \\55321 &:= 5! \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 1 \\55322 &:= 5! \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 2 \\55323 &:= 5! \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 3 \\55324 &:= 5! \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 4 \\55325 &:= 5! \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 5 \\55326 &:= 5! \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 6 \\55327 &:= 5! \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 7 \\55328 &:= 5! \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 8 \\55329 &:= 5! \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(2))) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}63420 &:= T(C(6, 3)) \times (T(4!) + 2) + 0 \\63421 &:= T(C(6, 3)) \times (T(4!) + 2) + 1 \\63422 &:= T(C(6, 3)) \times (T(4!) + 2) + 2 \\63423 &:= T(C(6, 3)) \times (T(4!) + 2) + 3 \\63424 &:= T(C(6, 3)) \times (T(4!) + 2) + 4 \\63425 &:= T(C(6, 3)) \times (T(4!) + 2) + 5 \\63426 &:= T(C(6, 3)) \times (T(4!) + 2) + 6 \\63427 &:= T(C(6, 3)) \times (T(4!) + 2) + 7 \\63428 &:= T(C(6, 3)) \times (T(4!) + 2) + 8 \\63429 &:= T(C(6, 3)) \times (T(4!) + 2) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}65520 &:= 6!/5 \times C(T(5), T(2)) + 0 \\65521 &:= 6!/5 \times C(T(5), T(2)) + 1 \\65522 &:= 6!/5 \times C(T(5), T(2)) + 2 \\65523 &:= 6!/5 \times C(T(5), T(2)) + 3 \\65524 &:= 6!/5 \times C(T(5), T(2)) + 4 \\65525 &:= 6!/5 \times C(T(5), T(2)) + 5 \\65526 &:= 6!/5 \times C(T(5), T(2)) + 6 \\65527 &:= 6!/5 \times C(T(5), T(2)) + 7 \\65528 &:= 6!/5 \times C(T(5), T(2)) + 8 \\65529 &:= 6!/5 \times C(T(5), T(2)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}67830 &:= C(T(6), 7)/T(8) \times T(T(3)) + 0 \\67831 &:= C(T(6), 7)/T(8) \times T(T(3)) + 1 \\67832 &:= C(T(6), 7)/T(8) \times T(T(3)) + 2 \\67833 &:= C(T(6), 7)/T(8) \times T(T(3)) + 3 \\67834 &:= C(T(6), 7)/T(8) \times T(T(3)) + 4 \\67835 &:= C(T(6), 7)/T(8) \times T(T(3)) + 5 \\67836 &:= C(T(6), 7)/T(8) \times T(T(3)) + 6\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 67837 &:= C(T(6),7)/T(8) \times T(T(3)) + 7 \\ 67838 &:= C(T(6),7)/T(8) \times T(T(3)) + 8 \\ 67839 &:= C(T(6),7)/T(8) \times T(T(3)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 73990 &:= 7! - C(T(T(3)),9) + 9! + 0 \\ 73991 &:= 7! - C(T(T(3)),9) + 9! + 1 \\ 73992 &:= 7! - C(T(T(3)),9) + 9! + 2 \\ 73993 &:= 7! - C(T(T(3)),9) + 9! + 3 \\ 73994 &:= 7! - C(T(T(3)),9) + 9! + 4 \\ 73995 &:= 7! - C(T(T(3)),9) + 9! + 5 \\ 73996 &:= 7! - C(T(T(3)),9) + 9! + 6 \\ 73997 &:= 7! - C(T(T(3)),9) + 9! + 7 \\ 73998 &:= 7! - C(T(T(3)),9) + 9! + 8 \\ 73999 &:= 7! - C(T(T(3)),9) + 9! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 84420 &:= 8! + C(T(4),4)^2 + 0 \\ 84421 &:= 8! + C(T(4),4)^2 + 1 \\ 84422 &:= 8! + C(T(4),4)^2 + 2 \\ 84423 &:= 8! + C(T(4),4)^2 + 3 \\ 84424 &:= 8! + C(T(4),4)^2 + 4 \\ 84425 &:= 8! + C(T(4),4)^2 + 5 \\ 84426 &:= 8! + C(T(4),4)^2 + 6 \\ 84427 &:= 8! + C(T(4),4)^2 + 7 \\ 84428 &:= 8! + C(T(4),4)^2 + 8 \\ 84429 &:= 8! + C(T(4),4)^2 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 86240 &:= C(8,6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 0 \\ 86241 &:= C(8,6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 1 \\ 86242 &:= C(8,6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 2 \\ 86243 &:= C(8,6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 3 \\ 86244 &:= C(8,6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 4 \\ 86245 &:= C(8,6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 5 \\ 86246 &:= C(8,6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 6 \\ 86247 &:= C(8,6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 7 \\ 86248 &:= C(8,6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$86249 := C(8,6) \times 2 \times T(T(T(4))) + 9$$

$$\begin{aligned} 95850 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 0 \\ 95851 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 1 \\ 95852 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 2 \\ 95853 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 3 \\ 95854 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 4 \\ 95855 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 5 \\ 95856 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 6 \\ 95857 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 7 \\ 95858 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 8 \\ 95859 &:= (-T(9) + C(T(5),8)) \times T(5) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 96390 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 0 \\ 96391 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 1 \\ 96392 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 2 \\ 96393 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 3 \\ 96394 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 4 \\ 96395 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 5 \\ 96396 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 6 \\ 96397 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 7 \\ 96398 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 8 \\ 96399 &:= T(C(9,6)) \times 3 \times 9 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98280 &:= T(T(9)) \times C(8,T(2)) + 8! + 0 \\ 98281 &:= T(T(9)) \times C(8,T(2)) + 8! + 1 \\ 98282 &:= T(T(9)) \times C(8,T(2)) + 8! + 2 \\ 98283 &:= T(T(9)) \times C(8,T(2)) + 8! + 3 \\ 98284 &:= T(T(9)) \times C(8,T(2)) + 8! + 4 \\ 98285 &:= T(T(9)) \times C(8,T(2)) + 8! + 5 \\ 98286 &:= T(T(9)) \times C(8,T(2)) + 8! + 6 \\ 98287 &:= T(T(9)) \times C(8,T(2)) + 8! + 7 \\ 98288 &:= T(T(9)) \times C(8,T(2)) + 8! + 8 \\ 98289 &:= T(T(9)) \times C(8,T(2)) + 8! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

1.2 General Representations

Below are selfie numbers in a general way. The results are up to 7-digits numbers.

$$231 := T(T(C((2 \times 3),1)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 241 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(C(4,1))) \\ 246 &:= (C(T(T(2)),4) + T(T(6))) \\ 372 &:= -((T(3) - C(T(7),2))) \\ 427 &:= (T(C(4,2)) + T(T(7))) \\ 435 &:= T(((C(4,3))! + (5))) \\ 462 &:= C(-((T(4) - T(6))),T(T(2))) \\ 496 &:= T((C(T(4),9) + T(6))) \\ 525 &:= (C(T(5),2) \times 5) \\ 687 &:= (T(6) + T(T(C(8,7)))) \\ 741 &:= T((T(7) + T(C(4,1)))) \\ \\ 1081 &:= T((C(10,8) + 1)) \\ 1128 &:= T((C(11,2) - 8)) \\ 1176 &:= T(((C(1,1) + 7) \times 6)) \\ 1224 &:= (C(12, T(T(2))) + T(4!)) \\ 1288 &:= (1 + C((T(T(T(2))) - 8), 8)) \\ 1364 &:= (-1 + C(-((T(3) - T(6))), 4)) \\ 1387 &:= ((1 + (T(3))!) + T(T(C(8,7)))) \\ 1483 &:= ((-1 + T(T(T(4)))) - C(8,3)) \\ 1533 &:= ((-1 + T(T(C(5,3)))) - T(3)) \\ 1535 &:= (T(T(C((1 \times 5), 3))) - 5) \\ 1561 &:= (T(T(T(-((1 - 5)))))) + T(C(6,1)) \\ 1826 &:= ((-1 + T(C(8, T(2)))) + T(T(6))) \\ 1998 &:= (T((1 + C(9,9))) \times T(T(8))) \\ 2022 &:= (C(((T(2) + 0!))!), T(2)) - 2) \\ 2024 &:= C(((T(2) + 0!))!, T(-((2 - 4)))) \\ 2034 &:= (C(((T(2) + 0!))!, 3) + T(4)) \\ 2069 &:= (C(((T(2) + 0!))!), T(6)) + T(9)) \\ 2233 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) + T((T(T(3)) + T(T(3)))))) \\ 2268 &:= ((C(T(2), 2) \times T(6)) \times T(8)) \\ 2278 &:= T(((C(T(2), 2) + T(7)) + T(8))) \\ 2284 &:= (T(T(2)) + T(-((T(2) - (C(8, 4)))))) \\ 2324 &:= (C(((-2) + T(3))!), T(2)) + T(4!)) \\ 2353 &:= -((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (C(T(T(3)), T(5))/T(T(3)))))) \\ 2394 &:= ((-2) + T(T(3))) \times C(9, 4)) \\ 2395 &:= (-C(T(T(2)), 3) + T((T(T(9))/T(5)))) \\ 2427 &:= (-((T(2) - C(4!, T(2)))) + T(T(7))) \\ 2431 &:= ((T(T(2)))! + T((T(T(4)) + C(3, 1)))) \\ 2436 &:= (C((T(2) + T(4)), T(3)) + 6!) \\ 2470 &:= -((C(T(T(2)), 4) - T(70))) \\ 2484 &:= ((T(2) - (4)) + T(C(8, 4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2539 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))/T(T(3))) - T(9)) \\ 2541 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times ((C(5,4)! + 1)) \\ 2584 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))/T(T(T((8/4)))) \\ 2600 &:= C(26, T((0! + 0!)) \\ 2624 &:= (C(26, T(2)) + 4!) \\ 2629 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))), 6)/T(T(T(2)))) + T(9)) \\ 2646 &:= (C((T(2) + (6)), 4) \times T(6)) \\ 2922 &:= (C((T(2) \times 9), T(2)) - T(2)) \\ 2923 &:= (-2) + C((9 \times T(2)), 3)) \\ 2925 &:= C((T(2) \times 9), -((2 - 5))) \\ 2928 &:= (2 + T((C(9, T(2)) - 8)) \\ 2931 &:= (T(T((2 + 9))) + (T(C(3, 1)))!) \\ 2946 &:= (C((T(2) \times 9), 4!) + T(6)) \\ 2955 &:= -(((T(2) + T(9)) - C(T(5), 5))) \\ 2997 &:= (T(2) \times (T(T(9)) - C(9, 7))) \\ 3003 &:= C(T((T(3) - 0!)), -((0! - T(3)))) \\ 3272 &:= -(((T(3) - 2) - C(T(7), T(2)))) \\ 3273 &:= (-C(3, 2) + C(T(7), 3)) \\ 3324 &:= (3 + T((C(3, 2)^4)) \\ 3325 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), 3)/(-2)) \times (-5)) \\ 3328 &:= (C(T(T(3)), 3) - (-T(2) \times T(T(8)))) \\ 3353 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) - (C(T(T(3)), 5)))/(-T(3))) \\ 3432 &:= (C((3 + T(4)), T(3)) \times 2) \\ 3462 &:= ((C(T(3), 4) \times T(T(6))) - T(2)) \\ 3596 &:= (T(T(3)) - (-5 - T(C(9, 6)))) \\ 3599 &:= (((T(3))! \times 5) - C(9, 9)) \\ 3696 &:= ((T(3) \times T(6)) + T(C(9, 6))) \\ 3723 &:= ((T(3))! + C((7 \times 2), T(3))) \\ 3772 &:= (T((3 + T(7))) + C(T(7), T(2))) \\ 3783 &:= ((3^7) + T(C(8, 3))) \\ 3844 &:= (-T(3) + (C(8, 4) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 3963 &:= (3 \times (-9) + C(T(6), 3)) \\ 4218 &:= (C(4, 2) \times T((1 + T(8)))) \\ 4241 &:= (T(T(4)) + T(T((T(2) + T(C(4, 1)))))) \\ 4284 &:= ((T(C(T(4), 2)) + T(8)) \times 4) \\ 4359 &:= (C((T(4) + T(3)), 5) - 9) \\ 4378 &:= ((C(4, 3) + 7!) - T(T(8))) \\ 4410 &:= (C(T(4), 4) \times T(T(T((1 + 0!)))) \\ 4422 &:= (2 \times T(C((2 + T(4)), T(4)))) \\ 4434 &:= ((C(T(4), 4) \times T(T(3))) + (4!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4535 &:= ((T(4) \times C(T(5), 3)) - T(5)) \\4536 &:= (C(T(4), 5) \times (3 \times 6)) \\4847 &:= (-4) + T((C(8, 4) + T(7))) \\4976 &:= -((T(T(4)) - (-9) + (C(7, 6)!)) \\5002 &:= (C(T(5), T(T((0! + 0!)))) - T(2)) \\5005 &:= C(T(5), (0! + 05)) \\5026 &:= (C(T(5), T(T(02))) + (T(6))) \\5035 &:= (-5) + ((0! + C(T(3), 5))!) \\5125 &:= (C(T(5), T((1 + 2))) + 5!) \\5176 &:= (T((T(5) + 1)) + (C(7, 6))!) \\5228 &:= ((C(T(5), T(T(2))) + T(T(T(T(2)))) - 8) \\5233 &:= ((C(T(5), T(T(2))) + T(T(T(3)))) - 3) \\5246 &:= ((C(T(5), T(T(2))) + T(4)) + T(T(6))) \\5250 &:= (C(T(5), 2) \times 50) \\5304 &:= ((C(T(5), T(3)) - 0!) + T(4!)) \\5305 &:= (C(T(5), T(3)) + T((-((0! - (5)))))) \\5328 &:= ((C(5, 3) - 2) \times T(T(8))) \\5356 &:= (C(T(5), T(3)) + T((5 + T(6)))) \\5375 &:= ((C(T(5), 3) + 7!) - 5!) \\5400 &:= (5! \times C(T(4), (0! + 0!))) \\5424 &:= ((5! \times C(T(4), 2)) + 4!) \\5444 &:= ((C(T(5), 4) - (4)) \times 4) \\5445 &:= ((C(T(5), 4) \times 4) - T(5)) \\5543 &:= (-C(5, 5) - (-4!) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\5634 &:= ((-5!) - T(T(6))) + C(T(T(3)), 4) \\5635 &:= (C(T(5), 6) + T(35)) \\5671 &:= (C(T(5), 6) + T(T((7 + 1)))) \\5678 &:= ((C(T(5), 6) + (7)) + T(T(8))) \\5715 &:= (C(T(5), 7) - ((1 + 5))!) \\5716 &:= ((C(T(5), 7) + 1) - 6!) \\5835 &:= ((C(T(5), 8) - (T(3))!) + (5!)) \\5964 &:= -((T((T(5) - 9)) - (C(T(6), 4)))) \\5979 &:= -((T(5) + (T(C(9, 7)) \times (-9)))) \\6162 &:= (T(T((C(6, 1) + 6))) \times 2) \\6216 &:= (C(T(6), (T(2) + 1)) + T(T(6))) \\6291 &:= ((-T(6) + (T(T(2))))!) \times C(9, 1) \\6358 &:= ((T(T(6)))/(-3) + C(T(5), 8)) \\6370 &:= (C(T(6), 3) + ((7 + 0))!) \\6524 &:= ((-T(6) + C(T(5), T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\6545 &:= ((-T(T(C(6, 5)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 5\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6657 &:= ((T(T(6)) + (C(6,5))!) \times 7) \\ 6853 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times 8) + (C(T(5), T(3)))) \\ 6975 &:= (T(-((6 - C(9,7)))) \times T(5)) \\ 7227 &:= (7! + (C(T(2), 2)^7)) \\ 7315 &:= C((T(7) - T(3)), -((1 - 5))) \\ 7546 &:= (C((7 + T(5)), 4) + T(T(6))) \\ 8442 &:= (8! - (C(4!, 4) \times T(2))) \\ 8526 &:= (T((C(8,5)/2)) \times T(6)) \\ 8544 &:= ((C(8,5) + T(4!)) \times 4!) \\ 8658 &:= (T(T(8)) \times (T(C(6,5)) - 8)) \\ 8673 &:= ((T(C(8,6)) + (7)) \times T(T(3))) \\ 8991 &:= ((T(8) - T(T(9))) \times (-C(9,1))) \\ 9399 &:= (C(9,3) + (9 \times T(T(9)))) \\ 9856 &:= (T(98) + C(T(5), 6)) \\ 9981 &:= ((9 \times T(T(9))) + T(T(C(8,1)))) \\ \\ 10164 &:= (((10 - 1))! - C(T(6), T(4))) \\ 10398 &:= (T((1 + 0!)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(C(9,8)))) \\ 10638 &:= ((-1) - 0!) + (C(T(6), 3) \times 8) \\ 10644 &:= ((T((1 + 0!)) \times 6) + C(4!, 4)) \\ 10692 &:= (T((1 + 0!)) \times (-6 + T(C(9, T(2)))))) \\ 10773 &:= ((T(T(10)) \times 7) - C(7, T(3))) \\ 10962 &:= ((-1) + T((0! + (C(9,6)))) \times T(2)) \\ 11223 &:= (T((T(11) + C(T(T(2)), T(2)))) \times 3) \\ 11437 &:= -((T((1 + 1)) - C((T(4) + T(3)), 7))) \\ 11439 &:= (-1) + C((T((1 \times 4)) + T(3)), 9) \\ 11440 &:= C(((1 + 1)^4), (T(4) - 0!)) \\ 11625 &:= -((T((1 + 1)) - C((T(6) - 2), 5))) \\ 11628 &:= C((-((1 + 1)) + T(6)), -((T(2) - 8))) \\ 11672 &:= ((1 + C(16, 7)) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 11773 &:= (-1) + ((1 + T(7)) \times T(T(C(7, T(3)))))) \\ 11835 &:= (T(T((C(1, 1) + 8))) + ((T(3))! \times T(5))) \\ 11988 &:= (((C(1, 1) + 9) + 8) \times T(T(8))) \\ 12143 &:= (-1) + (T((2 + 1)) \times C(4!, 3)) \\ 12159 &:= ((-1) + (T(T(2)))!) + (C((1 + T(5)), 9)) \\ 12225 &:= ((-1) + C((T(T(2)) \times T(2)), T(2)) \times T(5)) \\ 12236 &:= ((C(((1 + T(2)))!, T(T(2))) \times T(T(3)))/T(T(6))) \\ 12321 &:= ((-1 + T(T(2)))! - T(T(T(3))))^{C(2,1)} \\ 12368 &:= (C((-1) + (T(2) \times T(3))), 6) - 8 \\ 12586 &:= (-((1 - (2^5))) \times T(C(8, 6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12644 &:= -((T((1+2)) - C((T(6) + (4)), 4))) \\12646 &:= ((-1) - T(2)) + C((T(6) + (4)), T(6)) \\12665 &:= (C(-((1-26)), T(6)) + T(5)) \\12683 &:= -((T((1+T(T(T(2)))))) + (T(T(6)) \times (-C(8,3)))) \\12726 &:= (((1+T(2)))! - T(C(7, T(2)))) \times (-T(6)) \\12752 &:= (12 + (T(7) \times C(T(5), T(2)))) \\12835 &:= (1 + (T(2) \times T(-((C(8, T(3)) - 5!)))) \\12885 &:= (C(((1 \times 2) \times 8), 8) + T(5)) \\12936 &:= (C(((1-2) + 9), 3) \times T(T(6))) \\12937 &:= (1 + (C((2+9), T(3)) \times T(7))) \\12982 &:= ((1 + T(T(T(2)))) - (9!/(-C(8,2)))) \\13104 &:= (C(T((1+T(3))), T((1+0!))) \times 4) \\13273 &:= (1 + (T(T(3)) \times (2 + T(C(7,3)))) \\13287 &:= ((1 - C(T(T(3))), T(2)) - (-T(8)) \times T(T(7))) \\13290 &:= ((1 - C(T(T(3))), T(2)) \times (-9 - 0!)) \\13300 &:= (T((1+3)) \times C(T(T(3)), T((0! + 0!)))) \\13310 &:= ((-1) - C(T(T(3)), 3)) \times (-10) \\13334 &:= ((-1) - T(T(T(3)))) - (C(T(T(3)), T(3))/(-4)) \\13427 &:= ((13 \times T(C(T(4), 2))) - (T(7))) \\13546 &:= (1 + (T(T(3)) \times (C(T(5), 4) - 6!))) \\13574 &:= (1 + ((C(T(T(3))), T(5)) + (T(7)))/4) \\13648 &:= ((C(13, 6) - T(4)) \times 8) \\13671 &:= (T((-1) + (3 \times T(6)))) \times C(7, 1) \\13734 &:= (T(T((1 \times 3))) \times (T(C(7, 3)) + 4!)) \\13754 &:= ((-1) + (3 \times 7!)) - C(T(5), 4) \\13769 &:= -((T(13) - (C(T(7), 6) - 9!)) \\13922 &:= (-1) + (T(T(3)) \times (T(C(9, 2)) - T(2))) \\13973 &:= (-13) + (T(C(9, 7)) \times T(T(3))) \\13976 &:= -((T((1+3)) - (T(C(9, 7)) \times T(6)))) \\13978 &:= ((T(T((1 \times 3))) \times T(C(9, 7))) - 8) \\13985 &:= (-1) + (T(T(3)) \times T(C(9, (-8) + T(5)))) \\13987 &:= (1 + (T(T(3)) \times T(C(C(9, 8), 7)))) \\14167 &:= (-1) - (C(4!, T((1 \times 6))) \times (-7)) \\14168 &:= (C((-1) + 4!), (-1) + T(6)) \times 8) \\14248 &:= ((C((-1) + 4!), T(2)) + T(4)) \times 8) \\14293 &:= (1 + (4 \times (T(2) + T(C(9, 3)))) \\14364 &:= (C((-1) + T(4)), 3) \times T((-6) + 4!)) \\14385 &:= ((-1) - (C(T(4), 3) \times (-8))) \times T(5) \\14391 &:= ((T((1 + T(T(4)))) + 3) \times C(9, 1)) \\14425 &:= ((1 + 4!) + (C(T(4), T(2)) \times 5!))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}14454 &:= (-1) + (((T(4))!/C(T(4),5) + T(T(4)))) \\14467 &:= ((-1) + T(4!)) - (C(4!, T(6)) \times (-7)) \\14535 &:= (C((14 + 5), 3) \times T(5)) \\14558 &:= ((1 - C(T(4), 5)) \times (-58)) \\14565 &:= ((-1) + (C(T(4), 5) + 6!)) \times T(5) \\14642 &:= 1 + (-T(4) + T(6))^{C(4, T(2))} \\14648 &:= ((1 + T((4 \times C(6, 4)))) \times 8) \\14663 &:= (-1) + ((T(T(4)) \times (-6!)) + (C(T(6), T(3)))) \\14665 &:= (1 + ((T(T(4)) \times (-6!)) + (C(T(6), T(5)))) \\14696 &:= ((C(T(T(-(1 - 4))), 6) - 9!)/(-T(6))) \\14783 &:= (-1) + (T((4 + T(7))) \times C(8, T(3))) \\14859 &:= ((T(T((1 \times 4))) + T(C(8, 5))) \times 9) \\14875 &:= ((C(14, 8) - T(7)) \times 5) \\14931 &:= (T(T(-(1 - 4))) \times (-9) + (T(C(3, 1)))!) \\14943 &:= ((C(T((1 + 4)), 9) - 4!) \times 3) \\15012 &:= ((-1) + C(T(5), T(T((0! + 1)))) \times T(2)) \\15264 &:= ((1 + C(T(5), 2)) \times (6 \times 4!)) \\15295 &:= ((C(-(1 - 5))!, T(2)) + T(T(9))) \times 5) \\15385 &:= ((1 - 5!) + C(((T(3))!/T(8)), 5)) \\15436 &:= (1 + ((T(C(5, 4)) + (T(3))!) \times T(6))) \\15459 &:= (C(((1 \times 5) \times 4), 5) - T(9)) \\15479 &:= (-1) + (5! \times (C(T(4), 7) + 9)) \\15497 &:= ((C((1 + 5), 4) \times T(T(9))) - (T(7))) \\15503 &:= (-1) + C((5 + T(5)), -(0! - T(3))) \\15505 &:= (1 + C((5 + T(5)), 05)) \\15524 &:= (-1) + (T(5) \times T((T(C(5, 2)) - T(4)))) \\15525 &:= (T(C(((1 \times 5) + 5), 2)) \times T(5)) \\15576 &:= (((-1) + C(T(5), 5)) - T(T(7))) \times 6) \\15631 &:= (((1 \times 5)^6) + T(C(3, 1))) \\15682 &:= ((1 + (5^6)) + C(8, T(2))) \\15876 &:= ((T((1 + 5)) \times T(C(8, 7))) \times T(6)) \\15939 &:= (C((-1) + T(5) + 9), 3) \times 9) \\15968 &:= ((C((-1) + T(5)), 9) - (6)) \times 8) \\15974 &:= (((-1 - 5))! \times T(C(9, 7))) - T(4)) \\16225 &:= ((1 + 6!) + C(C(T(T(2)), T(2)), 5)) \\16355 &:= ((C(T((1 + 6)), 3) - (5)) \times 5) \\16456 &:= ((1 + T(C(6, 4))) \times T((-5) + T(6))) \\16463 &:= (-1) + ((6! + C(4!, T(6))) \times T(3)) \\16528 &:= ((C((1 + T(6)), T(5))/T(2)) - 8!) \\16539 &:= (C((-1) + T(6)), (5 \times 3)) + T(T(9)))\end{aligned}$$

16549 := ((C((-1) + T(6)), 5) + T(4)) + T(T(9)))
16583 := ((-1) - 6!) × (5 - C(8, T(3)))
16594 := ((C((-1) + T(6)), 5) + T(T(9))) + T(T(4)))
16653 := ((1 + C((6 + 6), 5)) × T(T(3)))
16842 := ((T(16) + T(T(8))) × T(C(4, 2)))
17009 := (-1) + (C(T(7), (0! + 0!)) × T(9))
17024 := (C((17 + 0!), T(T(2))) - T(T(T(4))))
17136 := (C((17 + 1), 3) × T(6))
17430 := (C((-1) + T(7)), 4) - ((T(3) - 0!))!
17437 := ((T(C((1 + 7), 4)) + T(3)) × 7)
17454 := ((C((-1) + T(7)), 4) - 5!) + 4!
17475 := (C((-1) + T(7)), 4) - 75
17495 := (C((-1) + T(7)), 4) - T(T((9 - 5)))
17496 := (C((-1) + T(7)), 4) - ((9 × 6))
17529 := ((C(17, 5) × T(2)) - T(T(9)))
17545 := (C(((-1) + T(T(7))) / T(5)), 4) - 5
17550 := C((-1) + T(7)), ((5! / 5) - 0!)
17568 := (((-1) - T(C(7, 5))) + 6!) × T(8)
17653 := -((T((1 + T(7))) + (C(T(6), T(5)) / (-3))))
17723 := (-1) + (T(7) × (T(C(7, T(2))) + 3))
17862 := (((-1) + T(7)) × T(T(8))) - T(C(6, 2))
17935 := ((17 + T(C(9, 3))) × 5)
17976 := (((-1) + T(7)) × T(C(9, 7))) - (6)
18243 := ((1 + 8) × (T(2) + C(4!, 3)))
18264 := (C(18, T(T(2))) - (T((6 × 4)))
18292 := ((1 + (T(C(8, 2)) × T(9))) + T(T(T(2))))
18294 := ((T(C((1 × 8), 2)) × T(9)) + 4!)
18297 := (-1) + ((T(C(8, 2)) × T(9)) + T(7))
18333 := (C(18, T(3)) - T(T((3 + 3))))
18336 := ((C(18, T(3)) + 3) - T(T(6)))
18343 := ((C(18, T(3)) + T(4)) - T(T(T(3))))
18344 := (C(18, T(3)) - (4 × T(T(4))))
18354 := (C(18, T(3)) - T((5 × 4)))
18375 := (T((C((1 × 8), 3) - 7)) × T(5))
18486 := (T((C((1 × 8), 4) + 8)) × 6)
18519 := (C(18, (5 + 1)) - T(9))
18525 := ((1 + C(8, 5)) × T(25))
18528 := (C(18, T((5 - 2))) - T(8))
18536 := -((T(-((1 - 8))) - C((T(5) + 3), 6)))
18549 := ((C(18, T(5)) × 4!) - T(T(9)))

$$\begin{aligned} 18554 &:= (C(18, T((T(5)/5))) - T(4)) \\ 18557 &:= (C(18, T((T(5)/5))) - 7) \\ 18558 &:= (C(18, 5) - (-T(5) \times T(T(8)))) \\ 18562 &:= (C(18, -(T(5) - T(6)))) - 2) \\ 18563 &:= (-1) + C(((8 - 5) \times 6), T(3)) \\ 18564 &:= C(18, T(((5 - 6) + 4))) \\ 18574 &:= (C(18, (5 + 7)) + T(4)) \\ 18609 &:= (C(18, 6) + T(09)) \\ 18619 &:= (C(18, 6) + T((1 + 9))) \\ 18642 &:= (C(18, 6) + T((4!/2))) \\ 18647 &:= ((C(18, 6) + T(T(4))) + (T(7))) \\ 18649 &:= (1 - (-C(8, 6) \times T((4 \times 9)))) \\ 18729 &:= ((1 + T((C(8, 7)^2))) \times 9) \\ 18752 &:= (-1) + ((T(T(8)) \times T(7)) + C(T(5), 2)) \\ 18872 &:= (((1 \times 8) + T(T(8))) \times T(C(7, T(T(2)))))) \\ 18873 &:= (1 + ((8 + T(T(8))) \times T(C(7, T(3)))))) \\ 18942 &:= (((1 + T(8)) + T(9)) \times T(T(C(4, 2)))) \\ 18981 &:= (T((1 + T(8))) \times (-9) + T(C(8, 1))) \\ 18981 &:= (T((1 + T(8))) \times (-9) + T(C(8, 1))) \\ 19082 &:= (((1 + T(9)) + 0!) \times T(C(8, 2))) \\ 19227 &:= (-1) + (C((T(9) - T(T(T(2))))), T(T(2))/7)) \\ 19237 &:= (1 + ((T(C(9, 2)) + T(T(3))) \times T(7))) \\ 19265 &:= -((T((1 + T(9))) + (T(2) - C(T(6), 5)))) \\ 19278 &:= (T(-((1 - C(9, 2)))) + (T(7) \times T(T(8)))) \\ 19313 &:= ((-1) - T(T(9))) + C(T(T(3)), (-1) + T(3)) \\ 19314 &:= ((-1) \times T(T(9))) + C(T(T(3)), (1 + 4)) \\ 19315 &:= ((1 - T(T(9))) + C(T(T(3)), (1 \times 5))) \\ 19321 &:= (1 + (C(9, 3) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 1))) \\ 19335 &:= (((-1) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(3))) + C(T(T(3)), 5) \\ 19345 &:= (((-1) + T(C(9, 3))) + T(4!)) \times 5 \\ 19353 &:= -((T((-1) + T(9)) - (C(T(T(3)), 5) - T(3))) \\ 19359 &:= (T((1 \times 9)) + (C(T(T(3)), 5) - T(T(9)))) \\ 19372 &:= ((1 - 9) + (C(T(T(3)), 7)/T(T(2)))) \\ 19403 &:= (-1) + (C(9, (4 - 0!)) \times T(T(T(3)))) \\ 19455 &:= ((C(19, 4) + T(5)) \times 5) \\ 19467 &:= (19 + C((-4) + T(6), 7)) \\ 19632 &:= (((1 + C(9, 6)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - T(2)) \\ 19635 &:= ((1 + C(9, 6)) \times T((T(3) + T(5)))) \\ 19636 &:= (1 + ((C(9, 6) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(6)))) \\ 19746 &:= (-((1 \times 9)) + (C(T(7), 4!) - 6!)) \end{aligned}$$

- 19798 := (19 × (7 + T(T(C(9,8))))))
19853 := (-1) + (9 × (T(T(8)) + T(T(C(5,3))))))
20229 := (C(T(T(T(2))), (-0! + T(T(2)))) - T((T(T(2)) + 9)))
20234 := -((T(T(2)) + (C((0! + T(2)))!, 3) × (-T(4))))
20235 := (C(T(T(T(2))), (-0! + T(T(2)))) + ((T(3) - 5!))
20257 := (C(T(T(T(2))), (-0! + T(T(2)))) - (5! - T(7)))
20258 := (C(T(T(T(2))), (-0! + T(T(2)))) - T((5 + 8)))
20269 := (C(T(T(T(2))), (-0! + T(T(2)))) + (6!/(-9)))
20283 := (C(T(T(T(2))), (-0! + T(T(2)))) - T((8 + 3)))
20294 := (C(T(T(T(2))), (-0! + T(T(2)))) - (T(9) + T(4)))
20304 := (C(T(T(T(2))), -(0! - T(3))) - T(-(0! - T(4))))
20321 := (C(T(T(T(2))), -(0! - T(3))) - T((T(T(2)) + 1)))
20322 := (C(T(T(T(2))), -(0! - T(3))) - (T(2)^{T(2)}))
20325 := -((((T(2) + 0!)! - (C(T((3 × 2)), 5))))
20329 := (-20) + C(T(T(3)), ((T(T(2)))!/T(9)))
20334 := (C(T(T(T(2))), -(0! - T(3))) - C(T(3), 4))
20335 := ((-20) + T(3)) + C(T(T(3)), 5)
20338 := (C(T(T(T(2))), -(0! - T(3))) - (3 + 8))
20339 := -((T((T(2) + 0!) - C(T(T(3)), ((T(3))!/T(9))))))
20340 := (C(T(T(T(2))), -(0! - T(3))) - (T(4) - 0!))
20342 := -(((T(T(2)) + 0!) - C(T(T(3)), (T(4)/2))))
20343 := ((T(T(2)) × (-0!)) + C(T(T(3)), (T(4) + T(3))))
20344 := -(((T(T(2)) - 0!) - C(T(T(3)), (4 × 4))))
20345 := -(((T(2) + 0!) - C((-3) + 4!), 5))
20348 := ((-2) + 0!) + C(T(T(3)), (4! - 8))
20349 := C(T((2 × 03)), -(4 - 9))
20364 := (T((T(T(2)) - 0!)) + C(T(T(3)), (6 + T(4))))
20365 := ((2^{0!+3}) + C(T(6), 5))
20369 := (20 + C(T(T(3)), (6!/T(9))))
20392 := (C(T(T(T(2))), -(0! - T(3))) + (T(9) - 2))
20404 := (C(T(T(T(2))), (0! + (4))) - (0 - T(T(4))))
20429 := (C(T(T(T(2))), (0! + (4))) + ((T(T(2)))!/9))
20444 := (C(T((T(T(2)) + 0!)), 4) - (-4! + T(T(4))))
20445 := ((-2) + C(T((0! + (4))), 4)) × T(5)
20447 := (C(((T(2) + 0!) + 4!), 4!) - T(7))
20449 := (C(T(T(T(2))), (0! + (4))) + (T(T(4)) + T(9)))
20451 := (C(T((T(T(2)) + 0!)), 4) - ((5 - 1)!))
20455 := (C(T((T(T(2)) + 0!)), 4) - (5 + T(5)))
20463 := (C(T((T(T(2)) + 0!)), 4) - (6 + T(3)))
20464 := (C(T((T(T(2)) + 0!)), 4) - (T(6) - T(4)))

- 20476** := $(C(T((T(T(2)) + 0!)), 4) + (7 - 6))$
20494 := $(C(T((T(T(2)) + 0!)), 4) + (9 + T(4)))$
20565 := $(C(T(T(T(2))), 05) + (T(T(6)) - T(5)))$
20573 := $((C(T(T(T(2))), 05) - 7) + T(T(T(3))))$
20574 := $((T(T(T(2))) \times (-0!)) + ((5! + C(T(7), 4!)))$
20592 := $(T(T(2)) \times C(-((0! - T(5))), (9 - 2)))$
20602 := $(T((T(T(T(2))) + 0!)) + (C(T(6), (-0! + T(T(2))))))$
20602 := $(T((T(T(T(2))) + 0!)) + (C(T(6), (-0! + T(T(2))))))$
20635 := $(T(T((T(2) + 0!))) + (T(T(6)) + C(T(T(3)), 5)))$
20649 := $(T(((T(2) + 0!))!) + C(T(6), -(4 - 9)))$
20650 := $(T(((T(2) + 0!))!) + ((C(T(6), 5) + 0!))$
20652 := $(T(((T(2) + 0!))!) + ((C(T(6), 5) + T(2)))$
20654 := $((T(T(2)) - (0! - C(T(6), 5))) + T(4!))$
20682 := $(C(T(T(T(2))), -((0! - (6)))) - (T(T(8))/(-2)))$
20705 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) + (-0! + C(T(7), -((0! - (5))))))$
20725 := $((-2) + T(-((0! - T(7)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), 5))$
20757 := $(2 + (C(T(-((0! - (7))))), 5) + (T(T(7))))$
20765 := $((T((T(2) + 0!)) + T(T(7))) + (C(T(6), 5)))$
20796 := $((T(T(2)))! \times (0! + T(7))) - C(9, 6)$
20931 := $((20 \times T(T(9))) + T(T(T(C(3, 1))))$
20932 := $(T(T(T(T(2)))) - (-0! + (T(T(9)) \times (-C(T(3), T(2)))))$
20995 := $(C(T(T(T(2))), 09)/(9 + 5))$
21135 := $((T(T(2)))! - (-T(11) - C(T(T(3)), 5)))$
21174 := $((T(T(2)))! - T(T(T((1 + 1)))) + (C(T(7), 4!)))$
21244 := $(2 \times ((-1) - T(2)) + C(4!, 4))$
21246 := $(2 \times C(((1 + T(2)))!, 4) - 6)$
21396 := $(T(T(2)) \times (-((1 + 3)) + T(C(9, 6))))$
21432 := $((2 + T(C((-1) + T(4)), 3)) \times T(T(2)))$
21482 := $-((T((T(T(T(2))) + 1)) + (-T(C(T(4), 8))) \times T(T(T(2))))))$
21495 := $(C(T((T(T(2)) + 1)), 4) + ((T(T(9)) - T(5))))$
21579 := $(C((T(T(T(2))) - 1), 5) - (-7! - T(T(9))))$
21672 := $((T(2) + 1)! \times T((T(6) + C(7, 2))))$
21729 := $(-T((2 + 1))) - (-C(7, 2) \times T(T(9)))$
21732 := $((T(T((C(2, 1) + 7))) \times T(T(3))) - T(2))$
21759 := $((T(2) + 1)! - (-C(7, 5) \times T(T(9))))$
21832 := $-((((T(T(2)) - 1)! - ((C(8, T(3))^{T(2)}))))$
21861 := $((T(T(2)) + T(T((1 + 8)))) \times T(C(6, 1)))$
21882 := $(T(2) + ((C(18, 8)/2))$
21925 := $((T(T(2)) \times T((1 + C(9, T(2)))) - 5)$
21966 := $(T(T(2)) \times (T((1 + C(9, 6))) + (6)))$

$$\begin{aligned} 22052 &:= (2 + (T(20) \times C(T(5), 2))) \\ 22155 &:= ((T(C(T(T(2)), T(2))) + 1) \times (5! - T(5))) \\ 22162 &:= (T(C(T(T(2)), T(2))) + ((T((1 + 6))^{T(2)})) \\ 22224 &:= ((C((T(T(2)) + T(T(2))), T(T(2))) + 2) \times 4!) \\ 22232 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2)))/(-T(2))) + (((T(3) + 2)!)) \\ 22238 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2)))/(-T(2))) + ((T(3) + 8!)) \\ 22260 &:= (-T(T(2))) \times (C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) - ((6 + 0!))!) \\ 22274 &:= (-C((2^{T(2)}), T(2))) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(4))) \\ 22319 &:= (-C(2, 2) + (T(31) \times T(9))) \\ 22324 &:= -((T(T(2)) - (T(C((2^3), 2)) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 22372 &:= ((C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(3))) + ((T(7)^{T(2)})) \\ 22379 &:= -T(T(T(T(2)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), 3) \times (-T(7) + T(9)) \\ 22422 &:= -(((2^{T(T(2))}) - C(4!, T(T(2))))/T(T(2))) \\ 22422 &:= -(((2^{T(T(2))}) - C(4!, T(T(2))))/T(T(2))) \\ 22432 &:= ((-(2 + 2) + C(4!, T(3)))/T(T(2))) \\ 22433 &:= ((2 + C(24, T(3)))/T(3)) \\ 22436 &:= (T(2) - ((-2) - C(4!, T(3)))/6) \\ 22525 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) - 5) \times (2 + T(5))) \\ 22546 &:= ((T(T(2)) \times T((T(T(2)) \times T(5)))) - (C(4!, T(6)))) \\ 22562 &:= ((2 + C(T(T(T(2))), 5)) + T(T((T(T(6))/T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 22563 &:= ((T(2) + C(T(T(T(2))), 5)) + T(T((T(T(6))/T(T(3)))))) \\ 22565 &:= (T(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))))) + (5 + C(T(6), 5))) \\ 22566 &:= (T(T(2)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 5) + T(66))) \\ 22589 &:= -((T(T(T(2))) - (C((T(T(2)) + T(5)), 8)/9)) \\ 22595 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))), (T(2) + (5)))/9) - T(5)) \\ 22635 &:= (-C(T(2), 2) \times (T(T(6)) - ((T(3)^5))) \\ 22673 &:= ((C(2, 2) + 6!) + (T(7)^3)) \\ 22680 &:= ((C(2, 2) + 6) \times T(80)) \\ 22756 &:= (C(T(T(2)), T(2)) - (T(T(7)) \times (-56))) \\ 22769 &:= (-C(2, 2) - (-((T(7) - (6))) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 22791 &:= (T(T(T(2))) - ((T(T(2)) - (T(7))) \times T(T(C(9, 1)))))) \\ 22841 &:= (T(T(T(T(2)))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 8)/(T(4) - 1))) \\ 22869 &:= (((C(T(2), 2) + 8) \times T(T(6))) \times 9) \\ 22892 &:= ((T(T(2)) + (C((2 \times 8), 9))) \times 2) \\ 22895 &:= ((2 \times C((2 \times 8), 9)) + T(5)) \\ 22911 &:= ((C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(11))) \\ 22962 &:= ((T(T(2)) \times T((T(2) + (C(9, 6)))) - T(T(2))) \\ 22964 &:= ((T(T(2)) \times T((T(2) + (C(9, 6)))) - 4) \\ 22979 &:= -((C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) + (-9) \times T((T(7) + T(9)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23049 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))), (T(3) - 0!)) + (T(4!) \times 9)) \\ 23075 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) + C(((3 + 0!)!, 7)) / T(5)) \\ 23229 &:= (((C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) / T(T(T(2)))) - T(2)) \times 9) \\ 23235 &:= -((T(T(T(2))) - (T(3) \times C((-2) + T(T(3))), T(5)))) \\ 23245 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))), (T(T(3)) / T(2))) - (T(T(4)))) / 5) \\ 23246 &:= -((C(T(T(T(2))), 3) - (T(T(2)) \times (4^6))) \\ 23252 &:= (2 \times (C((T(T(3)) - 2), 5) - 2)) \\ 23256 &:= (C((-2) + T((3 \times 2))), T(5)) \times 6) \\ 23282 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))), 3) + ((28^{T(2)})) \\ 23292 &:= (((T(T(2))^{T(3)}) / 2) - C(9, 2)) \\ 23296 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))), 3) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(9))) + T(T(6)))) \\ 23351 &:= (T((T(T(T(T(2)))) / 3)) + ((C(T(T(3))), 5) - 1)) \\ 23385 &:= ((C((T(2)^3), 3) \times 8) - T(5)) \\ 23408 &:= ((C((T(2)^3), 4!) + 0!) \times 8) \\ 23493 &:= -((T(2) - (T(3) \times T((4 + C(9, 3)))))) \\ 23496 &:= ((2 \times 3) \times T((4 + C(9, 6)))) \\ 23538 &:= (-T(2) + (T(T(3)) \times (C(T(5), 3) + T(T(8)))))) \\ 23541 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times (T(((T(3))! / T(5))) - T(T(C(4, 1)))))) \\ 23554 &:= (((T(T(2)))! + (C(T(T(3))), 5)) + T((T(5) + T(T(4)))))) \\ 23652 &:= ((T(2) \times 3) \times T((6! / C(5, 2)))) \\ 23751 &:= C((-((2 - 3)) + T(7)), (5 - 1)) \\ 23754 &:= (T(2) + C(((T(3) + T(7)) - (5)), 4)) \\ 23757 &:= (-T(2) + ((T(3))! \times (T(C(7, 5)) / 7))) \\ 23786 &:= -((C(T(T(T(2))), 3) - (T(7) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(6)))))) \\ 23892 &:= ((T((2^3)) \times T(T(8))) - C(9, T(2))) \\ 23928 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((T(3) \times T(C(9, 2))) - 8)) \\ 23967 &:= ((T(T(2)))! + (T(-((3 - C(9, 6)))) \times 7)) \\ 23970 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((T(3) \times T(C(9, 7))) - 0!)) \\ 23973 &:= ((T((2^3)) \times T(C(9, 7))) - 3) \\ 23976 &:= (T((2^3)) \times T(C(9, C(7, 6)))) \\ 23978 &:= ((T(T(2)) / 3) + (T(C(9, 7)) \times T(8))) \\ 24024 &:= (T(2) \times C((4^0 2), T(4))) \\ 24054 &:= (T(2) \times (T(4) + C((0! + T(5)), T(4)))) \\ 24159 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(4)) / (-1) + T(5)) - T(T(9))) \\ 24225 &:= (C((2 \times T(4)), (2 + 2)) \times 5) \\ 24252 &:= -(((T(2) - C(4!, T(2))) \times (T(5) - T(2)))) \\ 24253 &:= (-2) + ((T(C(T(4), 2)) + (5!)) \times T(T(3))) \\ 24257 &:= (2 + (T(T(C(4, 2))) \times (T(5) \times 7))) \\ 24258 &:= ((T(2) - T(T(4))) + C((2 + T(5)), 8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24261 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + C(6,1)) \\ 24265 &:= ((2 - (T(T(C(4,2))) \times (-T(6)))) \times 5) \\ 24283 &:= (((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + C(8, T(3))) \\ 24289 &:= -((T(T(T(2))) - C((T((4^2))/8), 9))) \\ 24290 &:= -((T(T(T(2))) - (C((-4) + T(T(T(2))), 9) + 0!))) \\ 24295 &:= (C((2 \times T(4) - T(2)), 9) - T(5)) \\ 24298 &:= (-2) + (((C(4,2))! - T(9)) \times T(8)) \\ 24299 &:= (-2) + (C((-4) + T(T(T(2))), 9) - 9) \\ 24307 &:= (-T(2)) + C((-4) + T(T(3)), (0! + (7))) \\ 24308 &:= (-2) + C(((4! - T(3)) - 0!), 8) \\ 24310 &:= C((T(T(T(2))) - 4), ((T(3) + 1) + 0!)) \\ 24324 &:= (T(2) \times ((C(4!, 3) + T(2)) \times 4)) \\ 24343 &:= (((2 \times (4!))! / (T(T(3)))! + T(T(C(4,3)))) \\ 24384 &:= (((2^{T(C(4,3))}) - 8) \times 4!) \\ 24456 &:= ((C((2 \times T(4)), 4) \times 5) + T(T(6))) \\ 24473 &:= (((T(T(2)))! \times (4! + T(4))) - C(7, T(3))) \\ 24492 &:= (((2^{T(4)}) \times 4!) - C(9, T(2))) \\ 24535 &:= (T(T(((2 \times 4) + 5))) + C(T(T(3)), 5)) \\ 24572 &:= (2 + ((4! + T(5)) \times T(C(7, T(2)))) \\ 24573 &:= (T(2) + ((4! + T(5)) \times T(C(7, 3)))) \\ 24641 &:= ((T((2 \times 4!)) \times T(6)) - T(T(C(4, 1)))) \\ 24655 &:= (T(T((T(2) + T(4)))) + (C(T(6), 5) + 5!)) \\ 24669 &:= ((T(2) - (C(4!, T(6)) + 6!)) \times (-9)) \\ 24726 &:= ((2 + 4!) \times (T(C(7, 2)) + 6!)) \\ 24751 &:= (((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7))) - T(C(5, 1))) \\ 24752 &:= (2 \times C((4! - (7)), T((5 - 2)))) \\ 24773 &:= (((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7))) + C(7, T(3))) \\ 24795 &:= (T((2 + C((4 + 7), 9))) \times T(5)) \\ 24816 &:= (T((2 + C(T(4), 8))) \times (1 + T(6))) \\ 24838 &:= (-2) + (T(C(T(4), 8)) \times (3 \times 8)) \\ 24844 &:= (-2) + ((T(4) \times T(C(8, 4))) - (4)) \\ 24846 &:= (2 + ((T(4) \times T(C(8, 4))) - (6))) \\ 24848 &:= (T(T(2)) + (((T(4) \times T(C(8, 4))) - 8))) \\ 24850 &:= ((T(T(2)) + 4) \times T(C(8, (5 - 0!)))) \\ 24855 &:= (((T(T(2)) + T(T(4))) + T(C(8, 5))) \times T(5)) \\ 24883 &:= ((-2) - T(C(T(4), 8))) - (-T(8) \times (T(3))!) \\ 24937 &:= ((2 - T(T(4))) + (T(C(9, 3)) \times 7)) \\ 24939 &:= (((T(2) - T(4!)) \times (-C(9, 3))) - 9) \\ 24962 &:= (2 + ((4! \times T(T(9))) + T(C(6, 2)))) \\ 24976 &:= ((T(T(2)) \times T((T(4) \times 9))) + T(T(C(7, 6)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24978 &:= (T(2) + ((T(4!) \times T(C(9,7)))/8)) \\ 24985 &:= ((C(C(T(T(2)),4),9) - 8) \times 5) \\ 24995 &:= ((T(T(2)) - C((4! - 9),9)) \times (-5)) \\ 25004 &:= -((T(T(T(2))) - (C(T(5),T((0! + 0!))) \times T(T(4)))))) \\ 25015 &:= ((2 - C(T(5),T(T((0! + 1)))))) \times (-5) \\ 25022 &:= (-T(2) - (-5 \times C(T((-0!) + T(T(2))),T(T(2)))))) \\ 25023 &:= (-2) + (5 \times C(T((-0!) + T(T(2))),T(3))) \\ 25025 &:= (C((T(2) \times 5),T(T(02))) \times 5) \\ 25035 &:= ((2 + C(T(5),T(03))) \times 5) \\ 25046 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + (5 \times C(T((0! + (4))),6))) \\ 25055 &:= ((T(T(2)) + (C(T(5), (0! + (5)))))) \times 5) \\ 25122 &:= ((T(T(2)) \times T(C((T(5) - 1),2))) + T(T(2))) \\ 25194 &:= -((T(T(2)) - (5! \times C((1 + 9),4))) \\ 25223 &:= (2 + ((5! \times T(C(T(T(2)),T(2)))) + (T(T(3)))))) \\ 25253 &:= ((-T(2) + (C(T(5),T(T(2))) \times 5)) + T(T(T(3)))) \\ 25256 &:= ((C((T(2) \times 5),T(T(2))) \times 5) + T(T(6))) \\ 25257 &:= ((2 + T(C(5,2))) - (-5 \times 7!)) \\ 25269 &:= -((T(T(T(2))) + ((-C(T(5),2) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(9)))))) \\ 25300 &:= (C(25,T(T(3))) \times (0! + 0!)) \\ 25302 &:= ((C(25,T(T(3))) + 0!) \times 2) \\ 25320 &:= (T((T(2) \times 5)) \times (T(C(T(3),T(2))) + 0!)) \\ 25322 &:= (2 + (5! \times (T(T(T(3))) - C(T(T(2)),T(2)))))) \\ 25324 &:= ((C(25,T(T(3))) \times 2) + (4!)) \\ 25334 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))),5) + ((T(T(3))/3)!) - (T(T(4)))))) \\ 25355 &:= ((T(T(2)) + (C(T(5),3))) \times 55) \\ 25368 &:= -(((T(2) \times (C(T(5),T(3)) - T(6))) - 8!)) \\ 25372 &:= (-T(2) + ((5 + (T(3))!) \times C(7,T(2)))) \\ 25373 &:= (-2) + ((5 + (T(3))!) \times C(7,3)) \\ 25411 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (5! - T(4))) + C(1,1)) \\ 25413 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))),5) - (-4! - ((1 + T(3))!)) \\ 25425 &:= (((2 + 5)!) + C(T(4),2)) \times 5) \\ 25431 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times (5! \times T(4))) + T(T(T(C(3,1)))))) \\ 25442 &:= (2 + (5! \times (C(T(4),4) + 2))) \\ 25461 &:= ((T(2) + 5!) \times (-4! + T(T(C(6,1)))))) \\ 25475 &:= ((T((2 \times C(5,4)) + 7!) \times 5) \\ 25519 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))),5) - (5 \times (1 - T(T(9)))))) \\ 25539 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))),5) - (5 \times (-3 - T(T(9)))))) \\ 25553 &:= (T((2^5)) + (5 \times C(T(5),T(3)))) \\ 25562 &:= (((T(T(2)))^5) + (C(T(5),6))) \times 2) \\ 25595 &:= ((T(T(2)) - (5! + C(T(5),9))) \times (-5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25635 &:= (((2 + 5!) \times T(C(6, 3))) + T(5)) \\ 25647 &:= -((T(2) - ((5! \times C(T(6), 4))/T(7)))) \\ 25655 &:= ((T(T(2)) + ((C(T(5), 6) + 5!))) \times 5) \\ 25696 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 5!) - C(-((T(6) - T(9))), T(6))) \\ 25724 &:= ((-2) + (C(T(5), 7) - 2)) \times 4) \\ 25732 &:= ((-2) + C(T(5), 7)) \times (T(3) - 2) \\ 25734 &:= (T(T(2)) - ((C(T(5), 7) - 3) \times (-4))) \\ 25737 &:= -((T(2) - (C(T(5), 7) \times (-3 - 7)))) \\ 25755 &:= ((C((-2) + T(5)), 7) \times T(5)) + T(5) \\ 25764 &:= ((C((T(2) \times 5), 7) + (6)) \times 4) \\ 25774 &:= (T(T(2)) - ((C(T(5), 7) + (7)) \times (-4))) \\ 25784 &:= ((T(2) + (C(T(5), 7) + 8)) \times 4) \\ 25787 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))), 5) - (-((7! - 8) - T(T(7)))) \\ 25794 &:= ((T(T(2)) \times T((5! - T(7)))) + C(9, 4)) \\ 28593 &:= (((T(2))! \times T(C(8, 5))) - T(9)) \times 3) \\ 28596 &:= ((T(2))! \times ((-8) + C(T(5), 9) - T(T(6)))) \\ 28623 &:= (-(((T(2) - T(8)) - C(T(6), T(2)))) \times T(3!)) \\ 28625 &:= (((T(2))!! + (C((T(8) - T(6)), (T(2))!))) \times 5) \\ 28645 &:= ((-((2^8)) + C(T(6), 4)) \times 5) \\ 28649 &:= -((T(T((T(2))!)) - (8! - C((6 + T(4)), 9)))) \\ 28654 &:= -(((T(2) + 8) - (T(6) \times C(T(5), 4)))) \\ 28694 &:= -(((T(2))! - (C(8, 6) \times (T(T(9)) - T(4)))) \\ 28745 &:= ((C(T((T(2))!), 8)/7) - (T((T(4) + T(5)))) \\ 28755 &:= -(((T(2) - (8!/C(7, 5))) \times T(5))) \\ 28836 &:= (T(2) \times (T(8) + (T(C(8, 3)) \times 6))) \\ 28973 &:= ((28 \times T(T(9))) - C(7, 3!)) \\ 28980 &:= (28 \times T(T((C(9, 8) + 0)))) \\ 29037 &:= ((C(T((T(2))!), (9 - 0!)) - T(T(3!)))/7) \\ 29067 &:= ((C(T((T(2))!), (9 - 0!)) - (T(6)))/7) \\ 29172 &:= (T(((T(2))! + T(9))) \times (1 + C(7, 2))) \\ 29176 &:= (((T(2))! + T(T(9))) + 1) \times T(C(7, 6)) \\ 29183 &:= (T(T((T(2))!)) + ((T(T(9)) - 1) \times C(8, 3!))) \\ 29235 &:= ((T((2 \times 9))^2) - C(3!, 5)) \\ 29245 &:= ((C((T(2) \times 9), T(2)) \times T(4)) - (5)) \\ 29260 &:= (C(T((T(2))!), (9/T(2))) \times (T(6) + 0!)) \\ 29295 &:= (((T(2) \times T(C(9, 2))) - T(9)) \times T(5)) \\ 29321 &:= ((C(T((T(2))!), 9) - ((3!)!)/T((T(2) + 1))) \\ 29342 &:= (((C(T((T(2))!), 9) - ((3!)!)/T(4)) + T((T(2))!)) \\ 29345 &:= (((C(T((T(2))!), 9) + ((3!)!)/T(4)) - (5!)) \\ 29372 &:= ((C(T((T(2))!), 9)/(3 + 7)) - T((T(2))!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29382 &:= ((C((2 \times 9), 3) \times T(8)) + (T(2))!) \\ 29391 &:= (T(T((T(2))!)) - (-9 \times T((3)!/C(9, 1)))) \\ 29393 &:= (C(T((T(2))!), 9)/T((3+9)/3)) \\ 29413 &:= ((C(T((T(2))!), 9)/T(4)) + (-1 + T(3!))) \\ 29422 &:= ((-2) + (T(T(9)) \times (-4!))) + C(T((T(2))!), (T(2))!) \\ 29423 &:= ((C(T((T(2))!), 9) + T(4!))/T((-2) + 3!)) \\ 29443 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))), 9)/T(4)) + (T(4!)/T(3))) \\ 29472 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((-C(9, 4) + 7!) - 2)) \\ 29474 &:= ((T(T(2)) \times (-C(9, 4) + 7!)) - T(4)) \\ 29512 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times C(9, 5)) + T(T((1 + T(T(2))))) \\ 29562 &:= (((2 + C(9, 5)) \times T(T(6))) - T(T(2))) \\ 29564 &:= (((2 + C(9, 5)) \times T(T(6))) - 4) \\ 29592 &:= ((2 + T((T(9) - 5))) \times C(9, 2)) \\ 29592 &:= ((2 + T((T(9) - 5))) \times C(9, 2)) \\ 29646 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (-9) + T((T(C(6, 4)) - T(6)))) \\ 29697 &:= -((T(2) + (T(9) \times (6 - T(C(9, 7))))) \\ 29820 &:= ((T(2) + 9) \times T(C(8, (T(2) + 0!))) \\ 29844 &:= (((T(2) + 9) \times T(C(8, 4))) + 4!) \\ 29891 &:= (2 - (-9) \times T((T(8) + T(C(9, 1))))) \\ 29892 &:= (T(2) - (-C(9, 8) \times T((9^2)))) \\ 29892 &:= (T(2) - (-C(9, 8) \times T((9^2)))) \\ 29900 &:= (C(T(-(2 - 9)), 9)/T(T(T(T((0! + 0!)))))) \\ 29931 &:= ((T(T(2)) \times T(99)) + T(T(T(C(3, 1)))) \\ 29968 &:= (-2) + (T(9) \times T(C(9, -(6 - 8)))) \\ 29971 &:= (2 + ((T(9) \times T(C(9, 7))) - 1)) \\ 29981 &:= ((2 + 9) - (-T(9) \times T(T(C(8, 1)))) \\ 29987 &:= ((29 \times T(T(C(9, 8)))) - (T(7))) \\ 29991 &:= (T(T(T(2))) - (-T(9) \times T((T(9) - C(9, 1)))) \\ 30036 &:= (T(3) \times (0! + C(T(-(0! - T(3))), 6))) \\ 30435 &:= (((T(3) - 0!) + C(4!, 3)) \times T(5)) \\ 30436 &:= ((T(T((3 + 0!))) \times T(T(T(4)))) - (C(T(T(3)), 6))) \\ 30465 &:= (((T(3) + 0!) + C(4!, T(6))) \times T(5)) \\ 30555 &:= (((T(3) + 0!)! - (C(T(5), 5))) \times T(5)) \\ 30645 &:= ((T(3))! - (C(T(06), 4) \times (-5))) \\ 30856 &:= (T(T((T(3) + 0!))) \times (T(C(8, 5))/T(6))) \\ 31185 &:= (T(T(3)) \times T(-(((1 + 1) - C(8, 5)))) \\ 31374 &:= (T((C(3, 1)^3)) \times (T(7) + T(T(4)))) \\ 31395 &:= ((C(T((T(3) - 1)), 3) \times T(T(9)))/T(5)) \\ 31524 &:= ((T(((3 + 1))!)) \times C(T(5), 2)) + (4!) \\ 31542 &:= (T(T(3)) \times ((-1) - C(T(5), T(4)))/(-2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 31564 &:= ((T(3) \times (-1) + C(T(5), 6)) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 31575 &:= ((T(3) - 1) \times (C(T(5), 7) - 5!)) \\ 31625 &:= (T((T(T(3)) + 1)) \times (T(C(6, 2)) + (5))) \\ 31779 &:= (C(-((3 \times (1 - 7))), 7) - T(9)) \\ 31803 &:= -((T(T(3)) - (C(18, (0! + T(3)))))) \\ 31818 &:= -((T(3) - C(18, -((1 - 8)))))) \\ 31821 &:= (-3 + C(18, (T(T(2)) + 1))) \\ 31830 &:= (T(3) + C(18, (T(3) + 0!))) \\ 31845 &:= (T(T(3)) + (C(18, (-4) + T(5)))) \\ 31941 &:= (-T(T(3))) \times (19 - T(T(T(C(4, 1)))))) \\ 32064 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), T(2)) + 06) \times 4!) \\ 32124 &:= (C((T(3) \times T(2)), (1 + T(T(2)))) + T(4!)) \\ 32135 &:= -(((C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) + 1) + ((T(3))! \times (-5!))) \\ 32175 &:= (C(T((3 + 2)), (1 \times 7)) \times 5) \\ 32234 &:= (C(T(3), T(2)) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (T(3) - T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 32235 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (C(22, 3) - 5)) \\ 32265 &:= (-3) \times ((C(T(2), 2) - 6!) \times T(5)) \\ 32292 &:= (C((3^{T(2)}), 2) \times 92) \\ 32312 &:= (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - (T((T(3) + 1))^{T(2)})) \\ 32335 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(C((2 + 3), 3)))) - 5) \\ 32364 &:= ((T(T(C((3 + 2), 3))) \times T(6)) + (4!)) \\ 32372 &:= (((T(3))! \times T((T(2) \times 3))) - T(C(7, T(T(2)))))) \\ 32380 &:= (-C(T(3), T(2)) + ((T(3))! \times T((8 + 0!)))) \\ 32382 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (2 + T(C((3 + 8), 2)))) \\ 32384 &:= (C(((T(3) - 2))!, 3) \times (-8 + 4!)) \\ 32391 &:= (((T(3))! \times T((T(2) \times 3))) - C(9, 1)) \\ 32395 &:= (((C(3, 2) + 3))! \times T(9)) - (5) \\ 32399 &:= (((T(3))! \times T((T(2) \times 3))) - C(9, 9)) \\ 32420 &:= (T(T(3)) - (((T(T(2)))! \times (-C(T(4), 2))) + 0!)) \\ 32421 &:= (T(T(3)) - ((T(T(2)))! \times (C(T(4), 2) \times (-1)))) \\ 32423 &:= ((T(T(3)) + 2) - (-C(T(4), 2) \times (T(3))!)) \\ 32423 &:= ((T(T(3)) + 2) - (-C(T(4), 2) \times (T(3))!)) \\ 32424 &:= ((T((3^2)) \times (C(4, 2))!) + 4!) \\ 32434 &:= (C(T(T(3)), T(2)) + (4! \times (T(3)^4))) \\ 32454 &:= (-T(3) + ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (C(5, 4))!)) \\ 32485 &:= (((T(3))! + 2) \times C(T(4), 8)) - 5) \\ 32531 &:= (-((T(3) - (2^{T(5)}))) - T(T(T(C(3, 1)))))) \\ 32536 &:= -((T(T(T(3))) - ((2^{T(5)}) - C(T(3), 6)))) \\ 32593 &:= ((C((T(T(3)) + 2), 5) - T(T(9))) - T(T(3))) \\ 32664 &:= (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) + (6! \times (-6) - 4!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32689 &:= (((C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) \times T(6))/T(8)) + T(T(9))) \\ 32724 &:= -(((T(3)^2) - (C(T(7), T(2)) \times T(4)))) \\ 32727 &:= (C((T(3) \times T(2)), 7) + T((T(T(2)) \times 7))) \\ 32734 &:= -((T(3) + ((2 - C(T(7), 3)) \times T(4))) \\ 32745 &:= (((C(3, 2)^7) - 4) \times T(5)) \\ 32747 &:= -((T(T(3)) - (2^{T(C(7, 4)/7)}))) \\ 32752 &:= -(((T(3) + 2) - (C(T(7), 5)/T(2)))) \\ 32753 &:= ((T((3 \times 2)) - C(T(7), 5))/(-3)) \\ 32769 &:= (C((T(3) \times T(2)), 7) + (T(6) \times T(9))) \\ 32774 &:= (T(3) + (2^{T(C(7, 7)+4)})) \\ 32835 &:= ((-((C(3, 2)^8)) - T(3)) \times (-5)) \\ 32844 &:= (((T(3))! - T(T(2))) \times (C(8, 4) - 4!)) \\ 32853 &:= ((-T(T(3))) + (T(T(2)))!) \times (-8 + T(C(5, 3))) \\ 32886 &:= ((T((3^2)) + T(8)) \times T(C(8, 6))) \\ 32928 &:= (T((C(3, 2) + T(9))) \times 28) \\ 33120 &:= ((T(3))! \times (T((C(3, 1)^2) + 0!)) \\ 33243 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), 3) + T((-2) + 4!)) \times T(T(3))) \\ 33245 &:= -(((T(T(3))^3) + (-2) - C(4!, 5))) \\ 33265 &:= (C(3, 3) + (((T(T(2)))! \times (-T(T(6))))/(-5))) \\ 33274 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), 3) \times (-T(2) - T(7))) + (4!)) \\ 33278 &:= (-T(C(T(3), 3)) - (T(T((T(T(2)) + 7))) \times (-8))) \\ 33284 &:= (C(T(3), 3) - (((T(T(2)))! + (T(T(8)))) \times (-4!))) \\ 33292 &:= (T(T((T(T(3))/3))) \times (-2) + C(9, T(2))) \\ 33295 &:= (((T(3))! + C(T(3), T(2))) \times T(9)) - 5) \\ 33298 &:= (C(T(T(3)), 3) - (-((T(2) + T(9))) \times T(T(8)))) \\ 33325 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), 3) + 3) \times 25) \\ 33342 &:= (-3) + (((T(3))! + T(T(3))) \times C(T(4), 2)) \\ 33348 &:= (3 + (((T(3))! + T(T(3))) \times C(T(4), 8))) \\ 33355 &:= ((T(T(3)) - (C(T(T(3)), 3) \times (-5))) \times 5) \\ 33364 &:= (C((3 \times T(3)), (T(T(T(3)))/T(6))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 33383 &:= (-C(T(T(3)), 3) + (T(T(3)) \times T((T(8) + T(T(3))))) \\ 33415 &:= ((-3) - T(T(T(3)))) + C((4! - 1), 5) \\ 33428 &:= ((C(T(3), 3) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T((2 \times T(8)))) \\ 33441 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + (T(3^4) \times T(C(4, 1)))) \\ 33445 &:= (((C(T(T(3)), 3) \times 4!) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(5)) \\ 33464 &:= (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) - ((T(4) \times T(64)))) \\ 33474 &:= (T(3) \times (C(T(T(3)), 4) - (T((7 \times 4)))) \\ 33488 &:= (T(T(((C(3, 3) + 4) + 8))) \times 8) \\ 33522 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T(C((3 + 5), T(2)))) + T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33538 &:= (((3 - C(T(T(3)), 5))/3) + 8!) \\ 33579 &:= (((T(3))! + C((3 + T(5)), 7)) + T(T(9))) \\ 33592 &:= ((C((3^3), T(5))/T(T(9))) \times 2) \\ 33625 &:= ((-3) - T(T(3))) + C((T(6) + 2), 5) \\ 33642 &:= (-((T((3^3)) - C(T(6), 4))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 33643 &:= ((C((3 + T(T(3))), 6)/4) - T(3)) \\ 33649 &:= C(((T(3)/3) + T(6)), -((4 - 9))) \\ 33650 &:= (C(((T(3)/3) + T(6)), 5) + 0!) \\ 33652 &:= (C(((T(3)/3) + T(6)), 5) + T(2)) \\ 33655 &:= (T(3) + C((3 \times 6) + 5), 5) \\ 33664 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), 3) - 6) - (-T(6) \times T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 33683 &:= -((T(T(T(3))) + (((T(3) - C(T(6), 8))/T(3)))))) \\ 33727 &:= (((T(T(3)) + C(T(T(3)), 7))/T(2)) - (7!)) \\ 33838 &:= (C(T(T(3)), 3) - (-T(8) \times T((T(3) + T(8)))))) \\ 33839 &:= ((-C(3, 3) + 8!) + ((T(3))! \times (-9))) \\ 33858 &:= ((-((3^3)) + 8!) - C(T(5), 8)) \\ 33869 &:= (((T(3) - C(T(T(3)), 8))/(-6)) - T(9)) \\ 33872 &:= ((C(T(3), 3) + 8!) + (-T(7) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 33878 &:= -((C((T(T(3)) - T(3)), 8) + (7 - 8!))) \\ 33891 &:= (33 \times (-8) + T(T(C(9, 1)))) \\ 33916 &:= ((T(3) + C(T(T(3)), (9 - 1)))/6) \\ 33943 &:= ((3 + ((T(3))! \times T(9))) + T(T(T(C(4, 3)))))) \\ 33987 &:= (T(T(3)) + ((T(3) + T(9)) \times T(T(C(8, 7)))))) \\ 34034 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(4)))) \times (-0! + T(C(T(3), 4)))) \\ 34232 &:= ((-T(T(3))) \times (-T(4!) - C(T(T(T(2))), 3))) + 2) \\ 34233 &:= (3 + ((T(4!) + C(T(T(T(2))), 3)) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 34235 &:= ((T((3 + T(T(4)))) \times C(T(T(2)), 3)) + T(5)) \\ 34236 &:= ((T(3))! + (T(C((4 \times 2), 3)) \times T(6))) \\ 34245 &:= (T(T(3)) + (C(4!, 2) \times (4 + 5!))) \\ 34248 &:= ((-3) \times C(4!, T((2 + 4)))) + 8! \\ 34275 &:= (3 \times (C((4^2), 7) - T(5))) \\ 34314 &:= (-((T(3) - C(T(4), 3))) \times (1 + T(4!))) \\ 34320 &:= (C((3 + T(4)), T(3)) \times 20) \\ 34328 &:= -((C(T(T(3)), 4) + ((T(T(3))/T(2)) - 8!))) \\ 34332 &:= (((T(3))! \times T(4)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3))/2)) \\ 34334 &:= (((C(T(T(3)), 4) - T(3)) \times T(3)) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 34343 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - ((T(T(3)) - (C(4!, 3)))))) \\ 34343 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - ((T(T(3)) - (C(4!, 3)))))) \\ 34348 &:= ((3 + T(4)) - (C(T(T(3)), 4) - 8!)) \\ 34352 &:= ((T(T(3)) + T(T(4))) \times (-3) + C(T(5), T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34354 &:= -((T(T(3)) - (T(T(C(4,3))) \times (5^4)))) \\ 34356 &:= -((C(T(T(3)),4) - (((3+5)! + T(6)))) \\ 34368 &:= (T(3) \times ((-C(4,3) + 6!) \times 8)) \\ 34384 &:= -(((C(T(T(3)),4) + (T(3) - 8!)) - T(T(4)))) \\ 34404 &:= ((T(C(T(3),4)) \times T(4!)) - T((0! + T(T(4)))) \\ 34445 &:= ((-C(T(3),4) - T(T(T(4)))) - (T(4!) \times (-5!))) \\ 34454 &:= ((-T(3) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(4!) \times (C(5,4)!)) \\ 34552 &:= (((T(3))! - (T(4))! + (5!)) / (-C(T(5),2))) \\ 34592 &:= (((T(3))! \times T(T(4))) - (C(T(5),9) + T(2))) \\ 34595 &:= (((T(3))! \times T(T(4))) - C(T(5), (-9) + T(5))) \\ 34736 &:= ((C(T(T(3)),T(4)) + C(T(7),T(3))) / T(6)) \\ 34738 &:= -(((C(T(T(3)),4) - T(T(7))) + (3 - 8!))) \\ 34756 &:= ((T(T(3)) - T(4!)) + (7 \times C(T(5),6))) \\ 34831 &:= -((C(T(T(3)),4) - ((8! + T(31)))) \\ 35273 &:= (((T(3))! - ((C(5,2))!)) \times (-7)) / (T(3))! \\ 35295 &:= (((T(3))! \times (-C(T(5),T(2)))) + ((9! + T(5)))) \\ 35308 &:= -((T(3) + ((C(T(5),T(3)) + 0!) - 8!)) \\ 35309 &:= (-((T(3) + C(T(5),T(3)))) + (-((0! - 9)))! \\ 35318 &:= (3 + ((C(T(5),T(3)) \times (-1)) + 8!)) \\ 35364 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(C(5,3))) + (6 \times 4!))) \\ 35399 &:= -((T(T(3)) - ((T(T(C(5,3))) \times T(T(9))) / T(9))) \\ 35414 &:= (-C(T(3),5) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (-1) + 4!)) \\ 35426 &:= (C(T(3),5) + (T(T(T(4))) \times (2 + T(6)))) \\ 35427 &:= ((T(T(3)) + ((C(5,4) + 2))! \times 7) \\ 35442 &:= ((-3 - T(5)) \times (T(T(4)) - (C(4!,T(2)))) \\ 35447 &:= -((((T(3))! - (C(T(5),4))) \times T(T(4))) + (T(7))) \\ 35456 &:= (((C(T(T(3)),T(5)) \times T(4)) / T(5)) - (6!)) \\ 35473 &:= (C(T(T(3)),5) + (4 + (7! \times 3))) \\ 35484 &:= -((T(3) - (C(T(5),4) \times (T(8) - T(4)))) \\ 35542 &:= ((T(T(3)) + 5) \times (C(T(5),4) + 2)) \\ 35568 &:= ((C((-3) + T(5)),5) \times (-6)) + 8! \\ 35798 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), (T(5) - 7)) / (-T(9))) + 8! \\ 35868 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (C((5+8),6) - 8)) \\ 35922 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), -(5-9)) + 2) \times T(T(2))) \\ 35925 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), -(5-9)) \times T(T(2))) + T(5)) \\ 35943 &:= (C(T(3),5) + ((9 + 4!)^3)) \\ 35945 &:= (-C((T(3) + 5),9) - (T(4!) \times (-5!))) \\ 35964 &:= (C(T(3),5) \times (9 + C(T(6),4))) \\ 35972 &:= (((T(3))! \times (5 + T(9))) - T(C(7, T(T(2)))) \\ 35979 &:= -((T(T(3)) - (5! \times T(((C(9,7)/9)!)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35991 &:= (((T(3))! \times (5 + T(9))) - C(9,1)) \\ 35999 &:= (((T(3))! \times (5 + T(9))) - C(9,9)) \\ 36036 &:= (C(((T(3) + (6)) + 0!), T(3)) \times T(6)) \\ 36054 &:= (T(3) \times (C(T(6), -((0! - (5)))) + (4!))) \\ 36225 &:= (T((3 + C((6 \times 2), 2))) \times T(5)) \\ 36231 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + (T(C(6,2)) \times T(((3 + 1)!))) \\ 36328 &:= ((-3) \times C(T(6), 3)) - (2 - 8!) \\ 36337 &:= -((T((T(T(3)) + (T(6)))) + (C(T(T(3)), 3) \times (-T(7)))) \\ 36423 &:= (3 \times ((6 \times C(4!, T(2))) - 3)) \\ 36426 &:= (((3 \times 6) \times C(4!, T(2))) - (6)) \\ 36442 &:= (((3 + 6))! + T(T(T(4)))) / T(C(4, T(2))) \\ 36477 &:= ((T((3 + C(6,4))) + 7!) \times 7) \\ 36498 &:= (T(3) \times (C(T(6), 4) + 98)) \\ 36542 &:= ((C(T(3), 6) + 5!) \times (T(4!) + 2)) \\ 36630 &:= ((T(3))! + (6 \times C(T(6), (3 + 0!)))) \\ 36642 &:= ((T(3))! + (6 \times (C(T(6), 4) + 2))) \\ 36694 &:= (T(T((T(3) + C(6,6)))) + ((9! / T(4)))) \\ 36756 &:= ((T(3))! + (T(6) \times C((T(7) - T(5)), 6))) \\ 36856 &:= ((C(T(3), 6) + 8!) - (T(5) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 36873 &:= -(((T((3 \times 6)) - 8!) + C(T(7), 3))) \\ 36884 &:= -((((T(3))! + T(T(6))) - (8! - T(C(8,4)))))) \\ 36939 &:= (C(T(T(3)), 6) + ((-9!) / T(T(3))) - T(9)) \\ 37038 &:= -((T(3) + (C(T(7), 03) - 8!)) \\ 37065 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (T(70) - (C(6,5)!)) \\ 37145 &:= (C((-3) + T(7)), 14) / 5! \\ 37220 &:= (-T(T(3))) + ((T(7) \times C(T(T(T(2))), T(2))) + 0!) \\ 37222 &:= (3 - (((-T(7)) \times C(T(T(T(2))), T(2))) + T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 37227 &:= (-((T(3) + (7))) - (C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) \times (-T(7)))) \\ 37232 &:= (-T(3) + ((T(7) \times C(T(T(T(2))), 3)) - 2)) \\ 37235 &:= (((T(T(3)) + 7) \times C(T(T(T(2))), 3)) - 5) \\ 37237 &:= (-3) - (-C(C(7,2), 3) \times T(7)) \\ 37243 &:= (3 + (T(7) \times C(T((2 + 4)), 3))) \\ 37254 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (T(T(7)) + ((T(2) + C(T(5), 4)))))) \\ 37275 &:= (T(((3 \times C(7,2)) + 7)) \times T(5)) \\ 37281 &:= (T(T(3)) + (T(T((7 + 2))) \times T(C(8,1)))) \\ 37284 &:= ((T(C((3 + 7), 2)) \times T(8)) + 4!) \\ 37324 &:= ((T(T(3)) + (7 \times C(T(T(3)), T(2)))) \times 4) \\ 37356 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-C(T(7), 3) + 5!)) / (-T(6))) \\ 37435 &:= (((T(3))! \times (T(7) + (C(4,3)!)) - 5) \\ 37454 &:= -(((T(3) + 7!) - (C(4!, 5) - (4)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 37457 &:= (T(T(3)) - ((7! - (C(4!,5) - T(7)))))) \\ 37485 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (C(7,4) \times (T(8) + T(5)))) \\ 37527 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times (7 + T(T(C(5,2)))))) + (7!) \\ 37548 &:= (((3 \times T(C(7,5))) \times (-4)) + 8!) \\ 37566 &:= -((C(T(T(3)),7) - (T((T(5) + T(6))) \times T(T(6)))))) \\ 37583 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(7)) \times (5! - C(8,T(3))))) \\ 37596 &:= (((T(3))! - T(T(7))) \times 5!) - C(9,6) \\ 37602 &:= -((((T(3))! - C(T(7),6))/T((0! + T(2)))))) \\ 37644 &:= -((T(3) - ((C(T(7),6)/T(4)) - 4!)) \\ 37677 &:= (3 + (C(T(7),6)/T((T(7)/7)))) \\ 37695 &:= (T(T(3)) + (C(T(7),6)/T((9 - 5)))) \\ 37848 &:= (((T(3) + 7) - T(C(8,4))) + 8!) \\ 37853 &:= (-((3^7)) - (-8) \times C(T(5),T(3))) \\ 37884 &:= (T(T(3)) + (((T(7) + 8!) - T(C(8,4)))))) \\ 37926 &:= ((T(3) \times 7) \times T((C(9,2) + 6))) \\ 37975 &:= (T((T(T(3)) + (T(7)))) \times (C(9,7) - 5)) \\ 38032 &:= -((((T(3))! + 8) - C((-0! + T(T(3))),T(T(2)))))) \\ 38213 &:= ((-3) + C(8,T(2))) \times (1 + (T(3))!) \\ 38220 &:= (T(T(3)) \times C((8 \times 2), (T(2) + 0!))) \\ 38235 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times C((8 + T(2)),3)) + (5!)) \\ 38241 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (C((8 \times 2),4) + 1)) \\ 38244 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times C((8 \times 2),4)) + (4!)) \\ 38283 &:= (((-3) \times T(C(8,T(2)))) \times (-8)) - T(T(3)) \\ 38283 &:= (((-3) \times T(C(8,T(2)))) \times (-8)) - T(T(3)) \\ 38284 &:= (-((T((3 + C(8,2))) - 8!)) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 38288 &:= -(((C((3 \times 8),T(2)) + 8) - 8!)) \\ 38302 &:= ((T(3) + 8!) - C(((3 + 0!)!, T(2))) \\ 38304 &:= ((T(3) \times T(C(8,3))) \times 04) \\ 38318 &:= -((C((T(3) + 8), (T(3) - 1)) - 8!)) \\ 38328 &:= (((-3) \times T(C(8,3))) - T(2)) \times (-8) \\ 38338 &:= ((T(T(3)) + 8) \times (C(T(T(3)),3) - 8)) \\ 38344 &:= (((T(3) \times T(C(8,3))) + T(4)) \times 4) \\ 38346 &:= (T(T(3)) + ((T(C(8,3)) \times 4!) + T(6))) \\ 38349 &:= (((T(3) \times T(C(8,3))) \times 4) + T(9)) \\ 38353 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (8 \times T(T(3)))) - (C(T(5),3))) \\ 38358 &:= -((T(3) \times ((T(8) + T(3)) - C(T(5),8)))) \\ 38416 &:= ((T(3) + 8)^{C(4,16)}) \\ 38435 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T((T(8) + (C(4,3))!))) + 5) \\ 38438 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T((T(8) + (C(4,3))!))) + 8) \\ 38532 &:= (T(38) \times (T(C(5,3)) - T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38542 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + ((8! + T(5)) - C(4!, T(2)))) \\ 38544 &:= (((T(3) + T(C(8,5))) + (4)) \times 4!) \\ 38548 &:= -((T(T(T(3))) + ((T(C(8,5)) - T(T(4))) - 8!)) \\ 38562 &:= (T(3) \times (-8) + C(T(5), (6 + 2))) \\ 38578 &:= -(((T((3 + C(8,5))) - T(7)) - 8!)) \\ 38583 &:= (T(T(3)) + ((-8) + C(T(5), 8)) \times T(3)) \\ 38583 &:= (T(T(3)) + ((-8) + C(T(5), 8)) \times T(3)) \\ 38586 &:= (-((3 \times 8)) - (C(T(5), 8) \times (-6))) \\ 38588 &:= (C((3 \times 8), 5) - T(88)) \\ 38624 &:= (C(((T(3))!/T(8)), 6) - T((2^4))) \\ 38640 &:= (C(((T(3))!/T(8)), 6) - ((4 + 0!)!)) \\ 38646 &:= ((-((3^8)) + T(C(6,4))) \times (-6)) \\ 38655 &:= (C(((T(3))!/T(8)), 6) + (T(5) - 5!)) \\ 38668 &:= -((T((T(T(3)) + T(8))) + (-C(6,6)) - 8!)) \\ 38680 &:= (C(((T(3))!/T(8)), 6) - (80)) \\ 38682 &:= (C(((T(3))!/T(8)), 6) - T((T(8)/T(2)))) \\ 38697 &:= (C(((T(3))!/T(8)), 6) - (9 \times 7)) \\ 38703 &:= -(((T(T(3)) - 8!) + T(C((7 + 0!), 3))) \\ 38721 &:= ((-3) + 8!) - T((T(7) \times C(2,1))) \\ 38724 &:= (T(T(3)) \times ((8 \times T(C(7,2))) - (4))) \\ 38733 &:= (-((T(3) - C((-8) + T(7)), T(3))) - T(T(3))) \\ 38736 &:= (-3) + (C((-8) + T(7)), T(3)) - T(6)) \\ 38739 &:= -(((T(3) - 8!) - (-C(7,3)) \times T(9))) \\ 38753 &:= (((T(3))! + T(T(8))) \times T(7)) - T(C(5,3)) \\ 38757 &:= (-3) + C((-8) + T(7)), T(T(-((5 - 7)))) \\ 38773 &:= (((T(3))! + T(T(8))) \times T(7)) - C(7,3) \\ 38832 &:= ((-3) + 8!) - T((C(8,3) - 2)) \\ 38836 &:= -((T(((T(3))! - T(T(8)))) - ((8! + C(T(3), 6)))) \\ 38849 &:= -(((T(T(3)) - (8! - T(C(8,4)))) - T(T(9))) \\ 38886 &:= ((T(3) + 8!) + (8!/(-C(8,6)))) \\ 38924 &:= -(((T(3))! - ((8! - T(C(9,2))) - T(4))) \\ 38961 &:= ((3^8) + (T(9) \times (C(6,1)!)) \\ 39036 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + (T(9) + C((-0!) + T(T(3))), 6)) \\ 39204 &:= ((-T(3)) + T(C(9, T(2)))) \times (0! + T(4)) \\ 39281 &:= ((-T(3)) - T(T(9))) - (-2) - (C(8,1)!)) \\ 39312 &:= ((T(3) \times C(9,3)) \times T(12)) \\ 39454 &:= (((-3) \times T(T(9))) + C(4!, 5)) + T(T(4)) \\ 39572 &:= (((T(3))! \times T(T((9 - 5)))) - T(C(7, T(T(2)))) \\ 39599 &:= (((T(3))! \times T(T((9 - 5)))) - C(9,9)) \\ 39648 &:= (3 + ((T(9) \times (-C(6,4))) + 8!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39649 &:= -((T(3) - ((9! - C(T(6),4))/9)) \\ 39654 &:= ((T(3) \times 9) + ((C(6,5)! \times T(T(4)))) \\ 39728 &:= ((3 - T((C(9,7) - 2))) + 8!) \\ 39738 &:= (((3 + T(9)) - T(C(7,3))) + 8!) \\ 39739 &:= -((T(T(3)) - ((-9!) + (C(7, T(3)))!)/(-9))) \\ 39853 &:= ((-((3 + 9)) + 8!) - C(T(5),3)) \\ 39883 &:= -((T((T(T(3)) + 9)) - ((8! + C(8, T(3))))) \\ 39887 &:= ((-((3 \times C(9,8))) + 8!) - T(T(7))) \\ 39987 &:= -(((T((3 \times 9)) - T(9)) - (C(8,7)!)) \\ 40038 &:= -((C(4!, (0! + 0!)) + (T(3) - 8!)) \\ 40089 &:= -((C(4!, (0! + 0!)) - (8! + T(9))) \\ 40275 &:= (-C(T(4),02) + ((-7) + T(5)))! \\ 40299 &:= -((T(C(4,02)) + (9!/(-9))) \\ 40300 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + C((-0!) + T(T(3))), T(T((0! + 0!)))) \\ 40425 &:= (T(T(4)) \times ((C(04,2)! + T(5))) \\ 40545 &:= (((T(4!) \times (-0!)) + (C(T(5), T(4)))) \times T(5)) \\ 40548 &:= ((C(T(4),05) - 4!) + 8!) \\ 40581 &:= (T((4! - 0!)) - (T(5) - (C(8,1)!)) \\ 40652 &:= (((4! - 0!) - C(T(6),5)) \times (-2)) \\ 40656 &:= ((T(T(4)) + 0!) \times (C(6,5) + 6!)) \\ 40876 &:= ((T((4! + 0!)) + (C(8,7)!)) + T(T(6))) \\ 40881 &:= (T(((4! + 0!) + 8)) + (C(8,1)!)) \\ 40965 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) - (0! + C((T(9) - T(6)),5))) \\ 40974 &:= ((4! + (-((0! - 9)))! + T(C(7,4))) \\ 41181 &:= (T(41) + (C((1 \times 8),1)!)) \\ 41292 &:= (((T(T(4)) + 1) + T(T(2))) \times T(C(9,2))) \\ 41445 &:= ((-4!) - T(T((-1) + T(4)))) + C(4!,5) \\ 41459 &:= (((T(4) \times (-1)) + C(4!,5)) - T(T(9))) \\ 41481 &:= ((T(41) + T(4!)) + (C(8,1)!)) \\ 41497 &:= ((C(4!, (1 + 4)) - T(T(9))) + (T(7))) \\ 41586 &:= ((T(T((C(4,1) + 5))) + 8!) + T(T(6))) \\ 41624 &:= (C(4!, T((1 \times 6))) + ((T(T(2)))! \times T(T(4)))) \\ 41643 &:= -((T(41) - (T(6) \times C(4!,3))) \\ 41762 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - 1) \times T(7)) - (C(T(6), T(2)))) \\ 41776 &:= ((T((T(T(4)) - 1)) + 7) \times T(C(7,6))) \\ 41861 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - (-1 - (C(8, (6 + 1))))!) \\ 41875 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + ((C((1 \times 8),7)! + T(5))) \\ 41897 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + ((1 + 8!) + C(9,7))) \\ 41975 &:= ((C(T(T((4 - 1))),9)/7) - T(5)) \\ 42039 &:= (C(4!, (T(T(2)) - 0!)) - T((T(T(3)) + 9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}42063 &:= ((C(4!, T(2)) - T(06)) \times T(T(3))) \\42074 &:= (C(4!, (T(T(2)) - 0!)) - (T(T(7)) + (4!))) \\42084 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (T(T(2))))! - ((0! - T(C(8, 4)))) \\42099 &:= (C(4!, (T(T(2)) - 0!)) - (9 \times T(9))) \\42153 &:= (C(4!, (T(T(2)) - 1)) - T((5 + T(T(3)))) \\42159 &:= -((T(4!) - (C(((T(2) + 1))!, 5) - T(9))) \\42204 &:= (C(4!, (2 + T(2))) - T((04)!)) \\42235 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (-T(2)) - (-2) \times C(T(T(3)), 5))) \\42238 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (T((C(T(2), 2)^3)) + 8!)) \\42245 &:= -(((T((4! - 2)) + T(T(2))) - C(4!, 5))) \\42249 &:= ((C(4!, (2 + T(2))) - T(4!)) + T(9)) \\42252 &:= (((C(4!, T(2)) + T(2)) - T(5)) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\42264 &:= (((T(C(T(4), 2)) + T(T(2))) + (6!)) \times 4!) \\42273 &:= (C(4!, (2 + T(2))) - T((7 \times 3))) \\42281 &:= ((-T(T(4))) + T((T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))))) + (C(8, 1)!)) \\42323 &:= ((C(4!, T(2)) - T(T(3))) + ((2^3)!)) \\42329 &:= T(T(T(4))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(9) \\42333 &:= (C(4!, (2 + 3)) - T((3 \times T(3)))) \\42338 &:= ((C(4!, T(2)) - (3 + 3)) + 8!) \\42344 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) + ((3 \times 4) - 4)!) \\42345 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (-T(2))) + ((T(3) + C(4!, 5)))) \\42354 &:= ((C(4!, T(2)) + ((3 + 5)!)) + T(4)) \\42369 &:= (((C(4!, T(2)) - T(3)) \times T(6)) - 9) \\42378 &:= (((C(4!, T(2)) + T(3)) + T(7)) + 8!) \\42381 &:= ((T((T(4) \times T(T(2)))) + T(T(T(3)))) + (C(8, 1)!)) \\42386 &:= ((C(4!, T(2)) + T(T(3))) + ((8! + T(6)))) \\42389 &:= ((C(4!, T((2 \times 3))) + 8!) + T(9)) \\42398 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) + ((T(3) \times 9) + 8!)) \\42399 &:= -((T(C(4, 2)) \times (T(3) - (T(9) \times T(9)))) \\42404 &:= -(((T(4)^2) - C(4!, (0! + (4)))) \\42413 &:= -((T((T(4) + T(2))) - (C(4!, (-1) + T(3)))) \\42433 &:= (T(T(4)) - ((T(T(2)) - (C(4!, 3))) \times T(T(3)))) \\42435 &:= (T(C(T(4), 2)) \times (-4) + (3 \times T(5))) \\42440 &:= -(((4^{T(2)}) - C(4!, (4 + 0!))) \\42444 &:= ((-T(4)) \times T(T(2))) - (C(4!, 4) \times (-4)) \\42445 &:= ((-C(4, T(2))) - T(T(4))) + C(4!, 5) \\42449 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) - (T(T(4)) \times (T(4!) - T(T(9)))) \\42450 &:= -((T(T(4)) - (C(24, 5) + 0!)) \\42451 &:= ((T(T(4)) + (-2) - C(4!, 5)) \times (-1)) \\42452 &:= -((T(T(4)) - (C(24, 5) + T(2)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42455 &:= -(((4^{T(2)}) - (C(4!, 5) + T(5)))) \\ 42458 &:= -(((T(4) - C(24, 5)) + T(8))) \\ 42459 &:= (C((C(4, 2) \times 4), 5) - T(9)) \\ 42462 &:= (T(C(4, 2)) \times (C(4!, T(6)) - 2)) \\ 42466 &:= (4 + ((-2) + C(4!, T(6))) \times T(6)) \\ 42468 &:= ((C(4!, T((2 + 4))) \times T(6)) - T(8)) \\ 42471 &:= (T((4! + 2)) \times (C(T(4), 7) + 1)) \\ 42494 &:= (C(4!, ((-2) - 4!) + T(9))) - T(4) \\ 42497 &:= (C(4!, ((-2) - 4!) + T(9))) - (7) \\ 42499 &:= ((T(4)/(-2)) + C(4!, (T(9)/9))) \\ 42501 &:= (C((C(4, T(2)))!, 5) - T((0! + 1))) \\ 42502 &:= (C(4!, ((T(2) + T(5)) + 0!)) - 2) \\ 42503 &:= (C((C(4, T(2)))!, 5) - ((0 \times 3)!)) \\ 42504 &:= C(4!, ((T(2) \times 5) - T(04))) \\ 42505 &:= (C((C(4, T(2)))!, 5) + ((0 \times 5)!)) \\ 42510 &:= (C((C(4, T(2)))!, 5) + T(T((1 + 0!)))) \\ 42514 &:= ((C(4!, T(2)) \times T((5 + 1))) + T(4)) \\ 42515 &:= ((-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))) + (C(((5 - 1)!), 5))) \\ 42522 &:= (C((C(4, T(2)))!, 5) + (T(T(2)) \times T(2))) \\ 42523 &:= ((C((C(4, T(2)))!, 5) - 2) + T(T(3))) \\ 42524 &:= (C((C(4, T(2)))!, 5) + (2 \times T(4))) \\ 42524 &:= (C((C(4, T(2)))!, 5) + (2 \times T(4))) \\ 42525 &:= ((4! + T(2)) \times (C(T(5), 2) \times T(5))) \\ 42531 &:= (((4 \times 2)! + T(T((C(5, 3) + 1)))) \\ 42532 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times C((5 + 3), 2)) \\ 42537 &:= (C((C(4, T(2)))!, 5) - (T(T(T(3)))/(-7))) \\ 42545 &:= (((4! + 2) + T(5)) + C(4!, 5)) \\ 42548 &:= ((-T(T(4))) - (T(T(2)))!) + (C(T(5), T(4)) + 8!) \\ 42549 &:= (C(4!, ((T(2) \times 5) - T(4))) + T(9)) \\ 42554 &:= (C((C(4, T(2)))!, 5) + (5 \times T(4))) \\ 42559 &:= (C((C(4, T(2)))!, 5) + T(T(-(5 - 9)))) \\ 42564 &:= (C((C(4, T(2)))!, 5) + (6 \times T(4))) \\ 42584 &:= (C((C(4, T(2)))!, 5) + (8 \times T(4))) \\ 42594 &:= (C((C(4, T(2)))!, 5) + (9 \times T(4))) \\ 42595 &:= (T((T(4) + T(2))) + (C((T(5) + 9), 5))) \\ 42645 &:= ((C(T(4), T(2)) + T(6)) + C(4!, 5)) \\ 42654 &:= ((C(4!, T(2)) \times T(6)) + (T(5) \times T(4))) \\ 42675 &:= (C(T(4), 2) + ((-T(6)) \times T(T(7))) \times (-5)) \\ 42693 &:= ((C(4!, -(T(2) - (6)))) + 9) \times T(T(3)) \\ 42694 &:= ((C(4!, T(2)) \times T(6)) + T((9 + T(4)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}42735 &:= (T(T(C(4,2))) + (C(((7-3)!),5))) \\42744 &:= (C(4!, -((2-7))) + (4! \times T(4))) \\42745 &:= ((T(4) + T((T(2) \times 7))) + C(4!,5)) \\42756 &:= ((C(4!, T(2)) + (7+5)) \times T(6)) \\42757 &:= (C(4!, -((2-7))) + T((T(5) + (7)))) \\42777 &:= (T(C(4,2)) \times (7! - T(77))) \\42778 &:= ((C(4!, T(2)) + T(T(7))) + (T(7) + 8!)) \\42804 &:= (T(4!) + C((T(2) \times 8), (0! + (4)))) \\42805 &:= (((4 \times 2)!) + T(C(8, -((0! - (5)))))) \\42824 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) - (-T((8 \times 2))) \times T(4!)) \\42824 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) - (-T((8 \times 2))) \times T(4!)) \\42833 &:= (((C(4!, T(2)) + 8!) - T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(3))!)) \\42861 &:= ((T(4) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) - (-8! - T(T(C(6,1)))) \\42891 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T((T(2) + T(8)))) - C(9,1)) \\42899 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T((T(2) + T(8)))) - C(9,9)) \\42900 &:= (T(T(4)) \times T((T(2) + C(9, (0! + 0!)))))) \\42945 &:= (((T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) \times 9) + C(4!,5)) \\42963 &:= (((T(T(C(4,2))) - T(9)) \times T(T(6))) - 3) \\42983 &:= -(((T(T(4)) - C((2 \times 9), 8)) + (T(3))!)) \\42994 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(-((2-9)))) - C(9,4)) \\43032 &:= (C(4!, (T(3) - 0!)) + T(32)) \\43035 &:= ((T(4!) + T(T(T(3)))) + (C(((0! + 3)!),5))) \\43092 &:= (C(T(4), (T(3) - 0!)) \times T((9 \times 2))) \\43170 &:= (C(4!, (T(3) - 1)) + T(T((7 + 0!)))) \\43174 &:= ((T(T(C(4,3))) - 1) + (T(7) \times T(T(T(4)))))) \\43203 &:= (((C(T(4), 3)^2) + 0!) \times 3) \\43228 &:= (((C(T(4), T(3)) - 2)^2) - T(8)) \\43233 &:= (C(4!, (3 + 2)) + (3^{T(3)})) \\43245 &:= ((4! + (T(3))!) - (T(2) - C(4!, 5))) \\43248 &:= (((C(T(4), 3) + 2) \times 4!) + 8!) \\43254 &:= ((-4!) \times T(T(3))) + C((T(2) + T(5)), T(4)) \\43255 &:= (T(T(4)) + ((C(3,2) \times 5!) \times 5!)) \\43263 &:= (((C(T(4), 3)^2) + T(6)) \times 3) \\43264 &:= ((C(T(4), T(3)) - 2)^{6-4}) \\43266 &:= (((C(4!, 3) + 2) \times T(6)) + 6!) \\43269 &:= ((C(4!, (3 + 2)) + 6!) + T(9)) \\43320 &:= (C(T(4), 3) \times (((T(3))!/2) + 0!)) \\43336 &:= (-C(4!, 3)) - ((T(3))! \times (-3 \times T(6))) \\43395 &:= (T(T(4)) \times (-3 - C((3 + 9), 5))) \\43404 &:= ((T(4!) \times 3) + C(4!, (0! + (4))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43431 &:= ((T(4!) \times (T(3) \times 4!)) + T(T(T(C(3,1)))))) \\ 43439 &:= (-(T(4)) + (T(T(3)) \times (C(4!,3) + T(9)))) \\ 43488 &:= (((C(T(4),3) \times T(4)) + 8) \times T(8)) \\ 43539 &:= (C(4!, ((3+5) - 3)) + T(T(9))) \\ 43549 &:= ((C((C(4,3))!,5) + T(4)) + T(T(9))) \\ 43555 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times C((-3) + T(5)),5) - 5) \\ 43558 &:= ((4 + T(T(T(3)))) + (C(T(5),5) + 8!)) \\ 43572 &:= -(((4! - ((3+5)!) - C(T(7),T(2)))) \\ 43575 &:= ((T((4^3)) - 5) \times C(7,5)) \\ 43594 &:= ((C((C(4,3))!,5) + T(T(9))) + T(T(4))) \\ 43659 &:= (T((4! - 3)) \times (T(C(6,5)) \times 9)) \\ 43669 &:= (T(C(4,3)) + (T(T(6)) \times (T(6) \times 9))) \\ 43673 &:= ((T((4^3)) \times T(6)) - C(7,T(3))) \\ 43734 &:= (C((4! - T(3)), (7+3)) - 4!) \\ 43748 &:= ((-4) - T(3)) + C((T(7) - T(4)),8)) \\ 43749 &:= (C(((4) - T(3)) + T(7)),T(4)) - 9) \\ 43754 &:= (-4) + C(-((3 - C(7,5))),T(4)) \\ 43758 &:= C((4! - T(3)), ((7 - 5) + 8)) \\ 43768 &:= (T(4) + C(((T(T(3))/7) \times 6),8)) \\ 43795 &:= ((T(T(C(4,3))) + T(T(7))) \times 95) \\ 43813 &:= (C((4! - T(3)),8) + T(T((1+3)))) \\ 43814 &:= ((C((4! - T(3)),8) + 1) + T(T(4))) \\ 43822 &:= (C((4! - T(3)),8) + (2^{T(T(2))})) \\ 43824 &:= (4! \times (T(3) + (C((8 \times 2),4)))) \\ 43829 &:= ((C(4!,3) + 8!) + T((T(T(2)) \times 9))) \\ 43834 &:= ((C((4! - T(3)),8) + T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \\ 43836 &:= (C((4! - T(3)),8) + T((T(3) + (6)))) \\ 43838 &:= (-(T(4)) + ((3 \times T(C(8,T(3)))) \times T(8))) \\ 43849 &:= (C((4! - T(3)),8) + T((4+9))) \\ 43854 &:= ((C((4! - T(3)),8) + 5!) - 4!) \\ 43864 &:= ((4! + (T(3))!) + (C(8,6) \times T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 43865 &:= -((T(T(C(4,3))) - (8! + (6! \times 5)))) \\ 43878 &:= (C((4! - T(3)),8) + T((7+8))) \\ 43885 &:= (T((C(T(4),3) - T(8))) + ((8! - 5))) \\ 43892 &:= (((-4) + T(3)) + 8!) + T(C(9,T(2))) \\ 43893 &:= (C((4! - T(3)),8) + (T(9) \times 3)) \\ 43935 &:= ((4 + C((3 \times 9),3)) \times T(5)) \\ 43953 &:= ((C(4!,3) + (T(T(9))/T(5))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 43956 &:= (T((C(4,3) \times 9)) \times T((5+6))) \\ 43968 &:= ((T((4 \times 3)) + T(C(9,6))) + 8!)$$

$$\begin{aligned}44023 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + ((C(4!, (-0!) + T(T(2)))) - T(T(3)))) \\44034 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (C(4!, -((0! - T(3)))) - T(4)) \\44037 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (C(4!, -((0! - T(3)))) - 7)) \\44042 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (C(4!, (0! + (4))) - 2)) \\44044 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (C(4!, 04) \times 4)) \\44044 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (C(4!, 04) \times 4)) \\44045 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (((4 \times 0)! + C(4!, 5))) \\44058 &:= (T(4!) + C(((4 - 0!) + T(5)), 8)) \\44115 &:= ((C(T(4), 4)^{1+1}) + T(5)) \\44124 &:= ((C(T(4), 4)^{1 \times 2}) + 4!) \\44157 &:= (C(4!, (4 + 1)) + T(57)) \\44205 &:= ((C(T(4), 4)^2) + T(-((0! - T(5)))) \\44235 &:= ((4! + C((4! + T(2)), 3)) \times T(5)) \\44244 &:= (-4) \times (T(C(T(4), 2)) - ((T(4)!/T(4!))) \\44244 &:= (-4) \times (T(C(T(4), 2)) - ((T(4)!/T(4!))) \\44262 &:= (-(((T(4)^4) + 2)) + C(T(6), T(T(2)))) \\44266 &:= -((((T(4)^4) - 2) - C(T(6), 6))) \\44268 &:= ((C(T(4), 4)^2) - (T(6) \times (-8))) \\44275 &:= ((T(T(4)) + C(T(4), T(2))) \times T((7 + T(5)))) \\44310 &:= (C(T(4), 4) \times (T((T(T(3)) - 1) + 0!)) \\44332 &:= -(((T(4!) + (C(4!, 3))) - (T(3)^{T(T(2))})) \\44334 &:= ((4! \times 4!) + C((3 \times T(3)), T(4))) \\44349 &:= (((C(4!, 4) + (T(3)!)) \times 4) - T(T(9))) \\44358 &:= ((T(4!) + T(4!)) + C((3 + T(5)), 8)) \\44400 &:= (T(4!) + ((C(T(4), 4)^{0!+0!})) \\44424 &:= (T(4!) + ((C(T(4), 4)^2) + 4!)) \\44478 &:= (((4!/4)!) + C(-((T(4) - T(7))), 8)) \\44484 &:= (44 \times (T(C(T(4), 8)) - (4!))) \\44499 &:= -((C(4!, 4) - (T(49) \times T(9)))) \\44533 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + C(4!, 5)) - T(T(T(3)))) + ((T(3)!)) \\44577 &:= -((T(4!) - ((4! - C(T(5), 7)) \times (-7))) \\44588 &:= (4 + (C(4!, 5) + T((8 \times 8)))) \\44593 &:= ((T(4) + C(4!, 5)) + (9 \times T(T(T(3)))) \\44594 &:= ((T(4) + C(4!, 5)) + T((9 + T(T(4)))) \\44596 &:= -(((T(4!) \times T(4!)) - (C((T(5) + 9), 6))) \\44616 &:= ((-4) - C(4!, T(6))) \times (-1 - T(6)) \\44632 &:= (-C(4!, (4! - T(6)))) + (T(3)^{T(T(2))}) \\44633 &:= (((-4) + C(4!, 6))/3) - T(T(T(3))) \\44636 &:= ((4 - C(4!, T(6))) + (T(3)^6))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}44748 &:= (T(44) + C((T(7) - T(4)), 8)) \\44789 &:= (-4) + (C(-((T(4) - T(7))), 8) + T(T(9))) \\44796 &:= ((C(4!, 4) - T(79)) \times 6) \\44892 &:= (T((4! \times 4)) + ((8! - C(9, T(2)))) \\44973 &:= -(((4!^4) - 9) - C(T(7), T(3))) \\44998 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - (T(4!) - C((9 + 9), 8))) \\45009 &:= ((-4) + C(T(5), T(T((0! + 0!)))) \times 9) \\45025 &:= ((C(4!, 5) + 0!) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-5!))) \\45034 &:= (C(4!, 5) + (T((0! + T(T(3)))) \times T(4))) \\45035 &:= -((T(4) - (C((T(5) - 0!), T(3)) \times T(5)))) \\45045 &:= (C((T(4) + (5)), T(04)) \times T(5)) \\45049 &:= (4 + (C((T(5) - 0!), T(4)) \times T(9))) \\45054 &:= (4! - (T(5) \times (0! - C(T(5), T(4)))) \\45054 &:= (4! - (T(5) \times (0! - C(T(5), T(4)))) \\45055 &:= (T(4) + (C(T(5), 05) \times T(5))) \\45069 &:= (4! + (C(T(5), 06) \times 9)) \\45105 &:= ((4 + C(T(5), 10)) \times T(5)) \\45116 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) - ((C(5, 1) + 1)^6)) \\45132 &:= (C(4!, 5) + T((((1 + 3)! \times T(2)))) \\45195 &:= ((T(4) + C(T(5), (1 + 9))) \times T(5)) \\45225 &:= -(((T(4) - (T(C(5, 2))^2)) \times T(5)) \\45234 &:= ((C(T(4), 5) \times (-2) + (T(3))!)/4) \\45255 &:= ((4! - C(T(5), T(2))) \times (T(5) - 5!)) \\45258 &:= ((T(4!) \times 5) + C((T(2) + T(5)), 8)) \\45287 &:= (-T(4) + (C(T(5), T(T(2))) + ((8! - T(7)))) \\45289 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (C((T(5) + T(2)), 8) - 9)) \\45325 &:= (C((T(4) + (5)), T(3)) + ((T(2) + (5))!)) \\45328 &:= ((C((T(4) + (5)), T(3)) + T(2)) + 8!) \\45331 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T((5!/3))) + T(T(T(C(3, 1)))) \\45335 &:= (T(4) + (C(T(5), T(3)) + ((3 + 5)!)) \\45338 &:= (T(4) + ((C(T(5), T(3)) + 3) + 8!)) \\45354 &:= (C(4!, 5) + T((3 \times (T(5) + T(4)))) \\45354 &:= (C(4!, 5) + T((3 \times (T(5) + T(4)))) \\45360 &:= (C(T(4), 5) \times (3 \times 60)) \\45405 &:= ((4! + C(T(5), T(4))) \times T(05)) \\45432 &:= (4! \times (C(T(5), 4) + T(32))) \\45435 &:= (T(4!) + ((C(T(5), T(4)) + T(3)) \times T(5))) \\45454 &:= (C(4!, 5) - ((T(4!) - 5) \times (-T(4)))) \\45454 &:= (C(4!, 5) - ((T(4!) - 5) \times (-T(4)))) \\45499 &:= (((T(4!) \times (-C(T(5), 4))) + 9)/(-9))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 45507 &:= (C(4!, 5) + T((T((T(5) - 0!)) - (T(7)))))) \\ 45522 &:= ((C(4!, 5) + T(5)) + T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(2)))) \\ 45544 &:= ((C(4!, 5) + T(5)) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 45583 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + ((C(T(5), 5) + 8!) + (T(3)!)) \\ 45585 &:= ((C((T(4) + (5)), 5) + T(8)) \times T(5)) \\ 45597 &:= ((C(T(4), 5) - T(5)) - (-9 \times 7!)) \\ 45625 &:= ((T(4!) + (C(T(5), 6))) + ((T(2) + (5)))!) \\ 45628 &:= (T(4!) + ((C(T(5), 6) + T(2)) + 8!)) \\ 45647 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) + ((C(T(5), 6) - 4!)) \times 7) \\ 45654 &:= (C(4!, 5) + ((T(6) \times T(5)) \times T(4))) \\ 45654 &:= (C(4!, 5) + ((T(6) \times T(5)) \times T(4))) \\ 45676 &:= (4 \times (C((-5) + T(6), 7) - T(6))) \\ 45696 &:= ((4 \times T((-5) + T(6))) \times C(9, 6)) \\ 45699 &:= ((C(4!, 5) + T((6!/9))) - T(9)) \\ 45724 &:= ((C(4!, 5) + (7!/T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\ 45728 &:= (C(4!, 5) + ((T(T(7)) - T(2)) \times 8)) \\ 45736 &:= ((T(4)^5) - (C((7 \times 3), 6))) \\ 45744 &:= (C(4!, 5) + T(((7 \times T(4)) + T(4)))) \\ 45752 &:= (C(4!, 5) + (T(T(7)) \times (5 + T(2)))) \\ 45759 &:= (C(4!, 5) + (7 \times T(-((T(5) - T(9)))))) \\ 45773 &:= ((C(4!, 5) - (7)) + C(T(7), 3)) \\ 45825 &:= (C(4!, 5) + T((T(8) + (T(2) \times T(5)))))) \\ 45843 &:= ((C(4!, 5) + T(84)) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 45857 &:= ((-4) + (C(T(5), 8) + 5!)) \times 7 \\ 45858 &:= ((C(4!, 5) + (8!/T(5))) + T(T(8))) \\ 45864 &:= (C(T(4), 5) \times ((8 + 6!)/4)) \\ 45876 &:= (4 \times ((C(T(5), 8) + 7!) - (6))) \\ 45891 &:= ((T((T(4) \times 5)) \times T(8)) - C(9, 1)) \\ 45899 &:= ((T((T(4) \times 5)) \times T(8)) - C(9, 9)) \\ 45924 &:= (4! - (T(5) \times (-C((9 \times 2), 4)))) \\ 45996 &:= (((4^5) \times T(9)) - (C(9, 6))) \\ 46204 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times C(T(6), 2)) + 0!) \times 4) \\ 46207 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T(C(6, 2))) + 0!) \times 7) \\ 46227 &:= (T(4!) + (T(6) \times (C(T(2), 2)^7))) \\ 46230 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) + C(6, T(T(2)))) \times 30) \\ 46239 &:= (4! + (C(6, 2) \times T(T((3 + 9)))))) \\ 46244 &:= (T(T(4)) + (C(C(6, T(2)), T(4))/4)) \\ 46299 &:= (-C((4 \times 6), 2) - (T(T(9)) \times (-T(9)))) \\ 46386 &:= (((C(4!, T(6)) \times 3) + 8!) - (6)) \\ 46430 &:= ((T(T(-((4 - C(6, 4)))))) \times T(T(3))) - 0!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46434 &:= (((-T(4) + T(T(6))) \times C(T(4), T(3))) + (4!)) \\ 46466 &:= -((T((4 + C(6, 4))) - ((6^6))) \\ 46485 &:= (T(4!) + ((C(T(6), 4) + 8!) - 5!)) \\ 46508 &:= (C((-4) + T(6), 5) + (08)!) \\ 46552 &:= (C(4!, T(6)) \times ((5 \times 5) - 2)) \\ 46567 &:= (T(T(4)) + ((C(T(6), T(5)) \times (-6))/(-7))) \\ 46572 &:= ((T(4) - (C(T(6), T(5))/(-7))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 46573 &:= ((C(4!, T(6)) \times (-5) + T(7)) + T(T(3))) \\ 46575 &:= (((4 \times 6!) + C(T(5), 7)) \times 5) \\ 46588 &:= ((C(4!, T(6)) \times (T(5) + 8)) + T(8)) \\ 46631 &:= ((-4) - T(6)) + (6^{T(C(3,1))}) \\ 46642 &:= -(((T(4) - ((6^6))) + C(4, T(2)))) \\ 46683 &:= (T(T(4)) + ((6^6) - C(8, T(3)))) \\ 46711 &:= (T(T(4)) + ((6^{C(7,1)-1})) \\ 46745 &:= ((T(T(4)) + T(T((6 + 7)))) + C(4!, 5)) \\ 46839 &:= (C((4! - 6), 8) + T(T((3 + 9)))) \\ 46859 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + ((-6) + 8!) + C(T(5), 9)) \\ 46881 &:= (((4! - T(6))^8) + (C(8, 1))!) \\ 46979 &:= (C(4!, T(6)) - ((T(9) - 7!) \times 9)) \\ 47196 &:= ((C(4!, 7)/(-1) + T(9)) \times 6) \\ 47244 &:= (((T(4!) \times T(C(7, T(2)))) - (4!))/4) \\ 47245 &:= (((T(4!) \times T(C(7, T(2))))/4) - 5) \\ 47262 &:= ((-4!) + T(C(7, T(2)))) + (6^{T(T(2))}) \\ 47282 &:= ((-4) + T(C(7, T(2)))) + ((T(8)^{T(2)}) \\ 47286 &:= (((T(4!) - C(T(7), T(T(2))))/(-8)) + T(T(6))) \\ 47319 &:= ((T(4) \times 7!) - T(T((C(3, 1) + 9)))) \\ 47327 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T((C(7, 3) + T(T(2)))) - (T(7))) \\ 47336 &:= (C((4! - 7), 3) + (T(3)^6)) \\ 47376 &:= ((T(47) \times T(3)) \times C(7, 6)) \\ 47388 &:= (T(4!) - ((C(T(7), T(3)) - T(8))/(-8))) \\ 47394 &:= ((T((4 + 7)) \times (T(3))!) - C(9, 4)) \\ 47436 &:= (T((4 + C(7, 4))) + (T(3)^6)) \\ 47582 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) - ((C(T(7), 5) - T(8))/2))) \\ 47587 &:= -((T(4!) - ((T(T(7)) + C(T(5), 8)) \times 7))) \\ 47638 &:= (T(4) + ((-7) + C(T(6), 3)) \times T(8)) \\ 47652 &:= (T((4 + 7)) \times ((C(6, 5))! + 2)) \\ 47684 &:= (((T(4) \times 7!) - T(T(6))) - (T(C(8, 4)))) \\ 47685 &:= (((T(4))! + C(T(7), 6))/(-T(8) - 5!)) \\ 47825 &:= -((T(T(4)) - ((-7) + T(C(8, 2))) \times 5!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 47833 &:= (-47) + (T(8) \times C(T(T(3)), 3)) \\ 47852 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times T(T(7))) + T(C(8, 5))) \times 2) \\ 47853 &:= (C(-((T(4) - T(7))), 8) + T((T(5) \times T(3)))) \\ 47863 &:= -(((4! - 7) - (T(8) \times C(T(6), 3))) \\ 47900 &:= (C(-((T(4) - T(7))), 9) - (T(T((0! + 0!))))!) \\ 48249 &:= ((T(4!) \times (-T(8))) + ((T(2)^{C(T(4), 9)})) \\ 48255 &:= (((-4) + T(C(8, 2))) \times 5!) + T(5) \\ 48262 &:= ((T(4) + T(C(8, T(2)))) + (6^{T(T(2))})) \\ 48339 &:= (((4! \times 8!) / C(T(3), 3) - T(9)) \\ 48352 &:= ((4! + 8!) + C((T(T(3)) - 5), T(T(2)))) \\ 48374 &:= ((4! \times T((C(8, 3) + 7))) - T(4)) \\ 48377 &:= ((4! \times T((C(8, 3) + 7))) - 7) \\ 48382 &:= (((4! \times C(8, 3)) \times T(8)) - 2) \\ 48435 &:= (((4! + T(C(8, 4))) + (T(3)!) \times T(5)) \\ 48529 &:= -((T(T(4)) + (T(8) - C((T(5) + T(2)), 9)))) \\ 48534 &:= (((C(4!, 8) \times 5) - T(T(3))) - (T(4)!) \\ 48537 &:= (T(C(T(4), 8)) - (-((5! - 3) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 48545 &:= -((T(T(4)) - (T(8) \times (C(T(5), 4) - T(5)))) \\ 48572 &:= ((T((T(4) \times 8)) \times T(5)) - T(C(7, T(T(2)))) \\ \\ 48579 &:= ((C((-((4 - 8)))!, 5) + (7!)) + T(T(9))) \\ 48591 &:= ((T((T(4) \times 8)) \times T(5)) - C(9, 1)) \\ 48595 &:= (((C(T(4), 8) \times 5!) \times 9) - 5) \\ 48599 &:= ((T((T(4) \times 8)) \times T(5)) - C(9, 9)) \\ 48600 &:= (T((T(4) \times 8)) \times C(6, (0! + 0!))) \\ 48635 &:= (C((T(4) + 8), (6 + 3)) + T(5)) \\ 48639 &:= (T(T(4)) - ((T(8) - (C((6 \times 3), 9)))) \\ 48642 &:= (T((C(T(4), 8) + T(6))) \times (4! - 2)) \\ 48665 &:= -((T(T(4)) - (T(T((8 - C(6, 6)))) \times 5!)) \\ 48792 &:= (4! \times (C(8, 7) + (T(9)^2))) \\ 48836 &:= (-((T(4) - 8!)) + (T(C(8, T(3))) \times T(6))) \\ 48920 &:= (C((T(4) + 8), 9) + T(((T(2) + 0!)!)) \\ 48944 &:= ((C((T(4) + 8), 9) + 4!) + T(4!)) \\ 48945 &:= (C((T(4) + 8), 9) + T((T(4) + T(5)))) \\ 48972 &:= (-4) \times ((-8) - T(9)) \times T(C(7, 2))) \\ 48987 &:= (T(C(T(4), 8)) - ((-9!) \times T(T(8))) / 7!) \\ 48989 &:= ((C((T(4) + 8), 9) - T(T(8))) + T(T(9))) \\ 48998 &:= (C((T(4) + 8), 9) + T((-9) + T(8))) \\ 49221 &:= ((-4) \times T(T(9))) + (T(T(T(T(2))))^{C(2, 1)}) \\ 49227 &:= (C(-((4! - T(9))), T(T(2))) + ((T(2) - 7!))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 49229 &:= -((T(T(4)) + ((T(C(9,2)))^2)/(-9))) \\ 49236 &:= (((T(4!) \times T(T(9)))/T(2)) - C(T(T(3)),6)) \\ 49259 &:= (C(-((4! - T(9))),T(T(2))) - C(T(5),9)) \\ 49274 &:= -((T(4) + (T(C(9,2)) \times (-74))) \\ 49282 &:= ((-((T(4) - C(9,T(2)))) \times T(T(8))) - 2) \\ 49590 &:= -((T(4) \times (T(9) - (C(T(5),9) - 0!))) \\ 49595 &:= -(((T(4) \times (T(9) - C(T(5),9))) + (5))) \\ 49611 &:= ((4! + T(9)) \times (6! - C(1,1))) \\ 49632 &:= ((T(4) + (C(9,6))) \times T(32)) \\ 49656 &:= -((4! + ((-C(9,6) + T(5)) \times 6!)) \\ 49663 &:= (T(T(4)) - (T(96) - C(T(6),T(3)))) \\ 49673 &:= (((4! + T(9)) \times 6!) - C(7,T(3))) \\ 49722 &:= (((4! \times T(T(9))) + C(7,2)) \times 2) \\ 49724 &:= (4 \times (C((T(9) - T(7)),T(T(2))) + T(T(4)))) \\ 49725 &:= (T((C(T(4),9) + (7))) \times T(25)) \\ 49740 &:= (C(T(4),9) \times (7! - T((T(4) + 0!)))) \\ 49749 &:= ((T(T(4)) + T(C(9,7))) \times (4! + T(9))) \\ 49763 &:= -(((T((T(4) \times 9)) + T(T(7))) - (C(T(6),T(3)))) \\ 49825 &:= (T(4) + (T((C(9,8)^2)) \times T(5))) \\ 49940 &:= (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(9)) - (C(9,4) + 0!))) \\ 50045 &:= ((C(T(5),T(T((0! + 0!)))) \times T(4)) - 5) \\ 50050 &:= (C(T(5),T(T((0! + 0!)))) \times T((5 - 0!))) \\ 50232 &:= (T(C((T(5) - 0!),2)) \times (T(3) \times 2)) \\ 50267 &:= -(((5! + 0!) - C((-2) + T(6),7)) \\ 50268 &:= (C(T((5 + 0!)),T(T(2))) + (-6) \times T(T(8))) \\ 50379 &:= (C(((T(5) + 0!) + 3),7) - 9) \\ 50384 &:= (-((T(5) + 0!) + ((T(3))! \times C(8,4))) \\ 51282 &:= ((T(T(C((5 - 1),2))) \times T(T(8)))/T(2)) \\ 51475 &:= ((T(5) \times C(14,7)) - (5)) \\ 51480 &:= (T(5) \times C(14,(8 - 0!))) \\ 51576 &:= -((C(T((5 + 1)),T(5)) - (7! \times T(6))) \\ 51636 &:= -((T((51 + T(6))) - C(T(T(3)),6)) \\ 51784 &:= ((C((T(5) + 1),7) + 8!) + 4!) \\ 51975 &:= ((5 \times T((1 \times 9))) \times T(C(7,5))) \\ 51976 &:= (T((T(5) + 1)) + (9!/C(7,6))) \\ 52053 &:= -((T(T((5 + T(T(2)))) - C(T((0! + (5))),T(3)))) \\ 52248 &:= (C(T(T((5 - 2))),T(T(2))) - T((T(T(4)) + 8))) \\ 52266 &:= ((T(T((5 + T(2)))) \times (-T(2))) + (C(T(6),6))) \\ 52284 &:= (C(T(T((5 - 2))),T(T(2))) + (-T(8)) \times T(T(4))) \\ 52297 &:= ((C(T(5),T(2)) + 2) - (9!/(-7))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 52325 &:= (C(T(5), T(2)) \times (((3+2))! - (5))) \\ 52325 &:= (C(T(5), T(2)) \times (((3+2))! - (5))) \\ 52332 &:= (((C(T(5), T(T(2))) - T(T(3))) \times T(T(3)))/2) \\ 52344 &:= (((C(T(5), 2) \times T(T(3))) - (4!)) \times 4!) \\ 52345 &:= ((T(T(C(5, 2))) \times 34) - T(5)) \\ 52360 &:= (T(T(C(5, 2))) \times (T(3) + T((6+0!)))) \\ 52375 &:= ((T(T(C(5, 2))) \times (T(3) + T(7))) + T(5)) \\ 52405 &:= ((-5) - (T(T(2))))! + (C((4! + 0!), 5)) \\ 52415 &:= ((5 - (T(T(2))))! + C((4! + 1), 5)) \\ 52425 &:= (((T(5))^{T(2)} + C(T(4), T(2))) \times T(5)) \\ 52425 &:= (((T(5))^{T(2)} + C(T(4), T(2))) \times T(5)) \\ 52433 &:= ((-5!) - T((T(2) + T(T(4)))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3)))) \\ 52442 &:= (5 + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-4 + T(T(C(4, 2)))))) \\ 52445 &:= (-T(C(5, 2)) + (T(4!) \times (T(T(4)) + (5!)))) \\ 52500 &:= (C(T(5), 2) \times 500) \\ 52527 &:= ((-5!) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times 7)) \\ 52533 &:= ((5! - T(2)) \times (C(T(5), 3) - T(3))) \\ 52544 &:= (5! + ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) - T(T(T(4)))) - T(4!))) \\ 52556 &:= ((C(T(5), T(2)) \times (5! - 5)) + T(T(6))) \\ 52558 &:= (5 + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) - T(58))) \\ 52584 &:= (C(T(T((5-2))), T(5)) - (8!/4!)) \\ 52604 &:= (-5!) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6) - T(T(T(04)))) \\ 52629 &:= ((5! - (T(T(2))))! + ((C(T(6), T(T(2))) - T(T(9)))) \\ 52649 &:= (-5!) + ((C(T(T(T(2))), 6) - T(T(T(4)))) + T(9)) \\ 52688 &:= ((C((T(5) + 2), 6) + 8!) - 8) \\ 52694 &:= (T(5) + ((C(T(T(T(2))), 6) - T(9)) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 52720 &:= (C(5, 2) \times ((7! + T(T(T(T(2)))) + 0!)) \\ 52724 &:= (C(T(T((5-2))), T((7-2))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 52725 &:= ((5 \times T((2 + C(7, T(2)))) \times T(5)) \\ 52725 &:= ((5 \times T((2 + C(7, T(2)))) \times T(5)) \\ 52745 &:= ((C(T(5), 4) - T(T(7))) \times T((2 \times 5))) \\ 52773 &:= ((T((C(5, 2) \times 7)) + T(7)) \times T(T(3))) \\ 52794 &:= (((T(5) - 2) + T(T(7))) \times C(9, 4)) \\ 52824 &:= ((-C(5, 2) + T(T((8 + T(2)))) \times 4!) \\ 52833 &:= -((T(((T(5) + 2) + T(8))) - C(T(T(3)), T(3)))) \\ 52844 &:= (5! + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(T((8/4)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 52845 &:= (((C(5, 4))! + T(82)) \times T(5)) \\ 52858 &:= (T(52) + (8 \times C(T(5), 8))) \\ 52863 &:= ((-T(5) - (T(T(2))))! - (T(T(8)) - (C(T(6), T(3)))) \\ 52933 &:= ((-5) - T((T(T(2)) + T(9)))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 52944 &:= ((-5) + T(C((T(2) + 9), T(4)))) \times 4! \\ 52983 &:= (-((C(T(5), 2) - T((9 \times 8)))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 53088 &:= ((T((T(C(5, 3)) + 0!)) \times 8) + 8!) \\ 53109 &:= (-5! + (C(T(T(3)), T(T((1 + 0!)))) - T(T(9)))) \\ 53115 &:= -((T(5) - C(((3 + 1)! + 1), 5))) \\ 53125 &:= (-5) + C(((T(3) - 1)^2), 5) \\ 53130 &:= C((5^{3-1}), (T(3) - 0!)) \\ 53135 &:= (5 + C((31 - T(3)), 5)) \\ 53135 &:= (5 + C((31 - T(3)), 5)) \\ 53145 &:= (T(5) + (C(((3 + 1)!), 4) \times 5)) \\ 53184 &:= ((5 + T(T((C(3, 1) + 8)))) \times 4!) \\ 53200 &:= ((5! \times C(T(T(3)), T(2)))/T((0! + 0!))) \\ 53208 &:= (((5 \times C(T(T(3)), T(2))) + 0!) \times 8) \\ 53214 &:= ((-T(5) + C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))) - T(T((-1) + T(4)))) \\ 53224 &:= (((5! \times C(T(T(3)), T(2)))/T(2)) + (4!)) \\ 53229 &:= (C((T(5) + T(3)), (2 \times T(2))) - T(T(9))) \\ 53230 &:= (-T((T(5) \times 3)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) + 0!)) \\ 53232 &:= -(((T((T(5) \times 3)) - T(2)) - C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))))) \\ 53234 &:= ((5 + C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))) - T((T(T(3)) + (4!)))) \\ 53235 &:= (C(T(5), 3) \times ((T(2) - T(3)) + 5!)) \\ 53235 &:= (C(T(5), 3) \times ((T(2) - T(3)) + 5!)) \\ 53239 &:= (C(5, 3) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - T(T(9)))) \\ 53256 &:= -(((C(T(5), 3) \times (T(2) - 5!)) - T(6))) \\ 53257 &:= (-T((T(5) \times 3)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + (T(7)))) \\ 53259 &:= (T(5) + ((C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) + T(5)) - T(T(9)))) \\ 53269 &:= ((5!/3) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6) - T(T(9)))) \\ 53298 &:= ((5! + T(T(3))) \times T((T(2) \times C(9, 8)))) \\ 53306 &:= (-T(C(5, 3)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(06)))) \\ 53324 &:= ((-C(T(5), T(3)) - (T(3))!) + ((T(2)^{T(4)})) \\ 53326 &:= (-((T(5) + C(T(3), 3)) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 53336 &:= ((-5) - C(T(3), 3) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 53342 &:= (5 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (C(4, T(2))!)) \\ 53349 &:= (5! + (C(T(T(3)), C(T(3), 4)) - T(T(9)))) \\ 53355 &:= ((C(T(5), 3) \times (-3) + 5!) + 5!) \\ 53358 &:= (-5! + ((C(T(T(3)), T(3)) - (5!)) - T(T(8)))) \\ 53364 &:= (5! + ((C(T(T(3)), T(3)) - (6!)) - T(4!))) \\ 53371 &:= (C(5, 3) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T((7 - 1)))) \\ 53373 &:= (5 + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(7, T(3)))) \\ 53377 &:= (T(5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(7, 7))) \\ 53392 &:= (-5) + ((T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(9, 2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53397 &:= ((T((T(5) + T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(9,7)) \\ 53416 &:= (T(C(5,3)) - (T(T(T((4-1)))) \times (-T(T(6)))))) \\ 53426 &:= ((T(C(5,3)) + T(4)) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 53436 &:= ((5 \times C(T(3),4)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 53445 &:= ((T(5) \times T(T(3))) - (C(4!,4) \times (-5))) \\ 53466 &:= (T((C(5,3) + 4)) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 53478 &:= (-5! + (C(T(T(3)),T(-(4-7)))) - T(T(8))) \\ 53519 &:= ((C(T(5),3) \times 5!) - T((1 + T(9)))) \\ 53523 &:= (-T(5) + ((C(T(T(3)),T(5)) - T(T(2))) - (T(3)!))) \\ 53526 &:= (-T(5) + (C(T(T(3)),T(5)) - ((T(2) + 6!))) \\ 53528 &:= (5 + (C(T(T(3)),T(5)) - T((2 + T(8)))) \\ 53529 &:= ((-T(5)) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))) - (-((T(2) - 9)))! \\ 53530 &:= (-T(5) + ((C(T(T(3)),T(5)) - (T(3)!) + 0!)) \\ 53532 &:= (-T(5) + ((C(T(T(3)),T(5)) - (T(3)!) + T(2))) \\ 53533 &:= (-5) + ((C(T(T(3)),T(5)) - (T(3)!) - T(3)) \\ 53534 &:= ((C((T(5) + T(3)),T(5)) - (T(3)!) - T(4)) \\ 53536 &:= (-5) + (C(T(T(3)),T(5)) + (-3 - 6!)) \\ 53537 &:= ((C((T(5) + T(3)),T(5)) - (T(3)!) - 7) \\ 53538 &:= (T(5) + (C(T(T(3)),T(5)) - (T(38)))) \\ 53539 &:= (-5) + (C(T(T(3)),T(5)) - (-((3-9)!)) \\ 53543 &:= (-5) + ((C(T(T(3)),T(5)) + 4) - (T(3)!)) \\ 53544 &:= (C((T(5) + T(3)),T(5)) - ((4!/4)!)) \\ 53548 &:= (5 + ((C(T(T(3)),T(5)) - T(T(4))) - T(T(8)))) \\ 53560 &:= (T(5) + (C(T(T(3)),T(5)) - ((6! - 0!))) \\ 53562 &:= (T(5) + (C(T(T(3)),T(5)) - (6! - T(2)))) \\ 53564 &:= ((5! + (C(T(T(3)),T(5)) + (6!)) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 53567 &:= (-5) + (C(T(T(3)),T(5)) - ((6! - T(7)))) \\ 53572 &:= ((5! + C(T(T(3)),T(5))) + (T(T(7)) \times (-2))) \\ 53582 &:= ((5 + (C(T(T(3)),T(5)) - T(T(8)))) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 53583 &:= (-5!) + (C(T(T(3)),T(5)) - T((T(8) - 3))) \\ 53589 &:= ((C((T(5) + T(3)),T(5)) - T(T(8))) - 9) \\ 53598 &:= (C((T(5) + T(3)),(T(5) - 9)) - T(T(8))) \\ 53602 &:= (C(5,3) - (-((T(T(6)) + 0!) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 53622 &:= ((T((T(5) - 3)) + C(T(6),T(T(2)))) - (T(T(2)))! \\ 53626 &:= (-C(T(5),3) + ((T(T(6))^2) + (6!))) \\ 53627 &:= -((T((T(5) + T(3))) - (C(T(6),T(T(2))) - T(T(7)))))) \\ 53628 &:= ((5 \times T(3)) + (C(T(6),T(T(2))) - T(T(8)))) \\ 53638 &:= (((5!/3) + C(T(6),T(3))) - T(T(8))) \\ 53648 &:= (-5) + ((C(T(T(3)),6) + T(T(4))) - T(T(8))) \\ 53649 &:= (5! + ((C(T(T(3)),6) + T(4!)) - T(T(9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53654 &:= ((5! - (T(3))!) + ((C(T(6), T(5)) - T(4)))) \\ 53657 &:= ((5! - (T(3))!) + ((C(T(6), T(5)) - (7)))) \\ 53662 &:= ((5! - (T(3))!) + (C(T(6), 6) - 2)) \\ 53681 &:= (5! + (C(T(T(3)), 6) - T((T(8) + 1)))) \\ 53684 &:= (((T(T(C(5, 3))) - 6) \times T(8)) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 53718 &:= (5! + (C(T(T(3)), (7 - 1)) - T(T(8)))) \\ 53722 &:= -(((T((-5) + T(T(3)))) + (T(T(7)))) - C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2)))) \\ 53732 &:= ((-(5! + T(3)) - T(T(7))) + C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))) \\ 53733 &:= ((-(5^3) - T(T(7))) + C(T(T(3)), T(3))) \\ 53735 &:= ((-(5! + 3) - T(T(7))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \\ 53735 &:= ((-(5! + 3) - T(T(7))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \\ 53755 &:= (((C(T(5), 3) - 7) \times 5!) - 5) \\ 53825 &:= ((-C(T(5), T(3)) + (-8) \times (T(T(2)))!) \times (-5)) \\ 53832 &:= (-(((T(5) - 3) \times T(8))) + C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))) \\ 53844 &:= (-5!) + (C(T(T(3)), T(T((8/4)))) - T(4!)) \\ 53865 &:= ((T((C(5, 3) + 8) \times T(6)) \times T(5)) \\ 53900 &:= (T(T(C(5, 3))) \times (T((9 - 0!) - 0!)) \\ 53945 &:= -(T(C(5, 3)) - ((T(9) \times T(4)) \times 5!)) \\ 53964 &:= ((5! - T(T(3))) + (9 \times C(T(6), 4))) \\ 54033 &:= -(T(((5 \times 4) + 0!) - C(T(T(3)), T(3)))) \\ 54036 &:= ((C(T(5), T(4)) - 0!) \times (3 \times 6)) \\ 54054 &:= (((-5) + 4!) - 0!) \times C(T(5), T(4)) \\ 54057 &:= ((T(5)^4) + C(-((0! - T(5))), 7)) \\ 54133 &:= (-(((5! + T(4)) + 1) + C(T(T(3)), T(3))) \\ 54134 &:= (-5!) + (C(T(T((4 - 1))), T(3)) - T(4)) \\ 54135 &:= (-(((5! + T(4)) - 1) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \\ 54137 &:= (-5!) + (C(T(T((4 - 1))), T(3)) - 7) \\ 54144 &:= (-5!) + C(T(T((4 - 1))), (4!/4)) \\ 54153 &:= ((5! + C(T(T((4 - 1))), T(5))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 54154 &:= (-5!) + (C(T(T((4 - 1))), T(5)) + T(4)) \\ 54196 &:= (((T(5)^4) + 1) + T(C(9, 6))) \\ 54210 &:= (-54) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(T((1 + 0!)))) \\ 54214 &:= ((-5) \times T(4) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(-((1 - 4)))) \\ 54220 &:= (-T((5 + 4)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) + 0!)) \\ 54222 &:= ((C((-5) + 4!), T(T(2))) - T(T(T(2)))) \times 2 \\ 54223 &:= (T((-5) + 4!) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 54224 &:= (T(5) + (C(T(C(4, 2)), T(T(2))) - T(T(4)))) \\ 54225 &:= (5 \times (((C(4, 2))! + T(2)) \times T(5))) \\ 54226 &:= (((-5) + 4!) \times (-2) + C(T(T(T(2))), 6)) \\ 54227 &:= ((-5!) + T(T(4))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) + (T(7))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54228 &:= (C((5 + (4^2)), T(T(2))) - T(8)) \\ 54232 &:= (((5!/(-4)) - 2) + C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))) \\ 54233 &:= ((5 - T((4 \times 2))) + C(T(T(3)), T(3))) \\ 54234 &:= ((T(5) + T(4)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - (T(T(4))))) \\ 54235 &:= ((-5) - 4!) + C(T((2 \times 3)), T(5)) \\ 54236 &:= (((5!/(-4)) + 2) + C(T(T(3)), 6)) \\ 54239 &:= ((5 \times 4) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - T(9))) \\ 54243 &:= -(((T(5) - C(4!, T(2))) \times (4! + 3))) \\ 54244 &:= (-((5 \times 4) + C(T(T(T(2))), (4!/4))) \\ 54245 &:= ((5 - 4!) + C(T((2 + 4)), T(5))) \\ 54245 &:= ((5 - 4!) + C(T((2 + 4)), T(5))) \\ 54249 &:= -((T(5) - C(T(C(4, 2)), (4! - 9))) \\ 54250 &:= -((T(5) - (C(T(C(4, 2)), T(5)) + 0!)) \\ 54251 &:= (-((5!/T(4))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) - 1)) \\ 54252 &:= -((T(5) - (C(T(C(4, 2)), T(5)) + T(2))) \\ 54253 &:= (-5) + (C(T(C(4, 2)), T(5)) - T(3)) \\ 54254 &:= (C((5 + (4^2)), T(5)) - T(4)) \\ 54255 &:= (-((5 + 4) + C((T(T(2)) + T(5)), T(5))) \\ 54256 &:= ((-5) - 4!) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + (T(6))) \\ 54257 &:= (C((5 + (4^2)), T(5)) - (7)) \\ 54258 &:= ((5!/4) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) - T(8))) \\ 54259 &:= (-5) + C(T(C(4, 2)), (T(5) - 9)) \\ 54260 &:= (-5) + (C(T(C(4, 2)), 6) + 0!) \\ 54263 &:= (5 + (C(T(C(4, 2)), 6) - T(3)) \\ 54265 &:= (((5 - 4)^2) + C(T(6), T(5))) \\ 54266 &:= (((5 - 4) \times 2) + C(T(6), 6)) \\ 54267 &:= (-((T(5) + T(4))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6) + (T(7)))) \\ 54268 &:= ((5!/T(4)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6) - 8)) \\ 54269 &:= (5 + C(T(C(4, 2)), (6 + 9))) \\ 54275 &:= ((T(5) - (4)) + C((T(2) \times 7), T(5))) \\ 54276 &:= ((5!/T(4)) + C((T(2) \times 7), 6)) \\ 54279 &:= ((T(5)^{C(4, T(2))}) + (T(T(7)) \times 9)) \\ 54283 &:= ((-5) + 4!) + C(T(-((2 - 8))), T(3)) \\ 54303 &:= ((T(5) + 4!) + C(T(T(3)), T(03))) \\ 54304 &:= ((-T(5) + T(T(4))) + C(T(T(3)), T((0! + (4)))) \\ 54314 &:= ((5 \times T(4)) + C(T(T(3)), T(-((1 - 4)))) \\ 54322 &:= ((T(5) \times 4) + (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - 2)) \\ 54323 &:= ((5! - T(T(4))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - T(3)) \\ 54324 &:= (5 + (C((4! - 3), T(T(2))) + T(T(4)))) \\ 54325 &:= (T((T(5) - (4))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - 5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54326 &:= (((5! - T(T(4))) - 3) + C(T(T(T(2))), 6)) \\ 54327 &:= ((T(5) + T(T(4))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - 7)) \\ 54329 &:= ((5 \times 4) + (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) + T(9))) \\ 54331 &:= (T((T(5) - (4))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + 1)) \\ 54332 &:= ((5! - T(T(4))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(2))) \\ 54333 &:= (T((T(5) - (4))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + 3)) \\ 54334 &:= ((T(5) + C((4! - 3), T(3))) + T(T(4))) \\ 54335 &:= (T((T(5) - (4))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + 5)) \\ 54337 &:= (T((5 + 4) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + (T(7)))) \\ 54338 &:= (T((T(5) - (4))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + 8)) \\ 54339 &:= (5! + (C((4! - 3), T(3)) - T(9))) \\ 54342 &:= (T((5!/T(4))) + C(T(T(3)), C(4, 2))) \\ 54353 &:= ((5! - T(4)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T(T(3)))) \\ 54354 &:= ((C(T(5), T(4)) \times (3 + T(5))) + T(4!)) \\ 54355 &:= ((5! - 4!) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - 5)) \\ 54358 &:= ((5! + T(4)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T(8))) \\ 54359 &:= ((5 \times T(4)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) + T(9))) \\ 54374 &:= ((5! - T(4)) + C(T(T(3)), T((7 - 4)))) \\ 54394 &:= ((5! + T(4)) + C(T(T(3)), T((9 - 4)))) \\ 54405 &:= (T((5 \times T(4))) + (C((4! + 0!), 5))) \\ 54423 &:= ((5 - (T(T(T(4)))/(-T(4)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(3))) \\ 54429 &:= (5! + (C(T((4!/4)), T(T(2))) + T(9))) \\ 54433 &:= (T(5) + ((T(T(T(4)))/T(4)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(3)))) \\ 54440 &:= ((C(T(5), 4) - (4)) \times 40) \\ 54463 &:= ((5! + T(T(4))) + (4! + C(T(6), T(3)))) \\ 54482 &:= (-(((5! - C(4!, T(4)))/T(8))) + T(T(2))) \\ 54523 &:= ((-((C(T(5), 4) \times 5!)) + T(T(T(T(2)))))/(-3)) \\ 54525 &:= (5 \times ((4! \times C(T(5), T(2))) - T(5))) \\ 54528 &:= (((5! + C(4!, 5))/T(2)) + 8!) \\ 54535 &:= ((-5!) + T(T(4))) + ((C(T(5), 3) \times 5!)) \\ 54564 &:= (C(T(((5 - 4) + 5)), 6) + T(4!)) \\ 54585 &:= ((C(T(5), 4) \times (5 \times 8)) - T(5)) \\ 54595 &:= ((C(T(5), 4) \times (-5) + T(9)) - 5) \\ 54622 &:= ((T(5) \times 4!) + (C(T(6), T(T(2))) - 2)) \\ 54624 &:= ((T(5) \times 4!) + C(T(6), (2 + 4))) \\ 54633 &:= -((T(5) + (C(4!, T(6)) \times (-3^3)))) \\ 54634 &:= ((T(5) \times 4!) + (C(T(6), T(3)) + T(4))) \\ 54639 &:= ((5! + T(4!)) + (C(T(6), T(3)) - T(9))) \\ 54643 &:= (-5) + (C(4!, T(6)) \times (4! + 3)) \\ 54648 &:= ((C(T(5), 4) + T((T(6) - (4)))) \times T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54663 &:= (((-5) + 4!) \times T(6)) + C(T(6), T(3)) \\ 54669 &:= ((T(5) \times 4!) + (C(T(6), 6) + T(9))) \\ 54693 &:= ((T(5) + (C(4!, T(6)) \times 9)) \times 3) \\ 54733 &:= ((C(T(5), 4) + (7)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(T(T(3)))))) \\ 54736 &:= ((T((T(5) - 4))) + T(T(7))) + C(T(T(3)), 6)) \\ 54765 &:= ((5 + T((4! + 7))) + (C(T(6), T(5)))) \\ 54766 &:= (((5! - 4!) + T(T(7))) + (C(T(6), 6))) \\ 54865 &:= (((-5!) + T(T(4))) + T(T(8))) + (C(T(6), T(5))) \\ 54872 &:= ((5!/4) + C(8, 7))^{T(2)} \\ 54879 &:= (C(T(5), T(4)) - (-T(8)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(9)))) \\ 54891 &:= (((-T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(8)) - C(9, 1) \\ 54894 &:= ((-C(T(5), 4) - T(T(8))) + (T(T(9)) \times T(T(4)))) \\ 54899 &:= (((-T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(8)) - C(9, 9) \\ 54900 &:= ((-T(5)) + T(T(T(4)))) \times C(9, (0! + 0!)) \\ 54935 &:= ((5 + T((4 \times 9))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \\ 54956 &:= ((T(5) - 4) \times (-9) + C(T(5), 6)) \\ 54966 &:= ((T((5!/T(4))) \times 9) + (C(T(6), 6))) \\ 55237 &:= (-C(T(5), 5) + (T((2^{T(3)})) \times T(7))) \\ 55265 &:= ((C(T(5), 5)/T(2)) + C(T(6), T(5))) \\ 55266 &:= ((5! \times C(T(5), T(2))) + T((6 \times 6))) \\ 55269 &:= (-((T(5) + T(5))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6) + T(T(9)))) \\ 55284 &:= (((-5) + T(T(C(5, 2)))) \times T(8)) + (4!) \\ 55299 &:= (C(T(T((T(5)/5))), -(T(2) - 9)) + T(T(9))) \\ 55335 &:= (T(5) + ((C(T(5), 3) + T(3)) \times 5!)) \\ 55363 &:= (((-C(5, 5) + (T(3))!) \times T(T(6)))/3) \\ 55384 &:= (-C((5!/T(5)), 3) - (-T(8)) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 55392 &:= (C(T(T((T(5)/5))), T(3)) + T((T(9) + 2))) \\ 55435 &:= (-5) + (C((T(5) - 4), T(3)) \times 5!) \\ 55455 &:= (T(5) + (C((T(5) - 4), 5) \times 5!)) \\ 55455 &:= (T(5) + (C((T(5) - 4), 5) \times 5!)) \\ 55461 &:= ((T((5!/T(5))) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(C(6, 1))) \\ 55464 &:= ((5! \times C((T(5) - 4), 6)) + 4!) \\ 55473 &:= ((C(5, 5) + T(4)) \times (7! + 3)) \\ 55642 &:= (C(T(T((T(5)/5))), 6) + T((T(T(4)) - T(2)))) \\ 55785 &:= (-5) \times (T(5) - (7 \times T(C(8, 5)))) \\ 55847 &:= (C(5, 5) + ((T(8) \times T(T(T(4)))) + (T(T(7)))))) \\ 55923 &:= ((T(T((5!/T(5)))) \times C(9, T(2))) - (T(T(3)))) \\ 55934 &:= ((T(T((5!/T(5)))) \times C(9, 3)) - T(4)) \\ 55937 &:= ((T(T((5!/T(5)))) \times C(9, 3)) - 7) \\ 55938 &:= -((T((T(5)/5)) + (-C(9, 3)) \times T(T(8)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55950 &:= (T(5) \times (C(T(5), 9) - T(50))) \\ 55965 &:= (T(T((5!/T(5)))) + ((T(T(9)) + (C(T(6), T(5)))))) \\ 55968 &:= ((5!/5) - (-C(9, 6) \times T(T(8)))) \\ 56222 &:= ((5 + T(62)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2)))) \\ 56232 &:= ((T(5) + T(62)) + C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))) \\ 56262 &:= ((T((T(5) + T(6))) \times T(2)) + C(T(6), T(T(2)))) \\ 56324 &:= (((5 \times 6!) + C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 56329 &:= ((-5) + C(T(6), T(3))) + (2 \times T(T(9))) \\ 56382 &:= ((5! + C(T(6), T(3))) - (T(T(8)) \times (-T(2)))) \\ 56435 &:= -((C(T(5), 6) - ((4^{T(3)}) \times T(5))) \\ 56465 &:= (T(T((5 + 6))) - (T(4) - C(T(6), T(5)))) \\ 56465 &:= (T(T((5 + 6))) - (T(4) - C(T(6), T(5)))) \\ 56694 &:= ((T(5) + C(T(6), 6)) + T((T(9) + 4!))) \\ 56700 &:= ((T(5) \times 6) \times T(C(7, T((0! + 0!)))) \\ 56724 &:= (((T(5) \times 6) \times T(C(7, T(2)))) + (4!)) \\ 56823 &:= ((5! + T(6)) \times (T(C(8, 2)) - 3)) \\ 56832 &:= ((-5!) + T(T(6))) \times (8^{C(3, 2)}) \\ 56952 &:= ((5 - T(T(6))) \times (-C(9, 5) \times 2)) \\ 56980 &:= (T(C((5 + 6), 9)) \times (T(8) + 0!)) \\ 57324 &:= ((5! \times T(7)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - T(4!))) \\ 57325 &:= (-5) + (T(C(7, 3)) \times T((-2) + T(5))) \\ 57329 &:= ((5 \times T(T(7))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) + T(T(9)))) \\ 57344 &:= C(T(T(T(-5 + 7))), T(3)) + T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(4))) \\ 57345 &:= (T(T((5 + 7))) + (C((-3) + 4!), T(5))) \\ 57366 &:= ((T(T((5 + 7))) + T(T(3))) + (C(T(6), 6))) \\ 57375 &:= ((C(T(5), C(7, T(3))) + 7!) \times 5) \\ 57375 &:= ((C(T(5), C(7, T(3))) + 7!) \times 5) \\ 57431 &:= (-T((T(5) + 7))) \times (4 - T(T(T(C(3, 1)))))) \\ 57464 &:= (5! + (T(7) \times (C(4!, T(6)) + 4!))) \\ 57528 &:= ((T(57) - T(C(5, 2))) \times T(8)) \\ 57634 &:= ((5! \times T(7)) + (C(T(6), T(3)) + T(4))) \\ 57669 &:= ((5! \times T(7)) + (C(T(6), 6) + T(9))) \\ 57699 &:= (((C(T(5), 7) + T(6)) - T(9)) \times 9) \\ 57723 &:= ((T((T(5) + 7))) \times T(C(7, 2))) - (T(3))!) \\ 57735 &:= ((T(57) \times C(7, 3)) - 5!) \\ 57789 &:= (C(T(5), 7) + ((7! + T(T(8))) \times 9)) \\ 57798 &:= (T((5 + 7)) \times T((-7) + T(C(9, 8)))) \\ 57828 &:= (5! + ((7 + T(C(8, T(2)))) \times T(8)) \\ 57904 &:= (((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) - 0!) - T(4)) \\ 57905 &:= ((C(T(5), 7) \times 9) - T(-((0! - 5)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 57907 &:= (((C(T(5),7) \times 9) - 0!) - (7)) \\ 57908 &:= (((C(T(5),7) \times 9) + 0!) - 8) \\ 57912 &:= C(T(5),7) \times 9 - 1 - 2 \\ 57913 &:= C(T(5),7) \times 9 + 1 - 3 \\ 57914 &:= C(T(5),7) \times 9 - 1^4 \\ 57915 &:= C(T(5),7) \times C(9,1^5) \\ 57916 &:= C(T(5),7) \times 9 + 1^6 \\ 57920 &:= (((C(T(5),7) \times 9) + T(T(2))) - 0!) \\ 57921 &:= ((C(T(5),7) \times 9) + T((2+1))) \\ 57922 &:= ((C(T(5),7) \times 9) + (T(T(T(2))))/T(2))) \\ 57923 &:= ((C(T(5),7) \times 9) + (2^3)) \\ 57925 &:= ((C(T(5),7) \times 9) + (2 \times 5)) \\ 57926 &:= ((C(T(5),7) \times 9) + (T(T(T(T(2)))))/T(6))) \\ 57928 &:= (((C(T(5),7) \times 9) + T(T(T(2)))) - 8) \\ 57933 &:= ((C(T(5),7) \times 9) + (3 \times T(3))) \\ 57937 &:= (((C(T(5),7) \times 9) - T(3)) + T(7)) \\ 57939 &:= (((C(T(5),7) \times 9) - T(T(3))) + T(9)) \\ 57940 &:= (((C(T(5),7) \times 9) + 4!) + 0!) \\ 57942 &:= (((C(T(5),7) \times 9) + 4!) + T(2)) \\ 57943 &:= ((C(T(5),7) \times 9) + T((4+3))) \\ 57946 &:= (((C(T(5),7) \times 9) + T(4)) + T(6)) \\ 57947 &:= (((C(T(5),7) \times 9) + (4)) + T(7)) \\ 57954 &:= (((C(T(5),7) \times 9) + T(5)) + 4!) \\ 57958 &:= ((T(5) + T(7)) + (9 \times C(T(5),8))) \\ 57963 &:= (((-5) - T(T(7))) \times (-9)) + (C(T(6),T(3)))) \\ 57964 &:= (((C(T(5),7) \times 9) - (6)) + T(T(4))) \\ 57969 &:= ((C(T(5),7) \times 9) + ((6 \times 9))) \\ 57982 &:= ((T(5) + (7)) + (T(T(9)) \times C(8,T(2)))) \\ 57983 &:= ((-5) + T(7)) + (T(T(9)) \times C(8,3)) \\ 57989 &:= ((C(T(5),7) \times 9) - (T(T(8)))/(-9)) \\ 57993 &:= ((C(T(5),7) \times 9) + T((9+3))) \\ 58059 &:= (((C(T(5),8) + 0!) + T(5)) \times 9) \\ 58174 &:= (T(58) \times (-1 - C(7,4))) \\ 58236 &:= -((T((T(5)+8)) \times (C(T(T(2)),3) - T(T(6)))))) \\ 58239 &:= ((C(T(5),8) + T((2^3))) \times 9) \\ 58246 &:= (-((T(5) \times T(8))) - (C(T(T(T(2))),T(4)))/(-6)) \\ 58248 &:= ((C((5+8),2) + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(8)) \\ 58265 &:= (5 + ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(2))) + (C(T(6),T(5)))))) \\ 58266 &:= (-C(T(5),8) - (T(T((2 \times 6))) \times (-T(6)))) \\ 58338 &:= ((C(T(5), (8-3)) \times T(3)) + 8!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}58344 &:= ((5! + T(C(8,3))) \times (4! + T(4))) \\58365 &:= -((C(T(5),8) - ((T(3) \times 6!) \times T(5)))) \\58366 &:= (C((5!/8), T(3)) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(6)))) \\58386 &:= (((5! + T(C(8,T(3)))) \times T(T(8)))/6) \\58419 &:= (((C(T(5),8) + T(T(4))) + 1) \times 9) \\58426 &:= ((T(T((5+8))) - (4!)) + C(T(T(T(2))),6)) \\58435 &:= ((-T(5) + T((T(8) + T(T(4)))))) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \\58465 &:= ((T(5) + T((T(8) + T(T(4)))))) + (C(T(6), T(5))) \\58563 &:= (5! + (C((8 + T(5)), T(6)) \times T(T(T(3)))))) \\58629 &:= ((5! \times T(8)) + (C(T(6), T(T(2))) + T(9))) \\58638 &:= (((T(5) - 8)! + (C(T(6), T(3)))) - T(T(8))) \\58675 &:= (((-5) - 8!) + 6!) + C(T(7), 5) \\58828 &:= (((-5) + T(T(8))) \times C(8,2)) + 8! \\58926 &:= ((-5!) + T((-8) + C(9, T(2)))) \times T(6) \\58987 &:= (((C(T(5),8) \times 9) + T(T(8))) + T(T(7))) \\59049 &:= ((-(5-9) - 0!)^{C(T(4),9)}) \\59225 &:= (5 + (C(9, T(2)) \times ((T(T(2)))! - T(5)))) \\59235 &:= (T(5) - (-C(9, T(2)) \times ((T(3))! - T(5)))) \\59263 &:= ((C(T(5),9) - T(T(2))) + (C(T(6), T(3)))) \\59266 &:= ((C(T(5),9) - T(2)) + C(T(6),6)) \\59269 &:= (C(T(5),9) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(-(6-9)))) \\59284 &:= (((5 + C(9, T(2))) \times T(T(8))) + T(4)) \\59289 &:= (T(5) - (T(C(9,2)) \times (-89))) \\59349 &:= (T((T(5) + 9)) + (3^{C(T(4),9)})) \\59364 &:= ((5! \times T(9)) + (C(T(T(3)),6) - T(4!))) \\59385 &:= ((5! \times C((9+3),8)) - T(5)) \\59463 &:= ((5 \times T(T(9))) + (4! + C(T(6), T(3)))) \\59520 &:= (5! \times ((9 \times T(C(5,2))) + 0!)) \\59550 &:= (-T(5) \times (T(T(9)) - (C(T(5), (5+0!)))))) \\59625 &:= ((5 \times 9) \times (C(T(6), T(2)) - (5))) \\59654 &:= ((5! \times T(9)) + (C(T(6), T(5)) - T(4))) \\59657 &:= ((5! \times T(9)) + (C(T(6), T(5)) - (7))) \\59662 &:= ((5! \times T(9)) + (C(T(6),6) - 2)) \\59664 &:= ((5! \times T(9)) + C(T(6), C(6,4))) \\59667 &:= (-T(5) - ((C(9,6) - T(T(6))) \times T(T(7)))) \\59724 &:= (((C(T(5),9) - T(7)) \times T(2)) \times 4) \\59772 &:= (((T(5) \times T(C(9,7))) - T(7)) \times T(T(2))) \\59850 &:= ((T(5) + T(T(9))) \times (C(8,5) + 0!)) \\59864 &:= (5 + (9 \times (T(T(8)) + (C(T(6),4)))))) \\59892 &:= ((5 + C(9,8)) \times T(92))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59952 &:= ((C(T(5),9) - 9) \times (T(5) - T(2))) \\ 59985 &:= ((5! + 9) \times T((T(C(9,8)) - T(5)))) \\ 60339 &:= (((6 + 0!)!) + (C(T(T(3)),T(3)) + T(T(9)))) \\ 60438 &:= ((C(T(6),(0! + (4))) - T(T(T(3)))) + 8!) \\ 60774 &:= ((-T(6)) + ((0! + (7)))!) + (C(T(7),4!)) \\ 61053 &:= (6 - (C(T(T(T((1 + 0!)))),5) \times (-3))) \\ 61422 &:= ((C(T((6 + 1)),4!) \times T(2)) - T(2)) \\ 61425 &:= (C(T((6 + 1)),4!) \times (-2 - 5)) \\ 61524 &:= (-((C(6,1)^5) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(4!)))) \\ 61544 &:= ((T(6) \times (1 + C(T(5),T(4)))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 61920 &:= (6! \times (1 + (C(9,T(2)) + 0!)) \\ 62034 &:= ((C(T(6),2) + 0!) \times (-T(3) + T(4!))) \\ 62245 &:= ((T(T(6)) - C(T(T(2)),T(2))) \times (T(4!) - 5)) \\ 62271 &:= (T((C(6,2) + 2)) \times (T(T(7)) + 1)) \\ 62334 &:= (-T((6^2)) + (T(C(T(3),3)) \times T(4!))) \\ 62343 &:= ((T(6) \times C(T((2 + 3)),T(4))) - (T(3))!) \\ 62397 &:= ((T((T(T(6))/T(2))) \times T(T(3))) - T(C(9,7))) \\ 62489 &:= ((C(T(6),T(T(2))) - T(T(4))) + (8 \times T(T(9)))) \\ 62493 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((-2) + C(4!,9))/T(T(3))) \\ 62622 &:= ((T(T(6))^2) + ((T(6)^{C(T(2),2)})) \\ 62657 &:= ((T((T(T(6))/T(2))) \times T(C(6,5))) - (T(T(7)))) \\ 62736 &:= (6! + (C(T(T(T(2))),7) - (C(T(T(3)),6)))) \\ 62748 &:= (T(62) + (C(T(7),4!) + 8!)) \\ 62762 &:= -((T((T(6)/T(2))) - (C(T(7),6)/T(T(2)))) \\ 62763 &:= ((-T(6)) - T(T(2))) + ((C(T(7),6)/T(3))) \\ 62766 &:= -(((6 - 2)!) + (C(T(7),6)/(-6))) \\ 62868 &:= (C(T(6),T(T(2))) + ((8 + T(T(6))) \times T(8))) \\ 63210 &:= (T(C(6,3)) \times (T(((T(2) + 1)!) + 0!)) \\ 63231 &:= (T(T(6)) + (T(C(T(3),T(2))) \times T(((3 + 1)!))) \\ 63232 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((T(T(T(3))) + C(T(T(2)),3))^2)) \\ 63308 &:= -(((C(T(6),T(3))/T(3)) \times (0! - 8))) \\ 63406 &:= ((T(C(6,3)) \times T(4!)) + T(T((0! + (6)))) \\ 63407 &:= (((T(C(6,3)) \times T(4!)) + 0!) + T(T(7))) \\ 63441 &:= (-T(6)) \times (-T((3^4)) + T((C(4,1)!))) \\ 63444 &:= (6 \times ((3 - T(T(4))) + C(4!,4))) \\ 63465 &:= ((T(C(6,3)) \times T(4!)) + (T((6 \times 5)))) \\ 63486 &:= -(((C(T(6),3) - (4^8)) + 6!)) \\ 63524 &:= (C(T(6),T(3)) + ((T(5) \times (T(T(2)))!) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 63544 &:= (-6!) + (C(T(T(3)),T(5)) + (T(4)^4)) \\ 63552 &:= (-((T(T(6)) + (T(T(3)) \times (-C(T(5),5)))) + (T(T(2)))!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}63588 &:= (C(T(6), T(3)) + ((T(5) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(8)))) \\63648 &:= (((C(T(6), 3) \times (-6)) + 4!) \times (-8)) \\63774 &:= (6 \times (3 + C(((T(7)/7)!, 4))) \\63822 &:= (((C(T(6), 3) \times 8) - T(2)) \times T(T(2))) \\63825 &:= (((C(T(6), 3) \times 8) \times T(T(2))) - T(5)) \\63835 &:= (((C(T(6), 3) \times 8) \times T(3)) - (5)) \\63840 &:= (C(T(6), 3) \times (8 + 40)) \\63864 &:= ((C(T(6), 3) \times (8 \times 6)) + 4!) \\63874 &:= ((T(C(6, 3)) + 8) \times (-7) + T(4!)) \\63946 &:= ((C(T(6), 3) \times T(9)) + (4^6)) \\63948 &:= (C(T(6), T(3)) + ((T(T(9)) \times T(4)) - T(T(8)))) \\63966 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (-3) + T(9)) + (C(T(6), 6))) \\63987 &:= (T(T(6)) \times ((T(3) \times T(C(9, 8))) + (7))) \\64234 &:= ((-6) + C((4! + 2), T(T(3)))) - T(T(T(4))) \\64246 &:= ((6 - T(T(T(4)))) + C((2 + 4!), T(6))) \\64246 &:= ((6 - T(T(T(4)))) + C((2 + 4!), T(6))) \\64248 &:= (((C(T(6), 4) - T(2)) \times 4) + 8!) \\64296 &:= ((-6) + 4!) \times (2 + T(C(9, 6))) \\64344 &:= (T(6) \times (C((4! - T(3)), 4) + (4))) \\64422 &:= ((6 \times C(4!, 4)) + T(T((2^{T(2)}))) \\64428 &:= (((6 \times C(4!, 4)) + T(T(2))) + T(T(8))) \\64449 &:= (T(T(6)) \times ((C(T(4), 4) + 4!) + T(9))) \\64482 &:= (((T(6)^4) - T(C(T(4), 8)))/T(2)) \\64497 &:= ((6 \times C(4!, 4)) + T((T(9) - (7)))) \\64522 &:= (6 + ((C(T(4), 5) + 2)^2)) \\64524 &:= ((6! + (C(T(4), 5)^2)) + T(4!)) \\64526 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(4!)) - (C(T(5), T(T(2))) - T(T(6)))) \\64571 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((T(4) \times (C(T(5), 7) - 1))) \\64575 &:= ((C(T(6), 4) \times T(5)) + (7! \times (-5))) \\64580 &:= (T(T(6)) + (((T(4) \times C(T(5), 8)) - 0!)) \\64581 &:= (T(T(6)) - (T(4) \times (C(T(5), 8) \times (-1)))) \\64584 &:= (-6) + (T(4) \times (C(T(5), 8) + 4!)) \\64802 &:= (((6! \times C(T(4), 8)) + 0!) \times 2) \\64815 &:= (((T(C(6, 4)) \times T(8)) + 1) \times T(5)) \\64824 &:= ((6! \times (C(T(4), 8) \times 2)) + 4!) \\65034 &:= (C(T(6), (5 - 0!)) + (3^{T(4)})) \\65063 &:= (((6! \times T(5)) - 0!) + C(T(6), T(3))) \\65142 &:= (T(T(6)) \times ((5 + 1) + C(4!, 2))) \\65338 &:= ((T(6) + C(T(5), T(3))) \times (T(T(3)) - 8)) \\65345 &:= (C((T(6) + (5)), T(T(3))) - T((4! + (5))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 65352 &:= (C(T(6), T(5)) + (((T(3))!/T(5)) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 65367 &:= (((C(T(6), 5) \times 3) - 6!) + 7!) \\ 65372 &:= ((C((T(6) + (5)), T(T(3))) - T(T(7))) - 2) \\ 65373 &:= (T(T(6)) \times ((C(5, 3) \times T(7)) + 3)) \\ 65374 &:= (C((T(6) + (5)), T(T(3))) - (T((7 \times 4)))) \\ 65424 &:= (C(T(6), T(5)) + (4! \times T((T(2) \times T(4)))) \\ 65450 &:= ((-T(T(C(6, 5)))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 50 \\ 65491 &:= (((T(6) - (5))^4) - T(C(9, 1))) \\ 65504 &:= (C((T(6) + (5)), 5) - T(-((0! - 4!))) \\ 65536 &:= ((T(6) - (5))^{C(5, 3) - 6}) \\ 65549 &:= (C((T(6) + (5)), 5) - T(-((4! - T(9)))) \\ 65555 &:= (C((T(6) + (5)), 5) - (T(5) \times T(5))) \\ 65565 &:= ((T(6) + 5!) \times T((5 \times C(6, 5)))) \\ 65644 &:= (C((T(6) + (5)), T(6)) - T((4 \times 4))) \\ 65649 &:= (C(T(6), T(5)) + ((T(6) - T(4)) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 65655 &:= ((C((T(6) + (5)), T(6)) - (5)) - 5!) \\ 65660 &:= (C((T(6) + (5)), T(6)) - ((6 - 0!)!) \\ 65674 &:= ((C((T(6) + (5)), T(6)) - T(T(7))) + T(4!)) \\ 65675 &:= (C((T(6) + (5)), T(6)) + (-7) \times T(5)) \\ 65690 &:= (C((T(6) + (5)), T(6)) - (90)) \\ 65696 &:= (C((T(6) + (5)), T(6)) - (C(9, 6))) \\ 65699 &:= (C((T(6) + (5)), T(6)) - ((9 \times 9))) \\ 65708 &:= (((C(T(6), 5) + 7!) - 0!) + 8!) \\ 65709 &:= (C(T(6), 5) - (7! \times (0 - 9))) \\ 65772 &:= ((T(T(6)) - 57) \times C(T(7), 2)) \\ 65775 &:= (C((T(6) + (5)), (-7) + T(7)) - (5)) \\ 65780 &:= C((T(6) + (5)), ((T(7) - 8) + 0!)) \\ 65795 &:= (C((T(6) + (5)), T(T(T(-((7 - 9)))))) + T(5)) \\ 65845 &:= (65 + C((T(8) - T(4)), 5)) \\ 65846 &:= (T((6 + 5)) + C((T(8) - T(4)), T(6))) \\ 65853 &:= ((T((6!/T(5))) \times C(8, 5)) - 3) \\ 65856 &:= (T((C(6, 5) \times 8)) \times 56) \\ 65856 &:= (T((C(6, 5) \times 8)) \times 56) \\ 65924 &:= -((((T(6) - 5!) \times T(C(9, 2))) + T(4))) \\ 65927 &:= -((((T(6) - 5!) \times T(C(9, 2))) + (7))) \\ 65934 &:= -((((T(6) - 5!) \times T(C(9, (3 + 4)))))) \\ 65964 &:= (C(T(6), T(5)) + ((T(9) - (6)) \times T(4!))) \\ 65979 &:= -((((T(6) - 5!) \times T(C(9, 7))) - T(9))) \\ 66239 &:= (-C(6, 6) + ((2^{T(3)}) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 66276 &:= (6 \times ((T(C(6, 2)) + T(T(7))) \times T(6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 66279 &:= (C(T(6), 6) + (T(2) \times (7! - T(T(9)))))) \\ 66297 &:= ((T(6) + (C(T(6), 2) \times T(9))) \times 7) \\ 66360 &:= (T(6) \times (C(T(6), 3) + T(60))) \\ 66399 &:= -((T(6) - (C(6, 3) \times T((9 \times 9)))))) \\ 66464 &:= -((6! - ((C(T(6), T(4))/T(6)) \times 4))) \\ 66487 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((6! + (4^{C(8,7)}))) \\ 66500 &:= (6! + C((T(6) + (5)), T(T(T((0! + 0!)))))) \\ 66570 &:= ((T(T(6)) + (C(6, 5)!) \times 70) \\ 66584 &:= (C(T(6), C(6, 5)) - (-8 \times T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 66639 &:= -((T(T(6)) + ((C((T(6) + (6)), T(3)) - 9!))) \\ 66724 &:= (-C(T(6), 6) - (T(T(7)) \times (2 - T(4!)))) \\ 66939 &:= -((T(6) - (6! \times (C(9, 3) + 9)))) \\ 67032 &:= ((T(6) \times T(C((7 + 0!), 3))) \times 2) \\ 67368 &:= (T(6) \times (C(T(7), 3) - 68)) \\ 67551 &:= (T(T(6)) + (T((T(7) + (5))) \times (C(5, 1)!)) \\ 67575 &:= (C(T(6), 7) + ((-5!) \times T(T(7))) + T(5)) \\ 67683 &:= ((T(6) \times (-7)) + (C(T(6), 8)/3)) \\ 67753 &:= (((-6) \times T(T(7))) \times (-T(7))) - (C(T(5), 3))) \\ 67823 &:= ((-C(T(6), -(T(7) - T(8)))) + T(T(T(2))))/(-3)) \\ 67825 &:= ((C(T(6), -(T(7) - T(8)))/T(2)) - 5) \\ 67827 &:= ((T(T(6)) - C((-7) + T(8), T(T(2))))/(-7)) \\ 67830 &:= ((C(T(6), 7)/T(8)) \times T(T((3 + 0)))) \\ 67854 &:= ((-C(T(6), 7) - T(T(8))) - (-5!) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\ 68061 &:= ((T(6) \times T(80)) + T(C(6, 1))) \\ 68235 &:= ((T(6) \times T(T(8))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - T(5))) \\ 68237 &:= (((C(T(6), 8) + T(2))/3) + T(T(7))) \\ 68283 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((-T(T(8))) - C(T(T(T(2))), 8))/(-3)) \\ 68288 &:= ((6! + C(8, T(2))) \times 88) \\ 68295 &:= ((C(T(6), 8)/T(2)) + T((T(9) - T(5)))) \\ 68334 &:= ((C(T(6), 8)/3) - (T(T(3)) \times (-4!))) \\ 68524 &:= (-((6! + (C(8, 5)))) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(4!)))) \\ 68594 &:= (-6) - (-C(8, 5) \times T((T(9) + (4)))) \\ 68628 &:= (T(6) \times (C(C(8, 6), T(2)) - 8)) \\ 68640 &:= (C((T(6) - 8), 6) \times 40) \\ 68648 &:= (((T(6) \times T(C(8, 6))) + T(T(4))) \times 8) \\ 68670 &:= (-C(T(6), 8) - (-6!) \times T((T(7) - 0!))) \\ 68796 &:= ((6! + T(8)) \times (7 + C(9, 6))) \\ 68894 &:= (-T(T((6 + C(8, 8)))) - (-T(9) \times T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 69272 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) - T(C(7, T(T(2)))) \\ 69291 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) - C(9, 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 69295 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(((C(9,2)/9)!)) - 5) \\ 69299 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T((T(9) - T(T(T(2)))))) - C(9,9)) \\ 69428 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times C(9,4) + (2 + 8!)) \\ 69436 &:= (T((6!/T(9))) + (T((C(4,3))!) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 69482 &:= (((C(T(6),9)/T(4)) + 8!) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 69530 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((T(9) \times T(T(C(5,3)))) - 0!)) \\ 69543 &:= ((6! \times 9) - (-C(T(5),T(4)) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 69678 &:= (T(6) \times (T(C(9,6)) + (-7 \times T(8)))) \\ 69694 &:= ((6! + 9!) - (C(T(6),9) - 4!)) \\ 69759 &:= ((6 \times C((-9) + T(7)),5) - 9) \\ 69936 &:= ((T((6 + 9)) \times T(T(9))) - C(T(T(3)),6)) \\ 69972 &:= ((T(6) \times T((9 \times 9))) + T(C(7,2))) \\ 70245 &:= (((7 + 0!)! - (C(T(T(T(2))),4) \times (-5))) \\ 70248 &:= (C(T((7 - 0!)),T(T(2))) + (4! \times T(T(8)))) \\ 71253 &:= (C((T(7) + 1),25) \times 3) \\ 71393 &:= (-7) + ((-1) + T(T(3))) \times T(C(9,3))) \\ 72066 &:= ((C(T(7),T(2)) \times (0! + T(6))) - (6)) \\ 72072 &:= (C(T(7),T(2)) \times (0! + C(7,2))) \\ 72276 &:= ((T(C(7,2)) + (T(T(2)))!) \times 76) \\ 72288 &:= ((T((C(7,2) \times T(2))) - 8) \times T(8)) \\ 72292 &:= ((T(7) \times (C(T(T(T(2))),T(T(2))) - T(9)))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 72325 &:= (T((7 + T(2))) \times (C(T(T(3)),T(2)) - T(5))) \\ 72352 &:= (T(7) \times (C(C(T(T(2)),3),5)/T(T(2)))) \\ 72356 &:= ((-T(7)) \times (T(2) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))))/(-T(6)) \\ 72396 &:= (C(T(7),T(2)) + ((T(3))! \times 96)) \\ 72423 &:= ((-7) - (T(T(2)))!) + (T(T(4)) \times C(T(T(T(2))),3))) \\ 72429 &:= (7 \times (-T(2)) + (T(C(4,T(2))) \times T(T(9)))) \\ 72450 &:= (T(C(7,T(2))) \times ((-4) + 5!) - 0!) \\ 72475 &:= -((7! - (C((2 \times T(4)),7) - (5)))) \\ 72480 &:= -((7! - C((2 \times T(4)),(8 - 0!)))) \\ 72632 &:= (-T(7)) \times (-C(26,3) + T(T(2))) \\ 72634 &:= -((T(T(7)) + ((2 - C(T(6),3)) \times T(T(4)))))) \\ 72654 &:= (((T(T(7)) - (T(T(2)))!) \times (-T(T(6)))) + (C(5,4))!) \\ 72738 &:= ((C(T(7),T(2)) \times (T(7) - T(3))) + T(T(8))) \\ 72765 &:= (T(((7 \times 2) \times C(7,6))) \times T(5)) \\ 72785 &:= ((C(7,T(2)) \times T((T(7) + T(8)))) - T(5)) \\ 72800 &:= (C(7,T(2)) \times T((8^{0!+0!}))) \\ 72824 &:= ((C(7,T(2)) \times T((8^2))) + 4!) \\ 72842 &:= ((-T(7)) + T(T(2))) + ((T(8) \times C(4!,T(2)))) \\ 72843 &:= (-C(7,2) + (T(8) \times C(4!,3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}72928 &:= (T(C(7, T(T(2)))) + (((T(9)^2) \times T(8)))) \\72952 &:= (C(T(7), 2) + ((9!/5) - 2)) \\72954 &:= (C(T(7), 2) + (9!/C(5, 4))) \\72955 &:= (C(T(7), 2) + ((9! + (5))/5)) \\72985 &:= (T(T(7)) + (T(2) + ((C(9, 8))!/5))) \\72996 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T((2 \times 9))) + (T(C(9, 6)))) \\73122 &:= (-T(7) + (T(T((3 + 1))) \times C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)))) \\73206 &:= ((C(T(7), 3) + T(20)) \times T(6)) \\73269 &:= (((T(T(7)) \times C(T(3), T(2))) + (T(6))) \times 9) \\73276 &:= ((T(T(7)) + T(T((T(T(T(3)))/T(T(T(2))))) \times T(C(7, 6))) \\73464 &:= ((T(7) \times T((3 \times 4!)) - T(C(6, 4))) \\73535 &:= -((T(T((7 + 3))) - ((C(T(5), T(3)) \times T(5)))) \\73548 &:= (((7! + T(3)) - C(T(5), T(4))) \times T(8)) \\73584 &:= (T(7) \times T(-((3 - 5) - C(8, 4)))) \\73593 &:= (((C(T(7), T(3))/5) - T(T(9))) - (T(3))!) \\73836 &:= (T(C(7, 3)) + (T(83) \times T(6))) \\73962 &:= ((C(T(7), T(3)) + 9!)/T((6 - 2))) \\73969 &:= ((7! - T(T(3))) + ((9! - C(T(6), 9)))) \\74203 &:= (-((T(T(7)) + 4) + C((T(T(T(2))) + 0!), T(3))) \\74207 &:= -((T(T(7)) - C((4! - 2), -((0! - (7)))))) \\74214 &:= (7 \times (C(4!, (T(2) + 1)) - 4!)) \\74244 &:= ((-7) + C(4!, 2)) \times (-4! + T(4!)) \\74256 &:= ((T(7) - 4!) \times C((T(2) + T(5)), 6)) \\74262 &:= ((C((-7) + 4!), T(T(2))) \times 6) + T(T(2)) \\74263 &:= (7 + (4 \times C((T(2) \times 6), T(3)))) \\74278 &:= (T(T(7)) + ((C(4!, T(2)) + T(7)) \times T(8))) \\74306 &:= ((-7) - T(4!)) + C((T(T(3)) + 0!), 6) \\74313 &:= -((T((T(7) - 4)) - C((T(T(3)) + 1), T(3)))) \\74333 &:= (T(7) + (T(T(4)) \times (C(T(T(3)), 3) + T(T(3)))) \\74361 &:= (7! + ((T(4!) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(C(6, 1)))) \\74364 &:= (7! + ((T((C(4, 3))!) \times T(T(6))) + (4!))) \\74368 &:= ((T(7) \times (C(4, 3)^6)) - 8!) \\74381 &:= ((7 \times C(4!, ((T(3))!/T(8)))) - 1) \\74402 &:= (((7 \times C(4!, 4)) - 0!) + T(T(T(2)))) \\74417 &:= (T(7) + ((C(4!, 4) + 1) \times 7)) \\74418 &:= ((7 \times C(4!, 4)) + T((1 \times 8))) \\74422 &:= ((7 \times (C(4!, 4) + T(T(2)))) - 2) \\74427 &:= ((7 \times C(4!, 4)) + T((2 + 7))) \\74429 &:= ((7 \times C(4!, 4)) + (2 + T(9))) \\74434 &:= ((7 \times (C(4!, 4) + T(3))) + T(4))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}74437 &:= ((7 \times C(4!, 4)) + T((3 + 7))) \\74442 &:= ((7 \times C(4!, 4)) + (T(4) \times T(T(2)))) \\74443 &:= (((7 \times C(4!, 4)) + T(T(4))) + T(3)) \\74446 &:= ((7 \times (C(4!, 4) + T(4))) - (6)) \\74463 &:= (-7) - (T(T(4)) \times (-4! + C(T(6), 3))) \\74469 &:= ((7 \times (C(4!, 4) + (6))) + T(9)) \\74473 &:= (7 \times ((C(4!, 4) + (7)) + T(3))) \\74519 &:= ((T(C(7, 4)) \times 5!) - T((1 + T(9)))) \\74574 &:= (T(C(7, 4)) + (T(T((5 + 7))) \times 4!)) \\74592 &:= ((7!/45) \times T(C(9, 2))) \\74595 &:= -((((T(7) + (4)) - C(T(5), 9)) \times T(5))) \\74602 &:= (-((7 + 4) + C((T(6) + 0!), T(T(2)))) \\74603 &:= -((T((T(7) - 4!)) - (C((T(6) + 0!), T(3)))) \\74606 &:= ((T(7)/(-4) + C((T(6) + 0!), 6)) \\74613 &:= C(((7 \times 4) - 6), T((1 \times 3))) \\74616 &:= ((7 - 4) + C((T(6) + 1), 6)) \\74662 &:= (T(T(7)) + (C((-4) + T(6)), 6) \times T(T(2))) \\74755 &:= (((T(C(7, 4)) - (7)) \times 5!) - (5)) \\74766 &:= (T((-7) + 4!) + C((T(7) - (6)), 6)) \\74784 &:= ((C(7, 4) + T(78)) \times 4!) \\74851 &:= ((T(T(7)) - T(C(T(4), 8))) \times (-5! - 1)) \\74965 &:= ((T(T((7 - 4))) \times T(C(9, 6))) - 5) \\74966 &:= -(((T(7) - 4!) - (T(C(9, 6)) \times T(6)))) \\74970 &:= (T(T((7 - 4))) \times T(C(9, (7 - 0!)))) \\75033 &:= ((T(7) \times T(5)) + C((0! + T(T(3))), T(3))) \\75047 &:= ((T(C(7, 5)) \times T((0! + 4!))) - (T(7))) \\75048 &:= ((7 \times C(((5 - 0!)!, 4)) + T(T(8))) \\75053 &:= (-7) - (T(5) \times (0! - C(T(5), T(3)))) \\75074 &:= -((T(T(7)) + ((5! \times (0! - T(C(7, 4)))))) \\75239 &:= -((T(T(7)) - ((C(T(5), 2) \times (T(3))!) + T(9)))) \\75243 &:= (T((7 \times 5)) + C((-2) + 4!), T(3)) \\75280 &:= ((C((7 + T(5)), T(T(2))) + T(T(8))) + 0!) \\75282 &:= ((C((7 + T(5)), T(T(2))) + T(T(8))) + T(2)) \\75333 &:= (C((7 + T(5)), T(3)) + ((3 + 3))!) \\75336 &:= ((C((7 + T(5)), T(3)) + 3) + 6!) \\75343 &:= ((C((7 + T(5)), T(3)) + T(4)) + (T(3))!) \\75347 &:= (((7! - T(5)) \times C(T(3), 4)) - T(7)) \\75355 &:= ((7 \times C(T(5), T(3))) + ((5!/T(5)))!) \\75372 &:= (((7! \times T(5)) + 3) - T(C(7, 2))) \\75393 &:= (C((7 + T(5)), T(3)) + T((T(9) - T(3))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}75397 &:= ((7 \times T(T(C(5,3)))) - 9) \times 7 \\75447 &:= ((7! \times T(C(5,4))) - T((4! - (7)))) \\75475 &:= ((7! \times T(5)) - (C(T(4),7) + (5))) \\75480 &:= ((7! \times T(5)) - C(T(4), (8 - 0!))) \\75522 &:= ((7! \times T(5)) - T((C(5,2) + 2))) \\75526 &:= (((7! - (5)) \times T(5)) + C(T(T(2)),6)) \\75531 &:= (((7! - (5)) \times T(5)) + T(C(3,1))) \\75535 &:= (((7! \times T(5)) + T(C(5,3))) - 5!) \\75545 &:= ((7! \times T(5)) - T((C(5,4) + 5))) \\75556 &:= (T(T(7)) + (T(5) \times (5 + C(T(5),6)))) \\75557 &:= (((7! - C(5,5)) \times T(5)) - T(7)) \\75557 &:= (((7! - C(5,5)) \times T(5)) - T(7)) \\75572 &:= ((7! \times T(5)) - C((T(5) - (7)),2)) \\75587 &:= ((7! \times T(5)) - (5 + C(8,7))) \\75591 &:= ((T((7 \times 5)) \times 5!) - C(9,1)) \\75594 &:= (((7! \times T(5)) + 5!) - (C(9,4))) \\75595 &:= ((7! \times T(5)) - C(5, (9 - 5))) \\75612 &:= ((7! \times T(5)) + (C(6,1) \times 2)) \\75621 &:= ((7! \times T(5)) + T(C(6, (2 - 1)))) \\75726 &:= ((7! \times T(5)) + (C(7,2) \times 6)) \\75742 &:= ((7 + C(T(5),7)) - (-T(4!) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\75753 &:= ((7! \times T(5)) + T((7 + C(5,3)))) \\75824 &:= ((7! \times T(5)) + (C(8, T(2)) \times 4)) \\75988 &:= (T(T(7)) + C((T(T(-(5 - 9)))) - T(8)),8)) \\76079 &:= -(((T(T(7)) - (C((T(6) - 0!),7))) + T(T(9)))) \\76125 &:= ((7! + C((6 + 1), T(2))) \times T(5)) \\76266 &:= ((7! \times C(6,2)) + T((6 \times 6))) \\76274 &:= ((-((C(T(7), T(6)) \times T(2))) - T(T(7))) + (T(4))!) \\76275 &:= (((C(7,6))! + T((2 + 7))) \times T(5)) \\76324 &:= (C((T(7) - (6)), T(3)) + T((T(2) + T(T(4)))))) \\76434 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (-T(6) - C(T(4), T(3)))) - T(4!)) \\76435 &:= (((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) \times C(T(4), 3)) - 5) \\76488 &:= (((T(T(7)) \times T(6)) + T(C(T(4), 8))) \times 8) \\76524 &:= ((C(T(7), 6)/5) + T((2 \times 4!))) \\76568 &:= ((T(T(7)) + (C(6,5))!) \times 68) \\76573 &:= (T(T(7)) + ((C(T(6), 5) + 7!) \times 3)) \\76581 &:= (((7! + T(6)) \times T(5)) + T(T(C(8,1)))) \\76582 &:= (T(T(C(7,6))) + (T((T(5) + 8))^2)) \\76585 &:= ((7! - (C(T(6), 5) + 8)) \times (-5)) \\76590 &:= (((C(7,6))! \times T(5)) + T((T(9) - 0!)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}76594 &:= (-T(T(C(7,6)))) + ((5 + T(9)) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\76617 &:= -((T((7 \times 6)) - C((T(6) - 1), 7))) \\76698 &:= ((T(T(C(7,6))) \times (T(6) \times 9)) - T(8)) \\76752 &:= ((7! + (C(T(6), 7)/T(5))) \times T(T(2))) \\76815 &:= (((C(7,6))! + (81)) \times T(5)) \\76832 &:= (T(7) \times ((6 + 8)^{C(3,2)})) \\76839 &:= ((7! - T(6)) + (T(C(8,3)) \times T(9))) \\76965 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (T(6) \times 9)) + T(T(C(6,5)))) \\77175 &:= ((7! + T((C(7,1) + 7))) \times T(5)) \\77224 &:= (7 \times (T(T(7)) + C(((2 + 2)!, 4))) \\77321 &:= (((T(T(7)) + (C(T(7), 3))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 1) \\77392 &:= (7 - (-C(7,3) \times T(T((9 + 2)))))) \\77424 &:= (7! + ((7! - C(4!, T(2))) \times 4!)) \\77520 &:= C(((T(7)/7) \times 5), (T(T(2)) + 0!)) \\77525 &:= (-((T(T(7)) - (C(T(7), 5)))) - C(T(T(T(2))), 5)) \\77527 &:= (7 + C(((T(7) - 5) - T(2)), 7)) \\78421 &:= ((-7) + T(T(8))) \times (C(T(4), T(2)) - 1) \\78435 &:= (C((-7) + T(8), 4!) - ((3 + 5)!)) \\78438 &:= ((C((-7) + T(8), 4!) + 3) - 8!) \\78479 &:= -((T(T(7)) + ((T(T(8)) \times (-C(T(4), 7))) + T(T(9)))))) \\78547 &:= ((7 + 8!) + (C(T(5), 4) \times T(7))) \\78562 &:= (-T(7) - ((T(T(8)) \times (-5!)) + (C(T(6), T(2)))))) \\78795 &:= (C((T(7) - 8), 7) + T((T(9) + (5)))) \\79044 &:= (7 \times (T(T((9 - 0!))) + (C(4!, 4)))) \\79342 &:= (T(T(7)) + ((T(9) - T(3)) \times C(4!, T(2)))) \\79408 &:= (T(7) - (-C(9, 4) \times T(-((0! - T(8)))))) \\79534 &:= ((C(T(7), T((9 - 5)))/3)/T(T(4))) \\79692 &:= ((-((7 - C(9, 6))) \times T(T(9))) - T(2)) \\79695 &:= (-((7 - C(9, 6))) \times T((9 \times 5))) \\79723 &:= (T(7) - (T(T(9)) \times (T(C(7, 2))/(-3)))) \\79847 &:= (-((T(7) + T(9))) - (T(T(8)) \times (-C(T(4), 7)))) \\79944 &:= (((7! \times 9) \times T(9)) - C(4!, T(4))) \\80222 &:= (((8! + 0!) - T(C(T(T(2)), T(2)))) \times 2) \\80532 &:= (((8! + 0!) - T(C(5, 3))) \times 2) \\80565 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (0! + 5!)) - T(C(6, 5))) \\80722 &:= (-8) + C(-((0! - T(7))), (2 + T(2))) \\80730 &:= C(-(((8 \times 0)! - T(7)), (T(3) - 0!)) \\80738 &:= (8 + C(-((0! - T(7))), -(3 - 8))) \\80754 &:= (C(-(((8 \times 0)! - T(7))), 5) + (4!)) \\80758 &:= (T(8) + (C(-((0! - T(7))), 5) - 8))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}80872 &:= (((8! + 0!) + 8!) + T(C(7,2))) \\81252 &:= (T(C((8 + 1),2)) \times (5! + 2)) \\81272 &:= (((8! + 1) \times 2) + T(C(7,T(2)))) \\81395 &:= (T(T(8)) - (1 - C((3 \times 9),5))) \\81396 &:= (T(C(C(8,1),3)) \times (T(9) + (6))) \\81928 &:= (T((8 - 1)) \times T((C(9,T(2)) - 8))) \\81972 &:= ((8! + T(C((1 \times 9),7))) \times 2) \\82158 &:= (8! + (C(((T(2) + 1)!,5) - T(T(8)))) \\82284 &:= (T(C(8,T(2))) + (2 \times (8! + 4!))) \\82362 &:= ((T(C(8,T(2))) - ((T(3))! \times T(T(6))))/(-2)) \\82368 &:= (((T(C(8,T(2))) \times T(3)) + (6!)) \times 8) \\82394 &:= (-T(C(8,2)) - ((T(T(T(3))) + T(9)) \times (-T(4!)))) \\82433 &:= (((8! \times 2) + C(4!,3)) - T(T(T(3)))) \\82544 &:= (C(8,2) \times (C(T(5),T(4)) - T(T(4)))) \\82578 &:= (8! + ((C(T(T(T(2))),T(5))/T(7)) + 8!)) \\82596 &:= (T(C(8,T(2))) - ((5! \times (T(9) - 6!)))) \\82643 &:= (((8! \times 2) - T(6)) + C(4!,3)) \\82754 &:= (((-T(T(8))) \times T(T(T(2)))) + (C(T(7),5))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\82768 &:= (C(8,T(2)) \times (-7 + T((6! - T(T(8))))) \\82845 &:= ((T((8 - 2)) + 8!) + C(4!,5)) \\82992 &:= (T(C(8,T(2))) \times (T(9) + (9 - 2))) \\83055 &:= ((8! + T(T(T(3)))) + C((-((0! - 5)!),5)) \\83104 &:= (-T(C(8,3)) + (T(T(10)) \times T(T(4)))) \\83268 &:= (((T(C(8,3)) - T(2)) + 6!) \times T(8)) \\83300 &:= ((-8!) - C(T(T(3)),3)) \times (- (0! + 0!)) \\83302 &:= ((8! + (C(T(T(3)),3) + 0!)) \times 2) \\83324 &:= (((-8!) - C(T(T(3)),3)) \times (-2)) + (4!) \\83358 &:= ((8! - (T(3))!) + C((3 + T(5)),8)) \\83376 &:= (T(8) \times ((-C(T(3),3)) + T(T(7))) \times 6)) \\83382 &:= (((T(C(8,3)) + (T(3))!) \times T(8)) + T(T(2))) \\83384 &:= (C(8,3) \times (T(((T(3))! - T(T(8)))) + 4)) \\83538 &:= ((T(8) \times C((3 + T(5)),T(3)))/8) \\83538 &:= ((T(8) \times C((3 + T(5)),T(3)))/8) \\83544 &:= ((T(83) - C(5,4)) \times 4!) \\83625 &:= ((T(T(8)) + 3) \times (T(C(6,2)) + (5))) \\83644 &:= (-C(8,3) - ((T(6) - T(4!)) \times T(4!))) \\83649 &:= ((-8!) - T(T(T(3)))) + (T(C(6,4)) \times T(T(9))) \\83662 &:= (((-8!) + C(T(T(3)),6)) \times 6) - 2) \\83768 &:= (8 \times (T(3) + (C(T(7),6)/T(8)))) \\83826 &:= (((T(C(8,3)) + 8!) \times 2) - (6))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}83832 &:= (((T(C(8,3)) + 8!) \times T(3))/T(2)) \\83859 &:= ((8! + C((3 \times 8),5) + T(T(9))) \\83888 &:= ((T(C(8,T(3))) \times 8) + ((8! + 8!))) \\83916 &:= (T(T(8)) \times (T(3) + T((C(9,1) + 6)))) \\83958 &:= ((T(8) + T(3)) + (C(9,5) \times T(T(8)))) \\83972 &:= (-8 - ((C(T(T(3)),9)/7) \times (-2))) \\83975 &:= (((8 \times C(T(T(3)),9))/T(7)) - 5) \\83980 &:= ((8 \times C(T(T(3)),9))/T((8 - 0!))) \\84078 &:= (8! + C(((T(4) + 0!) + (7)),8)) \\84231 &:= (((8!/T(4)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(C(3,1)))) \\84246 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times T(C(4,2))) + T(T(4))) \times 6) \\84273 &:= (((8 - T(C(T(4),2))) + (7!)) \times T(T(3))) \\84294 &:= ((T(T(8)) + T((4 - 2))) \times C(9,4)) \\84336 &:= ((-T(8) - T(4!)) \times (-C(T(3),3) - T(T(6)))) \\84452 &:= -((T(T(8)) + ((T(T(4)) + C(4!,5)) \times (-2))) \\84476 &:= ((-8) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(4)))) \times T(C(7,6)) \\84490 &:= (T(C(8,4)) \times ((4! + 9) + 0!)) \\84529 &:= -((T(T(8)) - (T(T(4)) \times (T(T(C(5,2))) + 9)))) \\84541 &:= (T(T(8)) + ((T(T(T(4))) - T(5)) \times T(T(C(4,1))))) \\84562 &:= (((-8) - C(4!,5)) + T(T(6))) \times (-2) \\84635 &:= -((T(C(8,4)) - ((6! + T(3)) \times 5!)) \\84646 &:= (T(T(8)) - ((T(T(4)) \times (-C(T(6),T(4))))/T(T(6)))) \\84728 &:= ((T(C(8,4)) + (7)) \times (-2 + T(8))) \\84732 &:= (-T((8 \times 4)) + (T(T(7)) \times T(C(T(3),T(2))))) \\84754 &:= (T(T(8)) + (4 + (T(7) \times C(T(5),T(4))))) \\84765 &:= (((T(T(8)) - T(T(4))) + (C(7,6)!)) \times T(5)) \\84848 &:= ((T(T(8)) - (-4 \times T(C(8,4)))) \times 8) \\84848 &:= ((T(T(8)) - (-4 \times T(C(8,4)))) \times 8) \\84969 &:= -((T(T(8)) - ((4! \times T(C(9,6))) - T(9)))) \\84972 &:= -((T(8) + (C(4!,(-9) + T(7))) \times (-2))) \\84992 &:= ((8 - C(4!,(T(9)/9))) \times (-2)) \\85064 &:= (C(8,5) \times ((0 - T(6)) + T(T(T(4))))) \\85065 &:= ((T(T(8)) + (C(T(5),06))) \times T(5)) \\85134 &:= -((T(T(8)) - (5! \times C(13,4))) \\85149 &:= ((T(C(8,5)) \times (-1) + T(T(4))) - T(T(9))) \\85237 &:= ((-8) - T(5)) + (T(C(T(T(2)),3)) \times T(T(7))) \\85260 &:= (T((C(8,5)/2)) \times T((T(6) - 0!))) \\85272 &:= (C((-8) + (T(5) \times 2)),7)/2 \\85335 &:= ((-((T(8) - C(T(5),T(3)))) + (T(3)!)) \times T(5)) \\85338 &:= (((8!/C(5,3)) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(8)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}85461 &:= ((T(8) + C(T(5),4)) \times 61) \\85485 &:= (8! + ((C(T(5),T(4)) + 8) \times T(5))) \\85672 &:= (-8) + (T((-5) + T(6))) \times T(C(7,T(2)))) \\85689 &:= (8! + ((C(T(5),6) + T(8)) \times 9)) \\85697 &:= ((T(8) + C(T(5),6)) \times (T(9) - T(7))) \\85744 &:= (8 \times ((5! - T(7)) + C(4!,4))) \\85764 &:= -((T(8) + (5! \times (-C((7+6),4)))))) \\85834 &:= -((T(T((-8) + T(5)))) + (-C(8,3)) \times T(T(T(4)))))) \\85914 &:= (T(T(8)) \times (5! + C(9,1^4))) \\85974 &:= (-T(C(8,5))) - (T(9) \times (-T(T(7))) - T(T(T(4)))))) \\85984 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (5! + 9)) + C(8,4)) \\85986 &:= (T(T(8)) - (5! \times (C(9,8) - 6!))) \\86043 &:= -((T(86) \times (0! - (C(4,3)!))) \\86184 &:= ((T(8) - 6!) \times (-C((1+8),4))) \\86212 &:= (C(8,6) \times (-2) + T(T(12))) \\86262 &:= ((C(8,6) \times T(T((2 \times 6)))) - T(T(2))) \\86264 &:= ((C(8,6) \times T(T((2 \times 6)))) - 4) \\86268 &:= (C(8,6) \times T(((2 \times T(6)) + T(8)))) \\86268 &:= (C(8,6) \times T(((2 \times T(6)) + T(8)))) \\86343 &:= (-T(8)) - ((-6!) \times T(C(T(3),4))) + T(T(3))) \\86372 &:= (-C(8,6)) - ((T(3)! \times (-((7-2)!))) \\86391 &:= ((T((T(8) - T(6))) \times (T(3)!)) - C(9,1)) \\86399 &:= ((T((T(8) - T(6))) \times (T(3)!)) - C(9,9)) \\86433 &:= (T(8) + ((6! \times C(T(4),3)) - 3)) \\86436 &:= (T(8) - (-C((6+4),3)) \times 6!) \\86548 &:= (C(8,6) + (5! \times (T(T(4)) + T(T(8)))))) \\86625 &:= (((8 \times 6!) + C(6,2)) \times T(5)) \\86653 &:= (T((C(8,6) - 6)) - (-5!) \times (T(3)!)) \\86658 &:= ((-8) + T(6)) \times (T(T(6)) + C(T(5),8)) \\86730 &:= ((T(C(8,6)) + 7) \times T((T(T(3)) - 0!)) \\86855 &:= ((8 + T(6)) \times (-8) + C(T(5),5)) \\86961 &:= ((T(8) \times T(69)) + T(C(6,1))) \\86969 &:= ((8 + T(6)) - (-C(9,6)) \times T(T(9))) \\86996 &:= ((8!/6!) - (T(T(9)) \times (-C(9,6)))) \\87032 &:= ((T(8) + 7) \times C(((0! + 3)!), T(2))) \\87228 &:= (((8! + C(T(7), T(2))) \times 2) + T(8)) \\87326 &:= (8 - (-C(T(7), (T(3)/T(2)))) \times T(T(6))) \\87346 &:= (T((T(8) + 7)) - (T(C(T(3),4)) \times (-6!))) \\87372 &:= (((C(8,7)^{T(3)}) - T(7))/T(2)) \\87426 &:= (((T(8) \times T(T(7))) - C(T(4),2)) \times 6)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}87480 &:= (-((8 - C(7,4))) \times T(80)) \\87546 &:= (T(T(C(8,7))) - (5! \times (-4) - 6!)) \\87641 &:= (((-T(8)) \times T(T(7))) \times (-6)) - T(T(C(4,1)))) \\87759 &:= (8! + ((7! + T(C(7,5))) \times 9)) \\88220 &:= ((8 + T(C(8, T(2)))) \times T(T((T(2) + 0!)))) \\88244 &:= (((8 + T(C(8, T(2)))) \times T(T(4))) + (4!)) \\88254 &:= -((T(T(8)) - (T((T(8) + 2)) \times (C(5,4)!))) \\88362 &:= (T(T(8)) - (T(C(8, T(3))) \times (-6^{T(2)}))) \\88368 &:= ((C((8 + 8), T(3)) \times 6) + 8!) \\88425 &:= ((T(8) \times T(C(8,4))) - T((T(2) \times T(5)))) \\88449 &:= (((T(8) \times T(C(8,4))) + 4!) - T(T(9))) \\88452 &:= (T(8) \times (T(C(8,4) - T((5 + 2)))) \\88473 &:= ((T(8) \times (T(C(8,4) - T(7))) + T(T(3))) \\88572 &:= (T(T(8)) - (T(T((8 + 5))) \times (-C(7,2)))) \\88884 &:= (T(8) \times (-((8 + 8) + T(C(8,4)))) \\89214 &:= (-T(8)) - (T(C(9, T(2))) \times (-1) - 4!)) \\89244 &:= (T(T(8)) \times ((T(9) \times T(2)) - C(4,4))) \\89298 &:= -((T(T(8)) + (-C(9, T(2))) \times (T(T(9)) + T(8)))) \\89298 &:= -((T(T(8)) + (-C(9, T(2))) \times (T(T(9)) + T(8)))) \\89342 &:= ((T((T(8) - 9)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (C(4!, T(2)))) \\89422 &:= (((T(8) \times 9) \times C(4!, 2)) - 2) \\89468 &:= (8 + (T(9) \times (C(4!, T(6)) - T(8)))) \\89624 &:= (((8!/9) \times C(6, T(2))) + 4!) \\89667 &:= (T((T(8) + T(9))) \times (-C(6,6) + T(7))) \\89744 &:= (((T(8) \times T(C(9,7))) - T(T(T(4)))) \times 4) \\89824 &:= (8! + (C((9 + 8), T(T(2))) \times 4)) \\89944 &:= (-C(8, (T(9)/9))) + (T(4!) \times T(4!)) \\89962 &:= (((T(8) + T(T(9))) \times C(9,6)) - 2) \\89964 &:= ((T(8) + T(T(9))) \times C(9, T((6 - 4)))) \\91122 &:= ((T(9)^{C(1,1)+2}) - T(2)) \\91126 &:= ((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) + C(T(T(2)), 6)) \\91131 &:= ((T(9)^{T(1+1)}) + T(C(3,1))) \\91737 &:= (9 + (C(T((1 \times 7)), 3) \times T(7))) \\91772 &:= ((T(9) - 1) + (T(7) \times C(T(7), T(2)))) \\91773 &:= (T(9) + (T((1 \times 7)) \times C(T(7), 3))) \\92250 &:= (T(9) \times (C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) + (((5 + 0!))!)) \\92268 &:= ((T(C(9,2)) \times T((2 \times 6))) + 8!) \\92324 &:= ((-9) \times T(T(2))) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), T(4)) \\92333 &:= (-T(9)) + C((-2) + T(T(3)), (3 \times 3)) \\92335 &:= ((T(9)^{T(2)}) + (C(T(T(3)), 3) - (5!)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 92369 &:= (-9) + C(((T(T(2)))/(-3)) + (T(6)), 9) \\ 92391 &:= (((T(9)^{T(2)}) + T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(C(9,1)))) \\ 92393 &:= (9 + (C((-2) + T(T(3))), 9) + T(3)) \\ 92397 &:= (-9) + (C((-2) + T(T(3))), 9) + (T(7))) \\ 92448 &:= (((T(C(9,2)) - 4!) \times 4) \times T(8)) \\ 92484 &:= (C(9, T(2)) + (T(T(4)) \times (8!/4!))) \\ 92549 &:= (T((9 \times 2)) + C((-5) + 4!), 9) \\ 92586 &:= (-T(9) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-5) + T(C(8,6)))) \\ 92693 &:= ((T(T(9)) + C((-2) + T(6)), 9) - (T(3))!) \\ 92721 &:= ((T(9)^{T(2)}) + T((T(7) \times C(2,1)))) \\ 92741 &:= (-T(T(9))) - ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-T(T(7)))) + T(C(4,1))) \\ 92743 &:= (((T(9)^{T(2)}) - T(T(7))) + (C(4!, 3))) \\ 92757 &:= -(((T(T(9)) - T(T(2))) - (T(C(7,5)) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 92772 &:= ((-T(T(9))) + T(T(T(2)))) + (T(T(7)) \times T(C(7,2))) \\ 92844 &:= ((T(C(9, T(2))) \times (T(8) - T(4))) + (4!)) \\ 92988 &:= (T((9 - 2)) \times T((T(C(9,8)) + T(8)))) \\ 93024 &:= (((9 + T((3 + 0!)))!)/(C(T(T(2)), 4))!) \\ 93258 &:= (-T((T(9) + T(3)))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + 8!)) \\ 93321 &:= (9 + ((T(3)^{T(3)}) \times C(2,1))) \\ 93375 &:= ((T(T(9)) + T(C(T(3), 3))) \times 75) \\ 93465 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T((3 + T(4)))) - (C(6,5))!) \\ 93492 &:= ((T(T(9)) + (T((3 \times 4)))) \times C(9, T(2))) \\ 93572 &:= ((T((T(9) - T(3))) \times 5!) - T(C(7, T(T(2)))) \\ 93591 &:= ((T((T(9) - T(3))) \times 5!) - C(9, 1)) \\ 93599 &:= ((T((T(9) - T(3))) \times 5!) - C(9, 9)) \\ 93681 &:= ((T(T((9 - 3))) \times T(T(6))) + (C(8,1))!) \\ 93786 &:= (T(((9/3) \times 7)) \times T(C(8,6))) \\ 93830 &:= (T(9) - ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(C(8, T(3)))) + 0!)) \\ 93831 &:= (T(9) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(C(8, (3 - 1)))))) \\ 93933 &:= ((T((T(9) - 3)) + (T(C(9, 3)))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 93996 &:= ((C(9, 3) + T(T(9))) \times C(9, 6)) \\ 94228 &:= (-T(9) + (C(4!, T(T(2))) - (T(2) + 8!))) \\ 94269 &:= ((-((T(9) - C(4!, T(2)))) \times T(T(6))) - 9!) \\ 94278 &:= (9 + (C(4!, T(T(2))) - (7 + 8!))) \\ 94292 &:= (((9!/4) + 2) + T(C(9, T(2)))) \\ 94293 &:= (((9!/4) + T(2)) + T(C(9, 3))) \\ 94296 &:= (((9!/4) + T(T(2))) + (T(C(9, 6)))) \\ 94472 &:= (((T(9) \times T(4!)) - 4) \times C(7, T(T(2)))) \\ 94582 &:= ((C((T(9) - 4!), T(5)) + 8!) - 2) \\ 94599 &:= ((9 \times C(4!, -(5 - 9))) - T(T(9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 94731 &:= (((T(9) \times T(4!)) \times 7) + T(T(T(C(3,1)))))) \\ 94766 &:= ((T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + (T(T(C(7,6))) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 94866 &:= ((T(9) \times 4!) + (T(C(8,6)) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 94878 &:= (C(9,4) \times (87 + T(T(8)))) \\ 95256 &:= (-((C(9,5)^2)) \times (T(5) - T(6))) \\ 95262 &:= (((C(9,5)^2) \times 6) + T(T(2))) \\ 95276 &:= ((T(T(9)) + (C(T(5), T(2)))) + (T(T(7)) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 95304 &:= ((T(T(9)) - ((C(T(5), T(3)) + 0!))) \times (-4!)) \\ 95328 &:= (((C(9,5) \times T(T(3))) + 2) \times T(8)) \\ 95444 &:= ((-9) \times (T(5) - C(4!, 4))) - T(T(4)) \\ 95472 &:= (C(((9 + 5) + 4), 7) \times T(2)) \\ 95487 &:= ((9! + C(T(5), T(4))) - (T(T(8)) \times T(T(7)))) \\ 95544 &:= (9 \times (C((5!/5), 4) - T(4))) \\ 95634 &:= (9 \times C((T(5) + (6 + 3)), 4)) \\ 95755 &:= ((T(95) \times C(7,5)) - (5)) \\ 95820 &:= ((T(9) + T(5)) \times (T(C(8, T(2))) + 0!)) \\ 95895 &:= (T(9) + ((C(T(5), 8) - T(9)) \times T(5))) \\ 95940 &:= ((C(9,5) - 9) \times T(40)) \\ 96348 &:= (C(9,6) \times ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(4))) - 8)) \\ 96430 &:= -((T(C(9,6)) - (T(4)^{T(3)-0!})) \\ 96454 &:= -((T(C(9,6)) - ((T(4)^5) + 4!)) \\ 96475 &:= (((T(T(9)) - T(T(6))) \times C(T(4), 7)) - 5) \\ 96498 &:= ((T(C(9,6)) + (4)) \times (-9 + T(8))) \\ 96522 &:= ((T(9) \times T(65)) - C(T(2), 2)) \\ 96526 &:= ((T(9) \times T(65)) + C(T(T(2)), 6)) \\ 96531 &:= ((T(9) \times T(65)) + T(C(3,1))) \\ 96546 &:= (((T(T(9)) + (C(6,5)!)) \times T(T(4))) + (T(6))) \\ 96564 &:= ((9! + (6! \times 5!)) - C(T(6), T(4))) \\ 96577 &:= (C((T(9) - T(6)), (5 + 7)) / T(7)) \\ 96768 &:= ((96 \times T(C(7,6))) \times T(8)) \\ 96795 &:= (T(T(9)) - (6! \times (-7 + C(9,5)))) \\ 96798 &:= (T((T(9) + (6))) \times (T(7) + T(C(9,8)))) \\ 96936 &:= (((T(C(9,6)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(3))) + T(T(6))) \\ 96943 &:= -((T(T(9)) + ((C(T(6), 9) + (4)) / (-3)))) \\ 97125 &:= -((T(T(9)) - (C(T(7), (-1) + T(T(2)))) - (5!))) \\ 97163 &:= ((T(9) + T(7)) \times (1 + C(T(6), 3))) \\ 97217 &:= -((T(T(9)) - (C(T(7), (T(T(2)) - 1)) - (T(7)))) \\ 97266 &:= -((T(T(9)) - (C(T(7), (2 + T(6))) + T(6))) \\ 97417 &:= ((C((-9) + T(7)), T(4)) - 1) + 7! \\ 97418 &:= (C((-9) + T(7), T(4)) + (-((1 - 8)!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 97422 &:= ((-9) - (T(T(7)) \times (-C(T(4), T(2)))) \times 2) \\ 97425 &:= (T(T(9)) - (-T(C(7, 4))) \times T((2 + T(5)))) \\ 97464 &:= (-C(9, 7) + (T(4!) \times T((T(6) + (4)))) \\ 97515 &:= -((T(9) - (C(T(7), 5) - ((1 + 5)!))) \\ 97516 &:= -((T(9) - ((C(T(7), 5) + 1) - 6!))) \\ 97536 &:= ((-((T(9) - C(T(7), 5))) - (T(3)!)) + (T(6))) \\ 97542 &:= -((((T(T(9)) - (C(T(7), 5))) - T(4!)) + T(2))) \\ 97545 &:= ((T(9) + C(T(7), 5)) - T((4! + T(5)))) \\ 97551 &:= (-9) + (C(T(7), 5) - ((5 + 1)!)) \\ 97556 &:= (-9) + ((C(T(7), 5) + (5)) - 6!) \\ 97563 &:= (9 + ((C(T(7), 5) - 6!) - T(3))) \\ 97569 &:= ((9 + C(T(7), 5)) - (T(-((6 - 9))))!) \\ 97576 &:= (9 + ((C(T(7), 5) + (7)) - 6!)) \\ 97587 &:= ((-T(9)) - (-C(7, 5)) \times T(T(8))) \times 7) \\ 97596 &:= (T(9) + ((C(T(7), 5) - 9) - 6!)) \\ 97775 &:= ((T(T(9)) - T(T(T((T(7)/7)))) + (C(T(7), 5))) \\ 97776 &:= (T((97 - C(7, 7))) \times T(6)) \\ 97846 &:= (T((C(9, 7) - 8)) \times (T(4) + T(T(6)))) \\ 97865 &:= ((-9) - T(T(7))) + (C(C(8, 6), 5)) \\ 98235 &:= -((T(9) - (C(C(8, (2 \times 3)), 5))) \\ 98256 &:= -(((T(9) - (C(C(8, 2), 5))) - T(6))) \\ 98325 &:= (T(9) + (C((C(8, 3)/2), 5))) \\ 98355 &:= -((T(9) - (C(C(8, T(3)), 5) + 5!))) \\ 98370 &:= (T(C(9, 8)) \times ((3^7) - 0!)) \\ 98375 &:= ((98 - 3) + C(T(7), 5)) \\ 98556 &:= (T(9) + (C(T((-8) + T(5)), 5) + T(T(6)))) \\ 98663 &:= ((C((-9) + T(8)), T(6)) - T(6))/3) \\ 98682 &:= ((C((-9) + T(8)), T(6)) + T(8))/T(2)) \\ 98736 &:= (T((C(9, 8) + 7)) \times (T(3) + 6!)) \\ 98752 &:= ((T((T(9) - 8)) + (C(T(7), 5))) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 99315 &:= (T(T(9)) + (C(((9 \times 3) + 1), 5))) \\ 99486 &:= (-9) - (-T(9) \times T((C(T(4), 8) + T(6)))) \\ 99552 &:= (C((9 + 9), T(5)) \times (5! + 2)) \\ 99792 &:= ((99 \times T(7)) \times C(9, 2)) \\ 99912 &:= -((T(T(9)) - C((T(T(9))/T(9)), T((1 + 2)))) \\ 99933 &:= -((T(T(9)) - (C((T(T(9))/T(9)), T(3)) + T(T(3)))) \\ 99937 &:= ((T(T(9))/(-T(9))) + ((T(C(9, 3)) \times T(7))) \\ 99945 &:= -((T((C(9, 9) + 9)) - (T(4)^5))) \end{aligned}$$

2 Reverse Order of Digits

This section brings **selfie numbers** written in reverse order of Digits. The results are up to 7-digits numbers. It is divided in three subsections. One with symmetric and consecutive. Second symmetric and nonconsecutive and third general values.

2.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

$$\begin{aligned}
 3270 &:= 0 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3) \\
 3271 &:= 1 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3) \\
 3272 &:= 2 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3) \\
 3273 &:= 3 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3) \\
 3274 &:= 4 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3) \\
 3275 &:= 5 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3) \\
 3276 &:= 6 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3) \\
 3277 &:= 7 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3) \\
 3278 &:= 8 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3) \\
 3279 &:= 9 + C(T(7), T(2)) - T(3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 02210 &:= 0 + T(C(12, 2)) - 0! \\
 02211 &:= 1 + T(C(12, 2)) - 0! \\
 02212 &:= 2 + T(C(12, 2)) - 0! \\
 02213 &:= 3 + T(C(12, 2)) - 0! \\
 02214 &:= 4 + T(C(12, 2)) - 0! \\
 02215 &:= 5 + T(C(12, 2)) - 0! \\
 02216 &:= 6 + T(C(12, 2)) - 0! \\
 02217 &:= 7 + T(C(12, 2)) - 0! \\
 02218 &:= 8 + T(C(12, 2)) - 0! \\
 02219 &:= 9 + T(C(12, 2)) - 0!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 03690 &:= 0 + T(C(9, 6)) + (T(3) - 0!)! \\
 03691 &:= 1 + T(C(9, 6)) + (T(3) - 0!)! \\
 03692 &:= 2 + T(C(9, 6)) + (T(3) - 0!)! \\
 03693 &:= 3 + T(C(9, 6)) + (T(3) - 0!)! \\
 03694 &:= 4 + T(C(9, 6)) + (T(3) - 0!)! \\
 03695 &:= 5 + T(C(9, 6)) + (T(3) - 0!)! \\
 03696 &:= 6 + T(C(9, 6)) + (T(3) - 0!)! \\
 03697 &:= 7 + T(C(9, 6)) + (T(3) - 0!)! \\
 03698 &:= 8 + T(C(9, 6)) + (T(3) - 0!)! \\
 03699 &:= 9 + T(C(9, 6)) + (T(3) - 0!)!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$04390 := 0 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 04391 &:= 1 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40) \\
 04392 &:= 2 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40) \\
 04393 &:= 3 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40) \\
 04394 &:= 4 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40) \\
 04395 &:= 5 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40) \\
 04396 &:= 6 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40) \\
 04397 &:= 7 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40) \\
 04398 &:= 8 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40) \\
 04399 &:= 9 + T(C(9, 3)) + T(40)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 14490 &:= 0 + T(T(9)) \times (4! - T(C(4, 1))) \\
 14491 &:= 1 + T(T(9)) \times (4! - T(C(4, 1))) \\
 14492 &:= 2 + T(T(9)) \times (4! - T(C(4, 1))) \\
 14493 &:= 3 + T(T(9)) \times (4! - T(C(4, 1))) \\
 14494 &:= 4 + T(T(9)) \times (4! - T(C(4, 1))) \\
 14495 &:= 5 + T(T(9)) \times (4! - T(C(4, 1))) \\
 14496 &:= 6 + T(T(9)) \times (4! - T(C(4, 1))) \\
 14497 &:= 7 + T(T(9)) \times (4! - T(C(4, 1))) \\
 14498 &:= 8 + T(T(9)) \times (4! - T(C(4, 1))) \\
 14499 &:= 9 + T(T(9)) \times (4! - T(C(4, 1)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 17280 &:= 0 + 8! \times T(2)/C(7, 1) \\
 17281 &:= 1 + 8! \times T(2)/C(7, 1) \\
 17282 &:= 2 + 8! \times T(2)/C(7, 1) \\
 17283 &:= 3 + 8! \times T(2)/C(7, 1) \\
 17284 &:= 4 + 8! \times T(2)/C(7, 1) \\
 17285 &:= 5 + 8! \times T(2)/C(7, 1) \\
 17286 &:= 6 + 8! \times T(2)/C(7, 1) \\
 17287 &:= 7 + 8! \times T(2)/C(7, 1) \\
 17288 &:= 8 + 8! \times T(2)/C(7, 1) \\
 17289 &:= 9 + 8! \times T(2)/C(7, 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 20240 &:= 0 + C(4!, T(2)) \times T(0! + T(2)) \\
 20241 &:= 1 + C(4!, T(2)) \times T(0! + T(2)) \\
 20242 &:= 2 + C(4!, T(2)) \times T(0! + T(2))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20243 &:= 3 + C(4!, T(2)) \times T(0! + T(2)) \\ 20244 &:= 4 + C(4!, T(2)) \times T(0! + T(2)) \\ 20245 &:= 5 + C(4!, T(2)) \times T(0! + T(2)) \\ 20246 &:= 6 + C(4!, T(2)) \times T(0! + T(2)) \\ 20247 &:= 7 + C(4!, T(2)) \times T(0! + T(2)) \\ 20248 &:= 8 + C(4!, T(2)) \times T(0! + T(2)) \\ 20249 &:= 9 + C(4!, T(2)) \times T(0! + T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20470 &:= 0 + C(T(7), 4!) + 0! - T(T(2)) \\ 20471 &:= 1 + C(T(7), 4!) + 0! - T(T(2)) \\ 20472 &:= 2 + C(T(7), 4!) + 0! - T(T(2)) \\ 20473 &:= 3 + C(T(7), 4!) + 0! - T(T(2)) \\ 20474 &:= 4 + C(T(7), 4!) + 0! - T(T(2)) \\ 20475 &:= 5 + C(T(7), 4!) + 0! - T(T(2)) \\ 20476 &:= 6 + C(T(7), 4!) + 0! - T(T(2)) \\ 20477 &:= 7 + C(T(7), 4!) + 0! - T(T(2)) \\ 20478 &:= 8 + C(T(7), 4!) + 0! - T(T(2)) \\ 20479 &:= 9 + C(T(7), 4!) + 0! - T(T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21420 &:= 0 + T(T(2)) \times T(C((T(4) - 1), T(2))) \\ 21421 &:= 1 + T(T(2)) \times T(C((T(4) - 1), T(2))) \\ 21422 &:= 2 + T(T(2)) \times T(C((T(4) - 1), T(2))) \\ 21423 &:= 3 + T(T(2)) \times T(C((T(4) - 1), T(2))) \\ 21424 &:= 4 + T(T(2)) \times T(C((T(4) - 1), T(2))) \\ 21425 &:= 5 + T(T(2)) \times T(C((T(4) - 1), T(2))) \\ 21426 &:= 6 + T(T(2)) \times T(C((T(4) - 1), T(2))) \\ 21427 &:= 7 + T(T(2)) \times T(C((T(4) - 1), T(2))) \\ 21428 &:= 8 + T(T(2)) \times T(C((T(4) - 1), T(2))) \\ 21429 &:= 9 + T(T(2)) \times T(C((T(4) - 1), T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22680 &:= 0 + T(8) \times (C(T(6), 2) \times T(2)) \\ 22681 &:= 1 + T(8) \times (C(T(6), 2) \times T(2)) \\ 22682 &:= 2 + T(8) \times (C(T(6), 2) \times T(2)) \\ 22683 &:= 3 + T(8) \times (C(T(6), 2) \times T(2)) \\ 22684 &:= 4 + T(8) \times (C(T(6), 2) \times T(2)) \\ 22685 &:= 5 + T(8) \times (C(T(6), 2) \times T(2)) \\ 22686 &:= 6 + T(8) \times (C(T(6), 2) \times T(2)) \\ 22687 &:= 7 + T(8) \times (C(T(6), 2) \times T(2)) \\ 22688 &:= 8 + T(8) \times (C(T(6), 2) \times T(2)) \\ 22689 &:= 9 + T(8) \times (C(T(6), 2) \times T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23850 &:= 0 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \\ 23851 &:= 1 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \\ 23852 &:= 2 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \\ 23853 &:= 3 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \\ 23854 &:= 4 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \\ 23855 &:= 5 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \\ 23856 &:= 6 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \\ 23857 &:= 7 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \\ 23858 &:= 8 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \\ 23859 &:= 9 + T(5) \times (T(C(8, 3)) - T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24850 &:= 0 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \\ 24851 &:= 1 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \\ 24852 &:= 2 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \\ 24853 &:= 3 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \\ 24854 &:= 4 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \\ 24855 &:= 5 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \\ 24856 &:= 6 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \\ 24857 &:= 7 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \\ 24858 &:= 8 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \\ 24859 &:= 9 + 5 \times T(C(8, 4)) \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26250 &:= 0 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \\ 26251 &:= 1 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \\ 26252 &:= 2 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \\ 26253 &:= 3 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \\ 26254 &:= 4 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \\ 26255 &:= 5 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \\ 26256 &:= 6 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \\ 26257 &:= 7 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \\ 26258 &:= 8 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \\ 26259 &:= 9 + 5^{T(2)} \times C(T(6), 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26600 &:= 0 + (-0! + T(6)) \times C(T(6), T(2)) \\ 26601 &:= 1 + (-0! + T(6)) \times C(T(6), T(2)) \\ 26602 &:= 2 + (-0! + T(6)) \times C(T(6), T(2)) \\ 26603 &:= 3 + (-0! + T(6)) \times C(T(6), T(2)) \\ 26604 &:= 4 + (-0! + T(6)) \times C(T(6), T(2)) \\ 26605 &:= 5 + (-0! + T(6)) \times C(T(6), T(2)) \\ 26606 &:= 6 + (-0! + T(6)) \times C(T(6), T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26607 &:= 7 + (-0! + T(6)) \times C(T(6), T(2)) \\ 26608 &:= 8 + (-0! + T(6)) \times C(T(6), T(2)) \\ 26609 &:= 9 + (-0! + T(6)) \times C(T(6), T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27360 &:= 0 + 6! \times (3 + C(7, T(2))) \\ 27361 &:= 1 + 6! \times (3 + C(7, T(2))) \\ 27362 &:= 2 + 6! \times (3 + C(7, T(2))) \\ 27363 &:= 3 + 6! \times (3 + C(7, T(2))) \\ 27364 &:= 4 + 6! \times (3 + C(7, T(2))) \\ 27365 &:= 5 + 6! \times (3 + C(7, T(2))) \\ 27366 &:= 6 + 6! \times (3 + C(7, T(2))) \\ 27367 &:= 7 + 6! \times (3 + C(7, T(2))) \\ 27368 &:= 8 + 6! \times (3 + C(7, T(2))) \\ 27369 &:= 9 + 6! \times (3 + C(7, T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27930 &:= 0 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 27931 &:= 1 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 27932 &:= 2 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 27933 &:= 3 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 27934 &:= 4 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 27935 &:= 5 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 27936 &:= 6 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 27937 &:= 7 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 27938 &:= 8 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \\ 27939 &:= 9 + C(T(T(3)), T(9-7)) \times T(T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28980 &:= 0 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2) \\ 28981 &:= 1 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2) \\ 28982 &:= 2 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2) \\ 28983 &:= 3 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2) \\ 28984 &:= 4 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2) \\ 28985 &:= 5 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2) \\ 28986 &:= 6 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2) \\ 28987 &:= 7 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2) \\ 28988 &:= 8 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2) \\ 28989 &:= 9 + T(T(8) + 9) \times C(8, 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32400 &:= 0 + C(T(04), 2) \times (T(3))! \\ 32401 &:= 1 + C(T(04), 2) \times (T(3))! \\ 32402 &:= 2 + C(T(04), 2) \times (T(3))! \\ 32403 &:= 3 + C(T(04), 2) \times (T(3))! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32404 &:= 4 + C(T(04), 2) \times (T(3))! \\ 32405 &:= 5 + C(T(04), 2) \times (T(3))! \\ 32406 &:= 6 + C(T(04), 2) \times (T(3))! \\ 32407 &:= 7 + C(T(04), 2) \times (T(3))! \\ 32408 &:= 8 + C(T(04), 2) \times (T(3))! \\ 32409 &:= 9 + C(T(04), 2) \times (T(3))! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32411 &:= 11 + C(T(4), 2) \times T(3)! \\ 32422 &:= 22 + C(T(4), 2) \times T(3)! \\ 32433 &:= 33 + C(T(4), 2) \times T(3)! \\ 32444 &:= 44 + C(T(4), 2) \times T(3)! \\ 32455 &:= 55 + C(T(4), 2) \times T(3)! \\ 32466 &:= 66 + C(T(4), 2) \times T(3)! \\ 32477 &:= 77 + C(T(4), 2) \times T(3)! \\ 32488 &:= 88 + C(T(4), 2) \times T(3)! \\ 32499 &:= 99 + C(T(4), 2) \times T(3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32640 &:= 0 + 4! \times C(T(6), T(2)) + T(3)! \\ 32641 &:= 1 + 4! \times C(T(6), T(2)) + T(3)! \\ 32642 &:= 2 + 4! \times C(T(6), T(2)) + T(3)! \\ 32643 &:= 3 + 4! \times C(T(6), T(2)) + T(3)! \\ 32644 &:= 4 + 4! \times C(T(6), T(2)) + T(3)! \\ 32645 &:= 5 + 4! \times C(T(6), T(2)) + T(3)! \\ 32646 &:= 6 + 4! \times C(T(6), T(2)) + T(3)! \\ 32647 &:= 7 + 4! \times C(T(6), T(2)) + T(3)! \\ 32648 &:= 8 + 4! \times C(T(6), T(2)) + T(3)! \\ 32649 &:= 9 + 4! \times C(T(6), T(2)) + T(3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33250 &:= 0 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3) \\ 33251 &:= 1 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3) \\ 33252 &:= 2 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3) \\ 33253 &:= 3 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3) \\ 33254 &:= 4 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3) \\ 33255 &:= 5 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3) \\ 33256 &:= 6 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3) \\ 33257 &:= 7 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3) \\ 33258 &:= 8 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3) \\ 33259 &:= 9 + 5^2 \times C(T(T(3)), 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34220 &:= 0 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3) \\ 34221 &:= 1 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34222 &:= 2 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3) \\ 34223 &:= 3 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3) \\ 34224 &:= 4 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3) \\ 34225 &:= 5 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3) \\ 34226 &:= 6 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3) \\ 34227 &:= 7 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3) \\ 34228 &:= 8 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3) \\ 34229 &:= 9 + C(T(T(2)), T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)) + 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34230 &:= 0 + (C(T(T(3)), T(2)) + T(4!)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 34231 &:= 1 + (C(T(T(3)), T(2)) + T(4!)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 34232 &:= 2 + (C(T(T(3)), T(2)) + T(4!)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 34233 &:= 3 + (C(T(T(3)), T(2)) + T(4!)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 34234 &:= 4 + (C(T(T(3)), T(2)) + T(4!)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 34235 &:= 5 + (C(T(T(3)), T(2)) + T(4!)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 34236 &:= 6 + (C(T(T(3)), T(2)) + T(4!)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 34237 &:= 7 + (C(T(T(3)), T(2)) + T(4!)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 34238 &:= 8 + (C(T(T(3)), T(2)) + T(4!)) \times T(T(3)) \\ 34239 &:= 9 + (C(T(T(3)), T(2)) + T(4!)) \times T(T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36840 &:= 0 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6,3)) \\ 36841 &:= 1 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6,3)) \\ 36842 &:= 2 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6,3)) \\ 36843 &:= 3 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6,3)) \\ 36844 &:= 4 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6,3)) \\ 36845 &:= 5 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6,3)) \\ 36846 &:= 6 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6,3)) \\ 36847 &:= 7 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6,3)) \\ 36848 &:= 8 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6,3)) \\ 36849 &:= 9 + T(T(4)) \times T(T(8)) + T(C(6,3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 37890 &:= 0 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7,3)) \\ 37891 &:= 1 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7,3)) \\ 37892 &:= 2 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7,3)) \\ 37893 &:= 3 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7,3)) \\ 37894 &:= 4 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7,3)) \\ 37895 &:= 5 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7,3)) \\ 37896 &:= 6 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7,3)) \\ 37897 &:= 7 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7,3)) \\ 37898 &:= 8 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7,3)) \\ 37899 &:= 9 + T(T(9)) \times T(8) + T(C(7,3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38430 &:= 0 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8,3)) \\ 38431 &:= 1 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8,3)) \\ 38432 &:= 2 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8,3)) \\ 38433 &:= 3 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8,3)) \\ 38434 &:= 4 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8,3)) \\ 38435 &:= 5 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8,3)) \\ 38436 &:= 6 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8,3)) \\ 38437 &:= 7 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8,3)) \\ 38438 &:= 8 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8,3)) \\ 38439 &:= 9 + T(T(3)) \times T(4 + C(8,3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38760 &:= 0 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3)) \\ 38761 &:= 1 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3)) \\ 38762 &:= 2 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3)) \\ 38763 &:= 3 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3)) \\ 38764 &:= 4 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3)) \\ 38765 &:= 5 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3)) \\ 38766 &:= 6 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3)) \\ 38767 &:= 7 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3)) \\ 38768 &:= 8 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3)) \\ 38769 &:= 9 + C(T(6) + 7 - 8, T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39480 &:= 0 + 8! - T(4) \times C(9,3) \\ 39481 &:= 1 + 8! - T(4) \times C(9,3) \\ 39482 &:= 2 + 8! - T(4) \times C(9,3) \\ 39483 &:= 3 + 8! - T(4) \times C(9,3) \\ 39484 &:= 4 + 8! - T(4) \times C(9,3) \\ 39485 &:= 5 + 8! - T(4) \times C(9,3) \\ 39486 &:= 6 + 8! - T(4) \times C(9,3) \\ 39487 &:= 7 + 8! - T(4) \times C(9,3) \\ 39488 &:= 8 + 8! - T(4) \times C(9,3) \\ 39489 &:= 9 + 8! - T(4) \times C(9,3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42350 &:= 0 + T(T(C(5,3)))/2 \times T(T(4)) \\ 42351 &:= 1 + T(T(C(5,3)))/2 \times T(T(4)) \\ 42352 &:= 2 + T(T(C(5,3)))/2 \times T(T(4)) \\ 42353 &:= 3 + T(T(C(5,3)))/2 \times T(T(4)) \\ 42354 &:= 4 + T(T(C(5,3)))/2 \times T(T(4)) \\ 42355 &:= 5 + T(T(C(5,3)))/2 \times T(T(4)) \\ 42356 &:= 6 + T(T(C(5,3)))/2 \times T(T(4)) \\ 42357 &:= 7 + T(T(C(5,3)))/2 \times T(T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$42358 := 8 + T(T(C(5,3)))/2 \times T(T(4))$$

$$42359 := 9 + T(T(C(5,3)))/2 \times T(T(4))$$

$$42480 := 0 - 8! + C(4!,2) \times T(4!)$$

$$42481 := 1 - 8! + C(4!,2) \times T(4!)$$

$$42482 := 2 - 8! + C(4!,2) \times T(4!)$$

$$42483 := 3 - 8! + C(4!,2) \times T(4!)$$

$$42484 := 4 - 8! + C(4!,2) \times T(4!)$$

$$42485 := 5 - 8! + C(4!,2) \times T(4!)$$

$$42486 := 6 - 8! + C(4!,2) \times T(4!)$$

$$42487 := 7 - 8! + C(4!,2) \times T(4!)$$

$$42488 := 8 - 8! + C(4!,2) \times T(4!)$$

$$42489 := 9 - 8! + C(4!,2) \times T(4!)$$

$$42540 := 0 + C(4!,5) + T(2 \times 4)$$

$$42541 := 1 + C(4!,5) + T(2 \times 4)$$

$$42542 := 2 + C(4!,5) + T(2 \times 4)$$

$$42543 := 3 + C(4!,5) + T(2 \times 4)$$

$$42544 := 4 + C(4!,5) + T(2 \times 4)$$

$$42545 := 5 + C(4!,5) + T(2 \times 4)$$

$$42546 := 6 + C(4!,5) + T(2 \times 4)$$

$$42547 := 7 + C(4!,5) + T(2 \times 4)$$

$$42548 := 8 + C(4!,5) + T(2 \times 4)$$

$$42549 := 9 + C(4!,5) + T(2 \times 4)$$

$$43380 := 0 + 8! + C(3 \times T(3),4)$$

$$43381 := 1 + 8! + C(3 \times T(3),4)$$

$$43382 := 2 + 8! + C(3 \times T(3),4)$$

$$43383 := 3 + 8! + C(3 \times T(3),4)$$

$$43384 := 4 + 8! + C(3 \times T(3),4)$$

$$43385 := 5 + 8! + C(3 \times T(3),4)$$

$$43386 := 6 + 8! + C(3 \times T(3),4)$$

$$43387 := 7 + 8! + C(3 \times T(3),4)$$

$$43388 := 8 + 8! + C(3 \times T(3),4)$$

$$43389 := 9 + 8! + C(3 \times T(3),4)$$

$$48620 := 0 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4)$$

$$48621 := 1 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4)$$

$$48622 := 2 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4)$$

$$48623 := 3 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4)$$

$$48624 := 4 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4)$$

$$48625 := 5 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4)$$

$$48626 := 6 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4)$$

$$48627 := 7 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4)$$

$$48628 := 8 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4)$$

$$48629 := 9 + C(T(2) \times 6, T(8)/4)$$

$$51840 := 0 + T(4)!/(C(8, -1 + 5))$$

$$51841 := 1 + T(4)!/(C(8, -1 + 5))$$

$$51842 := 2 + T(4)!/(C(8, -1 + 5))$$

$$51843 := 3 + T(4)!/(C(8, -1 + 5))$$

$$51844 := 4 + T(4)!/(C(8, -1 + 5))$$

$$51845 := 5 + T(4)!/(C(8, -1 + 5))$$

$$51846 := 6 + T(4)!/(C(8, -1 + 5))$$

$$51847 := 7 + T(4)!/(C(8, -1 + 5))$$

$$51848 := 8 + T(4)!/(C(8, -1 + 5))$$

$$51849 := 9 + T(4)!/(C(8, -1 + 5))$$

$$52240 := 0 - C(4!, T(2)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$$

$$52241 := 1 - C(4!, T(2)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$$

$$52242 := 2 - C(4!, T(2)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$$

$$52243 := 3 - C(4!, T(2)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$$

$$52244 := 4 - C(4!, T(2)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$$

$$52245 := 5 - C(4!, T(2)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$$

$$52246 := 6 - C(4!, T(2)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$$

$$52247 := 7 - C(4!, T(2)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$$

$$52248 := 8 - C(4!, T(2)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$$

$$52249 := 9 - C(4!, T(2)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$$

$$53130 := 0 + C(31 - T(3), 5)$$

$$53131 := 1 + C(31 - T(3), 5)$$

$$53132 := 2 + C(31 - T(3), 5)$$

$$53133 := 3 + C(31 - T(3), 5)$$

$$53134 := 4 + C(31 - T(3), 5)$$

$$53135 := 5 + C(31 - T(3), 5)$$

$$53136 := 6 + C(31 - T(3), 5)$$

$$53137 := 7 + C(31 - T(3), 5)$$

$$53138 := 8 + C(31 - T(3), 5)$$

$$53139 := 9 + C(31 - T(3), 5)$$

$$53340 := 0 - 4 \times T(T(T(3))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))$$

$$53341 := 1 - 4 \times T(T(T(3))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))$$

$$53342 := 2 - 4 \times T(T(T(3))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53343 &:= 3 - 4 \times T(T(T(3))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\ 53344 &:= 4 - 4 \times T(T(T(3))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\ 53345 &:= 5 - 4 \times T(T(T(3))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\ 53346 &:= 6 - 4 \times T(T(T(3))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\ 53347 &:= 7 - 4 \times T(T(T(3))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\ 53348 &:= 8 - 4 \times T(T(T(3))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\ 53349 &:= 9 - 4 \times T(T(T(3))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53970 &:= 0 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5) \\ 53971 &:= 1 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5) \\ 53972 &:= 2 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5) \\ 53973 &:= 3 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5) \\ 53974 &:= 4 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5) \\ 53975 &:= 5 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5) \\ 53976 &:= 6 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5) \\ 53977 &:= 7 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5) \\ 53978 &:= 8 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5) \\ 53979 &:= 9 + (T(7) + T(C(9,3))) \times T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54240 &:= 0 - 4! + C(T(2+4), T(5)) \\ 54241 &:= 1 - 4! + C(T(2+4), T(5)) \\ 54242 &:= 2 - 4! + C(T(2+4), T(5)) \\ 54243 &:= 3 - 4! + C(T(2+4), T(5)) \\ 54244 &:= 4 - 4! + C(T(2+4), T(5)) \\ 54245 &:= 5 - 4! + C(T(2+4), T(5)) \\ 54246 &:= 6 - 4! + C(T(2+4), T(5)) \\ 54247 &:= 7 - 4! + C(T(2+4), T(5)) \\ 54248 &:= 8 - 4! + C(T(2+4), T(5)) \\ 54249 &:= 9 - 4! + C(T(2+4), T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54330 &:= 0 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5)) \\ 54331 &:= 1 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5)) \\ 54332 &:= 2 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5)) \\ 54333 &:= 3 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5)) \\ 54334 &:= 4 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5)) \\ 54335 &:= 5 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5)) \\ 54336 &:= 6 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5)) \\ 54337 &:= 7 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5)) \\ 54338 &:= 8 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5)) \\ 54339 &:= 9 + C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(-4 + T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54360 &:= 0 + C(T(6), T(3)) - 4! + 5! \\ 54361 &:= 1 + C(T(6), T(3)) - 4! + 5! \\ 54362 &:= 2 + C(T(6), T(3)) - 4! + 5! \\ 54363 &:= 3 + C(T(6), T(3)) - 4! + 5! \\ 54364 &:= 4 + C(T(6), T(3)) - 4! + 5! \\ 54365 &:= 5 + C(T(6), T(3)) - 4! + 5! \\ 54366 &:= 6 + C(T(6), T(3)) - 4! + 5! \\ 54367 &:= 7 + C(T(6), T(3)) - 4! + 5! \\ 54368 &:= 8 + C(T(6), T(3)) - 4! + 5! \\ 54369 &:= 9 + C(T(6), T(3)) - 4! + 5! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54670 &:= 0 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), (T(4) + (5))) \\ 54671 &:= 1 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), (T(4) + (5))) \\ 54672 &:= 2 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), (T(4) + (5))) \\ 54673 &:= 3 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), (T(4) + (5))) \\ 54674 &:= 4 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), (T(4) + (5))) \\ 54675 &:= 5 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), (T(4) + (5))) \\ 54676 &:= 6 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), (T(4) + (5))) \\ 54677 &:= 7 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), (T(4) + (5))) \\ 54678 &:= 8 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), (T(4) + (5))) \\ 54679 &:= 9 + T(T(7)) + C(T(6), (T(4) + (5))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 62670 &:= 0 + (C(T(7), 6) - T(T(2))!)/6 \\ 62671 &:= 1 + (C(T(7), 6) - T(T(2))!)/6 \\ 62672 &:= 2 + (C(T(7), 6) - T(T(2))!)/6 \\ 62673 &:= 3 + (C(T(7), 6) - T(T(2))!)/6 \\ 62674 &:= 4 + (C(T(7), 6) - T(T(2))!)/6 \\ 62675 &:= 5 + (C(T(7), 6) - T(T(2))!)/6 \\ 62676 &:= 6 + (C(T(7), 6) - T(T(2))!)/6 \\ 62677 &:= 7 + (C(T(7), 6) - T(T(2))!)/6 \\ 62678 &:= 8 + (C(T(7), 6) - T(T(2))!)/6 \\ 62679 &:= 9 + (C(T(7), 6) - T(T(2))!)/6 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 62740 &:= 0 + (-T(4!) + C(T(7), T(T(2))))/6 \\ 62741 &:= 1 + (-T(4!) + C(T(7), T(T(2))))/6 \\ 62742 &:= 2 + (-T(4!) + C(T(7), T(T(2))))/6 \\ 62743 &:= 3 + (-T(4!) + C(T(7), T(T(2))))/6 \\ 62744 &:= 4 + (-T(4!) + C(T(7), T(T(2))))/6 \\ 62745 &:= 5 + (-T(4!) + C(T(7), T(T(2))))/6 \\ 62746 &:= 6 + (-T(4!) + C(T(7), T(T(2))))/6 \\ 62747 &:= 7 + (-T(4!) + C(T(7), T(T(2))))/6 \\ 62748 &:= 8 + (-T(4!) + C(T(7), T(T(2))))/6 \end{aligned}$$

$$62749 := 9 + (-T(4!) + C(T(7), T(T(2))))/6$$

$$64240 := 0 - T(T(T(4))) + C(2 + 4!, T(6))$$

$$64241 := 1 - T(T(T(4))) + C(2 + 4!, T(6))$$

$$64242 := 2 - T(T(T(4))) + C(2 + 4!, T(6))$$

$$64243 := 3 - T(T(T(4))) + C(2 + 4!, T(6))$$

$$64244 := 4 - T(T(T(4))) + C(2 + 4!, T(6))$$

$$64245 := 5 - T(T(T(4))) + C(2 + 4!, T(6))$$

$$64246 := 6 - T(T(T(4))) + C(2 + 4!, T(6))$$

$$64247 := 7 - T(T(T(4))) + C(2 + 4!, T(6))$$

$$64248 := 8 - T(T(T(4))) + C(2 + 4!, T(6))$$

$$64249 := 9 - T(T(T(4))) + C(2 + 4!, T(6))$$

$$64260 := 0 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6)$$

$$64261 := 1 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6)$$

$$64262 := 2 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6)$$

$$64263 := 3 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6)$$

$$64264 := 4 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6)$$

$$64265 := 5 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6)$$

$$64266 := 6 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6)$$

$$64267 := 7 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6)$$

$$64268 := 8 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6)$$

$$64269 := 9 + C(T(6) - T(2), 4) \times T(6)$$

$$67830 := 0 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$67831 := 1 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$67832 := 2 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$67833 := 3 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$67834 := 4 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$67835 := 5 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$67836 := 6 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$67837 := 7 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$67838 := 8 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$67839 := 9 + C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7/T(6)$$

$$76680 := 0 - 8! + 6! + C(T(6), 7)$$

$$76681 := 1 - 8! + 6! + C(T(6), 7)$$

$$76682 := 2 - 8! + 6! + C(T(6), 7)$$

$$76683 := 3 - 8! + 6! + C(T(6), 7)$$

$$76684 := 4 - 8! + 6! + C(T(6), 7)$$

$$76685 := 5 - 8! + 6! + C(T(6), 7)$$

$$76686 := 6 - 8! + 6! + C(T(6), 7)$$

$$76687 := 7 - 8! + 6! + C(T(6), 7)$$

$$76688 := 8 - 8! + 6! + C(T(6), 7)$$

$$76689 := 9 - 8! + 6! + C(T(6), 7)$$

$$77520 := 0 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$77521 := 1 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$77522 := 2 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$77523 := 3 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$77524 := 4 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$77525 := 5 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$77526 := 6 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$77527 := 7 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$77528 := 8 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$77529 := 9 + C(-2 + T(5) + 7, 7)$$

$$85260 := 0 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

$$85261 := 1 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

$$85262 := 2 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

$$85263 := 3 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

$$85264 := 4 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

$$85265 := 5 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

$$85266 := 6 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

$$85267 := 7 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

$$85268 := 8 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

$$85269 := 9 + C(T(6), 2) \times T(T(T(5) - 8))$$

2.2 General Representations

$$24 := (C(4, T(2)))!$$

$$15 := T(C(5, 1))$$

$$\begin{aligned}105 &:= C(T(5), (0! + 1)) \\168 &:= (8 \times T(C(6, 1))) \\254 &:= (C(T(4), 5) + 2) \\286 &:= C((T(6) - 8), T(2)) \\351 &:= T((T(T(3)) + C(5, 1))) \\378 &:= T(-((8 - C(7, 3)))) \\455 &:= C(T(5), (5!/T(4))) \\525 &:= (C(T(5), 2) \times 5) \\637 &:= (T(T(C(7, T(3)))) + T(T(6))) \\645 &:= (C(T(5), 4) - 6!) \\792 &:= C((T(2) + 9), 7) \\ \\0139 &:= (C(9, 3) + T(10)) \\0234 &:= ((C(4, 3))! + T(20)) \\0238 &:= (C(8, T(3)) + T(20)) \\0247 &:= -((T(7) - (C(4!, 2) - 0!))) \\0285 &:= (C((5 + 8), T(2)) - 0!) \\0374 &:= (-4 + C(T(7), (3 - 0!))) \\0386 &:= ((-T(6) + T(C(8, T(3)))) + 0!) \\0452 &:= -((T(2) - C(T(5), (4 - 0!)))) \\0455 &:= C(T(5), (5!/40)) \\0475 &:= (-5! + T((C(7, 4) - 0!))) \\0496 &:= (C((T(6) - 9), 4) + 0!) \\0593 &:= ((T(3))! + (-C(9, 5) - 0!)) \\0924 &:= (T(C(4, 2)) \times (T(9) - 0!)) \\0935 &:= (-T(C(5, 3)) + T((T(9) - 0!))) \\1034 &:= (T(C(T(4), (3 - 0!))) - 1) \\1129 &:= (T((T(9) + 2)) + C(1, 1)) \\1156 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times 5) + C(1, 1)) \\1176 &:= T((6 \times C((7 + 1), 1))) \\1227 &:= (T((7^2)) + C(2, 1)) \\1266 &:= (6 \times (C(T(6), 2) + 1)) \\1284 &:= ((-4!) + T(T(8))) \times C(2, 1) \\1309 &:= (T(T((9 + 0!))) - T(T(T(C(3, 1)))))) \\1326 &:= (C(T(6), T(2)) - (3 + 1)) \\1333 &:= (C(T(T(3)), 3) + C(3, 1)) \\1336 &:= (C(T(6), 3) + T(C(3, 1))) \\1337 &:= (7 - (C(T(T(3)), 3) \times (-1))) \\1339 &:= (9 - (C(T(T(3)), 3) \times (-1))) \\1345 &:= ((5^4) + (T(C(3, 1)))) \\1356 &:= ((T(T(6)) - 5) \times T(C(3, 1)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1365 &:= C(T(5), ((6 - 3) + 1)) \\1368 &:= (8 \times T(C((6 \times 3), 1))) \\1383 &:= ((-3) + T(T(8))) + (T(C(3, 1)))! \\1386 &:= (T(6) \times T(C((8 + 3), 1))) \\1389 &:= ((T(9) \times T(8)) - T(T(T(C(3, 1)))))) \\1432 &:= (2 \times ((T(3))! - C(4, 1))) \\1435 &:= (T(53) + C(4, 1)) \\1436 &:= ((6! + (T(3))!) - C(4, 1)) \\1444 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - (4! \times C(4, 1))) \\1445 &:= ((5 \times T(4!)) - T(T(C(4, 1)))) \\1487 &:= (T(T(7)) + T((T(8) + T(C(4, 1))))) \\1494 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - (-9 + T(T(C(4, 1))))) \\1525 &:= (-T(5) + T(T(C((2 \times 5), 1)))) \\1534 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - C(T(3), C(5, 1))) \\1535 &:= (T(T(C(5, 3))) - C(5, 1)) \\1536 &:= (T(C(6, 3)) + T(51)) \\1557 &:= (T(C(7, 5)) + T(51)) \\1568 &:= (C(8, 6) + T(T(T((5 - 1)))))) \\1575 &:= ((T(5) \times 7) \times T(C(5, 1))) \\1582 &:= ((1 - T(5)) + T(C(8, T(2)))) \\1588 &:= (-8) + T((C(8, 5) \times 1)) \\1617 &:= (7 \times T(T(C((1 \times 6), 1)))) \\1623 &:= ((T(3))! + T((2 \times T(C(6, 1))))) \\1638 &:= (T((T(8)/3)) \times T(C(6, 1))) \\1653 &:= T((T((3 + 5)) + T(C(6, 1)))) \\1654 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (5! - C(6, 1))) \\1736 &:= (C(T(6), 3) + T(T(C(7, 1)))) \\1824 &:= (-4!) - (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-C(8, 1))) \\1832 &:= ((2 - T(T(T(3)))) \times (-C(8, 1))) \\1842 &:= (T((2 \times 4!)) + T(T(C(8, 1)))) \\1845 &:= (T(5) + T((4! + T(C(8, 1))))) \\1938 &:= (T((T(8) + T(3))) + T(T(C(9, 1)))) \\1998 &:= (T(T(8)) \times T((C(9, 9) + 1))) \\2022 &:= (-2) + C(((T(2) + 0!)!, T(2))) \\2024 &:= C(4!, T(((2 \times 0) + 2))) \\2034 &:= (C(4!, 3) + T((0! + T(2)))) \\2079 &:= (9 \times T(C(7, 02))) \\2145 &:= T((5! - T(C((4 + 1), 2)))) \\2211 &:= T(C((1 \times 12), 2)) \\2255 &:= ((-5) + T(T(C(5, 2)))) + (T(T(2)))!\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2268 &:= ((T(8) + 6!) \times C(T(2), 2)) \\ 2275 &:= (5 \times C(T((7 - 2)), T(2))) \\ 2283 &:= -(((T(3))! - C((8 + T(T(2))), T(T(2)))))) \\ 2288 &:= (8 \times C((-8) + T(T(T(2))), T(2))) \\ 2295 &:= (T(5) \times C((9 \times 2), 2)) \\ 2324 &:= (T(4!) + C(((-2) + T(3))!), T(2))) \\ 2328 &:= ((C(8, T(2)) + (T(3))!) \times T(2)) \\ 2353 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), T(5))/T(T(3))) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 2354 &:= ((4^5) + C(T(T(3)), T(2))) \\ 2358 &:= ((T(T(8)) + (5!)) \times C(3, 2)) \\ 2365 &:= (-5!) + T((T(C(6, 3))/T(2))) \\ 2388 &:= ((-8) + T(C(8, T(3)))) \times T(T(2)) \\ 2427 &:= (T(T(7)) - (T(2) - C(4!, T(2)))) \\ 2447 &:= (-T(7)) + (T(T(4)) \times C(T(4), 2)) \\ 2475 &:= (T(5) \times C((7 + 4), T(2))) \\ 2481 &:= ((-1) + T(C(8, 4))) - T(2) \\ 2482 &:= (-T(2) + T(C(8, C(4, T(2)))))) \\ 2484 &:= ((-4) + T(C(8, 4))) + T(2) \\ 2488 &:= (T(C(8, (8 - 4))) + T(2)) \\ 2491 &:= (T(C(-(1 - 9)), 4) + T(T(2))) \\ 2494 &:= (T(4) + (9 \times C(4!, 2))) \\ 2539 &:= (-T(9)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 2544 &:= (4! + (4! \times C(T(5), 2))) \\ 2558 &:= (T((C(8, 5) + T(5))) + 2) \\ 2569 &:= ((T(T(9)) - 6) + T(T(C(5, 2)))) \\ 2595 &:= (5! + (T(9) \times T(C(5, 2)))) \\ 2596 &:= ((T(6) + T(T(9))) + T(T(C(5, 2)))) \\ 2597 &:= -((T(T(7)) - C((9 + 5), T(T(2)))))) \\ 2605 &:= (T(50) + C(T(6), T(2))) \\ 2627 &:= (T(72) - C(6, T(T(2)))) \\ 2629 &:= (T(9) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6)/T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 2643 &:= (T((3 \times 4!)) + C(6, 2)) \\ 2649 &:= ((C(9, 4) \times T(6)) + T(2)) \\ 2736 &:= (6! + T((3 \times C(7, 2)))) \\ 2748 &:= -((T((8 \times 4)) - C(T(7), T(2)))) \\ 2779 &:= ((-9) + T(T(7))) \times C(7, T(T(2))) \\ 2829 &:= (T(C(9, T(2))) - T((T(8) + 2))) \\ 2842 &:= ((T(2) + (4)) \times T(C(8, 2))) \\ 2848 &:= (8 \times (T(4!) + C(8, T(2)))) \\ 2856 &:= (T(C(6, 5)) \times T((8 \times 2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2878 &:= (T(8) + (7 \times T(C(8,2)))) \\ 2897 &:= -((T(7) - C((-9) + T(8)), T(2))) \\ 2922 &:= -((T(2) - C((T(2) \times 9), T(2))) \\ 2925 &:= C(((5 - 2) \times 9), T(2)) \\ 2926 &:= T((T(6) + C((2 + 9), 2))) \\ 2935 &:= (C(T(5), T(3)) - (T(T(9)) \times 2)) \\ 2945 &:= (-((5^4)) + T(C(9, T(2)))) \\ 2955 &:= ((C(T(5), 5) - T(9)) - T(2)) \\ 2964 &:= ((4 \times 6!) + C(9, T(2))) \\ 3003 &:= C(T((T(3) - 0!)), -(0! - T(3))) \\ 3025 &:= (T(C(5, 2))^{-0!+3}) \\ 3059 &:= (T(T(9)) + C(((5 - 0!)!, 3)) \\ 3192 &:= (2 \times T(C((9 - 1), 3))) \\ 3248 &:= (8 \times T(C((4 \times 2), T(3)))) \\ 3264 &:= (4 \times C((T(6) - T(2)), 3)) \\ 3268 &:= (-8) + C(T((T(6)/T(2))), 3)) \\ 3282 &:= (C(28, T(2)) + T(3)) \\ 3282 &:= (T(3) + C(28, T(2))) \\ 3297 &:= (C(T(7), (9/T(2))) + T(T(3))) \\ 3328 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times T(2)) + C(T(T(3)), 3)) \\ 3339 &:= (T(C(9, 3)) - T(T((3 + 3)))) \\ 3353 &:= ((-C(T(T(3)), 5) + T(T(T(3))))/(-T(3))) \\ 3394 &:= ((T(T(4)) + (T(C(9, 3)))) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 3432 &:= (2 \times C((3 + T(4)), T(3))) \\ 3445 &:= (C(T(5), 4) + T((4^3))) \\ 3478 &:= (-8) + T((T(7) + T(T(C(4, 3)))))) \\ 3536 &:= (T(T((6 + T(3)))) + (C(T(5), 3))) \\ 3538 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times 3) + T(T(C(5, 3)))) \\ 3564 &:= (C(4!, T(6)) + T(T(C(5, 3)))) \\ 3565 &:= (-5) + T(C((-6) + T(5)), 3)) \\ 3569 &:= ((T(C(9, 6)) + (5)) - T(3)) \\ 3594 &:= (4! + T(C(9, T((5 - 3)))))) \\ 3599 &:= (-C(9, 9) + (5 \times (T(3))!)) \\ 3723 &:= ((T(3))! + C((2 \times 7), T(3))) \\ 3755 &:= ((5^5) + T(C(7, 3))) \\ 3765 &:= -((T(5) + (-6) \times T(C(7, 3)))) \\ 3772 &:= (T((T(2) + T(7))) + (C(T(7), 3))) \\ 3784 &:= (4 \times T((8 + C(7, 3)))) \\ 3837 &:= (C(T(7), 3) + T((T(8) - 3))) \\ 3864 &:= ((T(4!) - T(T(6))) \times C(8, 3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3876 &:= (C(T(6),7)/(T(8) - T(3))) \\ 3888 &:= (T(88) - C(8, T(3))) \\ 3973 &:= ((-3) + T(T(7))) + (T(C(9,3))) \\ 3976 &:= (T((T(6) + (7))) + (T(C(9,3)))) \\ 4192 &:= (T(T((C(4,1) + 9))) + T(T(2))) \\ 4241 &:= (T(C(14,2)) + T(T(4))) \\ 4278 &:= T((8 + (C(7,2) \times 4))) \\ 4324 &:= (((C(4,2))! \times T(3)) + (4)) \\ 4434 &:= (4! - (T(T(3)) \times (-C(T(4),4)))) \\ 4445 &:= ((T(C(5,4)) \times T(4!)) - T(T(4))) \\ 4469 &:= (T((C(9,6) + T(4))) + 4) \\ 4486 &:= (T(6) + T((C(8,4) + 4!))) \\ 4525 &:= (C(T(5), T(T(2))) + (5! \times (-4))) \\ 4528 &:= (C(8,2) - (-T(5) \times T(4!))) \\ 4543 &:= (T(T((T(3) + (4)))) + (C(T(5), T(4)))) \\ 4696 &:= (T(T(6)) + T((C(9,6) + T(4)))) \\ 4705 &:= (C(T(5), -(0! - (7))) - T(4!)) \\ 4768 &:= ((C(8,6) + 7!) - T(4!)) \\ 4795 &:= (C(T(5), 9) - (7!/4!)) \\ 4866 &:= (T(6) + C((6!/T(8)), 4)) \\ 5005 &:= C(T(5), (0! + 05)) \\ 5125 &:= (C(T(5), T((2 + 1))) + 5!) \\ 5236 &:= (C(T(5), (2 \times 3)) + T(T(6))) \\ 5247 &:= (7! + (T(C(T(4), 2))/5)) \\ 5276 &:= ((T(T(6)) + (C(7, T(T(2))))!) + 5) \\ 5356 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((C(T(5), T(3)) + 5!)) \\ 5365 &:= (C(T(5), 6) - (-3 \times 5!)) \\ 5425 &:= ((C(T(5), T(T(2))) + T(4!)) + (5!)) \\ 5445 &:= ((C(T(5), 4) \times 4) - T(5)) \\ 5543 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times 4!) - C(5, 5)) \\ 5624 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) + (6! \times 5)) \\ 5635 &:= (T(T(C(5, 3))) + T((6 \times T(5)))) \\ 5676 &:= (6 \times T((T(C(7, 6)) + T(5)))) \\ 5677 &:= ((7! + T(T(7))) + T(T(C(6, 5)))) \\ 5796 &:= (T(6) \times (T(9) + T(C(7, 5)))) \\ 5825 &:= (C(T(5), T(T(2))) + (T((8 \times 5)))) \\ 5979 &:= ((T(C(9, 7)) \times 9) - T(5)) \\ 5985 &:= C(-((T(5) - T(8))), (9 - 5)) \\ 6162 &:= (2 \times T(T((C(6, 1) + 6))) \\ 6216 &:= (C(T(6), (1 + T(2))) + T(T(6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6342 &:= ((2 + T((C(4,3)))!) \times T(6)) \\6384 &:= ((4! \times T(C(8,3)))/6) \\6429 &:= ((T(C(9,2)) \times T(4)) - T(T(6))) \\6435 &:= C(T(5), C((3+4), 6)) \\6524 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) - T(T(T(2)))) + (C(T(5), 6))) \\6542 &:= ((-T(2) + T(T(T(4)))) + (C(T(5), 6))) \\6756 &:= (((C(6,5))! + T(T(7))) \times 6) \\6825 &:= (C(T(5), T(2)) \times (T(8) - T(6))) \\6935 &:= (C(T(5), 3) - (-9 \times 6!)) \\7064 &:= (C(4!, T(6)) + (07)!) \\7224 &:= ((T(C(T(4), 2)) - T(2)) \times 7) \\7227 &:= (7! + (C(T(2), 2)^7)) \\7242 &:= (-T(2) - (T(C(T(4), 2)) \times (-7))) \\7251 &:= (T(T((1 + C(5, 2)))) + (7!)) \\7483 &:= ((3 \times T(C(8, 4))) + T(7)) \\7753 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) + 7)/7) \\7756 &:= ((C(T(6), T(5)) + T(7))/7) \\7875 &:= (C(T(5), 7) + (8!/T(7))) \\7956 &:= (6 \times T((T(5) + C(9, 7)))) \\7992 &:= ((T(2) + 9) \times T(C(9, 7))) \\8336 &:= (C(6, 3) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T(8))) \\8442 &:= -(((T(2) \times C(4!, 4)) - 8!)) \\8532 &:= (C((T(2) \times T(3)), 5) - T(8)) \\9225 &:= ((-5) + T(C(T(T(2)), T(2)))) \times T(9)) \\9324 &:= (C(9, 3) + (T(T(2)) \times T(T(T(4)))))) \\9435 &:= ((T(9) \times C(T(4), T(3))) - T(5)) \\9445 &:= (-5) + (C(T(4), 4) \times T(9)) \\9445 &:= ((T(9) \times C(T(4), 4)) - 5) \\9675 &:= (C(T(5), 7) + T((6!/9))) \\ \\00174 &:= ((C(T(4), 7) + T(10)) - 0!) \\00189 &:= (T((C(9, 8) + 10)) - 0!) \\00274 &:= ((C((-4) + T(7)), 2) - 0!) - 0! \\00278 &:= ((8 \times C(7, T(2))) - (0! + 0!)) \\00283 &:= (C((T(T(3)) - 8), T(2)) - T((0! + 0!))) \\00358 &:= (((T(8) \times C(5, 3)) - 0!) - 0!) \\00627 &:= (T(C(7, T(2))) - (6/(0! + 0!))) \\00631 &:= (1 + (3 \times C(T(6), (0! + 0!)))) \\00632 &:= (2 + (3 \times C(T(6), (0! + 0!)))) \\00634 &:= (4 + (3 \times C(T(6), (0! + 0!)))) \\00792 &:= C((T(2) + 9), (7 + 00))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}00794 &:= (C(T(4), 9) + (T(7)^{0!+0!})) \\00798 &:= (T(C(8, T((9 - 7)))) / (0! + 0!)) \\00812 &:= (2 \times T(C((1 \times 8), (0! + 0!)))) \\00847 &:= (7 \times (C(T(4), (8 - 0!)) + 0!)) \\00926 &:= (- (C(6, T(2))) + T(((T(9) - 0!) - 0!))) \\00946 &:= ((T(6) \times C(T(4), (9 - 0!))) + 0!) \\01042 &:= ((T(T(2)) + T(C(T(4), (0! + 1)))) + 0!) \\01129 &:= (T((C(9, 2) + 11)) + 0!) \\01135 &:= (- (5) + C((T(T(3)) - 1), T((1 + 0!)))) \\01228 &:= ((T(C(8, 2)) \times T(2)) + 10) \\01234 &:= (C(T(4), T(3)) + (2^{10})) \\01255 &:= ((5! \times C(5, 2)) + T(10)) \\01298 &:= (((T(8) \times C(9, 2)) + 1) + 0!) \\01332 &:= ((C(T((2 \times 3)), 3) + 1) + 0!) \\01351 &:= (T((1 + 5)) + C(T(T(3)), T((1 + 0!)))) \\01355 &:= (C(T(5), (5 + T(3))) - 10) \\01357 &:= (- (7) + (C(T(5), (3 + 1)) - 0!)) \\01358 &:= (- (8) + (C(T(5), (3 + 1)) + 0!)) \\01364 &:= (4! + (C(T(6), 3) + 10)) \\01366 &:= (C((- (6) + T(6)), (3 + 1)) + 0!) \\01386 &:= (T(6) \times (C(8, 3) + 10)) \\01388 &:= ((T(T(8)) + C(8, T(3))) \times (1 + 0!)) \\01424 &:= (- ((C(T(4), T(2)) - (4))) + T(T(10))) \\01522 &:= (- ((C(T(2), 2) + T(5))) + T(T(10))) \\01583 &:= ((- (3) + T(C(8, 5))) - 10) \\01589 &:= (((- (9) + T(C(8, 5))) + 1) + 0!) \\01658 &:= ((T(C(8, 5)) + (61)) + 0!) \\01664 &:= (C(4!, T(6)) + (6! / (- (1) - 0!))) \\01733 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), 3) + T(T(7))) - T((1 + 0!))) \\01745 &:= ((T(5) \times C(T(4), 7)) - T(10)) \\01754 &:= ((C(T(4), 5) \times 7) - 10) \\01757 &:= ((T(C(7, 5)) + 7!) / T((1 + 0!))) \\01924 &:= ((C(4!, T(2)) - T(9)) - T(10)) \\01927 &:= ((C(T(7), 2) + 9) + T(T(10))) \\01958 &:= ((- (C(8, 5)) + T(T(9))) \times (1 + 0!)) \\01979 &:= ((C(9, 7) \times T((9 + 1))) - 0!) \\02004 &:= (C(4!, T((0! + 0!))) - (20)) \\02014 &:= (C(4!, T((1 + 0!))) - T((T(2) + 0!))) \\02046 &:= (T(6) + (C(4!, T(02)) + 0!)) \\02195 &:= ((- (T(5)) + T(T((C(9, 1) + 2)))) - 0!)\end{aligned}$$

- 02234** := $(C(4!, C(3, 2)) + T(20))$
02244 := $(T(4) + (C(4!, T(2)) + T(20)))$
02246 := $((T(T(6)) + T((T(C(4, 2)) \times T(2)))) - 0!)$
02248 := $((T(8) + T(C((4!/2), 2))) + 0!)$
02253 := $((((T(3))! + T(T(C(5, 2)))) - T(T(2))) - 0!)$
02261 := $(C(T((1 \times 6)), T(T(2)))/(T(2) + 0!))!$
02269 := $((C(9, 6) \times (T(2)^{T(2)})) + 0!)$
02273 := $((T(3) \times C(T(7), 2) + T(T(2))) - 0!)$
02299 := $(C(((T(9)/9)^2), T(2)) - 0!)$
02301 := $(C((1 + ((0! + 3))!), T(2)) + 0!)$
02304 := $((C((4! + 0!), 3) + T(2)) + 0!)$
02311 := $((11 \times T(C(T(3), T(2)))) + 0!)$
02319 := $(T((T(9) - 1)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(2)) - 0!))$
02369 := $(T(T(9)) + ((C(T(6), 3) + T(2)) + 0!))$
02385 := $(T(5) \times ((8 \times C(T(3), T(2))) - 0!))$
02399 := $((((T(9)/9))! \times C(T(3), T(2))) - 0!)$
02437 := $(T(T(7)) + (T(3) + (C(4!, T(2)) + 0!)))$
02439 := $(9 \times ((T(3) \times C(T(4), 2)) + 0!))$
02443 := $((T(3))! - T(4!)) + ((C(4!, T(2)) - 0!))$
02466 := $((T(6) \times T(6)) + (C(4!, T(2)) + 0!))$
02474 := $-(((T(4) - T((C(7, 4) \times 2))) + 0!))$
02477 := $((-7) + T((C(7, 4) \times 2))) - 0!$
02478 := $((-8) + T((C(7, 4) \times 2))) + 0!$
02483 := $((-3) + T(C(8, 4))) + ((2 \times 0))!$
02486 := $((T(6) + T(C(8, 4))) - (20))$
02519 := $((T(9) \times (1 + T(C(5, 2)))) - 0!)$
02534 := $(T(4^3) + (C(T(5), T(2)) - 0!))$
02542 := $(-2) + (4! \times (C(T(5), 2) + 0!))$
02544 := $(4! \times (T((4 + C(5, 2))) + 0!))$
02545 := $(5 \times (T(T(4)) + ((C(T(5), T(2)) - 0!)))$
02547 := $(T(7) + ((4! \times C(T(5), 2)) - 0!))$
02573 := $((C((T(3) + 7), 5) \times 2) - 0!)$
02575 := $((C(T(5), 7)/(-5) \times (-2)) + 0!)$
02592 := $((T(2) + T(9)) \times (T(C(5, 2)) - 0!))$
02594 := $((T(4!) \times 9) - (C(T(5), 2) + 0!))$
02642 := $(-2) \times (T(4) - (C(T(6), T(2)) + 0!))$
02654 := $(T(T(4)) + (C((5 + T(6)), T(2)) - 0!))$
02683 := $-((T(3) + ((8!/(-C(6, 2))) - 0!))$
02699 := $((9 \times T((9 + C(6, 2)))) - 0!)$
02783 := $((3 + 8) \times T((C(7, 2) + 0!))$

$$\begin{aligned}02794 &:= (T((4! + T(9))) + ((C(T(7), 2) + 0!))) \\02795 &:= (5 \times (C((9 + 7), T(2)) - 0!)) \\02796 &:= (6 \times (T((9 + C(7, 2)) + 0!)) \\02843 &:= (((3 + 4) \times T(C(8, 2))) + 0!) \\02849 &:= (T((9 + C((4 + 8), 2))) - 0!) \\02904 &:= (4! \times (C((0! + 9), T(2)) + 0!)) \\02932 &:= (T(T(2)) + (C((3 \times 9), T(2)) + 0!)) \\02934 &:= (T(4) + (C((3 \times 9), T(2)) - 0!)) \\02935 &:= ((5 \times (T(3))!) - (T(C(9, 2)) - 0!)) \\02975 &:= ((5 \times 7) \times (C(9, T(2)) + 0!)) \\02983 &:= ((-T(3)) - T(T(8))) + T((C(9, T(2)) + 0!)) \\02984 &:= (-4) + (T(8) \times (C(9, T(2)) - 0!)) \\02996 &:= (T(T((T(6) - 9))) - (C(9, T(2)) + 0!)) \\03025 &:= (T(C(5, 2))^{0!+(3 \times 0)!}) \\03104 &:= ((T(C(T(4), (0! + 1))) \times 3) - 0!) \\03145 &:= (-T(5)) + T((T((C(4, 1) \times 3)) + 0!)) \\03165 &:= (T(5) \times (T(C(C(6, 1), 3)) + 0!)) \\03221 &:= (C(T((1 + T(T(2))))), T(2)) - T(T((3 + 0!))) \\03224 &:= (T(4!) + (C((T(2)^{T(2)}), 3) - 0!)) \\03256 &:= -((T(6) - (C(T((5 + 2)), 3) + 0!)) \\03261 &:= (C(T((1 + 6)), T(2)) - T((T(3) - 0!)) \\03271 &:= ((C(T((1 \times 7)), T(2)) - T(3)) + 0!) \\03273 &:= (3 \times ((C(T(7), T(2))/3) - 0!)) \\03274 &:= ((C((4 \times 7), T(2)) - 3) + 0!) \\03275 &:= (C(C((T(5) - 7), 2), 3) - 0!) \\03276 &:= C((T(6) + 7), T((2 + (3 \times 0)))) \\03281 &:= (C(T(-(1 - 8)), T(2)) + (T(3) - 0!)) \\03283 &:= ((T(3) + C(C(8, 2), 3)) + 0!) \\03285 &:= (T(5) \times (C((T(8)/T(2)), 3) - 0!)) \\03288 &:= (8 \times ((T(C(8, 2)) + T(3)) - 0!)) \\03295 &:= (5 \times ((T(C(9, 2)) - T(3)) - 0!)) \\03296 &:= (T(6) + (C(T((9 - 2)), 3) - 0!)) \\03322 &:= (C(2, 2) + T((3^{3+0!})) \\03325 &:= ((-T(C(5, 2))) + (T(3))!) \times (T(3) - 0!) \\03345 &:= ((5! \times (C(4, 3))!) + T(30)) \\03361 &:= ((C(16, 3) \times T(3)) + 0!) \\03423 &:= (3 \times (C((2 \times T(4)), 3) + 0!)) \\03429 &:= -((T(C(9, 2)) - (4^{T(3)} - 0!)) \\03442 &:= (T((T(2)^4)) + (C(T(4), 3) + 0!)) \\03459 &:= (-9) + (C(T(5), T(4)) + T(30))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}03463 &:= ((T(3))! + (6! + (C(4!, 3) - 0!))) \\03468 &:= (C((T(8) - T(6)), T(4)) + T(30)) \\03499 &:= ((-C(9, 9) - T(T(T(4)))) + ((T(3) + 0!)!) \\03569 &:= (T(C(9, 6)) - ((5 - 3) \times 0)!) \\03574 &:= ((T((4 \times C(7, 5))) + 3) + 0!) \\03575 &:= (5 \times C((T(7) - T(5)), (3 + 0!))) \\03624 &:= ((C(4, T(2)))! + (6! \times (T(3) - 0!))) \\03628 &:= (C(8, 2) + (6! \times (T(3) - 0!))) \\03652 &:= (-T(2) + T((C((T(5) - (6)), 3) + 0!))) \\03656 &:= (T((65 + C(6, 3))) + 0!) \\03666 &:= (-6) \times (6! - (C(T(6), 3) + 0!)) \\03669 &:= ((T(C(9, 6)) - T(6)) + ((T(3) - 0!)!) \\03766 &:= ((6! - T(T(6))) + (C(T(7), 3) + 0!)) \\03783 &:= (3 \times ((T(8) \times C(7, 3)) + 0!)) \\03827 &:= (T(((C(7, 2) + 8) \times 3) - 0!) \\03869 &:= ((T(C(9, 6)) + T((8 \times 3))) - 0!) \\03915 &:= (T(((5 - 1) + C(9, 3))) - 0!) \\03947 &:= ((T(T(7)) + T(T(4))) + T((C(9, 3) - 0!))) \\03955 &:= (T((5!/5) + T((C(9, 3) + 0!))) \\04126 &:= (-6!) + (C((T(T(T(2))) - 1), 4) + 0!) \\04185 &:= (C(T(5), (8 + 1)) - T(40)) \\04226 &:= (T(T((C(6, 2) - 2))) + 40) \\04256 &:= ((T(6) + T(C(5, 2))) \times (T(T(4)) + 0!)) \\04275 &:= (5 \times (C(7, T(2)) + T(40))) \\04359 &:= (((T(T(9)) + T(C(5, 3))) \times 4) - 0!) \\04431 &:= (T(T((1 \times 3))) \times (C(T(4), 4) + 0!)) \\04432 &:= (T(T(T(2))) + ((T(T(3)) \times C(T(4), 4)) + 0!)) \\04434 &:= ((T(4!) \times C(T(3), 4)) - T((T(4) + 0!))) \\04466 &:= (T(((6 \times C(6, 4)) + 4) + 0!) \\04523 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))/ (5!/T(4))) + 0!) \\04674 &:= (T((C(T(4), 7) - T(6))) - T((4! - 0!))) \\04688 &:= -(((T(8) \times T(8)) - (C(T(6), 4) - 0!))) \\04689 &:= (T(T(9)) + (T(C(8, 6)) \times (T(4) - 0!))) \\04761 &:= ((T(16) \times C(7, 4)) + 0!) \\04827 &:= (7! - (T(2) \times (C(8, 4) + 0!))) \\04834 &:= (-T(4) + (C(((T(3))!/T(8)), 4) - 0!)) \\04835 &:= ((C(T(5), T(3)) - T((8 + T(4)))) + 0!) \\04838 &:= (-8) + (C(((T(3))!/T(8)), 4) + 0!) \\04852 &:= (T((T((2 + 5)) + (C(8, 4)))) + 0!) \\04913 &:= (((T(3) + 1))! - (C(9, 4) + 0!))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}04935 &:= (((C(T(5), T(3)) - T(9)) - 4!) - 0!) \\04965 &:= (((C(T(5), 6) - T(9)) + (4)) + 0!) \\05004 &:= (C(T((4 + 0!)), (0! + (5))) - 0!) \\05006 &:= (C(T((6 - 0!)), (0! + (5))) + 0!) \\05015 &:= (C(T(5), T(T((1 + 0!)))) + T((5 - 0!))) \\05236 &:= (T(T(6)) + (C(T((3 + 2)), (5 + 0!)))) \\05245 &:= (5 \times (T(C(T(4), 2)) + (T(5) - 0!))) \\05247 &:= ((7! + T(T(C(4, 2)))) - ((5 - 0!))!) \\05266 &:= ((C((T(6) + (6)), 2) \times T(5)) + 0!) \\05277 &:= (((7! + T(C(7, 2))) + (5)) + 0!) \\05305 &:= (C(T(5), T(03)) + T(((5 - 0!))!)) \\05313 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (C(T((1 + 3)), 5) + 0!)) \\05318 &:= -(((T(T(8)) + 1) - C(T(T(3)), (5 - 0!)))) \\05319 &:= -((T(T((9 - 1))) - C(T(T(3)), (5 - 0!)))) \\05329 &:= ((T(C(9, 2)) \times (3 + 5)) + 0!) \\05332 &:= ((-T(2)) - C(T(T(3)), 3)) \times (-5 + 0!) \\05426 &:= (C(T(6), T(2)) + (4^{5+0!})) \\05438 &:= -((T(T(8)) - (C(T(T(3)), 4) + ((5! - 0!)))) \\05475 &:= ((5! \times C(7, 4)) + T(50)) \\05537 &:= (7 \times (C((-3) + T(5)), 5) - 0!) \\05546 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times 4!) + (C(5, 5) + 0!)) \\05586 &:= ((T(6) \times T(C(8, 5)))/(5 + 0!)) \\05679 &:= (9 \times (T((C(7, 6) \times 5)) + 0!)) \\05682 &:= (-2) + (T(C(8, 6)) \times (T(5) - 0!)) \\05715 &:= (C(T(5), (1 \times 7)) - ((5 + 0!))!) \\05725 &:= (C(T(5), T(T(2))) + ((7 - ((5 \times 0))!))!) \\05776 &:= -((6! - (T(7) \times (T(C(7, 5)) + 0!))) \\05896 &:= (6! + ((T(T(C(9, 8))) \times 5) + 0!)) \\05935 &:= ((C(T(5), T(3)) + T(T(9))) - T((T(5) - 0!))) \\05946 &:= (((C(T(6), 4) - T(9)) + (5)) + 0!) \\05985 &:= (C(T(5), 8) - ((9 \times 50))) \\05986 &:= (C(T(6), (8 + 9)) + ((5 \times 0))!) \\06039 &:= (T(T(9)) + (C(T((T(3) - 0!)), 6) - 0!)) \\06046 &:= ((C(T(6), 4) + 0!) + (60)) \\06205 &:= (C(T(5), (0! + T(T(2)))) - (T(T(6)) - 0!)) \\06274 &:= ((T(4!) - C(T(7), T(T(2))))/(-60)) \\06375 &:= (C(T(5), C(7, T(3))) - (60)) \\06384 &:= (4 \times T((C(8, 3) + (6 \times 0)))) \\06407 &:= (-T(7)) + C(T((0! + (4))), (6 + 0!)) \\06427 &:= ((C(T(7), 2) \times (-4) + T(6)) + 0!)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}06432 &:= -((T(2) - C(C(T(3), 4), (6 + 0!))) \\06454 &:= ((C(T(4), 5) \times 4!) + T(T((6 + 0!))) \\06485 &:= ((C(T(5), 8) - T(4)) + (60)) \\06545 &:= ((5! - T(4)) + C(T(5), (6 + 0!))) \\06546 &:= (T(T((6 + 4))) + ((C(T(5), 6) + 0!))) \\06547 &:= ((T(7) \times 4) + C(T(5), (6 + 0!))) \\06557 &:= (((C(T(7), 5)/T(5)) + (6)) - 0!) \\06573 &:= (T((3 \times T(7))) + (C(T(5), (6 - 0!)))) \\06575 &:= (((C(T(5), 7) + 5!) + T(6)) - 0!) \\06624 &:= (4! \times C((T(2) + T(6)), (T(6) + 0!))) \\06783 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), 8) \times 7)/T((T(6) - 0!))) \\06786 &:= (C((T(6) + 8), 7)/T(T(6) - 0!)) \\06831 &:= (T((1 + T(T(3)))) \times (C(8, 6) - 0!)) \\06955 &:= (5! + (C(T(5), 9) + T(60))) \\06975 &:= (C(T(5), 7) + (9 \times 60)) \\06985 &:= ((5 \times T(T(8))) + T((C(9, 6) + 0!))) \\07156 &:= (6! + (C(T(5), (1 \times 7)) + 0!)) \\07243 &:= (-3) + ((T(C(T(4), 2)) \times 7) + 0!)) \\07288 &:= (C((8 + 8), T(T(2))) - ((7 - 0!)!)) \\07316 &:= (C((T(6) + 1), -((3 - 7))) + 0!) \\07345 &:= (-5) \times ((C(T(4), T(3)) \times (-7)) + 0!)) \\07392 &:= (C((T(2) + 9), 3!) \times (7 + 0!)) \\07424 &:= ((C(4, T(2)))^4 \times (T(7) + 0!)) \\07455 &:= (-((C(5, 5) - 4) \times T(70)) \\07469 &:= (T(T(9)) - (-C(C(6, 4), 7) + 0!)) \\07497 &:= ((7 \times 9) \times (C(T(4), 7) - 0!)) \\07545 &:= ((C(T(5), 4) \times 5) + ((7 - 0!)!)) \\07624 &:= (((T(T(C(4, 2))) \times T(T(6)))/7) + 0!) \\07635 &:= ((C(5, 3) \times 6!) + T((T(7) + 0!))) \\07723 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))/7) - (T(7) + 0!)) \\07937 &:= ((C(T(7), T(3))/T(9)) - T((T(7) + 0!))) \\07985 &:= (5 \times (T(C(8, T((9 - 7)))) + 0!)) \\07993 &:= (((3 + 9) \times T(C(9, 7))) + 0!) \\08165 &:= (C(T(5), 6) + T(-((1 - 80)))) \\08225 &:= ((C(T(5), T(2)) + (T(T(2)))!) \times (8 - 0!)) \\08244 &:= (4 \times ((C(4!, T(2)) + T(8)) + 0!)) \\08245 &:= (C(T(5), C(4, 2)) + T(80)) \\08249 &:= (((T(T(9)) - C(4, T(2))) \times 8) + 0!) \\08317 &:= ((T((C(7, 1) \times 3)) \times T(8)) + 0!) \\08337 &:= ((C(T(7), 3) + T(T(3))) + ((8 - 0!)!))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}08359 &:= (((T(T(9)) + C(5,3)) \times 8) - 0!) \\08428 &:= ((C(8,2) \times T(4!)) + T((8 - 0!))) \\08523 &:= (C((T(3) \times T(2)),5) - T((8 + 0!))) \\08525 &:= (T(C(5,2)) \times ((5! + T(8)) - 0!)) \\08533 &:= ((C((3 \times T(3)),5) - T(8)) + 0!) \\08569 &:= (((T(C(9,6))/T(5)) \times T(8)) + 0!) \\08735 &:= ((C(T(5),3) + 7!) + T(80)) \\09248 &:= (8 \times ((C(T(4),T(2)) + T(T(9))) + 0!)) \\09289 &:= (((T(T(C(9,8))) - T(2)) \times 9) + 0!) \\09379 &:= (((T(T(9)) + C(7,T(3))) \times 9) + 0!) \\09443 &:= -((T(3) - ((C(T(4),4) \times T(9)) - 0!))) \\09483 &:= (3 \times (T((C(8,4) + 9)) + 0!)) \\09535 &:= (-C(T(5),3) - (-T(5) \times T(T((9 - 0!)))))) \\09565 &:= (C(T(5),6) + T((5 + 90))) \\09582 &:= ((T(2))! \times (T(C(8,5)) + ((9 \times 0)!)) \\09586 &:= (((6 \times T(C(8,5))) + 9) + 0!) \\09614 &:= (C(4!, (1 + 6))/T((9 - 0!))) \\09828 &:= (C(8,2) \times T(((T(8) - 9) - 0!))) \\09867 &:= (C(T(7),T(6))/(((T(8)/9) + 0!))!) \\10524 &:= (-C(4!,2) + (T(5) \times (T(T((0! + 1))))!)) \\10627 &:= (C(((7 - T(2)))!, (T(6) - 0!)) + 1) \\10644 &:= ((C(4!,4) + T(6)) - T((0! + 1))) \\10646 &:= (T(6) + (C(4!, (T(6) - 0!)) - 1)) \\10692 &:= -(((T(T(2)) - (T(C(9,6)))) \times T((0! + 1)))) \\10745 &:= ((-5) + T(T(T(4)))) \times C(7,01) \\10794 &:= ((T(4!) \times C(9,7)) - T(T((0! + 1)))) \\11025 &:= (C(T(5),2)^{01+1}) \\11223 &:= (3 \times T((C(T(T(2)),T(2)) + (T(11)))))) \\11253 &:= (3 \times (T(T(C(5,2))) + T(T(11)))) \\11256 &:= (T(T(6)) + (C(T(5),2)^{1+1})) \\11344 &:= ((C(4!,4) + (T(3))!) - (1 + 1)) \\11367 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T((T(6)/3))) - C(1,1)) \\11368 &:= (T(C(8,6)) \times T((T(3) + C(1,1)))) \\11384 &:= ((C(T(4),8) \times T((T(T(3)) + 1))) - 1) \\11439 &:= (-T(T(9)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (T(T(4)) - C(1,1)))) \\11475 &:= (C(T(5),7) + (-((4 - 11)))!) \\11745 &:= (T((5 + 4!)) \times (T(7) - C(1,1))) \\11774 &:= (T((4 \times 7)) \times (T(7) + C(1,1))) \\11835 &:= ((T(5) \times (T(3))!) + T(T((C(8,1) + 1)))) \\11935 &:= (T(T(C(5,3))) + (T(9) \times T(T(T(T((1 + 1)))))))\end{aligned}$$

- 11988 := $(T(T(8)) \times (C((8+9), 1) + 1))$
12143 := $((T(3) \times C(4!, (1+2))) - 1)$
12145 := $(((((C(5,4) - 1)!)!)/(T(T(T(2))))!) + 1)$
12225 := $(T(5) \times (C((T(T(2)) \times T(2)), T(2)) - 1))$
12255 := $(T(5) \times (C((T(5) + T(2)), T(2)) + 1))$
12283 := $((T(((T(3))!/8)) \times T(2)) - C(2,1))$
12318 := $((8 \times T(T(T((1+3)))))) - C(2,1))$
12321 := $((-1 + T(T(2)))! - T(T(T(3))))^{C(2,1)}$
12324 := $(4 \times T(T(C((2 \times 3) \times 2), 1)))$
12352 := $(C((2 + T(5)), T(3)) - ((T(2) + 1)!))$
12371 := $((C(17, T(3)) - T(T(2))) + 1)$
12374 := $(C((4! - 7), T(3)) - C(2,1))$
12375 := $(C(((-5) + T(7)) - T(3)), T(T(2))) - 1)$
12376 := $C((T(6) - (7 - 3)), T((2 + 1)))$
12377 := $(C(((7 + 7) + 3), T(T(2))) + 1)$
12379 := $(C((T(9) - T(7)), T(3)) + (2 + 1))$
12397 := $(C(-((T(7) - T(9))), T(3)) + (21))$
12398 := $((C((8 + 9), T(3)) + T(T(T(2)))) + 1)$
12419 := $((T(9) \times C(((1 \times 4)!, 2)) - 1)$
12422 := $(2 \times ((T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4), 2))) + 1))$
12424 := $(4 \times ((T(2) \times T(C(T(4), 2))) + 1))$
12425 := $(5 \times T(((T(2) \times 4!) - C(2,1)))$
12435 := $(T(5) \times ((3 \times C(4!, 2)) + 1))$
12444 := $(T(4!) + ((4)!/(T(C(C(4, 2), 1))))!))$
12448 := $(8 \times (T(T(T(4))) + C((4^2), 1)))$
12454 := $(-(C(T(4), 5)) - ((-T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) - 1))$
12495 := $(T((5 + 9)) \times (C(T(4), T(2)) - 1))$
12558 := $(T(T((8 + 5))) \times C((5 - 2), 1))$
12585 := $(T(5) \times ((8 \times C(T(5), 2)) - 1))$
12597 := $(T((-7) + T(9))) \times (T(5) + C(2, 1))$
12645 := $(-5) + C((4 + T(6)), 21))$
12646 := $((C((T(6) + 4), T(6)) - T(2)) - 1)$
12651 := $(C((-((1 - 5)) + T(6)), T(T(T(2)))) + 1)$
12652 := $(C(25, T(6)) + C(2, 1))$
12655 := $((C((5 \times 5), T(6)) + T(T(2))) - 1)$
12704 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(C(07, 2))) - 1)$
12705 := $((5! + 0!) \times T(C((7 \times 2), 1)))$
12725 := $((C(T(5), T(2)) \times T(7)) - T((T(T(2)) - 1)))$
12735 := $((C(T(5), 3) \times T(7)) - T(T(2))) + 1)$
12744 := $(-4!) \times ((T(4!) + T(C(7, 2))) \times (-1))$

$$\begin{aligned}12769 &:= ((T((9 + 6)) - (7))^{C(2,1)}) \\12815 &:= (C((T(5) + 1), 8) - T(T((T(2) + 1)))) \\12823 &:= (((T(T(T(3)))) - 2) \times C(8, T(2))) - 1 \\12824 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) - (-T(8)) \times T(((T(2) + 1)!))) \\12848 &:= (8 \times (T(4) + T(C(8, (2 + 1)))))) \\12855 &:= ((T(5) + (C(T(5), 8) \times (-2))) \times (-1)) \\12857 &:= (((-7) + C(T(5), 8)) \times 2) + 1 \\12864 &:= (C((T(4) + (6)), 8) - T((2 + 1))) \\12885 &:= (((C(T(5), 8) + 8) \times 2) - 1) \\12892 &:= ((C(((T(T(2))))!/T(9)), 8) + T(T(T(2)))) + 1 \\12936 &:= (T(T(6)) \times ((T(3) \times 9) + C(2, 1))) \\12945 &:= (T(5) \times ((4! \times C(9, 2)) - 1)) \\12958 &:= ((-C(8, 5) + 9!)/T((T(T(2)) + 1))) \\12996 &:= ((69 + T(9))^{C(2,1)}) \\12997 &:= (((T(T(7)) - T(9)) \times C(9, 2)) + 1) \\13094 &:= ((T(4!) \times T(9)) - T(T((0! + T(C(3, 1)))))) \\13104 &:= ((4!^{T(0!+1)}) - (T(C(3, 1)))) \\13194 &:= ((T(4!) \times (T(9) - 1)) - T(C(3, 1))) \\13209 &:= (((9 - 0!)/T(2)) - T(T(T(C(3, 1)))))) \\13227 &:= ((T(C(7, T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - C(3, 1)) \\13231 &:= T(C(1 + T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) + 1 \\13233 &:= (3 \times ((T(C(T(3), T(2))) \times T(T(3))) + 1)) \\13237 &:= (7 \times T(((C(T(3), T(2)) \times 3) + 1))) \\13248 &:= (8 \times (C(4!, 2) \times T(C(3, 1)))) \\13254 &:= ((T(T((-4) + T(5))) - 2) \times T(C(3, 1))) \\13268 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times T(6)) + 2) - (T(C(3, 1)))) \\13269 &:= ((T((T(9) + T(6))) \times T(T(2))) + C(3, 1)) \\13293 &:= (((T(T(T(3))) + T(T(9)))/2) \times T(T(C(3, 1)))) \\13301 &:= ((10 \times C(T(T(3)), 3)) + 1) \\13319 &:= ((T(T((9 - 1))) \times C(T(3), 3)) - 1) \\13338 &:= (T((T(8)/3)) \times T((3 \times T(C(3, 1)))))) \\13358 &:= (((8! - T(5)) + T(T(T(3))))/(-C(3, 1))) \\13377 &:= ((7 + T(C(7, 3))) \times T(T(C(3, 1)))) \\13394 &:= ((T((T(4) + (C(9, 3)))) \times 3) - 1) \\13408 &:= (T((T(8) + 0!)) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(C(3, 1)))))) \\13418 &:= (((-8!) + T((1 + T(4))))/(-C(3, 1))) \\13422 &:= (((T(T(2)))! - T(2)) + (T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(C(3, 1)))))) \\13426 &:= (C(T(6), T(2)) + ((T(4)!/T(((3 + 1)!))) \\13428 &:= ((8!/T(2)) - C((4 \times 3), 1)) \\13445 &:= ((T(5) + ((4 + 4)!)/C(3, 1))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}13468 &:= ((8! - (T(6) \times (-4))) / C(3,1)) \\13479 &:= ((T(9) \times T((T(7) - (4)))) - T(T(C(3,1)))) \\13488 &:= (8 \times ((8!/4!) + T(C(3,1)))) \\13536 &:= ((C(T(6), T(3)) - 5!) / (3 + 1)) \\13539 &:= ((T((T(9) - 3)) \times T(5)) - T(C(3,1))) \\13563 &:= (-3 - (C(T(6), T(5)) / (-3 + 1))) \\13566 &:= (C(T(6), C(6,5)) / (3 + 1)) \\13568 &:= ((-8 - C(T(6), T(5))) / (-3 + 1)) \\13586 &:= (((C(T(6), 8) / T(5)) + T(T(3))) - 1) \\13623 &:= ((T(T(3)) - 2) \times (6! - C(3,1))) \\13656 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times 56) + (T(C(3,1)))) \\13685 &:= (((T(5) + 8!) + 6!) / C(3,1)) \\13728 &:= (C((8 + T(T(2))), 7) \times (3 + 1)) \\13797 &:= (((T(7) + T(T(9))) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(C(3,1)))) \\13818 &:= ((-8) + T(T((1 \times 8))) \times T(T(C(3,1)))) \\13832 &:= ((-2) + T(T(3))) \times (8 + (T(C(3,1)))) \\13845 &:= (T(5) \times (C((4 + 8), T(3)) - 1)) \\13849 &:= ((9 \times T(T(T(4)))) - C((8 + 3), 1)) \\13878 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times (-7)) + T(8)) \times (-C(3,1))) \\13888 &:= (T((8 - C(8, 8))) \times T(31)) \\13923 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (-T(2) - T(C(9, (3 - 1)))))) \\13926 &:= ((T(T(6)) / T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(T(C(3,1)))))) \\13938 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times T(T(3))) - (T(9) + C(3,1))) \\13942 &:= (-2) + (4 \times T((C(9, 3) - 1))) \\13983 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T(T(8))) - C((9/3), 1)) \\13992 &:= (T(T(2)) + (T((T(9) - 9)) \times T(T(C(3,1)))))) \\14035 &:= (5! + (T((T(T(3)) + 0!)) \times T(T(C(4, 1)))))) \\14124 &:= ((4!^{T(2)}) + T((C((1 \times 4), 1)!)) \\14139 &:= (9 \times (31 + T(T(T(C(4, 1)))))) \\14184 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) + T(8)) \times (-1) + T(C(4, 1))) \\14228 &:= ((T((T(8) \times 2)) \times T(T(2))) - T(T(T(C(4, 1)))))) \\14242 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(4)) - T(2) + T(T(T(C(4, 1)))) \\14269 &:= (((T(C(9, 6)) - T(2)) \times 4) + 1) \\14275 &:= (-5) + (T((T(7) \times T(2))) \times C(4, 1)) \\14279 &:= ((T((C(9, 7) - 2)) \times 4!) - 1) \\14283 &:= (((T(T(3)) \times T(T(8))) - T(2)) + T((C(4, 1)!)) \\14284 &:= ((4! \times T((T(8) - 2))) + C(4, 1)) \\14285 &:= (5 + (T((T(8) - 2)) \times (C(4, 1)!)) \\14288 &:= (8 + (T((T(8) - 2)) \times (C(4, 1)!)) \\14292 &:= ((-T(2)) - T(C(9, T(2)))) \times (-C(4, 1))\end{aligned}$$

- 14293** := $((3 + T(C(9, T(2)))) \times 4) + 1$
14326 := $((62 \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(4, 1))$
14345 := $((5!^{-4+T(3)} - T(T(C(4, 1))))$
14357 := $(7 \times (C(T(5), 3) + T((T(T(4)) + 1))))$
14368 := $((-(T(8) - 6!)) \times T(T(3))) + C(4, 1))$
14389 := $((9 \times T(C(8, 3)) + 4!) + 1)$
14419 := $((9 \times T((1 + T(T(4)))) + T(T(C(4, 1))))$
14486 := $((T(6) \times (T(T(8)) + (4!))) - C(4, 1))$
14568 := $(8 \times (C((T(6) - 5), 4) + 1))$
14587 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(8)) - (5 + (C(4, 1)!))$
14588 := $((8 - T(85)) \times (-C(4, 1)))$
14616 := $(T(6) \times (((1 \times 6)! - (C(4, 1)!))$
14624 := $((C(T(4), 2) \times T((T(6) + (4)))) - 1)$
14648 := $(8 \times (T((4 \times C(6, 4)) + 1))$
14649 := $((T(9) \times T((4 + T(6)))) + (C(4, 1)!))$
14654 := $(4! + (5 \times T((T(6) + T(T(C(4, 1))))))$
14664 := $((T(T(4)) \times (-6!)) + C(T(6), T((4 - 1))))$
14673 := $((T(T(3)) \times (-7 + 6!)) - T((C(4, 1)!))$
14676 := $(6 \times ((T(T(7)) \times 6) + T(C(4, 1))))$
14682 := $(-T(2) + ((T(8) + T(T(6))) \times T(T(C(4, 1))))$
14727 := $((C(T(7), T(2)) + T(T(7))) \times 4) - 1$
14728 := $(C(8, 2) \times (T(T(7)) + ((4 + 1)!))$
14752 := $(2^5 \times (T(T(7)) + T(T(C(4, 1))))$
14756 := $((T((6 \times T(5))) - T(T(7))) \times C(4, 1))$
14769 := $(9 \times ((T(T(6)) \times 7) + (C(4, 1)!))$
14774 := $((4! \times T(T(7))) + (7! - T(C(4, 1))))$
14777 := $(-7) - (-T(7) \times T((T(7) + C(4, 1))))$
14784 := $(T((4 \times 8)) \times C((7 \times 4), 1))$
14787 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(8)) + T((T(7) - T(C(4, 1))))$
14793 := $((3 \times (-9 + 7!)) - T((C(4, 1)!))$
14795 := $((T(5) \times T(9)) - T(T(7))) \times T(T(C(4, 1))))$
14824 := $((T(T(T(4))) \times T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(8)) / (C(4, 1)!))$
14838 := $-((T(T(8)) - C(((T(3))! / T(8)), (4 + 1)))$
14868 := $-((T(8) + (-6) \times (T(C(8, 4)) - 1)))$
14892 := $((T(T(2)) + T(9)) \times (-8 + T((C(4, 1)!))$
14894 := $(-T(4) + ((-T(9)) + T(T(8))) \times (C(4, 1)!))$
14897 := $(-7) + ((-T(9)) + T(T(8))) \times (C(4, 1)!))$
14905 := $((T(5) \times T(-((0! - T(9)))) + T(T(C(4, 1))))$
14949 := $(C(((T(9) - T(4)) - 9), 4) - 1)$
14973 := $(3 \times ((7! - T(9)) - C(4, 1)))$

$$\begin{aligned}14986 &:= ((T(6) \times (T(T(8)) + T(9))) + T(T(C(4,1)))) \\15015 &:= (C(T(5),10) \times C(5,1)) \\15168 &:= (8 \times (T(61) + C(5,1))) \\15237 &:= (((7! \times 3) - T(2)) + (C(5,1)!)) \\15246 &:= ((6! + C(4,2)) \times T((5+1))) \\15307 &:= (-((7! + 0!)) + (C(T(T(3)),5) - 1)) \\15308 &:= -((((8 - 0!))! - (C(T(T(3)),5) - 1))) \\15336 &:= (6 \times T((C(T(3),3) + (51)))) \\15345 &:= (T(5) \times ((C(4,3)^5) - 1)) \\15415 &:= ((T((5-1)) \times T(T(T(4)))) + T(C(5,1))) \\15428 &:= (T(C(8,2)) \times ((4! + T(5)) - 1)) \\15445 &:= (((5 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(4)) - C(5,1)) \\15459 &:= ((T(9) - C((5 \times 4),5)) \times (-1)) \\15497 &:= (-T(7) + (T(T(9)) \times (T(4) + C(5,1)))) \\15505 &:= (C((5 + T(05)),5) + 1) \\15522 &:= (2 \times ((T(T(2))^5) - T(C(5,1)))) \\15549 &:= (T(9) + (C((4 \times 5),5) \times 1)) \\15555 &:= (C((5 + T(5)),5) + (51)) \\15615 &:= ((C(5,1)^6) - T((5-1))) \\15624 &:= (((T(4)/2)^{C(6,5)}) - 1) \\15636 &:= (T(T(6)) + (T(T((T(3) + (6)))) \times C(5,1))) \\15666 &:= (T(6) \times ((6! + T(6)) + C(5,1))) \\15675 &:= (C(T(5),7) + (6 \times T(T(T((5-1)))))) \\15708 &:= (T((8-0!)) \times T((T(7) + C(5,1)))) \\15723 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times ((T(T(2)))! + (T(7)))) + T(C(5,1))) \\15765 &:= ((5^6) + (T(7) \times C(5,1))) \\15792 &:= (((2 + T(9)) \times 7!)/T(C(5,1))) \\15795 &:= (T(5) \times (T(9) - (7!/(-C(5,1)))))) \\15934 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 9) - C(5,1)) \\16128 &:= (8 \times T((C(2,1) + 61))) \\16174 &:= ((4^7) - T((-1) + T(C(6,1)))) \\16194 &:= (((T(4!) \times 9) - 1) \times C(6,1)) \\16224 &:= (((T(T(4)) - T(2))^2) \times C(6,1)) \\16248 &:= (8 \times (C(4!,T(2)) + (6 + 1))) \\16254 &:= ((T((4! + T(5))) - T(T(2))) \times T(C(6,1))) \\16275 &:= (-5) \times ((C(T(7),T(2)) - T(6)) \times (-1)) \\16284 &:= ((4! \times T(T(8))) + T((T(2) + T(C(6,1)))))) \\16302 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) + 0!) \times ((T(3))! + T(C(6,1)))) \\16345 &:= ((C(5,4)^{T(3)}) + (C(6,1)!))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}16348 &:= -((T(8) - (C(4,3)^{6+1}))) \\16358 &:= ((T(8) \times C(T(5),3)) - (T(6) + 1)) \\16375 &:= (-5) + (C(T(7),3) \times (6 - 1)) \\16379 &:= ((T((C(9,7) + 3)) \times T(6)) - 1) \\16386 &:= ((T(6) \times T((T(8) + 3))) + C(6,1)) \\16425 &:= ((5!^2) + (C(4!, T(6)) + 1)) \\16445 &:= (((C(5,4))! - T(T(4))) \times T((T(6) + 1))) \\16458 &:= (((8!/T(5)) + T(T(4))) \times C(6,1)) \\16463 &:= ((T(3) \times (6! + C(4!, T(6)))) - 1) \\16484 &:= (T(4!) - (-8) \times (C(4!, T(6)) - 1)) \\16488 &:= (8 \times (T(8) + (C(4!, T(6)) + 1))) \\16494 &:= ((T(4!) \times (T(9) + T(4))) - C(6,1)) \\16539 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (T(T(3)) - 5)) - T(C(6,1))) \\16548 &:= ((8 + T((4! + T(5)))) \times T(C(6,1))) \\16551 &:= ((T((1 + T(5))) \times 5!) + T(T(C(6,1)))) \\16573 &:= (-((3 - (7^5))) - T(T(C(6,1)))) \\16575 &:= (T(5) + ((T(7) - 5) \times (C(6,1)!)) \\16584 &:= (4! + ((8 + T(5)) \times (C(6,1)!)) \\16592 &:= ((2 + T(T(9))) \times (-5) + T(C(6,1))) \\16599 &:= ((T((9 \times 9)) \times 5) - C(6,1)) \\16645 &:= ((-T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) + (6! \times T(C(6,1)))) \\16695 &:= (((5! - T(9)) + 6!) \times T(C(6,1))) \\16737 &:= ((7! \times 3) - (-7) \times T(T(C(6,1)))) \\16744 &:= (4 \times T(((T(4) \times 7) + T(C(6,1)))) \\16842 &:= ((T((2^4)) + T(T(8))) \times T(C(6,1))) \\16848 &:= ((T(8) \times T((4 + 8))) \times C(6,1)) \\16947 &:= (7 \times (T((4! + T(9))) + C(6,1))) \\16989 &:= ((T(9) \times T((T(8) - 9))) - T(C(6,1))) \\17037 &:= ((T(C(7,3)) + 0!) \times (T(7) - 1)) \\17052 &:= ((T(2) \times (T(5) - 0!)) \times T(T(C(7,1)))) \\17155 &:= (5 \times (C((T(5) - 1), 7) - 1)) \\17204 &:= ((4! - 0!) \times ((T(T(2)))! + T(C(7,1)))) \\17224 &:= ((4! \times (T(T(2)))!) - (2 \times T(C(7,1)))) \\17244 &:= ((4! \times (C(4,2))!) - T((7 + 1))) \\17252 &:= (((-((T(T(2)) - T(5))))! / T(T(T(2)))) - T(C(7,1))) \\17273 &:= (((T(3))! \times ((7 - T(2)))!) - C(7,1)) \\17279 &:= ((9! - C(7,2)) / T((7 - 1))) \\17293 &:= (T(3) - ((-9!) / T(T(T(2)))) - C(7,1)) \\17299 &:= (-9) - ((-9!) / T(T(T(2)))) - T(C(7,1)) \\17308 &:= (((8 + 0!)! / T(T(3))) + T(C(7,1)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17329 &:= ((T(9) - 2) \times (-3) + T(T(C(7,1)))) \\ 17369 &:= ((T(9) \times (-C(6,3)) + T(T(7))) - 1) \\ 17374 &:= ((T((T(4) \times 7)) - 3) \times C(7,1)) \\ 17435 &:= (5 \times (T(T((3 \times 4))) + T(T(C(7,1)))))) \\ 17437 &:= (((T(T(7)) \times T(3)) + T(T(4))) \times C(7,1)) \\ 17454 &:= (4! + (5 \times T((T(T(4)) + T(C(7,1)))))) \\ 17455 &:= (5 \times (5 + T((T(T(4)) + T(C(7,1)))))) \\ 17473 &:= -((((T(3) - T(C(7,4))) \times T(7)) - 1)) \\ 17476 &:= (((6! + 7) \times 4!) + T(C(7,1))) \\ 17486 &:= (((T(6) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(T(4)))) + (C(7,1))!) \\ 17493 &:= ((-T(3) + T(T(9))) \times (4! - C(7,1))) \\ 17527 &:= ((C(7, T(T(2)))^5) + (((7 - 1))!)) \\ 17529 &:= -((T(T(9)) - C((T(2) + T(5)), (7 - 1)))) \\ 17542 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) + T((T(T(4)) + T(5)))) \times C(7,1)) \\ 17556 &:= (C(6,5) \times T((5 + 71))) \\ 17592 &:= (-T(2) + (T(9) \times (-T(5) + T(T(C(7,1)))))) \\ 17594 &:= ((T(4!) \times (T(9) + T(5))) - T(T(C(7,1)))) \\ 17595 &:= ((5 \times 9) \times (-T(5) + T(T(C(7,1)))))) \\ 17692 &:= ((T(T(2)) + ((9!/T(6)))) + T(T(C(7,1)))) \\ 17745 &:= (C(T(5),4) \times ((7 + 7) - 1)) \\ 17775 &:= (C(T(5),7) - (-T(7) \times (T(T(7)) - 1))) \\ 17784 &:= (4! \times T((T(8) + (C(7,7) + 1)))) \\ 17793 &:= (C(T(T(3)), (9 + 7)) - T(71)) \\ 17794 &:= ((-4) + T(9)) \times (T(T(7)) + T(C(7,1))) \\ 17847 &:= (C(T(7),4!) - T((T(8) + T((7 + 1)))))) \\ 17855 &:= (5 \times (T((5! - T(C(8,7)))) + 1)) \\ 17864 &:= (-((4 - (6 \times 8))) \times T(T(C(7,1)))) \\ 17892 &:= (-((2 - C(9,8))) \times T(71)) \\ 17895 &:= (-T(5) + (T(9) \times (-8) + T(T(C(7,1)))))) \\ 17909 &:= (T(9) + (-((0! - T(9))) \times T(T(C(7,1)))))) \\ 17946 &:= ((6! \times 4!) + T((C(9,7) \times 1))) \\ 17948 &:= (((8! \times 4)/9) + T(C(7,1))) \\ 17965 &:= (C(T(5),6) - ((9!/T(7)) \times (-1))) \\ 17982 &:= ((-T(2) \times T(T(8))) \times (-C(9, (7 + 1)))) \\ 18045 &:= ((-T(5) \times T((T(T(4)) - 0!)) + (C(8,1))!) \\ 18216 &:= (T((T(6) + 1)) \times (2 \times T(C(8,1)))) \\ 18224 &:= (T(((4^{T(2)}) + T(2))) \times C(8,1)) \\ 18235 &:= (C(T(5), T(3)) - (T(T(T(2))) \times (-T((T(8) - 1)))))) \\ 18242 &:= (((2 + 4!)^{T(2)}) + T(T(C(8,1)))) \\ 18243 &:= ((-3) - C(4!, T(2))) \times (-8 + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 18244 &:= ((T(4) \times T((T(T(4)) + T(T(2)))))) - T(T(C(8,1)))) \\ 18248 &:= (8 \times (T(T(T(4))) + T((2 + T(C(8,1)))))) \\ 18252 &:= ((T((2^5)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times T(C(8,1))) \\ 18285 &:= (T(5) + (T(C(8,2)) \times T((8 + 1)))) \\ 18294 &:= (4! + (T(9) \times T(C(28,1)))) \\ 18353 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times (T(T(C(5,3))) - T(T(8)))) - 1) \\ 18384 &:= ((T(4!) - (T(T(8)) \times (-3))) \times C(8,1)) \\ 18425 &:= (T(C(5,2)) \times (T(4!) + (T(8) - 1))) \\ 18456 &:= (6 \times (-5) + T(T(C((4 + 8),1)))) \\ 18486 &:= (6 \times T(((C(8,4) + 8) \times 1))) \\ 18496 &:= (T((6!/T(9)))^{T(4)-C(8,1)}) \\ 18563 &:= (C((3 \times 6), T(-(5 - 8))) - 1) \\ 18642 &:= (T((2 + T(4))) \times (T(T(6)) + C(8,1))) \\ 18678 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times T(7)) + (-6 + T(C(8,1)))) \\ 18682 &:= ((T(2))! - (-C(8,6) \times (T(T(8)) + 1))) \\ 18702 &:= ((T(T(2)))! + (-((0! - T(7)) \times T(T(C(8,1)))))) \\ 18714 &:= (T((T(4) + 1)) + (T(7) \times T(T(C(8,1)))))) \\ 18729 &:= ((T(C(9,2)) \times T(7)) + (81)) \\ 18753 &:= (C(T(T(3)), 5) + (T((7 \times 8)) \times (-1))) \\ 18759 &:= ((-9) + 5!) + (T(7) \times T(T(C(8,1)))) \\ 18837 &:= (C(T(7), T(3)) / (-8 + T((8 - 1)))) \\ 18928 &:= (C(8,2) \times ((9 + T(T(8))) + 1)) \\ 18963 &:= (T(T(3)) \times T((6 + C(9, (8 - 1)))))) \\ 19313 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), (-1) + T(3)) - T(T(9))) - 1) \\ 19347 &:= (C(T(7), 4!) - T(((3 + T(9)) - 1))) \\ 19353 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), 5) - T(3)) - T((T(9) - 1))) \\ 19354 &:= ((4 \times C(T(5), T(3))) - T(T((9 - 1)))) \\ 19356 &:= ((C(T(6), 5) - 3) - T((T(9) - 1))) \\ 19365 &:= (T(5) \times (T(C(6,3)) + T((T(9) + 1)))) \\ 19439 &:= (-9) + C((T(T(3)) - 4), (9 + 1)) \\ 19447 &:= (C((-7) + 4!), C(T(4), 9)) - 1) \\ 19464 &:= (4! \times (6! + T(C((4 + 9), 1)))) \\ 19485 &:= (C(T((T(5) - 8)), 4) - T((T(9) - 1))) \\ 19493 &:= ((3^9) - T((T(4) + C(9, 1)))) \\ 19536 &:= (T(T(6)) + (3 \times C(T(5), (9 - 1)))) \\ 19545 &:= (-5!) - ((-4) - T(5)) \times T(T(C(9, 1))) \\ 19575 &:= (((T(5) \times T(7)) + T(5)) \times T(C(9, 1))) \\ 19624 &:= (C(4, T(2)) \times (6! + T(91))) \\ 19647 &:= (((T(7))! / ((4 + T(6))!) - C(9, 1)) \\ 19665 &:= (((5! - 6) / 6) \times T(T(C(9, 1)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 19733 := ((C((3³),7)/T(9)) - 1)
19734 := (C((4! + 3),7)/T(C(9,1)))
19847 := (-7) + ((T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(8)))) × C(9,1)))
19888 := (8 × (T(C(8, (T(8)/9))) + 1))
19953 := (C(T(T(3)),5) + (-9) × (T(9) - 1))
19965 := (T(5) × (C(T(6), (9 + 9)) + 1))
20125 := (C(T(5), T(T(2))) + ((T(T((1 + 0!))))! × T(T(T(2))))))
20188 := ((-8!) - C(8, T((1 + 0!)))/(-2))
20234 := ((C(4!, 3) × T((T(2) + 0!))) - T(T(2)))
20235 := (-5!) + (C(T(T(3)), (T(T(2)) - 0!) + T(T(2))))
20294 := -((T(T(4)) - C(T((9 - T(2))), (-0!) + T(T(2))))))
20304 := -((T((T(4) - 0!) - C(T(T(3)), (-0!) + T(T(2))))))
20321 := -((T((1 + T(T(2)))) - (C(T(T(3)), (-0!) + T(T(2))))))
20322 := (-((T(2)^{T(2)})) + C(T(T(3)), (-0!) + T(T(2))))
20324 := ((-4) - T(T(T(2)))) + (C(T(T(3)), (-0!) + T(T(2))))
20338 := (-8) + (C(T(T(3)), (T(3) - 0!) - T(2)))
20342 := ((T(2) - T(4)) + C(T(T(3)), (-0!) + T(T(2))))
20343 := (C(T(T(3)), (T(4) + T(3))) - T(T(02)))
20346 := (C(T(6), (T(4) + T(3))) - T(02))
20347 := (C(T(T((7 - 4))), (T(3) - 0!)) - 2)
20349 := C((T(9) - 4!), (3 + 02))
20351 := (C(T((1 + 5)), (T(3) - 0!)) + 2)
20352 := (C((T(T(2)) + T(5)), (T(3) - 0!) + T(2)))
20353 := (C(T(T(3)), 5) + (3 + ((0 × 2)!))
20354 := ((T(4) - 5) + C(T(T(3)), (-0!) + T(T(2))))
20356 := ((C(T(6), 5) + T(3)) + ((0 × 2)!))
20357 := ((-7) + T(5)) + C(T(T(3)), (-0!) + T(T(2))))
20359 := (T((9 - 5)) + C(T(T(3)), (-0!) + T(T(2))))
20365 := ((-5) + T(6)) + C(T(T(3)), (-0!) + T(T(2))))
20373 := ((-((3 - 7)))! + C(T(T(3)), (-0!) + T(T(2))))
20377 := (T(7) + C((7 × 3), (-0!) + T(T(2))))
20392 := ((-2) + T(9)) + C(T(3!), (-0!) + (T(2)!))
20404 := (T(T(4)) + C(T(T(-(0! - 4))))), (-0!) + T(T(2))))
20433 := (T(T(3)) × ((T(3))! + C((4! - 0!), 2)))
20447 := (((C(T(7), 4!) - 4!) - 0!) - T(2))
20468 := ((C(C(8, 6), 4) - 0!) - T(T(2)))
20481 := (C(T(-(1 - 8)), 4) + T(T(02)))
20544 := (C((4! - 4), 5) + ((0! + T(T(2))))!)
20547 := (C(T(7), 4!) + (((5 - 0!)! × T(2)))
20556 := ((C(T(6), 5) - ((5 - 0!)!)) + T(T(T(T(2))))))

- 20565 := $(T(5) \times (6 + C(T(5), (0! + T(2))))$
20579 := $((C(T(T(T((9 - 7))))), 5) - 0!) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
20592 := $(T(T(2)) \times C((9 + 5), (0! + T(T(2))))$
20595 := $(5! + (T(9) \times C(T(5), T(02))))$
20643 := $((-T(3)) + T(4!)) + C(T(6), (-0!) + T(T(2))))$
20654 := $((T(4!) + 5) + C(T(6), (-0!) + T(T(2))))$
20706 := $(T(T(6)) + C(T(07), (0! + T(2))))$
20747 := $((-T(7)) + T(4!)) + (C(T(7), (0! + T(2))))$
20752 := $(C(T(T(T(2))), 5) + (T(T(7)) - T(02)))$
20753 := $((C(T(T(3))), 5) + T(T(7))) - 02$
20756 := $((C(T(6), 5) + T(T(7))) + ((0 \times 2)!))$
20853 := $(C(T(T(3))), 5) + (((8 + 0!)! / (T(T(2))!))$
20916 := $(6 \times T((-1) + C(9, T(02))))$
20932 := $((C(T(T(2)), 3) \times T(T(9))) + 0!) + T(T(T(T(2))))$
20958 := $((T(C(8, 5)) + ((9 - 0!)!)) / 2$
20979 := $((-C(9, 7)) + T(T(9))) \times T(T(T(02)))$
21244 := $((C(4!, 4) - T(2)) - 1) \times 2$
21246 := $(-6) - (C(4!, (T(2) + 1)) \times (-2))$
21248 := $((8 - C(4!, (T(T(2)) - 1))) / (-2))$
21249 := $(9 \times (-((C(4, 2))!)) + T(T(12)))$
21252 := $(C(T(T(T(2))), 5) + T((21 \times 2)))$
21393 := $-((T(T(3)) + (-((T(C(9, 3)) - 1)) \times T(T(2))))$
21394 := $((T(4) + T(T(9))) + C(T(T(3)), (-1) + T(T(2))))$
21396 := $(6 \times ((T(C(9, 3)) - 1) - T(2)))$
21435 := $(T(5) - (-T(3)) \times T(C((T(4) - 1), T(2))))$
21528 := $(T((C(8, 2) - 5)) \times T(12))$
21729 := $((T(C(9, 2)) \times T(7)) + T(T(12)))$
21732 := $(-T(2) + (T(T(3)) \times T(T((C(7, 1) + 2))))$
21966 := $(T(T(6)) + ((T(6) \times T(C((9 + 1), 2))))$
22183 := $(T(T(T(3))) + ((C(C(8, 1), 2)^{T(2)}))$
22224 := $(4! \times (C((T(T(2)) + T(T(2))), T(T(2)) + 2))$
22232 := $((C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) / (-T(2))) + (((2^{T(2)}))!))$
22238 := $(8! + ((C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) / (-T(2))) + T(T(2))))$
22275 := $((5 \times 7!) - C((T(2)^{T(2)}), T(2)))$
22324 := $((T(T(4)) \times T(C((2^3), 2))) - T(T(2)))$
22328 := $((T(C(8, 2)) \times T(T((T(3) - 2)))) - 2$
22344 := $((4! - T(4)) \times T(C((T(3) + 2), T(2))))$
22354 := $(4! - (-T(C(5, 3))) \times T(T((T(T(T(2))) / T(2))))$
22357 := $((T(T(7)) \times T(C(5, 3))) + (T(2)^{T(2)}))$
22378 := $(8! - ((C(T(7), T(3)) / T(T(T(2)))) + 2))$

$$\begin{aligned} 22379 &:= (-T(97) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), T(T(2)))) \\ 22386 &:= (T(6) \times (T(T(8)) + (C(T(3), T(2))^2))) \\ 22413 &:= (31 \times ((C(4, 2))! + T(2))) \\ 22419 &:= (9 \times (C((-1) + 4!), T(2)) + (T(T(2)))!) \\ 22424 &:= (((C(4!, T(T(2))) - T(T(4))) + T(2))/T(T(2))) \\ 22427 &:= (((-T(7)) - T(T(2))) + C(4!, T(T(2))))/T(T(2))) \\ 22431 &:= ((-T((1 + 3))) + C(4!, T(T(2))))/T(T(2))) \\ 22432 &:= (((2 - T(3)) + C(4!, T(T(2))))/T(T(2))) \\ 22433 &:= (((T(3)/3) + C(4!, T(T(2))))/T(T(2))) \\ 22434 &:= (((C(4!, T(3)) - T(4))/T(T(2))) + T(2)) \\ 22436 &:= ((C(6, 3) + C(4!, T(T(2))))/T(T(2))) \\ 22447 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T(T(4))) + (C(T(4), T(2)) - T(2))) \\ 22453 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), 5) + (4!)) + T((2^{T(T(2))}))) \\ 22484 &:= (((T(4!) - 8) \times T(T(C(4, 2))))/T(2)) \\ 22485 &:= (5! + ((T(C(8, 4)) \times T(2)) \times T(2))) \\ 22489 &:= (((T(T(9)) + T(8)) \times T(C(4, 2))) - 2) \\ 22499 &:= (-C(9, 9) + ((T(4!)/2)^2)) \\ 22525 &:= ((T(5) + 2) \times (-5) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(2))) \\ 22547 &:= (((T(T(7)) + 4) \times T(C(5, 2))) - T(2)) \\ 22561 &:= ((T(T((1 + 6))) \times T(C(5, 2))) + T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 22565 &:= ((5 + C(T(6), 5)) + T(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))))) \\ 22567 &:= ((7 + C(T(6), 5)) + T(T((T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))))) \\ 22608 &:= (T(8) \times (T(C((0! + 6)), T(2))) - 2) \\ 22618 &:= (T(T(8)) + ((T((1 + 6))^{C(T(2), 2)}))) \\ 22663 &:= (((T(3)^6) - C(T(6), T(2)))/2) \\ 22674 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - (T(T(7)))) \times C(6, T(2))) - T(T(2))) \\ 22704 &:= (4! \times T((0! + (C(7, 2) \times 2)))) \\ 22716 &:= (6 \times ((1 + T(C(7, T(2)))) \times T(T(2)))) \\ 22718 &:= ((T(8) \times (1 + T(C(7, T(2)))) + 2) \\ 22728 &:= ((C(8, T(2)) \times T(T(7))) - (2^{T(2)})) \\ 22734 &:= (((T(4) \times (T(3))!) + (C(T(7), 2))) \times T(2)) \\ 22758 &:= ((C(8, 5) \times T(T(7))) + 22) \\ 22769 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (-6) + T(7)) - C(2, 2)) \\ 22782 &:= -(((T(2))! - (T(8) \times (T(C(7, T(2))) + T(2)))))) \\ 22785 &:= ((-T(5) + T(T(8))) \times C(7, (2 + 2))) \\ 22806 &:= ((T(T(6)) + T(C((0! + 8), T(2)))) \times T(T(2))) \\ 22911 &:= (T(T(11)) + (T(T(9)) \times C(T(T(2)), T(2)))) \\ 22932 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (-T(3) + T((C(9, T(2)) + T(2)))))) \\ 22957 &:= ((T(7) \times T((-5) + T(9))) - C(T(2), 2)) \\ 22964 &:= (-4) + (6 \times T((C(9, T(2)) + T(2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22968 &:= (T(8) \times (6! - (C(9, T(2)) - 2))) \\ 22979 &:= ((9 \times T((T(7) + T(9)))) - C(T(T(T(2))), T(2))) \\ 23055 &:= (T(5) \times (T(T(C(5, 03))) - T(2))) \\ 23135 &:= (-((5^{T(3)})) + C((-1) + T(T(3))), T(T(2))) \\ 23145 &:= (T(5) \times (T(T(C((4 + 1), 3))) + T(2))) \\ 23184 &:= ((T(4!) + T(T(8))) \times ((1 + C(3, 2)))!) \\ 23223 &:= ((T(C(T(3), T(2))) - (T(T(2))^{T(3)})) / (-2)) \\ 23229 &:= (9 \times ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) / T(T(3))) - T(2))) \\ 23246 &:= ((6 \times (4^{T(T(2))}) - C(T(T(3)), T(2))) \\ 23247 &:= (7 \times T(((C(4, 2) + 3)^2)) \\ 23256 &:= (C(T(6), (5 + 2)) / (3 + 2)) \\ 23278 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times C(7, T(2))) - 32) \\ 23296 &:= T(T(6)) + T(T(9)) \times T(T(T(2))) + C(T(T(3)), T(2)) \\ 23308 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times C((0! + T(3)), 3)) - 2) \\ 23338 &:= (((T(8)^3) + C(T(3), 3)) / 2) \\ 23343 &:= (C(T(3), 4) + ((T(3))^{T(3)} / 2)) \\ 23358 &:= -((T(T(8)) + (C((-5) + T(T(3))), T(3)) \times (-T(2)))) \\ 23428 &:= (C(8, 2) + (T(4!) \times T((T(3) \times 2))) \\ 23433 &:= (((T(3))^{T(3)} + C(T(4), T(3))) / 2) \\ 23469 &:= (((9! / C(6, 4)) - (T(3))!) - T(2)) \\ 23474 &:= ((-4) + C(T(7), 4!)) + T((T(T(T(3))) / T(2))) \\ 23485 &:= ((5 + T(T(8))) \times C((4 + 3), T(2))) \\ 23495 &:= ((-T(5)) - (T(T(9)) \times (-4!))) - C(T(T(3)), T(2)) \\ 23527 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (T(2) + T(C(5, 3)))) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 23654 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) - ((5! \times T(C(6, 3))) - T(T(2)))) \\ 23688 &:= (T(8) \times (-8) + T(C((6 + 3), 2))) \\ 23738 &:= (83 \times C((7 + T(3)), T(2))) \\ 23739 &:= ((T(9) \times T(-(3 - C(7, 3)))) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 23744 &:= (((4 + T(T(4))) \times T(T(7))) - T(C(T(3), T(2)))) \\ 23745 &:= (C((5 + 4!), (7 - 3)) - T(T(2))) \\ 23751 &:= C(((1^5) + T(7)), (T(3) - 2)) \\ 23754 &:= (C((4! + 5), (7 - 3)) + T(2)) \\ 23757 &:= (((T(C(7, 5)) / 7) \times (T(3))!) - T(2)) \\ 23786 &:= (((T(T(6)) + T(T(8))) \times T(7)) - C(T(T(3)), T(2))) \\ 23824 &:= (-C(4!, T(2))) + (T(8) \times ((T(3))! - 2)) \\ 23843 &:= (T((T(3) + T(T(4)))) + ((C(8, T(3))^{T(2)})) \\ 23889 &:= -(((T(9) - C((8 + 8), T(3))) \times T(2))) \\ 23895 &:= (-5) \times (9 - (T(C(8, 3)) \times T(2))) \\ 23904 &:= ((T((4! - 0!)) \times C(9, 3)) + (T(T(2))))! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23925 &:= (T(C(5,2)) \times T((9 \times 3) + 2)) \\ 23938 &:= (((T(C(8,3)) \times T(9)) - T(3))/T(2)) \\ 23957 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times 59) + C(3,2)) \\ 23979 &:= -((T(9) - (C((7+9), T(3)) \times T(2)))) \\ 24024 &:= (C((4^2), T(04)) \times T(2)) \\ 24025 &:= ((C(T(5), T(2)) - T((04)!))^2) \\ 24054 &:= ((T(4) + C((T(5) + 0!), T(4))) \times T(2)) \\ 24079 &:= (C((T(9) - T(7)), -((0! - T(4)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 24115 &:= (C(T(5), T((1+1))) \times (T(T(4)) - 2)) \\ 24135 &:= ((T(5) \times T(T(T((3+1)))) + T(C(T(4), 2))) \\ 24148 &:= ((T((C(8,4) - 1)) \times T(4)) - 2) \\ 24165 &:= ((5 \times ((6+1)!) - T(C(T(4), 2))) \\ 24215 &:= (5 \times (C((-1) + T(T(T(2))), 4) - 2)) \\ 24225 &:= (5 \times C(C(T(T(2)), T(2)), C(4, T(2)))) \\ 24235 &:= (5 \times (C(C(T(3), T(2)), 4) + 2)) \\ 24252 &:= ((T(2) - T(5)) \times (T(2) - C(4!, T(2)))) \\ 24256 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times C(T(5), 2) + (4 - T(2))) \\ 24264 &:= (((C(4!, T(6)) - 2) \times 4) \times T(2)) \\ 24268 &:= ((-T(C(8,6))) \times (-T(2) - T(T(4)))) + (T(T(2)))! \\ 24274 &:= ((T(4!) - T(T(7))) \times (2 - T(T(C(4,2)))))) \\ 24276 &:= (((6 + T(7))^2) \times T(C(4,2))) \\ 24284 &:= (-4) + ((T(8)/T(2)) \times C(4!, T(2))) \\ 24289 &:= (C((9+8), (2 \times 4)) - T(T(T(2)))) \\ 24294 &:= ((T((T(4) \times 9)) \times T(T(2))) - (C(4!, 2))) \\ 24324 &:= (((C(4!, T(2)) + 3) \times 4!)/2) \\ 24344 &:= (((-4!) + T(T(4))) \times (T(3))!) + (C(4!, T(2))) \\ 24348 &:= ((8 \times T(T((4 \times 3)))) - T((C(4, T(2))))!) \\ 24364 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + ((T(T(6)) + (T(3))!) \times (C(4, T(2))))!) \\ 24368 &:= (((8 + T(6))^3) - T(C(4,2))) \\ 24378 &:= ((T(8) + (T(T(7)) \times T(C(T(3), 4))))/2) \\ 24395 &:= (5 \times ((T(C(9,3)) + T(T(T(4)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 24425 &:= ((C(T(5), T(2)) \times T(T(4))) - (T(4!) \times 2)) \\ 24427 &:= ((T(7)^{T(2)}) + (T(T(4)) \times C(T(4), 2))) \\ 24432 &:= (((-2) + (T(3))!) + T(4!)) \times (C(4, T(2)))! \\ 24434 &:= -((T(T((4+3))) - (4! \times T(C(T(4), 2)))))) \\ 24435 &:= ((T((T(5) - 3)) \times T(4!)) + T(C(T(4), 2))) \\ 24437 &:= ((T(7)^3) + T((C(T(4), 4)/T(2)))) \\ 24444 &:= ((T((4! \times 4))/4) \times T(C(4, 2))) \\ 24445 &:= ((-5) + C(4!, 4)) + (4!^{T(2)}) \\ 24458 &:= ((8 \times (C(T(5), T(4)) + T(T(4)))) - T(T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24459 &:= (((T(T(9)) - T(5)) \times 4!) - T(C(4,2))) \\ 24468 &:= (((8! \times 6)/T(4)) + C(4!,2)) \\ 24471 &:= (C((1 + T(7)),4) + (C(4,2))!) \\ 24478 &:= ((8 \times C((T(7) - T(4)),4)) - 2) \\ 24479 &:= ((T(9) - T(T(7))) + (4! \times T(C(T(4),2)))) \\ 24486 &:= ((T((6 \times 8)) - T(4)) \times T(C(4,2))) \\ 24488 &:= (8 \times (T(C(8,4)) + (4!^2))) \\ 24497 &:= ((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) \times (-4 + T(C(4,2)))) \\ 24504 &:= (-4!) \times (-((0! - T(5))) - T(C(T(4),2))) \\ 24524 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) + ((T(5) \times T(4))^2)) \\ 24525 &:= ((T(5) + (T(T(2)) \times (-C(T(5),4)))) \times (-T(2))) \\ 24532 &:= ((-T(2) + C(T(T(3)),5)) + T(T((T(4) + T(2)))) \\ 24534 &:= ((4! - T(3)) \times (C(T(5),4) - 2)) \\ 24549 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times 4!) - ((T(5) + C(4!,2)))) \\ 24565 &:= (5 \times ((T(C(6,5)) - (4))^{T(2)})) \\ 24566 &:= ((6 \times T((6 \times T(5)))) - C(4, T(2))) \\ 24567 &:= ((C(T(C(7,6)),5)/4) - T(2)) \\ 24571 &:= (-1) + ((C(T(7),5)/4) + 2) \\ 24577 &:= ((T(7) + C(T(7),5))/C(4, T(2))) \\ 24578 &:= (8 + (C(T(7),5)/C(4, T(2)))) \\ 24588 &:= ((T(8) + (T(8) \times C(T(5),4)))/2) \\ 24594 &:= (4! + (9 \times (C(T(5),4) \times 2))) \\ 24635 &:= (((C(T(5),3) + (6)) \times T(T(4))) - (T(T(2))))!) \\ 24649 &:= (((C(9,4) + T(6)) + T(4))^2) \\ 24686 &:= ((T(6) \times T((8 \times 6))) - T(C(4, T(2)))) \\ 24688 &:= (-8) + (T((8 \times 6)) \times T(C(4,2))) \\ 24692 &:= ((T((T(2) + T(9))) \times T(6)) - C(4, T(2))) \\ 24693 &:= (-3) - ((-9) \times (6! + C(4!, T(2)))) \\ 24738 &:= ((T(C(8,3)) \times (-7 - 4!))/(-2)) \\ 24752 &:= (C((2 + T(5)), T((7 - 4))) \times 2) \\ 24789 &:= (T(T(9)) + ((C((T(8) - 7),4) + T(2)))) \\ 24792 &:= ((-2) + T(T(9))) \times (T(7) - C(4, T(2))) \\ 24824 &:= ((T(4) \times (-2) + T(C(8,4))) - T(T(2))) \\ 24825 &:= (T(5) \times (2 + T((T(8) + T(C(4,2)))))) \\ 24835 &:= (-5) \times (3 - (T(C(8,4)) \times 2)) \\ 24841 &:= (1 + (4! \times T(C(T((8 - 4)),2)))) \\ 24844 &:= (-4) + ((T(4) \times T(C(8,4))) - 2) \\ 24845 &:= (T(5) + (T(4) \times (T(C(8,4)) - 2))) \\ 24846 &:= (-6) + ((T(4) \times T(C(8,4))) + 2) \\ 24847 &:= ((T((T(7) - 4!)) \times T(C(8,4))) - T(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}24848 &:= ((T((8-4)) \times T(C(8,4))) - 2) \\24873 &:= ((37 \times T(T(8))) + T(T(C(4,2)))) \\24875 &:= ((5 \times 7!) - C((T(8) - T(4)), 2)) \\24877 &:= ((T(T(7)) + (C((-7) + T(8)), 4)) + (T(T(2)))) \\24879 &:= ((T(C(9,7)) \times T(8)) + T(42)) \\24882 &:= ((T(2))! \times (T(88) + T(T(C(4,2)))))) \\24895 &:= (-5) \times (-9) - (T(C(8,4)) \times 2)) \\24909 &:= (T(9) - ((-0!) - T(T(9))) \times (C(4, T(2)))) \\24912 &:= ((T(2) + T(T((1 \times 9)))) \times (C(4, T(2)))) \\24933 &:= (T(T(3)) + ((3 + T(T(9))) \times (C(4, T(2)))) \\24939 &:= (-T(9) + ((T(3) + T(T(9))) \times (C(4, T(2)))) \\24948 &:= (T(8) \times ((4! + 9) \times T(C(4, 2)))) \\24955 &:= (-5) + ((5 + T(T(9))) \times (C(4, T(2)))) \\24975 &:= (5 \times (7! - T(C(9, (4 \times 2)))) \\24985 &:= (5 \times (-8) + C(T((9-4)), T(T(2)))) \\25015 &:= (5 \times ((-1) - 0!) + C(T(5), T(T(2)))) \\25022 &:= (-T(2) + ((T(T(2)) - 0!) \times C(T(5), T(T(2)))) \\25025 &:= (C(T(5), T(2)) \times T(C(05, 2))) \\25035 &:= (5 \times ((3 - 0!) + C(T(5), T(T(2)))) \\25045 &:= (5 \times (4 + C(T(05), T(T(2)))) \\25046 &:= (T(6) - (T(T(4)) \times (0 - C(T(5), T(2)))) \\25054 &:= (4! - (5 \times (-0!) - C(T(5), T(T(2)))) \\25055 &:= (5 \times (C(T(5), (0! + 5)) + T(T(2)))) \\25059 &:= (T(T(9)) - (((T(5) - 0!)! / (-C(5, 2)))) \\25064 &:= ((T(4) + T(T(6))) \times (-0! - C(T(5), 2))) \\25195 &:= (-5) + (T(9) \times C((1 + T(5)), T(2))) \\25223 &:= (T(T(3)) + ((T(C(T(T(2))), T(2)) \times 5!) + 2)) \\25238 &:= (T(8) - ((T(C(T(3), T(2))) \times (-5!)) - 2)) \\25247 &:= (((-7!) - T(C(4, T(2)))) \times (-5)) - T(2) \\25251 &:= (((-1) + C(T(5), T(T(2)))) \times 5) + T(T(T(T(2)))) \\25253 &:= (T(T(T(3))) + ((C(T(5), T(T(2))) \times 5) - T(2))) \\25255 &:= ((5 \times ((5 + 2))!) + T(C(5, 2))) \\25256 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((C(T(5), T(2)) \times T(C(5, 2)))) \\25257 &:= (((7! \times 5) + 2) + T(C(5, 2))) \\25285 &:= ((5! + (8!/2)) + C(T(5), T(T(2)))) \\25323 &:= (((T(T(T(3))) - C(T(T(2)), 3)) \times 5!) + T(2)) \\25325 &:= ((5! \times T(C(T(T(2)), 3))) + (5^{T(2)})) \\25332 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - ((T(3))! \times 5))/2) \\25341 &:= (((1 + C(T(4), T(3))) \times 5!) + T(T(T(2)))) \\25355 &:= (55 \times (T(3) + C(T(5), T(2))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25387 &:= (7! + (C(T((T(8)/T(3))),5) - 2)) \\ 25392 &:= ((-((2 - 9)))! + (C(T(3!),5) + T(2))) \\ 25404 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times C((0! + T(4)),5)) - T(T(2))) \\ 25424 &:= (T(C(T(4),2)) + (((4! + 5))^{T(2)})) \\ 25431 &:= (T(T((1 + T(3)))) + (T(T(4)) \times C(T(5),T(2)))) \\ 25437 &:= ((T(T(7)) + T(3)) + (T(T(4)) \times C(T(5),T(2)))) \\ 25439 &:= (((T(T(9)) + T(3)) \times 4!) + (C(T(5),T(2)))) \\ 25442 &:= (((2 + C(T(4),4)) \times 5!) + 2) \\ 25449 &:= (-(C(9,4)) + (T(T(4)) \times T((T(5) \times 2)))) \\ 25466 &:= ((T(6) \times T(6)) + (T(T(4)) \times C(T(5),T(2)))) \\ 25487 &:= (-7) \times (-(8^4) + C(T(5),T(2))) \\ 25495 &:= (5 \times (94 + C(T(5),T(T(2)))))) \\ 25529 &:= ((9!/(T(T(2)))!) + (5 \times C(T(5),T(T(2)))))) \\ 25536 &:= (T(6) + ((3^5) \times C(T(5),2))) \\ 25575 &:= (T(((5 \times 7) - 5)) \times T(C(5,2))) \\ 25604 &:= (-(T(4) - C((0! + T(6)),5)) - (T(T(2)))!) \\ 25607 &:= ((-7) + C((0! + T(6)),5) - (T(T(2)))!) \\ 25612 &:= ((-2) + C((1 + T(6)),5) - (T(T(2)))!) \\ 25616 &:= -((6! - (C((1 + T(6)),5) + 2)) \\ 25642 &:= -T(T(2))! + (-T(T(T(4))) + C(T(6),T(5)))/2 \\ 25678 &:= ((T(8) \times (-7) + 6!) + C(5,2)) \\ 25696 &:= (-(C(-(T(6) - T(9))),T(6))) + (5! \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 25704 &:= (C(((T(4) + 0!) + 7),5) \times T(2)) \\ 25725 &:= (((C(T(5),2) + 7!) \times T(5))/T(2)) \\ 25727 &:= ((T((7^2)) \times C(7,5)) + 2) \\ 25734 &:= ((C((T(4) + 3),7) \times T(5)) - T(T(2))) \\ 25737 &:= ((C((7 + T(3)),7) \times T(5)) - T(2)) \\ 25739 &:= ((T((T(9) - 3)) \times T(7)) + (C(T(5),T(2)))) \\ 25742 &:= ((C((T(2) + T(4)),7) \times T(5)) + 2) \\ 25743 &:= ((C((3 + T(4)),7) \times T(5)) + T(2)) \\ 25745 &:= (-5) \times ((-4) - 7!) - C(T(5),2)) \\ 25754 &:= ((4 \times (C(T(5),7) + 5)) - T(T(2))) \\ 25768 &:= ((T(C(8,6)) \times T(7)) + (5!^2)) \\ 25812 &:= -((T(T(2)) \times (T((1 + T(8))) - C(T(5),T(T(2)))))) \\ 25815 &:= (((5 + 1))! \times T(8)) - C(T(5),2) \\ 25822 &:= (((T(T(2)))! - T(2)) \times T(8)) + C(5,2) \\ 25835 &:= (((-T(5)) + (T(3))!) \times T(8)) + (C(T(5),T(2))) \\ 25837 &:= (-T(7)) + (((T(3))! \times T(8)) - T(C(5,2))) \\ 25845 &:= (5 \times ((T(C(T(4),8)) \times 5) - T(T(2)))) \\ 25847 &:= (-T(7)) + (T(C(T(4),8)) \times (5^2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25865 &:= ((5! \times 6) \times T(8)) - T(C(5,2)) \\ 25899 &:= (9! / (C(9,8) + 5)) - T(T(T(2))) \\ 25935 &:= (C(T(5),3) \times ((T(9) + T(5)) - T(2))) \\ 25942 &:= (-2) + (4! \times T((-9) + T(C(5,2)))) \\ 25974 &:= (-T(4) + (T(T(7)) \times (9 + T(C(5,2)))))) \\ 25983 &:= (((T(3))! \times T(8)) + (C(9,5)/2)) \\ 26125 &:= (5^{T(2)}) \times (-1) + C(T(6),2)) \\ 26187 &:= (7 \times T((C((8+1),6) + 2))) \\ 26194 &:= ((4! \times (T(T(9)) + 1)) + (C(T(6),T(2)))) \\ 26238 &:= ((T(8) \times (C(3,2)^6)) - T(T(2))) \\ 26265 &:= (T(5) \times (-C(T(6),T(2)) + T(T((6 \times 2)))))) \\ 26292 &:= (T((T(2))!) \times (-T((9 + T(2)) - (C(T(6),T(2)))))) \\ 26297 &:= (-T(7) + (9 \times C((T(T(2)) + (T(6))),T(2)))) \\ 26312 &:= (C(T((T(T(2)) + 1)),T(T(3)))/T((6 + T(2)))) \\ 26348 &:= ((8! + C((-4) + T(T(3))),6)/2) \\ 26355 &:= ((5 \times C(T(5),T(3))) + C(T(6),T(2))) \\ 26376 &:= ((T(6) + C(T(7),3)) \times (6 + 2)) \\ 26378 &:= ((8 \times (C(T(7),3) + T(6))) + 2) \\ 26399 &:= ((9 \times T(T((9 + 3)))) - (C(T(6),T(2)))) \\ 26404 &:= (4 \times (0! - (T(T(4)) \times (-T(C(6,2)))))) \\ 26412 &:= (C(-((T(T(2)) - (1 + 4!)),6) - (T(T(2))!)) \\ 26439 &:= ((T(C(9,3)) \times T(4)) - (T(6)^{T(2)})) \\ 26442 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((C(T(4),4) \times T(6)) - T(2))) \\ 26458 &:= ((T(8) \times (T(C(5,4) + 6!)) - 2) \\ 26475 &:= (T(5) - ((T(C(7,4)) \times T(6)) \times (-2))) \\ 26524 &:= (C((4! - 2),5) + T((T(6) - 2))) \\ 26537 &:= (-T(7) + (T(T(T(3))) \times (-5) + T(C(6,2)))) \\ 26568 &:= (8 \times T((6 + (5 \times C(6,2)))))) \\ 26615 &:= (T(5) + ((-1) + T(6)) \times C(T(6),T(2))) \\ 26627 &:= ((T(7) \times ((T(T(2))! + T(T(6)))) - C(6, T(T(2)))) \\ 26678 &:= ((T(C(8,7)) \times (6! + T(6))) + 2) \\ 26679 &:= ((C(9,7) \times (6! + T(6))) + T(2)) \\ 26691 &:= (C(19,6) - (T(6)^2)) \\ 26845 &:= ((5 - T(4!)) \times (-C((8 + 6),2))) \\ 26875 &:= (-5) - ((T(7) \times (-8)) \times T(C(6,2))) \\ 26878 &:= (((C(8,7))! + 8!) - (6))/T(2) \\ 26901 &:= (C((10 + 9),6) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 26922 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times (-((T(2) + T(9)) - C(T(6),T(2)))))) \\ 26943 &:= (((C(T(T(3)),4) \times 9) + (T(6)))/2) \\ 26964 &:= ((T(4!) + (T(6))) \times C(9, (6/2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26999 &:= (-C(9,9) + (9 + T(6))^{T(2)}) \\ 27027 &:= (C((7 + T(T(2))), (0! + (7))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 27048 &:= ((T(T(8)) + T(4!)) \times C((0! + (7)), 2)) \\ 27126 &:= (C((T(6) - 2), -((1 - 7))) - T(T(2))) \\ 27128 &:= ((-8) + C(T(T(T(2))), -((1 - 7))))/2 \\ 27131 &:= (-1) - (C(T(T(3)), -((1 - 7)))/(-2)) \\ 27132 &:= (C(T((2 \times 3)), -((1 - 7)))/2) \\ 27134 &:= ((4 + C(T(T(3))), -((1 - 7))))/2 \\ 27136 &:= ((C(T(6), T(3)) + (1 + 7))/2) \\ 27138 &:= ((T(C(8,3)) \times 17) + T(T(2))) \\ 27146 &:= ((C(T(6), T((4 - 1))) + T(7))/2) \\ 27168 &:= (T(8) + (C(T(6), -((1 - 7)))/2)) \\ 27216 &:= (C(T((6 + 1)), 2) \times 72) \\ 27223 &:= (C((T(T(3)) - 2), T(T(2))) + T((7 + T(T(2)))))) \\ 27225 &:= ((T(C(5,2))^2) \times (7 + 2)) \\ 27237 &:= ((7! \times T(3)) - C((2 \times 7), T(T(2)))) \\ 27251 &:= ((1 - 5!) \times (2 - T(C(7,2)))) \\ 27254 &:= (-4) + ((5! - 2) \times T(C(7,2))) \\ 27258 &:= (((8 \times T(5)) - 2) \times T(C(7,2))) \\ 27264 &:= (((C(4!, T(6)) \times 2) + 7!) \times T(2)) \\ 27295 &:= (-5) + (C(9, T(2)) \times T((T(7) - T(2)))) \\ 27324 &:= -((C(4!, 2) \times (T(3) - T((7 \times 2)))))) \\ 27332 &:= (-T(2) + ((C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + T(T(7)))/2)) \\ 27335 &:= ((C((T(5) + T(3)), T(3)) + T(T(7)))/2) \\ 27355 &:= (-5) - (5! \times (3 - T(C(7,2)))) \\ 27384 &:= (C(4!, (8 - 3)) - (7! \times T(2))) \\ 27423 &:= (((T(T(3))^{T(2)} - C(T(4), 7)) \times T(2)) \\ 27426 &:= ((C(T(6), T(2)) - 4!) \times C(7, 2)) \\ 27432 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((T(3)^4 + C(T(7), T(2)))) \\ 27445 &:= (-5) \times (T(T(4)) - ((4! \times T(C(7,2)))))) \\ 27447 &:= (((-T(T(7))) + T(T(T(4)))) \times 4!) + T(C(7,2)) \\ 27465 &:= ((5! \times T(T(6))) - (4! + T(C(7,2)))) \\ 27467 &:= (-T((T(7) - (6)))) + (C(T(4), 7) \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 27468 &:= (((8! \times 6)/T(4)) + C(T(7), T(2))) \\ 27475 &:= (((5! \times 7) - T(T(4))) \times C(7, T(2))) \\ 27485 &:= ((T(5) \times T((T(8) + 4!))) + C(7, T(2))) \\ 27495 &:= (-5) \times (T(9) - (4! \times T(C(7,2)))) \\ 27517 &:= (T(7) + ((-1) + 5!) \times T(C(7,2))) \\ 27532 &:= -((C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - (((-5!) + T(T(7)))^2)))) \\ 27545 &:= ((-5!) - T(T(4))) + ((5! \times T(C(7,2)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27565 &:= ((5! \times T(T(6))) - (5! + C(7, T(2)))) \\ 27566 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((-C(T(6), T(5))) - T(T(7)))/(-2)) \\ 27573 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times (-7)) + ((5! \times T(C(7, 2)))) \\ 27584 &:= -((T((4! - 8)) - ((5! \times T(C(7, 2))))) \\ 27594 &:= (((T(4))! - 9!)/5!) + (C(T(7), 2)) \\ 27615 &:= ((T(51) \times T(6)) - T(C(7, 2))) \\ 27668 &:= (((T(T(8)) + (C(T(6), 6))) + T(T(7)))/2) \\ 27685 &:= (((T(5) \times 8) \times T(T(6))) - C(7, T(2))) \\ 27699 &:= (((T(9)/9))! \times T(T(6))) - C(7, 2) \\ 27744 &:= (4! + (C(T(4), 7) \times T(C(7, 2)))) \\ 27746 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times C(T(4), 7)) + (T(7) - 2)) \\ 27756 &:= -(((6! + (-5) \times 7!) - C(T(7), T(2)))) \\ 27784 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - (((T(T(C(8, 7))) - (7!)) \times T(T(2)))) \\ 27825 &:= ((T(5) + T((T(2) + T(8)))) \times C(7, T(2))) \\ 27846 &:= (T(6) \times T((-4) + T((C(8, 7) + 2)))) \\ 27853 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T((T(5) + T(8)))) + C(7, T(T(2)))) \\ 27856 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times 5!) + T((C(8, 7) \times 2))) \\ 27925 &:= (-5) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T((9 - 7))) \times T(T(T(2)))) \\ 27944 &:= (((4 + 4))! - C((T(9) - T(7)), T(T(2)))) \\ 27946 &:= ((C(T(6), 4) + 9) + (T(7)^{T(2)})) \\ 27947 &:= (((T(C(7, 4)) \times T(9)) - T(T(7))) + T(2)) \\ 27948 &:= ((8! + (4)) - C((T(9) - T(7)), T(T(2)))) \\ 27964 &:= ((-4) + (T(6) \times T(C(9, 7)))) \times 2 \\ 27965 &:= (((-5) - T(T(6))) + T(T(9))) \times C(7, T(2)) \\ 27966 &:= (-6) + ((T(6) \times T(C(9, 7))) \times 2) \\ 27989 &:= ((T(9) + 8!) - C((T(9) - T(7)), T(T(2)))) \\ 28084 &:= ((T(4!)) + T((T(8) + 0!))) \times C(8, 2) \\ 28125 &:= ((5! \times T(T(T(T(2)))))) + (-1) + T(C(8, 2))) \\ 28126 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times ((T(T(2)) - 1)!) + (T(C(8, 2)))) \\ 28245 &:= (C(T(5), 4) + ((2 \times 8!)/T(2))) \\ 28263 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times C(T(6), T(2))) - (T(T(8)))/(-2)) \\ 28266 &:= (T(6) \times (C(T(6), T(2)) + (8 \times 2))) \\ 28288 &:= ((T(8) + T(C(8, 2))) \times (8²)) \\ 28325 &:= (T(C(5, 2)) \times (3 + (8^{T(2)}))) \\ 28334 &:= ((C(4!, 3) \times (T(3) + 8)) - 2) \\ 28336 &:= ((C(T(6), 3) \times T(T(3))) + (T(C(8, 2)))) \\ 28337 &:= ((-7) + C(T(T(3)), T(3))) + (-T(8) \times (T(T(2))!)) \\ 28342 &:= (T(T(2)) + (-C(4!, 3) \times (-8 - T(T(2)))) \\ 28344 &:= (((C(4!, 4) + 3) \times 8)/T(2)) \\ 28355 &:= ((T(5) \times (-C(T(5), T(3))) - T(T(8)))/(-T(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28357 &:= (7 \times (T(C(5,3)) + (T(T(8)) \times T(T(2)))))) \\ 28365 &:= (T(5) \times T((6 + C((3 + 8), 2)))) \\ 28378 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (7 \times T(3))) + (T(C(8,2)))) \\ 28391 &:= (-1) + ((T(T(9)) - T(T(3))) \times C(8,2)) \\ 28392 &:= (T((T(2) + 9)) \times C((3! + 8), T(2))) \\ 28428 &:= ((T(8)^2) + C((T(T(4)) - T(8)), T(T(2)))) \\ 28455 &:= ((5 \times C(T(5), T(4))) + (8!/T(2))) \\ 28497 &:= (7 \times ((T(9) \times T(T(4))) + T(C(8, T(2))))) \\ 28565 &:= (-5) \times (6! - (C(T(5), 8) - 2)) \\ 28579 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T(7)) - (-5 + T(C(8, 2)))) \\ 28588 &:= ((8 \times T(-(T(8) - 5!))) + C(8, 2)) \\ 28595 &:= (-C(T(5), 9)) + ((5 \times 8!)/T(T(2))) \\ 28625 &:= ((C(T(5), T(T(2))) + (6!)) \times (8 - T(2))) \\ 28665 &:= ((T(5) \times T(6)) \times C((6 + 8), 2)) \\ 28686 &:= ((T(6) \times T(C(8, 6))) + (8!/2)) \\ 28756 &:= ((C(T(6), T(5)) + (T(T(7)) \times 8))/2) \\ 28812 &:= ((T(T(2)) - T(T((1 + 8)))) \times (-C(8, 2))) \\ 28826 &:= (((T(6) \times T(2)) + 8) \times T(C(8, 2))) \\ 28855 &:= (5 \times ((C(T(5), 8) - T(T(8))) + 2)) \\ 28856 &:= ((6! \times (5 \times 8)) + C(8, T(2))) \\ 28898 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times T(9)) - T(T(8))) - (T(C(8, 2)))) \\ 28922 &:= (-2) + ((-2) + T(T(9))) \times C(8, 2)) \\ 28924 &:= ((-(4 - 2)) + T(T(9))) \times C(8, 2)) \\ 28946 &:= ((T(6) - T(T(4))) - (T(T(9)) \times (-C(8, 2)))) \\ 28948 &:= (-((8 \times 4)) - (T(T(9)) \times (-C(8, 2)))) \\ 28955 &:= (-((5 \times 5)) - (T(T(9)) \times (-C(8, 2)))) \\ 28957 &:= (-((T(7) - 5)) - (T(T(9)) \times (-C(8, 2)))) \\ 28959 &:= -((T((-9) + T(5))) + (T(T(9)) \times (-C(8, 2)))) \\ 28964 &:= (-((T(4) + 6)) - (T(T(9)) \times (-C(8, 2)))) \\ 28967 &:= (-((7 + 6)) - (T(T(9)) \times (-C(8, 2)))) \\ 28995 &:= (T(5) + (T(T(9)) \times T((C(9, 8) - 2)))) \\ 28996 &:= ((6!/T(9)) - (T(T(9)) \times (-C(8, 2)))) \\ 28997 &:= ((T(7) \times T(T(9))) + (T(9) - C(8, 2))) \\ 29048 &:= (8 \times (-4!) + T((0! + C(9, T(2))))) \\ 29226 &:= (-C(6, 2) + (T((2 \times 9))^2)) \\ 29232 &:= ((2^3) \times C(29, T(2))) \\ 29245 &:= (-5) + (T(4) \times C((T(2) \times 9), T(2))) \\ 29298 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times T(9)) - T(T(2))) - T(C(9, 2))) \\ 29304 &:= ((T(40) - T(3)) \times C(9, 2)) \\ 29322 &:= (T(T(2)) \times ((T(T(T(2))) \times T(T(T(3)))) + C(9, 2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29337 &:= ((7! \times T(3)) - T((T(3) + C(9,2)))) \\ 29344 &:= ((T(4) \times T((T(T(4)) + T(T(3)))))) + C(9, T(2))) \\ 29393 &:= (C(T(T(3)),9)/((3+9) - 2)) \\ 29422 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) - ((4! \times T(T(9))) + 2)) \\ 29426 &:= (C(T(6), T(T(2))) - ((4! \times T(T(9))) - 2)) \\ 29442 &:= (2 \times (C(4!,4) + T((T(9) \times 2)))) \\ 29457 &:= (((C(T(7),5)/T(4)) - 9) \times T(2)) \\ 29465 &:= (5 \times (C(T(6),4) - (92))) \\ 29474 &:= (-T(4) + ((T(T(7)) - T(T(4))) \times C(9, T(2)))) \\ 29476 &:= ((C(T(6),7)/4) + T(T((9 - 2)))) \\ 29486 &:= (((6! \times T(8)) - (4)) + T(C(9, T(2)))) \\ 29487 &:= ((C(T(7), T((8/4))) \times 9) + T(2)) \\ 29527 &:= (((C(T(7), T(2)) + (5)) \times 9) - 2) \\ 29534 &:= -((T((T(4) + T(T(3)))) + (-C(T(5),9)) \times T(T(2)))) \\ 29556 &:= (((T(T(6)) + T(5)) \times 5!) + C(9,2)) \\ 29579 &:= ((-T(9) - T(T(7))) - (-C(T(5),9)) \times T(T(2)))) \\ 29648 &:= (8 \times (T((T(4) + (6))) + T(C(9, T(2)))))) \\ 29652 &:= ((2 + T((5 + T(6)))) \times C(9, T(2))) \\ 29729 &:= (-T((9 \times 2))) - (-C(T(7),9)/T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 29733 &:= (-3) + (T(3) \times (7! - C(9, T(2)))) \\ 29747 &:= (-T((-7) + 4!)) - (-C(T(7),9)/T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 29756 &:= (((C(6,5))! - T(7)) \times (T(9) - 2)) \\ 29794 &:= ((T(T(4)) + ((T(C(9,7)) \times T(9)))) - T(T(T(T(2)))))) \\ 29799 &:= ((T(9) \times T(C(9,7))) - T((9 \times 2))) \\ 29889 &:= (9 \times T(((C(8,8) \times 9)^2))) \\ 29898 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times T(9)) - (T(8) + C(9,2))) \\ 29915 &:= -((T(T((5 - 1))) - ((T(9) \times T(C(9,2)))))) \\ 29916 &:= -((6! + ((-1) - T(9)) \times T(C(9,2)))) \\ 29925 &:= -(((T(5) \times T(2)) - (T(9) \times T(C(9,2)))))) \\ 29943 &:= ((-3) - 4!) + (T(9) \times T(C(9,2))) \\ 29945 &:= -(((T(5) + T(4)) - (T(9) \times T(C(9,2)))))) \\ 29949 &:= -(((T(9) - 4!) - (T(9) \times T(C(9,2)))))) \\ 29955 &:= -((T(5) + (-((5 \times 9)) \times T(C(9,2)))))) \\ 29957 &:= -(((T(7) - T(5)) - (T(9) \times T(C(9,2)))))) \\ 29968 &:= (-((8 - 6)) + (T(9) \times T(C(9,2)))) \\ 29983 &:= (T(T(3)) - (8 - (T(9) \times T(C(9,2)))))) \\ 29985 &:= (T(5) + ((T(8) + 9) \times T(C(9,2)))) \\ 30045 &:= (T(5) \times (C(4!, T((0! + 0!))) - T(T(3)))) \\ 30054 &:= (4! - (C(T(5), T(T((0! + 0!)))) \times (-T(3)))) \\ 30247 &:= (((7! \times C(4,2)) + 0!) + T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 30354 &:= ((T(T(4)) + ((C(T(5), T(3)) - 0!))) \times T(3)) \\ 30492 &:= (T((2 + 9)) \times C((T(4) + 0!), 3!)) \\ 30525 &:= (T(C(5, 2)) \times (T(50) - (T(3))!)) \\ 30555 &:= (T(5) \times (-C(T(5), 5) + ((0! + T(3))!)) \\ 30744 &:= ((C(4!, 4) - T((T(7) - 0!))) \times 3) \\ 30925 &:= (C(T(5), T(T(2))) + (T((9 - 0!)) \times (T(3))!)) \\ 31374 &:= ((T(T(4)) + (T(7))) \times T((C(3, 1)^3))) \\ 31388 &:= (8! - (T(C(8, T(3))) \times (1 + T(T(3))))) \\ 31524 &:= -((T(4!) - (C((T(2) + T(5)), (1 + T(3))))) \\ 31528 &:= ((-8!) - C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)))/(-1 \times 3)) \\ 31552 &:= (C((2 + T(5)), T(5)) \times (1 + T(T(T(3))))) \\ 31575 &:= ((C(T(5), 7) - 5!) \times (-1 + T(3))) \\ 31668 &:= (T(C(8, 6)) \times (6 \times 13)) \\ 31733 &:= (C((3 \times T(3)), 7) - T(13)) \\ 31814 &:= -((T(4) - C(18, (1 + T(3))))) \\ 31817 &:= (-7) + C(18, (1 + T(3))) \\ 31944 &:= (4! \times ((C(T(4), 9) + 1)^3)) \\ 32064 &:= (4! \times (C(T(6), T(02)) + T(3))) \\ 32135 &:= (((5! \times (T(3))!) - 1) - C(T(T(T(2))), T(3))) \\ 32139 &:= (((T(C(9, 3)) + 1) \times T(2)) \times 3) \\ 32214 &:= ((T(T(C((4 + 1), 2))) - T(T(2))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 32234 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - T(3)) \times T(T(T(2)))) + C(T(T(2)), 3)) \\ 32235 &:= ((-5) + T(T(C((3 + 2), 2)))) \times T(T(3)) \\ 32312 &:= -(((T((T(T(2)) + 1))^3) - C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)))) \\ 32325 &:= ((T(T(C(5, 2))) \times T(T(3))) - T((2 + 3))) \\ 32335 &:= ((T(T(C(5, 3))) \times T(T(3))) - (2 + 3)) \\ 32368 &:= (C(8, 6) - (-T(T(3)) \times T(T(T((-2) + T(3))))) \\ 32379 &:= ((T(9) \times (C((7 - 3), 2))!) - T(T(3))) \\ 32415 &:= (T(5) \times (1 + ((C(4, 2))! \times 3))) \\ 32421 &:= (((T((1 + 2)))! \times C(T(4), 2)) + T(T(3))) \\ 32424 &:= ((4 + C((-2) + 4!), T(2))) \times T(T(3)) \\ 32425 &:= ((5^2) - (-C(T(4), 2) \times (T(3))!)) \\ 32428 &:= (C(8, 2) - (-C(T(4), 2) \times (T(3))!)) \\ 32434 &:= (T(T(4)) + (((T(3))! \times C(T(4), 2)) - T(T(3)))) \\ 32435 &:= (-C(T(5), T(3))) + ((T(T(4)) - T(2)) \times (T(3))!) \\ 32438 &:= (C(8, 3) - ((T(T(T(4))) + 2) \times (-T(T(3))))) \\ 32449 &:= ((T(9) + (4)) - (-C(T(4), 2) \times (T(3))!)) \\ 32545 &:= (-5) + ((T(4) + T(T(C(5, 2)))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 32558 &:= ((8^5) - C(C(5, 2), T(3))) \\ 32565 &:= (((T(5) \times 6!) + T(C(5, 2))) \times 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32578 &:= ((C(8,7)^5) - T((-2) + T(T(3)))) \\ 32592 &:= (((T(2) + 9) + T(T(C(5,2)))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 32704 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T(-((0! - C(7, T(2)))))) - (T(T(3)))) \\ 32724 &:= -(((T(4) \times (T(2) - C(T(7), T(2)))) + T(3))) \\ 32725 &:= (T(C(5,2)) \times T((T(7) + (2 \times 3)))) \\ 32745 &:= (T(5) + (T(4) \times (C(T(7), T(2)) - 3))) \\ 32747 &:= (-7) + ((T(4) \times C(T(7), T(2))) - T(3)) \\ 32754 &:= ((4! \times C(T(5), (7 - T(2)))) - T(3)) \\ 32775 &:= (T(5) + (C(T(7), (7 - 2))/3)) \\ 32824 &:= (((T(C(T(4), 2)) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(2)))/T(T(3))) \\ 32827 &:= ((C(T(7), T(T(T(2))))/T(8)) - (T(2) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 32837 &:= ((C(T(7), -(3 - 8)) + T(T(T(T(2)))))/3) \\ 32845 &:= (5! + (T(T(4)) \times T((C(8, 2) + T(3)))) \\ 32852 &:= ((2^{T(5)}) + (C(8, 2) \times 3)) \\ 32867 &:= ((C(T(7), T(6))/T(8)) - (23)) \\ 32889 &:= (((T(9) + T(8)) \times T(C(8, 2))) + 3) \\ 32928 &:= (C(8, 2) \times T(((T(9) - T(2)) + T(3)))) \\ 33145 &:= ((T(5) \times T(T((T(4) + 1)))) - C(T(3), 3)) \\ 33154 &:= ((4! \times T(51)) + C(T(T(3)), 3)) \\ 33245 &:= (-5) + ((4 + T(T(T(2)))) \times C(T(T(3)), 3)) \\ 33274 &:= (4! + ((T(7) - T(2)) \times C(T(T(3)), 3)) \\ 33278 &:= ((8 \times T(T((7 + T(T(2)))))) - T(C(T(3), 3))) \\ 33284 &:= ((-4!) \times (-T(T(8)) - (T(T(2)))!) + C(T(3), 3)) \\ 33292 &:= ((-2) + C(9, T(2))) \times T(T((T(3!)/3))) \\ 33295 &:= (-5) + (T(9) \times (C(T(T(2)), 3) + (T(3))!)) \\ \\ 33298 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (T(9) + T(2))) + C(T(T(3)), 3)) \\ 33324 &:= ((C(T(4), 2) \times ((T(3))! + T(T(3)))) - T(T(3))) \\ 33325 &:= ((5^2) \times (C(T(T(3)), 3) + 3)) \\ 33348 &:= ((-8) + T(C((4!/3), 3))) \times T(T(3)) \\ 33355 &:= (5 \times ((5 \times C(T(T(3)), 3)) + T(T(3)))) \\ 33364 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + C((6 \times 3), (T(T(3))/3))) \\ 33378 &:= ((T(T(8)) - (7! \times C(T(3), 3)))/(-3)) \\ 33383 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T((T(8) + T(T(3)))) - (C(T(T(3)), 3))) \\ 33385 &:= (-5) + ((T(C(8, 3)) - T(3)) \times T(T(3))) \\ 33425 &:= -((C(T(5), T(T(2))) - (T((T(4) \times T(3))) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 33428 &:= (T((T(8) \times 2)) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-C(T(3), 3)))) \\ 33438 &:= (((T(C(8, 3)) - 4) \times T(T(3))) + T(3)) \\ 33445 &:= ((-T(5) + T(T(T(4)))) - (-4! \times C(T(T(3)), 3)) \\ 33464 &:= (-((T(4) \times T(64))) + C(T(T(3)), T(3))) \\ 33474 &:= (((-4!) - T(T(7))) + (C(4!, 3))) \times T(T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33481 &:= (1 - (T(8) \times (-C(T(4), T(3))) - (T(3))!)) \\ 33487 &:= (7 - (T(8) \times (-C(T(4), T(3))) - (T(3))!)) \\ 33508 &:= (-8) + (T((0! + T(C(5, 3))) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 33513 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times T((1 + T(C(5, 3)))) - 3) \\ 33516 &:= (T(6) \times T(C((1 \times 5) + 3), 3)) \\ 33519 &:= ((T(C((9 - 1), 5)) \times T(T(3))) + 3) \\ 33523 &:= (C((T(T(3)) + 2), 5) - (T(3) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 33538 &:= (8! - ((C(T(T(3)), 5) - 3)/3)) \\ 33558 &:= ((T(C(8, 5)) + (5 - 3)) \times T(T(3))) \\ 33649 &:= ((9 \times C(4!, 6))/(T(3) \times T(3))) \\ 33664 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(6)) + (C(T(6), 3) - T(3))) \\ 33683 &:= (((C(T(T(3)), 8) - 6)/T(3)) - T(T(T(3)))) \\ 33689 &:= ((9 \times T(86)) + C(T(3), 3)) \\ 33768 &:= (8! - (-6) \times (C(T(7), 3)/(-3))) \\ 33831 &:= ((T((-1) + T(3)) + T(C(8, 3))) \times T(T(3))) \\ 33838 &:= ((T(8) \times T((T(3) + T(8)))) + C(T(T(3)), 3)) \\ 33839 &:= ((-9) \times (T(3))! + (8! - C(3, 3))) \\ 33858 &:= (8! - (C(T(5), 8) + ((3^3))) \\ 33869 &:= -((T(9) - ((C(T(6), 8) - T(3))/T(3)))) \\ 33885 &:= ((C(T(5), 8) - 8!) \times (-C(3, 3))) \\ 33888 &:= (8! - ((T(T(8)) + T(C(8, T(3)))) \times T(3))) \\ 33916 &:= ((C(T(6), -(1 - 9)) + T(3))/T(3)) \\ 33958 &:= ((8^5) - (T(C(9, 3))/(-3))) \\ 33979 &:= (9! - ((C(T(7), 9) + T(T(3)))/T(T(3)))) \\ 33999 &:= ((T(9) \times (9 \times C(9, 3))) - T(T(3))) \\ 34125 &:= (C(T(5), T(2)) \times ((1 + 4!) \times 3)) \\ 34248 &:= (8! + (C(4!, T((2 + 4))) \times (-3))) \\ 34254 &:= (((T(4))!/C(T(5), 2) - T(4!)) - T(3)) \\ 34285 &:= (-T(5) + (C(8, 2) \times T((T(T(4)) - T(3)))))) \\ 34296 &:= (((T(T(6)) - T(9))^2) - T((C(4, 3))!)) \\ 34314 &:= ((T(4!) + 1) \times (-T(3) - C(T(4), 3))) \\ 34332 &:= (((2^3))! - (C(T(T(3)), 4) + 3)) \\ 34338 &:= ((T((C(8, 3) - 3)) \times 4!) - T(3)) \\ 34344 &:= (4! \times T((T(C(4, 3)) + 43))) \\ 34348 &:= ((8! + T(4)) - (C(T(T(3)), 4) - 3)) \\ 34354 &:= ((4! \times T(53)) + T(C(4, 3))) \\ 34364 &:= ((T(T((4 + 6))) \times T(T(3))) + (C(4!, 3))) \\ 34368 &:= (8 \times ((6! \times T(3)) - (C(4, 3))!)) \\ 34369 &:= ((C((T(9) - T(6)), T(3))/4) + (T(3))!) \\ 34375 &:= ((5^{7-3}) \times T(T(C(4, 3)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34384 &:= ((T(T(4)) + 8!) - (C(T(T(3)), 4) + T(3))) \\ 34398 &:= (T((T(8) - 9)) \times T((3 + T(C(4, 3)))))) \\ 34408 &:= (((8 - 0!) + T(4)) \times C(4!, 3)) \\ 34424 &:= (((C(4!, T(T(2)))/4) + T(T(4))) + (T(3))!) \\ 34427 &:= (((T(C(7, T(2)))) - 4) \times T(T(4))) - 3) \\ 34445 &:= ((-T(5) - T(T(T(4)))) + (T(4!) \times C(T(4), 3))) \\ 34448 &:= (8 \times (C(T(4), 4) + (4^{T(3)}))) \\ 34485 &:= (((-T(5) + T(T(8))) - (4!)) \times T(T(C(4, 3)))) \\ 34515 &:= (T(5) \times (1 + C((T(5) + T(4)), 3))) \\ 34595 &:= (-C(T(5), 9) - ((-5!) \times T(T(4))) \times T(3)) \\ 34647 &:= ((T(C(7, 4)) \times T((6 + 4))) - 3) \\ 34654 &:= (((T(4) \times T(5)) \times T(T(6))) + C(4, 3)) \\ 34696 &:= (((6 + T(9)) \times 6!) - C(4!, 3)) \\ 34735 &:= ((C(T(5), T(3)) \times 7) - T((C(4, 3))!)) \\ 34744 &:= (((T(4!) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(7))) + (C(4, 3))!) \\ 34758 &:= ((T(T(8)) - ((C(T(5), 7) + 4!)) \times (-T(3))) \\ 34769 &:= (((C(9, 6) \times T(T(7))) - T(T(4))) + (T(3))!) \\ 34825 &:= -(((C(T(5), T(2)) - 8!) + ((4 + 3))!) \\ 34842 &:= (((-T(2) + T(T(4))) \times T(T(8))) + C(T(4), T(3))) \\ 34882 &:= (-2) + (T(8) \times C((-T(8) + T(T(4))), 3)) \\ 34885 &:= -(((C(T(5), 8) - 8!) - (T(4)^3))) \\ 34926 &:= ((T(C(6, 2)) \times (-9) + T(4!)) + T(3)) \\ 34937 &:= ((-7) + (T(3))!) \times (T(9) + C(4, 3)) \\ 34957 &:= ((7 \times C(T(5), 9)) - T((4 \times 3))) \\ 35028 &:= ((T((C(8, T(2)) + 0!)) + T(5)) \times T(T(3))) \\ 35032 &:= -((T(2) - ((T(3) + 0!) \times C(T(5), T(3)))))) \\ 35035 &:= (C(T(5), T(3)) \times (((0 \times 5))! + T(3))) \\ 35042 &:= ((T(2) + 4) \times (0! + C(T(5), T(3)))) \\ 35046 &:= ((T(T(6)) + T(4!)) \times T((0! + C(5, 3)))) \\ 35077 &:= (-7) \times ((-7) + 0!) - C(T(5), T(3)) \\ 35078 &:= (T(8) + (7 \times (0! + C(T(5), T(3)))))) \\ 35083 &:= -((T(T(T(3))) - ((8! - 0!) - C(T(5), T(3)))))) \\ 35112 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) + 1) \times T((1 + T(C(5, 3)))))) \\ 35195 &:= -(((5! - ((9 - 1))!) + C(T(5), T(3))) \\ 35266 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((T(6)/T(2)) \times C(T(5), T(3)))) \\ 35294 &:= (-4) - (T(C(9, 2)) \times (-53)) \\ 35308 &:= (((8! - 0!) - T(3)) - C(T(5), T(3))) \\ 35309 &:= (((9 - 0))! - (T(3) + C(T(5), T(3)))) \\ 35315 &:= (((C(5, 1) + 3))! - C(T(5), T(3))) \\ 35318 &:= ((8! + (1 \times 3)) - C(T(5), T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35324 &:= (-C(4!, T(T(2))) - ((T(T(T(3))) + 5) \times (-T(3)!))) \\ 35352 &:= ((2^{T(5)} + (C(T(T(3)), T(5))/T(T(3)))) \\ 35377 &:= ((7 \times (7! + T(3))) + T(C(5, 3))) \\ 35384 &:= (((T(4!) + 8!) - T(T(T(3)))) - (C(T(5), T(3)))) \\ 35398 &:= ((T((8 + 9)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(C(5, 3))) \\ 35415 &:= (-5) \times (1 - (C(4!, 5)/T(3))) \\ 35435 &:= (-5) \times (-3 - (C(4!, 5)/T(3))) \\ 35455 &:= ((-5!) \times (5 - T(4!))) + T(C(5, 3)) \\ 35456 &:= (((C(T(6), T(5)) \times T(4))/T(5)) - (T(3)!)) \\ 35468 &:= ((8! + T((T(6) - (4)))) - (C(T(5), T(3)))) \\ 35475 &:= ((T(5) + T(C(7, 4))) \times T(C(5, 3))) \\ 35485 &:= (-5) + (T((8 + 4)) \times C(T(5), 3)) \\ 35495 &:= (((T(5) \times 9) \times T(4!)) - (C(T(5), T(3)))) \\ 35542 &:= (-T(2)) + ((T(4!) \times 5!) - (C(T(5), 3))) \\ 35545 &:= ((5! \times T(4!)) - C(T(5), T((5 - 3)))) \\ 35694 &:= ((T(4) \times T(C(9, C(6, 5)))) - T(3)) \\ 35695 &:= (-5) + (T(C(9, 6)) \times C(5, 3)) \\ 35727 &:= ((-T(7)) + (T(T(2)))!) + (7 \times C(T(5), T(3))) \\ 35735 &:= ((C(T(5), 3) - 7!) + ((5 + 3)!)) \\ 35738 &:= (((8! + 3) - 7!) + C(T(5), 3)) \\ 35794 &:= (T(4) + ((9! - 7!)/C(5, 3))) \\ 35825 &:= ((C(T(5), T(2)) + 8!) - T((5! - T(T(3)))) \\ 35846 &:= ((T(T(6)) + T(4!)) + (8! - C(T(5), T(3)))) \\ 35876 &:= (T((T(T(6))/7)) + (8! - C(T(5), T(3)))) \\ 35904 &:= (-4!) \times (-((0! - T(9))) - T(T(C(5, 3)))) \\ 35919 &:= (T(T(9)) + (C(19, 5) \times 3)) \\ 35945 &:= (((5! + 4) - T(9)) \times C(T(5), 3)) \\ 35946 &:= (((C(T(6), 4) - 9) + T(5)) \times T(3)) \\ 35954 &:= ((T(4!) \times 5!) - (-9 + T(C(5, 3)))) \\ 35999 &:= (-C(9, 9)) + ((T(9) + 5) \times (T(3)!)) \\ 36036 &:= (T(6) \times C(((T(3) + 0!) + (6)), T(3))) \\ 36081 &:= (T(18) \times (0! + T(C(6, 3)))) \\ 36197 &:= (-T(7)) + (T(T(9)) \times C((1 + 6), 3)) \\ 36204 &:= -(((T(4!) - C(((0! + T(2)))!, T(6))) \times T(T(3)))) \\ 36253 &:= (((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \times (-2)) - T(T(6)))/(-3)) \\ 36287 &:= ((T(7) \times (T(8)^2)) - C(6, T(3))) \\ 36289 &:= ((9!/(8 + 2)) + C(6, T(3))) \\ 36324 &:= ((C(4!, T(2)) - T(3)) \times (6 \times 3)) \\ 36328 &:= ((8! - 2) - (3 \times C(T(6), 3))) \\ 36337 &:= ((T(7) \times C(T(T(3)), 3)) - T((T(6) + T(T(3)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36423 &:= (-3) \times (T(2) - (C(4!, T(6)) \times T(3))) \\ 36426 &:= (((T(6) - T(2)) \times C(4!, T(6))) - T(3)) \\ 36429 &:= ((9 \times 2) \times C(4!, T(6))) - 3 \\ 36431 &:= (-1) + (3 \times (C(4!, T(6)) \times T(3))) \\ 36432 &:= ((T(2) \times T(3)) \times C((4 \times 6), 3)) \\ 36433 &:= (C(3, 3) - (((4!)! / (T(6))!) \times (-3))) \\ 36435 &:= (((T(5) + 3) \times C(4!, T(6))) + 3) \\ 36444 &:= (((-4!) - T(4!)) \times T(T(4))) + (C(T(6), T(3))) \\ 36453 &:= (((3 + T(5)) \times C(4!, T(6))) + T(T(3))) \\ 36468 &:= (T(8) + (-6) \times (C(4!, T(6)) \times (-3))) \\ 36494 &:= (-4) + ((9! / T(4)) + T(C(6, 3))) \\ 36498 &:= (((8! \times 9) / T(4)) + T(C(6, 3))) \\ 36573 &:= (-((3^7)) + C((5! / 6), T(3))) \\ 36575 &:= (5 \times C((7 + T(5)), (6 \times 3))) \\ 36595 &:= (-5) + (T((T(9) + T(5))) \times C(6, 3)) \\ 36642 &:= (((T(2) \times (4!)! / (T(6))!) + (T(C(6, 3)))) \\ 36652 &:= -((T((2 + 5)) \times (T(6) - C(T(6), 3))) \\ 36669 &:= ((T(9) + (6)) \times (6! - C(6, T(3)))) \\ 36673 &:= (T(T(3)) - ((T(7) \times (T(6) - C(T(6), 3)))) \\ 36728 &:= -(((8^{T(2)}) - (T(7) \times C(T(6), 3))) \\ 36764 &:= (-C(4!, 6) - ((-7) - T(T(6))) \times (T(3)!)) \\ 36774 &:= (4! + (7 \times (7! + T(C(6, 3)))) \\ 36835 &:= ((-T(5)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + ((8! - C(6, 3))) \\ 36856 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (-T(5))) + (8! + C(6, T(3)))) \\ 36939 &:= ((-9!) / T(T(3))) - ((T(9) - C(T(6), T(3)))) \\ 36947 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T((4 + 9))) + C(6, T(3))) \\ 36979 &:= (-9) + (T(7) \times (-9) + C(T(6), 3)) \\ 36988 &:= ((-8) + T(8)) \times (-9) + C(T(6), 3) \\ 36998 &:= ((8! - T((9 \times 9))) - C(6, T(3))) \\ 36999 &:= ((9! / 9) - T((C(9, 6) - 3))) \\ 37038 &:= ((8! - T(3)) - C(T(07), 3)) \\ 37048 &:= ((8! + (4)) - C(T(07), 3)) \\ 37058 &:= (((8! + T(5)) - 0!) - C(T(7), 3)) \\ 37089 &:= ((T(9) + 8!) - C(T(07), 3)) \\ 37122 &:= (T(2) \times (-2) + C(17, T(3))) \\ 37124 &:= (-4) + (T(2) \times C(17, T(3))) \\ 37128 &:= (C(8, 2) \times T((17 \times 3))) \\ 37222 &:= (T(2) - ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) \times (-T(7))) + (T(T(3)))) \\ 37227 &:= (-7) - ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) \times (-T(7))) + T(3)) \\ 37232 &:= (-2) - ((C(T(T(3))), T(2)) \times (-T(7))) + T(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 37234 &:= ((C((4! - 3), T(2)) \times T(7)) - T(3)) \\ 37235 &:= (-5) + (C(T(T(3)), T(2)) \times T(C(7, T(3)))) \\ 37237 &:= ((C((7 \times 3), T(2)) \times T(7)) - 3) \\ 37243 &:= ((C((-3) + 4!), T(2)) \times T(7)) + 3) \\ 37244 &:= ((4! - T(T(T(4)))) - (C(T(T(T(2))), 7) / (-3))) \\ 37246 &:= ((C(T(6), T((4 - 2))) \times T(7)) + T(3)) \\ 37261 &:= ((C(T((1 \times 6)), T(2)) \times T(7)) + T(T(3))) \\ 37264 &:= (-4) \times ((C(T(6), T(2)) \times (-7)) - T(3)) \\ 37296 &:= (((6 \times T(C(9, 2))) \times T(7)) / 3) \\ 37298 &:= ((T(8) \times T(T(9))) + (T(2) + C(7, 3))) \\ 37366 &:= ((T(T(6)) - C(T(6), 3)) \times (-T(7) + T(3))) \\ 37385 &:= ((C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)) - T((T(7) + T(T(3)))))) \\ 37453 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), 5) + (4^7)) + (T(3))!) \\ 37454 &:= (((C(4!, 5) - (4)) - 7!) - T(3)) \\ 37457 &:= ((T(7) \times (C(T(5), 4) - T(7))) + T(T(3))) \\ 37468 &:= ((8! + (6! \times (-4))) + T(C(7, T(3)))) \\ 37478 &:= (8! - (T((7 \times 4)) \times C(7, T(3)))) \\ 37479 &:= ((T((T(9) - 7)) \times T(T(4))) - (C(T(7), 3))) \\ 37554 &:= (C(4!, 5) - T((5! - ((7 \times 3)))))) \\ 37575 &:= (((T(5) \times T(T(7))) + (C(T(5), 7))) \times 3) \\ 37632 &:= (((2^{T(3)}) \times T(6)) \times T(C(7, T(3)))) \\ 37635 &:= (((T(5)^3) - C(T(6), 7)) / (-3)) \\ 37644 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (4! + 6!)) - (C(T(7), 3))) \\ 37647 &:= (-T(7) + (T(T(4)) \times (6! - C(7, 3)))) \\ 37697 &:= ((-T(7) - T(T(9))) - (C(T(6), 7) / (-3))) \\ 37736 &:= ((C(T(6), 3) \times T(7)) + T((T(7) + 3))) \\ 37744 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times 4!) + (T(7))) \times T(C(7, T(3)))) \\ 37752 &:= (C((-2) + T(5), 7) \times (T(7) - T(3))) \\ 37789 &:= ((T(9) + C(8, 7)) \times (-7) + (T(3))!) \\ 37807 &:= (-((T(70) - 8!)) - T(C(7, T(3)))) \\ 37835 &:= (((5 + 3))! - T(C(8, (7 - 3)))) \\ 37836 &:= (((6! \times T(3)) \times 8) + C(T(7), 3)) \\ 37838 &:= ((8! + 3) - T(C(8, (7 - 3)))) \\ 37848 &:= -((((T(C(8, 4)) - 8!) - 7) - T(3))) \\ 37857 &:= -((T((7!/5!)) - (C((-8) + T(7)), T(3)))) \\ 37908 &:= (T(8) \times (T((0! + T(9))) - T(C(7, T(3)))))) \\ 37968 &:= (((T(8) + T(6)) \times T(C(9, 7))) + T(3)) \\ 37995 &:= (T(5) + ((T(T(9)) \times C(9, 7)) + (T(3))!)) \\ 38213 &:= (((T(3))! + 1) \times (-T(2) - (C(8, 3)))) \\ 38232 &:= (((-2) + T(3))! \times (-T(2) - T(C(8, 3)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38235 &:= (-(((C(T(5),3) \times T(2)) - 8!)) - (T(3))!) \\ 38264 &:= (-T((T(4) + T(6)))) + C(((T(T(2)))!/T(8)), T(3)) \\ 38265 &:= ((-5) - (C(T(6), T(2)) - 8!)) - (T(3))! \\ 38288 &:= ((-8) + 8!) - C((T(2) \times 8), 3) \\ 38289 &:= -((((T(C(9,8))^2) - 8!) + T(3))) \\ 38293 &:= -((C(-((T(T(3)) - T(9))), T(2)) - ((8! - 3)))) \\ 38298 &:= (8! - ((T(C(9,2)) + 8) \times 3)) \\ 38302 &:= (-2) + (((0! + 3))! \times T(C(8,3))) \\ 38304 &:= (4! \times T(C(((0 \times 3) + 8), 3))) \\ 38314 &:= (T(4) + (((1 + 3))! \times T(C(8,3)))) \\ 38328 &:= (8 \times (T(2) + (3 \times T(C(8,3)))))) \\ 38338 &:= ((-8) + C(T(T(3)), 3)) \times (8 + T(T(3))) \\ 38344 &:= (4 \times (T(4) + (T(3) \times T(C(8,3)))))) \\ 38346 &:= ((T(6) - T(C(4,3))) \times T(83)) \\ 38349 &:= (T(9) - ((-4) \times T(3)) \times T(C(8,3))) \\ 38354 &:= (C((4 \times 5), T(3)) - T(C(8, T(3)))) \\ 38374 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times (-C(7,3))) + 8!) - T(T(3))) \\ 38409 &:= -((T(90) - C(4!, (8 - 3)))) \\ 38424 &:= (C(T(4), T(2)) + (4! \times T(C(8,3)))) \\ 38439 &:= ((T(9) \times 3) + (4! \times T(C(8,3)))) \\ 38444 &:= (((4! - T(4))^4) + C(8, T(3))) \\ 38479 &:= ((-C((9 + 7), 4) + 8!) - T(T(3))) \\ 38485 &:= ((-5) + 8!) - T((4 + C(8,3))) \\ 38486 &:= ((T(6) \times T((T(8) + 4!))) + C(8, 3)) \\ 38493 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times 9) + ((4! \times T(C(8,3)))))) \\ 38494 &:= (T((T(4) + 9)) + ((4! \times T(C(8,3)))))) \\ 38505 &:= -((T((T(5) - 0!)) - ((C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)))))) \\ 38519 &:= (-91) + (C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)) \\ 38529 &:= (-((9^2)) + (C(T(5), 8) \times T(3))) \\ 38532 &:= -((T((2 \times T(3))) - ((C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)))))) \\ 38533 &:= ((T(T(T(3)))/(-3)) + ((C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)))) \\ 38537 &:= (-73) + (C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)) \\ 38544 &:= (-4!) \times (-((T(4) \times 5!) - T(C(8, T(3)))))) \\ 38545 &:= (-5) - ((T(4) - C(T(5), 8)) \times T(3)) \\ 38546 &:= (-64) + (C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)) \\ 38555 &:= (-55) + (C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)) \\ 38556 &:= (T(6) \times ((5! + 5!) + T(C(8,3)))) \\ 38564 &:= (-46) + (C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)) \\ 38565 &:= ((T(5) - C((T(6) - 5), 8)) \times (-3)) \\ 38567 &:= (-7) + (6 \times (C(T(5), 8) - T(3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38568 &:= -(((T(8) + (6)) - (C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)))) \\ 38573 &:= (-37) + (C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)) \\ 38574 &:= (T(-(4 - 7))) \times (C(T(5), 8) - T(3)) \\ 38575 &:= -((5 \times 7)) + (C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)) \\ 38576 &:= ((-6) - T(7)) + (C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)) \\ 38582 &:= (-28) + (C(T(5), 8) \times 3!) \\ 38584 &:= ((T(4) - T(8)) + (C(T(5), 8) \times T(3))) \\ 38588 &:= ((8! - T((T(8) + T(5)))) - T(C(8, T(3)))) \\ 38591 &:= (-19) + (C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)) \\ 38592 &:= -((2 \times 9)) + (C(T(5), 8) \times T(3)) \\ 38598 &:= ((8! - (C(9, 5))) - T(C(8, 3))) \\ 38605 &:= (-5) + (C(T(-(0! - (6))), 8) \times T(3)) \\ 38624 &:= -((T((4^2)) - C((6!/T(8)), T(3))) \\ 38635 &:= -((5^3)) + C((6!/T(8)), T(3)) \\ 38644 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (-T(4) - 6!)) - T(C(8, T(3)))) \\ 38648 &:= -((C((-8) + 4!), 6) - (T(8)^3)) \\ 38655 &:= ((T(5) - 5!) + C((6!/T(8)), T(3))) \\ 38658 &:= ((8! - T((5 + 6))) - T(C(8, 3))) \\ 38668 &:= ((8! + C(6, 6)) - T((T(8) + T(T(3)))))) \\ 38697 &:= -((7 \times 9)) + C((6!/T(8)), T(3)) \\ 38703 &:= -(((T(T(3)) - ((0! + (7)))!) + T(C(8, 3)))) \\ 38705 &:= -((T(T((5 - 0!))) - (C((T(7) - 8), T(3)))))) \\ 38714 &:= -(((T(4) - ((1 + 7)))! + T(C(8, 3)))) \\ 38717 &:= ((-7) + ((1 + 7)))! - T(C(8, 3)) \\ 38718 &:= ((8! + ((1 - 7))) - T(C(8, 3))) \\ 38724 &:= ((C((4 \times 2), 7))! - T(C(8, 3))) \\ 38728 &:= (((8! - T(2)) + (7)) - T(C(8, 3))) \\ 38733 &:= -((3^3)) + C((T(7) - 8), T(3)) \\ 38738 &:= ((8! + T(T(3))) + (-7) - T(C(8, 3))) \\ 38739 &:= -((T((9 - 3)) - C((T(7) - 8), T(3)))) \\ 38742 &:= (T(T(2)) - ((4! - C((T(7) - 8), T(3)))))) \\ 38743 &:= -((T(T(3)) - (4 + C((T(7) - 8), T(3)))))) \\ 38744 &:= -((4 \times 4)) + C((T(7) - 8), T(3)) \\ 38745 &:= ((-5) - T(4)) + C((T(7) - 8), T(3)) \\ 38748 &:= (((8! - (4)) + T(7)) - T(C(8, 3))) \\ 38752 &:= -(((T(2) + (5)) - C((T(7) - 8), T(3)))) \\ 38754 &:= ((4! + C(T(5), 7)) \times (T(8)/T(3))) \\ 38755 &:= (-5) + C(((5 + 7) + 8), T(3)) \\ 38757 &:= -((T((7 - 5)) - C((T(7) - 8), T(3)))) \\ 38758 &:= (((-C(8, 5)) \times T(7)) + 8!) + T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38773 &:= ((T(3) + (7)) + C((T(7) - 8), T(3))) \\ 38775 &:= (T(5) + C(((T(7) + T(7)) - T(8)), T(3))) \\ 38779 &:= ((-9) + T(7)) + C((T(7) - 8), T(3)) \\ 38784 &:= (4! \times ((-8) + T(7)) + T(C(8,3))) \\ 38788 &:= (((8! + T(8)) + T(7)) - T(C(8,3))) \\ 38797 &:= ((T(7) + 9) + C((T(7) - 8), T(3))) \\ 38824 &:= (((T(4)^2) + 8!) - T(C(8,3))) \\ 38826 &:= ((C(C(6,2), 8) + T(8)) \times T(3)) \\ 38836 &:= (((T(T(6)) \times T(T(3))) \times 8) + C(8, T(3))) \\ 38844 &:= ((T((4! \times 4)) \times 8) + T(C(8,3))) \\ 38854 &:= (((T(4) + 5!) + 8!) - T(C(8,3))) \\ 38859 &:= (((9 \times T(5)) + 8!) - T(C(8,3))) \\ 38864 &:= (((T(4) + 6!) - T(8)) \times C(8, 3)) \\ 38865 &:= (((5! + T(6)) + 8!) - T(C(8,3))) \\ 38879 &:= -(((T(T(9)) + T(T(7))) - ((T(8) - C(8, T(3))))!)) \\ 38907 &:= ((T(7) - 0!) \times (T(T(9)) + T(C(8, T(3)))) \\ 38922 &:= ((T((C(2,2) + T(9))) \times T(8)) + T(3)) \\ 38934 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (T(3))!) - T(C(9, (8 - T(3)))) \\ 38936 &:= (((6! \times T(3)) \times 9) + (C(8,3))) \\ 38938 &:= ((8! - T((T(3) + T(9)))) - C(8, 3)) \\ 38948 &:= (8! - (49 \times C(8, T(3)))) \\ 38976 &:= ((6 \times (7 + 9)) \times T(C(8, T(3)))) \\ 38993 &:= -((C(T(T(3)), (9 + 9)) - ((8! + 3))) \\ 38996 &:= -(((C(T(6), (9 + 9)) - 8!) - T(3)) \\ 39268 &:= (((8! - C(6, T(2))) - T(T(9))) + 3) \\ 39285 &:= (T(5) + ((8 + T(2)) \times T(C(9, 3)))) \\ 39292 &:= ((2 + 9) \times (2 + T(C(9, 3)))) \\ 39294 &:= (4! - (-((9 + 2)) \times T(C(9, 3)))) \\ 39327 &:= (((C(7, T(2)) + 3) \times T(T(9))) - 3) \\ 39335 &:= (C(T(5), 3) - ((T(3))! \times (-9) \times T(3))) \\ 39336 &:= ((T(T(6))/T(T(3))) \times (T(3) + T(C(9, 3)))) \\ 39368 &:= (8! - (C(T(6), 3) - T((9 \times 3)))) \\ 39384 &:= (4 \times ((T(C(8, 3)) + T(9)) \times T(3))) \\ 39388 &:= ((-8) + 8!) - C((3 + 9), T(3)) \\ 39454 &:= ((C(4!, 5) + T(T(4))) - (T(T(9)) \times 3)) \\ 39461 &:= (((-1) + 6!) \times T(T(4))) - (C(9, 3)) \\ 39516 &:= ((6! \times T(T(-(1 - 5)))) - C(9, 3)) \\ 39564 &:= ((-4) \times C(T(6), 5)) - (9!/(-3)) \\ 39654 &:= ((C(4!, 5) + 6!) - T(C(9, 3))) \\ 39678 &:= (((C(8, 7))! - 6!) + T((9 + 3))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39684 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times ((T(8)/6)!) + (C(9,3))) \\ 39688 &:= (((8! + T(C(8,6))) - T(T(9))) - 3) \\ 39738 &:= ((8! + T(3)) - ((7 \times C(9,3)))) \\ 39744 &:= (4! \times (C(4!, -(7-9)) \times T(3))) \\ 39745 &:= (-T(5) + (T(4) \times (T(T(7)) + (T(C(9,3)))))) \\ 39795 &:= (((5 \times T(T(9))) \times 7) + (T(C(9,3)))) \\ 39827 &:= -((T(T(7)) + (((T(2) - 8!) + (C(9,3)))))) \\ 39835 &:= (-(((C(T(5),3) - 8!) + 9) - T(T(3)))) \\ 39836 &:= ((C(6,3) + 8!) + (-9!/(T(3)!)) \\ 39886 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times (-C(8,8) - T(T(9))))/(-T(3))) \\ 40355 &:= (((5!/T(5)))! + C((T(3) + 0!),4)) \\ 40424 &:= -((T((4^{T(2)})) - C(4!, (0! + (4)))))) \\ 40425 &:= (C(T(5),2) + ((4 + 04)!)) \\ 40446 &:= ((T(6) + T(4!)) \times C((T(4) - 0!),4)) \\ 40548 &:= (8! + (C(T(4),5) - (04)!)) \\ 40682 &:= (2 \times (-8) + C(T(6), (0! + (4)))) \\ 40954 &:= (((C(4!,5) - 9) - 0!) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 40956 &:= (C(6,5) + (T(90) \times T(4))) \\ 41454 &:= (C(4!,5) - (T(4) \times T(14))) \\ 41469 &:= -((T(T(9)) - C((6 \times 4), (1 + 4)))) \\ 41497 &:= ((T(7) - T(T(9))) + (C(4!, (1 + 4)))) \\ 41525 &:= ((C(T(5),T(2)) + T(((5-1)!)) \times T(T(4))) \\ 41568 &:= ((T(C(8,6)) + T(51)) \times 4!) \\ 41586 &:= ((T(T(6)) + 8!) + T(T((C(5,1) + 4)))) \\ 41678 &:= ((8! + T(7)) + C(T(6), -((1-4)))) \\ 41682 &:= -(((T(2) - 8!) - C(T((6-1),4))) \\ 41775 &:= -((5! - (7 \times C(T((7-1),4)))) \\ 41835 &:= (T(T(C(5,3))) + (((8! - 1) - 4!)) \\ 41954 &:= (C(4!,5) - (T((9+1)) \times T(4))) \\ 42154 &:= ((C(4!,5) + 1) - T((2+4!))) \\ 42175 &:= ((5! \times C((T(7)-1),2)) + T(T(4))) \\ 42204 &:= (C(4!, (0! + (2+2))) - T(4!)) \\ 42249 &:= ((T(9) + C(4!, (2+T(2)))) - T(4!)) \\ 42254 &:= ((C(4!,5) + T(2)) - T((-2+4!))) \\ 42264 &:= (4! \times (C((T(6)+2), T(2)) - T(4))) \\ 42334 &:= ((C(4!,3) + ((T(3)+2)!) - T(4)) \\ 42335 &:= ((T(5) \times C((3^3), T(2))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 42368 &:= (8! + (C((T(6)+3), T(2)) + 4!)) \\ 42384 &:= ((T(T(4)) + (T((C(8,3)+2)))) \times 4!) \\ 42396 &:= (-6) \times (-((C(9,3)^2) - T(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42421 &:= ((1 - (T(T(2))))!) \times (- (C(4, T(2))) - T(T(4)))) \\ 42422 &:= (2 + (T(T(T(2))) \times (C(4!, T(2)) - (4)))) \\ 42423 &:= (3 + (T(T(T(2))) \times (C(4!, T(2)) - (4)))) \\ 42433 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times (- (T(3) - C(4!, T(2)))) + T(T(4))) \\ 42435 &:= (T((T(5) \times 3)) \times (C(T(4), 2) - (4))) \\ 42436 &:= ((T(C(6, 3)) - (4))^{-2+4}) \\ 42443 &:= (-((T(3) - C(4!, (T(4)/2)))) - T(T(4))) \\ 42444 &:= ((C(4!, 4) - T((T(4)/2))) \times 4) \\ 42448 &:= (((-8) + C(4!, 4)) - T(T(2))) \times 4) \\ 42449 &:= -((T(9) - (C(4!, (T(4)/2)) - T(4))) \\ 42465 &:= -((T(5) - ((T(6) \times C(4!, T(2))) - 4!)) \\ 42469 &:= -((T(9) - ((T(6) \times C(4!, T(2))) + T(4))) \\ 42494 &:= (C(4!, (T((9 - 4))/T(2))) - T(4)) \\ 42495 &:= ((T(59) \times 4!) + C(T(T(2)), 4)) \\ 42496 &:= ((C(-((T(6) - T(9))), 4) - 2) \times 4) \\ 42502 &:= (C(((T(2) + 0!))!, 5) + ((2 - 4))) \\ 42503 &:= (C(((3 + 0!))!, 5) + ((T(2) - (4)))) \\ 42505 &:= (C(((5 - 0!))!, 5) - ((T(2) - (4)))) \\ 42512 &:= (C(((T(2) + 1))!, 5) + (2 \times 4)) \\ 42514 &:= (C(4!, (-1) + T((5 - 2)))) + T(4)) \\ 42515 &:= ((C(((5 - 1))!, 5) + T(T(T(2)))) - T(4)) \\ 42521 &:= ((C(((1 + T(2))!), 5) + T(T(T(2)))) - 4) \\ 42522 &:= ((C(((2 + 2))!), 5) - T(T(2))) + (4!)) \\ 42531 &:= ((C(((1 + 3))!), 5) + T(2)) + 4! \\ 42532 &:= (C(((-2) + T(3))!), 5) + T((T(2) + (4)))) \\ 42534 &:= (C((C(4, 3))!, 5) + (T(2) \times T(4))) \\ 42554 &:= (C(4!, 5) + ((T(5)/T(2)) \times T(4))) \\ 42559 &:= (C(((9 - 5))!, (T(5)/T(2))) + T(T(4))) \\ 42564 &:= (C((4 \times 6), 5) + (T(T(2)) \times T(4))) \\ 42595 &:= (C((T(5) + 9), 5) + T((T(2) + T(4)))) \\ 42598 &:= (8! + T(((C(9, 5)/2) + 4))) \\ 42614 &:= (C(4!, -((1 - 6))) + (2 \times T(T(4)))) \\ 42644 &:= (T(4!) + (C(4!, T(6)) + ((2 \times 4)!)) \\ 42647 &:= (((7 + C(4!, T(6))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - 4) \\ 42648 &:= ((T(8) + C(4!, (6 - 2))) \times 4) \\ 42654 &:= (C(4!, 5) + (C(6, 2) \times T(4))) \\ 42685 &:= -(((5! - 8!) - T(C((6 + 2), 4))) \\ 42689 &:= (T(T(9)) + (8! + (C(T(6), T(2)) + (4)))) \\ 42693 &:= (- (T(T(3))) \times (- ((T(C(9, 6)) + T(2))) + T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 42696 &:= (- (6) \times ((T(C(9, 6)) \times (-2)) + 4!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}42699 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T(9)) - (C((T(6) - 2), 4))) \\42754 &:= (C(4!, 5) + ((T(7) - T(2)) \times T(4))) \\42756 &:= ((C(6, 5) \times T(T(7))) + ((2 \times 4)!)) \\42804 &:= (C(4!, (0! + (8/2))) + T(4!)) \\42812 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) + 1) \times (T(C(8, 2)) + T(T(T(4)))))) \\42822 &:= ((T(2)^{T(2)}) \times (T(C(8, T(2))) - T(4))) \\42826 &:= ((C(T(6), T(2)) + 8!) + T((2 \times 4!))) \\42867 &:= (-(T((T(7) - (6)))) + (C(8, 2) \times T(T(T(4)))))) \\42899 &:= (((-C(9, 9)) + T(8))^{T(2)} + 4!) \\42982 &:= ((-2) + 8!) + (T(C(9, 2)) \times 4) \\43054 &:= (C(4!, 5) + (T((0! + 3)) \times T(T(4)))) \\43144 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T((C(4, 1) + 3))) + (4!)) \\43169 &:= ((T(C(9, 6)) - 1) + ((T(3))! \times T(T(4)))) \\43214 &:= (C(4!, (-1) + T(T(2)))) + ((T(3))! - T(4)) \\43224 &:= (((C(T(4), T(2))^2) \times 3) + 4!) \\43245 &:= (((5! \times 4!) + T(2)) \times C(T(3), 4)) \\43277 &:= (T(T(7)) + ((C(7, T(2))^3) - (4))) \\43373 &:= ((T(T(3)) - T(T(7))) + C((3 \times T(3)), T(4))) \\43398 &:= ((-8) \times T(9)) + C((3 \times T(3)), T(4)) \\43404 &:= (C(4!, (0! + (4))) - (-3) \times T(4!)) \\43433 &:= (C((3 \times T(3)), T(4)) - T((T(T(3)) + 4))) \\43449 &:= ((-9) - T(4!)) + C((4! - T(3)), T(4)) \\43454 &:= ((C(4!, 5) + T(43)) + (4)) \\43527 &:= -((T(C(7, 2)) - C((T(5) + 3), T(4)))) \\43539 &:= (C((T(9) - T(T(3))), 5) + T((T(T(3)) + (4!)))) \\43542 &:= ((T(2) + C(4!, 5)) + T((T(T(3)) + (4!)))) \\43545 &:= (-(C((5 \times 4), 5)) + (3^{T(4)})) \\43548 &:= ((T(T(8)) + C(4!, 5)) + T((3 + 4!))) \\43549 &:= (T(T(9)) + ((C(4!, 5) + T(3)) + (4))) \\43554 &:= (C(4!, 5) + ((5 \times T(T(3))) \times T(4))) \\43569 &:= ((-9) \times T(6)) + C((T(5) + 3), T(4)) \\43629 &:= ((T(9) \times C((-2) + T(6)), 3) + 4!) \\43653 &:= ((T(T(3)) \times (-5)) + C((6 \times 3), T(4))) \\43667 &:= -((T((7 + 6)) - C((6 \times 3), T(4)))) \\43692 &:= -((T((2 + 9)) - C((6 \times 3), T(4)))) \\43694 &:= -((T(T(4)) - (-9) + C((6 \times 3), T(4)))) \\43725 &:= (T(5) \times (C(27, 3) - T(4))) \\43734 &:= (C((4! - T(3)), (7 + 3)) - 4!) \\43746 &:= (-6) \times (4! - C((T(7) - T(3)), 4)) \\43748 &:= (C((8 + T(4)), (7 + 3)) - T(4))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}43749 &:= (-9) + C((-((4-7)) \times T(3)), T(4)) \\43754 &:= (-4) + C(((5+7) + T(3)), T(4)) \\43774 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(7)) + (T(C(7,3)) + 4!)) \\43785 &:= (((-5) \times 8!) + C(T(7), T(3)))/4 \\43825 &:= ((-T(5)) + (T(T(2)))!) + (C(8, T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\43829 &:= ((T(C(9, T(2)))) + ((8! - T(3)))) - T(T(4)) \\43834 &:= ((C((4! - T(3)), 8) + T(T(3))) + T(T(4))) \\43836 &:= (C((6 \times 3), 8) + T((3 \times 4))) \\43838 &:= (((T(8) \times 3) \times T(C(8, T(3)))) - T(4)) \\43864 &:= ((4! + 6!) + (C(8, T(3)) \times T(T(T(4)))) \\43869 &:= (((T(C(9, 6)) + 8!) + 3) - 4!) \\43875 &:= (((-5) \times (T(7)))!)/(-C(8, 3))/ (4!)! \\43935 &:= (T(5) \times (C((3 \times 9), 3) + 4)) \\43956 &:= (T((6 + 5)) \times T(C(9, (3 + 4)))) \\43965 &:= (T(5) \times (6 + C((9 \times 3), 4!))) \\44034 &:= ((C(4!, (T(3) - 0!)) - T(4)) + T(T(T(4)))) \\44042 &:= ((-2) + C(4!, (0! + (4)))) + T(T(T(4))) \\44058 &:= (C((8 + T((5 - 0!))), T(4)) + T(4!)) \\44135 &:= (C(T(5), 3) \times (1 - (4! \times (-4)))) \\44142 &:= ((T(T(T(2))) \times T((T(T(4)) + 1))) + (C(4!, 4))) \\44175 &:= ((T(5) \times C((T(7) - 1), 4!)) + T(4!)) \\44235 &:= (T(5) \times (C((3^{T(2)}), 4!) + 4!)) \\44236 &:= ((T(C(6, 3))^2) + T((4 \times 4))) \\44254 &:= ((4 + C(T(5), 2)) \times T((4! + (4)))) \\44256 &:= ((6 + C(T(5), T(2))) \times (4! \times 4)) \\44265 &:= ((5 \times C((T(6) + 2), 4)) - T(4)) \\44266 &:= ((C(T(6), 6) + 2) - (T(4)^4)) \\44274 &:= (C(4!, (7 - 2)) + T((4 + T(T(4)))) \\44288 &:= (((T(T(8)) \times T(C(8, T(2)))) - (4!))/4!) \\44325 &:= (-5) \times (-C(23, 4) - T(4)) \\44349 &:= -((T(T(9)) - (4 \times ((T(3))! + C(4!, 4)))) \\44423 &:= ((T(3))! + (C(-((T(T(2)) - (4!))), T(4)) - (T(T(4)))) \\44424 &:= (C((4! - T(T(2))), T(4)) + T(T((4 + 4)))) \\44435 &:= (-T(5)) - ((C(T(T(3)), 4) - T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(4))) \\44484 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T(8)) - (C(4!, 4) \times (-4))) \\44499 &:= ((T(9) \times T((T(9) + (4)))) - C(4!, 4)) \\44533 &:= (((T(3))! + C((3 + T(5)), T(4))) + T(T(4))) \\44564 &:= (T(4!) + (C(T(6), T(5)) - (T(4)^4))) \\44575 &:= ((5 \times C((T(7) - (5)), 4)) + T(4!)) \\44685 &:= (T(5) \times (C((T(8) - T(6)), T(4)) - 4!))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}44687 &:= ((T(7) \times T((8!/6!))) - C(4,4)) \\44728 &:= ((T(C(8,T(2))) \times T(7)) - (-4) \times T(4)) \\44745 &:= ((T(5)^4) - (T(7) \times C(T(4),4))) \\44793 &:= (((T(3))! - 9) \times (T(C(7,4))/T(4))) \\44814 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T((1 \times 8))) - (C(4!,4))) \\44826 &:= ((6^{T(2)}) - T((C(8,4) - T(4)))) \\44832 &:= -((T(2) \times (T(3) - C((T(8) - T(4)),4))) \\44835 &:= -((T(5) - (3 \times C((T(8) - T(4)),4))) \\44836 &:= ((6^{T(3)}) - C((-8) + 4!),4)) \\44935 &:= (((C(T(5),T(3)) \times 9) - T(T(4))) - T(T(4))) \\44959 &:= ((9 \times (C(T(5),9) - T(4))) + (4)) \\45015 &:= (T(5) \times ((-1) - 0!) + C(T(5),T(4))) \\45035 &:= ((C(T(5), (T(3) - 0!)) \times T(5)) - T(4)) \\45042 &:= (-T(2) + (T((4 + 0!)) \times C(T(5),T(4)))) \\45045 &:= (C(T(5),T(4)) \times T(C(05,4))) \\45055 &:= ((C(T(5),5) \times T(05)) + T(4)) \\45066 &:= (T(6) + (T((6 - 0!)) \times C(T(5),T(4)))) \\45116 &:= ((6^{C(1,1)+5}) - T(T(T(4)))) \\45135 &:= (T(5) \times (T(3) + C(15,T(4)))) \\45165 &:= (5! + (T((6 - 1)) \times C(T(5),T(4)))) \\45195 &:= (T(5) \times ((9 + 1) + C(T(5),T(4)))) \\45224 &:= (C(4!,T(2)) - ((T(T(2)))! \times (T(5) \times (-4)))) \\45255 &:= (((C(T(5),5) - T(T(2))) \times T(5)) + T(4!)) \\45277 &:= (-((T(7) - (C(T(7),2) \times 5!)) - T(T(4))) \\45285 &:= (T(5) \times ((8 \times 2) + C(T(5),T(4)))) \\45291 &:= ((T(-((1 - 9)))^{T(2)}) - (C(T(5),4))) \\45298 &:= (T(T(T((T(8)/9)))) + C((T(2) + T(5)),T(4))) \\45325 &:= (C(T(5),T(T(2))) + ((3 + C(5,4)))!) \\45335 &:= ((C(T(5),T(3)) + ((3 + 5)!)) + T(4)) \\45375 &:= ((T(5) + 7!) + ((3 + C(5,4)))!) \\45378 &:= (((8! + 7!) + 3) + T(C(5,4))) \\45384 &:= (4! \times T((C(8,3) + C(5,4)))) \\45405 &:= (T(5) \times ((04)! + C(T(5),T(4)))) \\45434 &:= (T((T(T(4)) + T(T(3)))) + (C(4!,5) + (4))) \\45477 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (T(7) \times 4)) + C(5,4)) \\45525 &:= (T(5) \times ((2^5) + C(T(5),T(4)))) \\45529 &:= -T(T(9)) + C(T(T(T(2))),T(5)) - 5 \times T(T(T(4))) \\45544 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (C(4!,5) - (-5) \times T(4!))) \\45583 &:= (((T(3))! + (8! + C(T(5),5))) + T(T(T(4)))) \\45585 &:= (T(5) \times (T(8) + C(T(5),C(5,4))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}45612 &:= (T(2) \times (C((-1) + T(6)), 5) - T(4!)) \\45636 &:= (((6^{T(3)}) - (C(6, 5))!) - T(4!)) \\45696 &:= ((C(-(T(6) - T(9))), T(6)) - (5!)) \times 4! \\45836 &:= ((6^{T(3)}) - T((8 \times C(5, 4)))) \\45857 &:= (7 \times ((C(T(5), 8) + 5!) - (4))) \\45864 &:= ((4! \times T(6)) \times T((8 + C(5, 4)))) \\45895 &:= ((T((5 + T(9))) \times T(8)) - C(5, 4)) \\46026 &:= ((6^{T(T(2))}) - T(C((0! + (6)), 4))) \\46116 &:= (T(6) \times (T(T(11)) - C(6, 4))) \\46145 &:= (((C(5, 4))! - 1) + 6!) \times T(T(4)) \\46185 &:= (((5! - 8!) \times (-1)) + C(T(6), 4)) \\46212 &:= (-T(2) + (T(T(12)) \times C(6, 4))) \\46248 &:= ((8! - T(T(4))) - (2 - C(T(6), 4))) \\46284 &:= -(((4! - 8!) - T(2)) - C(T(6), 4)) \\46286 &:= -(((T(6) - 8!) - 2) - C(T(6), 4)) \\46298 &:= ((8! - (9 - 2)) + C(T(6), 4)) \\46305 &:= (((5 + 03))! + C(T(6), 4)) \\46308 &:= ((8! + 03) + C(T(6), 4)) \\46311 &:= ((T(T(11)) \times T(T(3))) - T(C(6, 4))) \\46318 &:= ((8! + 13) + C(T(6), 4)) \\46326 &:= ((T(6) + ((2^3))!) + C(T(6), 4)) \\46328 &:= ((8! + (23)) + C(T(6), 4)) \\46338 &:= ((8! + 33) + C(T(6), 4)) \\46348 &:= ((8! + 43) + C(T(6), 4)) \\46356 &:= ((C(6, 5)^{T(3)}) - T((6 \times 4))) \\46358 &:= ((8! + (53)) + C(T(6), 4)) \\46378 &:= ((8! + 73) + C(T(6), 4)) \\46388 &:= ((8! + (83)) + C(T(6), 4)) \\46398 &:= ((8! + (93)) + C(T(6), 4)) \\46416 &:= ((T(6) \times T(T((1 + T(4)))) - C(6, 4)) \\46421 &:= ((T(C(12, T(4))) \times T(6)) - T(4)) \\46425 &:= ((5! + ((2 \times 4))!) + C(T(6), 4)) \\46431 &:= (T(T((1 \times 3))) \times T(T(-(4 - C(6, 4)))))) \\46466 &:= ((6^6) - T((4 + C(6, 4)))) \\46485 &:= ((-(5! - 8!)) + T(4!)) + (C(T(6), 4)) \\46557 &:= (7 \times (T(T((5!/T(5)))) + (C(T(6), 4)))) \\46636 &:= ((6^{T(3)}) - C(6, T((6 - 4)))) \\46711 &:= (C(1, 1) - 7)^6 + T(T(4)) \\46722 &:= ((T(T(2))^{T(T(2))}) + T((C(7, 6) + 4)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 46758 &:= (8! + (C(T(5), 7) + T((6 - 4)))) \\ 46778 &:= ((C(8, 7))! - ((-T(7)) \times T(T(6))) + T(4)) \\ 46834 &:= ((C(T(4), T(3)) \times (-8) + T(T(6)))) + 4 \\ 46849 &:= ((T(9) \times (T(C(T(4), 8) + 6)) + 4) \\ 46875 &:= ((C(T(5), 7) + 8!) + T(C(6, 4))) \\ 46884 &:= ((T(4!) \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(8)))) - (C(T(6), T(4)))) \\ 46992 &:= ((T(2) + 9) \times T((C(9, 6) + 4))) \\ 47244 &:= ((C(4!, (T(4)/2)) + 7!) - T(4!)) \\ 47283 &:= (-3) + ((T(8)^{T(2)} + T(C(7, 4)))) \\ 47286 &:= ((6^{8-2}) + T(C(7, 4))) \\ 47319 &:= -((T(T((C(9, 1) + 3))) - (7! \times T(4)))) \\ 47436 &:= ((6^{T(3)} + T((4 + C(7, 4)))) \\ 47534 &:= ((C((C(4, 3))!, 5) + 7!) - T(4)) \\ 47625 &:= (C(T(5), 2) + (6! \times T((7 + 4)))) \\ 47635 &:= (((5 + 3))! + C((-6) + T(7), 4)) \\ 47638 &:= ((8! + 3) + C((-6) + T(7), 4)) \\ 47663 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), 6) - ((T(6) + 7!))) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 47725 &:= (((C(T(5), 2) \times T(T(7))) + (7!)) + T(T(4))) \\ 47844 &:= (C(4!, (T(T(4)) - T(8))) + (7! + T(4!))) \\ 47888 &:= (8! - (-8) \times T((8 + C(7, 4)))) \\ 47924 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) + (T((T(9) - T(7))) \times T(4!))) \\ 47928 &:= (((T(8) \times 2) \times T(C(9, 7))) - 4!) \\ 47942 &:= (((T(2) \times 4!) \times T(C(9, 7))) - T(4)) \\ 47948 &:= (C((8 + T(4)), 9) - (T(7) \times 4!)) \\ 47973 &:= (3 \times (7 + (T(C(9, 7)) \times 4!))) \\ 47985 &:= ((T((T(5) + T(8))) + T(9)) \times C(7, 4)) \\ 48075 &:= (T(5) \times (((7 - 0!))! + (T(C(8, 4)))))) \\ 48224 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) - ((T(T(2)) - T(8)) \times T(T(T(4)))))) \\ 48254 &:= (C(4!, 5) - (((T(T(2)))! \times (-8)) + T(4))) \\ 48264 &:= (((T(4) + C(T(6), T(2))) \times T(8)) + 4!) \\ 48324 &:= ((C((4^2), T(3)) + 8!) - (4)) \\ 48328 &:= (8! + C(((2^3) + 8), T(4))) \\ 48335 &:= (((C(T(5), 3) \times T(T(3))) + 8!) - T(T(T(4)))) \\ 48345 &:= ((T(5) + ((C(4, 3))! \times T(8))) \times T(T(4))) \\ 48352 &:= (C((T(T(T(2))) - 5), T(3)) + ((8! + 4!))) \\ 48365 &:= (((T(5) + C(T(6), 3)) \times T(8)) - T(T(4))) \\ 48366 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(C(6, 3))) - (T(8) \times 4)) \\ 48369 &:= (T(T(9)) + (-T(6)) \times (T(T(T(3))) - (T(C(8, 4)))))) \\ 48425 &:= (5 \times (((T(T(2)))! \times T(4)) + (T(C(8, 4)))))) \\ 48435 &:= (T(5) \times ((T(3))! + (4! + T(C(8, 4)))))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}48468 &:= ((8 \times (C(T(6),4) + T(8))) + T(4!)) \\48498 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times 9) + C(4!, (-T(8) + T(T(4)))))) \\48599 &:= (-C(9,9) - (-T(5)) \times T((8 \times T(4)))) \\48635 &:= (T(5) + C((3 \times 6), (T(8)/4))) \\48644 &:= (4! + C((4! - 6), (T(8)/4))) \\48724 &:= ((C(T(4), T(2)) \times T(T(7))) + (8 - 4)) \\48726 &:= ((T(C(6,2)) \times T(T(7))) + T(T((8/4)))) \\48746 &:= ((T(C(6,4)) \times T(T(7))) + (T(8) - T(4))) \\48825 &:= ((5^2) \times T(-((8 - C(8,4)))))) \\48846 &:= (((C(T(6),4) \times 8) + T(T(8))) + T(4!)) \\48856 &:= (C(T(6), T(5)) + (-8) \times (T(T(8)) + T(4))) \\48895 &:= ((C(T(5),9) + 8!) + T(84)) \\48925 &:= ((T(T(C(5,2))) + T(T(9))) \times (-T(8) + T(T(4)))) \\48928 &:= ((C((T(8)/2),9) + 8) + T(4!)) \\49022 &:= -(((T(T(2)))! - C((T(T(T(2))) + 0!),9)/T(4))) \\49225 &:= (-C(T(5), T(2)) + ((2 \times T(T(9))) \times 4!)) \\49227 &:= (-((7! - T(2))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T((9 - 4)))) \\49229 &:= (((T(C(9,2))^2)/9) - T(T(4))) \\49237 &:= (-7!) + (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) + (9 + 4)) \\49254 &:= (C(4!,5) - (((T(T(2)))! - T(9)) \times (-T(4)))) \\49255 &:= ((5! \times (C(T(5), T(2)) - T(9))) + T(T(4))) \\49275 &:= -((T(5) \times (C(T(7), T(2)) - 9^4))) \\49336 &:= (6! + (C((3 \times T(3)),9) - (4))) \\49337 &:= ((C(T(7), T(T(3))) + (3 + T(9)))/4!) \\49434 &:= ((C(T(4), T(3)) + (4)) \times T((T(9) - 4!))) \\49528 &:= (C(8,2) + ((5! + T(9)) \times T(4!))) \\49546 &:= -(((T(6) \times 4!) - (C(T(5),9) \times T(4)))) \\49595 &:= (-5) - ((T(9) - C(T(5),9)) \times T(4)) \\49625 &:= -((T(C(5,2)) - (6! \times (T(9) + 4!))) \\49648 &:= (-8) + ((C(4!, T(6)) + T(9)) \times 4!) \\49728 &:= ((C(8, T(2)) + T((7 \times 9))) \times 4!) \\49734 &:= ((T(C(4,3)) \times 7!) - T((9 \times 4))) \\49736 &:= (-6) + (C(-((T(3) - T(7))),9)/T(4)) \\49742 &:= (C((2 \times (4 + 7)),9)/T(4)) \\49763 &:= (T(T(3)) + (C((-6) + T(7)),9)/T(4)) \\49938 &:= (T(C(8, T(3))) \times (99 + 4!)) \\49955 &:= (-5) + ((C(T(5),9) - 9) \times T(4)) \\50225 &:= ((C(T(5), T(T(2))) + ((T(T(2)) + 0!)!)) \times 5) \\50268 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times (-6)) + C(T(T(T(2))), (0! + (5)))) \\50625 &:= (T(5)^{-2+C(6,05)})\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 51345 &:= ((T(5)^{C(4,3)}) + ((1 + 5)!)) \\ 51576 &:= ((T(6) \times 7!) - C(T((5 + 1)), T(5))) \\ 51636 &:= (C(T(6), T(3)) - T((6!/T(-((1 - 5)))))) \\ 51667 &:= ((T(T(C(7,6))) + (T(6))) \times (1 + 5!)) \\ 51723 &:= (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - (T(71) - T(5))) \\ 51876 &:= (6! - (T(T(7)) \times (-C((8 + 1), 5)))) \\ 51948 &:= (8! + C((T(4) + 9), (1 \times 5))) \\ 52004 &:= -T(T(T(4))) - T(T(0! + 0!))! + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52052 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) - 0!) - T(T((T(T(2)) + 5)))) \\ 52053 &:= (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T(T((0! + (2 \times 5)))) \\ 52054 &:= -(((T(T((-4) + T(5)))) - 0!) - C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))) \\ 52058 &:= -T(T(8)) - T(T(T(5 - 0!))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52164 &:= ((-4!) + T(T(6))) \times C(T((1 + T(2))), 5) \\ 52184 &:= -((T((T(T(4)) + (8 + 1))) - C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)))) \\ 52192 &:= ((-2) \times (T(T(9)) + 1)) + C(T((T(2))!), T(5)) \\ 52226 &:= (C(6, T(2)) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5)) \\ 52229 &:= ((T(9) - T((2^{T(T(2))}))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52239 &:= (-((T(9) \times T((3^2)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52253 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T((T(2) \times T(T(T(2)))))) + 5) \\ 52263 &:= (-T((3 \times T(6))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) + T(5))) \\ 52266 &:= (C(T(6), 6) - (T(2) \times T(T((T(2) + 5)))))) \\ 52268 &:= (-((T(T(8)) + (C(T(6), T(2)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))) \\ 52284 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (-T(8))) + C(T((2 \times T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52287 &:= (((-7) + T(T(8))) \times (-T(2))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52314 &:= ((T((4! + 1)) \times (-T(3))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52353 &:= (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - (T(T(3)) \times T((-2) + T(5)))) \\ 52364 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) - (C(T(6), T(3)) - (T(2) \times 5!))) \\ 52373 &:= (-T((T(3) + T((7 + 3)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52416 &:= ((6! \times C(14, T(2)))/5) \\ 52424 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) + (T(4) \times ((2 + 5)!)) \\ 52427 &:= -T(T(7)) - T(-2 + T(T(4))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52432 &:= ((-2) - T((T(3) \times T(4)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52433 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), T(3)) - T((T(T(4)) + T(2)))) - (5!)) \\ 52434 &:= -((T((T(4) \times T(3))) - C(T(C(4, 2)), T(5)))) \\ 52442 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times (-4) + T(T(C(4, 2)))) + 5) \\ 52444 &:= (-C((4 \times 4), 4) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52449 &:= (((-9) - 4!) \times T(T(4))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52464 &:= ((T(4!) \times (-6)) + C(T(C(4, 2)), T(5)) \\ 52509 &:= (-((T(T(9)) + ((0! + 5)!)) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52527 &:= -7 * T(T(T(T(2)))) - 5! + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 52539 &:= (((T(T(9)))/(-3)) \times 5) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52544 &:= -T(4!) - T(T(T(4))) + 5! + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52553 &:= -(T((3 + 55))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52604 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times (-0!)) + (C(T(6), T(T(2))) - (5!))) \\ 52624 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) \times (-6 - (2^5))) \\ 52629 &:= ((-T(T(9))) - (T(T(2)))!) + ((C(T(6), T(T(2))) + (5!))) \\ 52649 &:= ((T(9) - T(T(T(4)))) + (C(T(6), T(T(2))) - (5!))) \\ 52693 &:= (-(((T(T(3)) + 9!)/T(T(6)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52722 &:= ((-2) - T(T((T(2) + (7)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52724 &:= -(T((T(4) + T((2 + 7)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52726 &:= (((T(T(6))^2) - T(C(7, T(2)))) - 5) \\ 52727 &:= -((T(T(7)) - ((T(2) + C((T(7) - T(2)), 5)))) \\ 52736 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (T(C(7, T(2))) - 5)) \\ 52752 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) - (-T(7) + T(T((2 \times 5)))) \\ 52758 &:= (-((T(T(8)) + (5! \times 7))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52786 &:= -(((T((6! - T(T(8)))) - 7) - C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))) \\ 52824 &:= ((4! + (T(T(2)))!) \times (C(8, T(2)) + T(5))) \\ 52833 &:= (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) - T(((T(8) + 2) + T(5)))) \\ 52834 &:= ((T(T(4)) - T(((T(3))! - T(T(8)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))) \\ 52844 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) - (C(T(T((4!/8))), T(T(2))) + (5!))) \\ 52863 &:= (((C(T(T(3)), 6) - T(T(8))) - (T(T(2)))!) - T(5)) \\ 52869 &:= (((-9) - 6!) - T(T(8))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52886 &:= (((-6!) - T(T(8))) + 8) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52904 &:= (-((T((4! + 0!)) + T(T(9)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52914 &:= -(((T(T(T(4))) - T(19)) - C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))) \\ 52933 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), T(3)) - T((T(9) + T(T(2)))) - 5) \\ 52934 &:= ((-4) - T((T(3) + T(9)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52946 &:= (((T(T(6)) - T(T(T(4)))) - 9) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52948 &:= (T((C(8, 4) - 9)) \times T((2 + 5))) \\ 52953 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T((T(9) + T(T(2)))) + T(5)) \\ 52954 &:= (((T(T(4)) \times (-5)) - T(T(9))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 52964 &:= -(((T(T(T(4))) - ((T(T(6)) + 9))) - C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))) \\ 52976 &:= (-((T((-6) + T(7))) + T(T(9))) + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) \\ 53024 &:= -(((T(T(T(4))) - T(((T(2) + 0!)!)) - (C(T(T(3)), T(5)))) \\ 53039 &:= -((T(((T(9) + 3) + 0!)) - C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \\ 53054 &:= (-((T(4) \times (5! + 0!))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\ 53109 &:= (-T(T(9))) + (C(T(T(T((0! + 1))))), T(3)) - (5!)) \\ 53115 &:= -((T(5) - C((1 + ((1 + 3)!), 5))) \\ 53145 &:= (T(5) + C((4! + (1^3)), 5)) \\ 53164 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (-T(6) - 1)) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53184 &:= ((4! \times T(T((C(8,1) + 3)))) + (5!)) \\ 53208 &:= (8 \times (0! - (C(T(T(T(2))),3) \times (-5)))) \\ 53209 &:= ((-((T(T(9)) - 0!)) - T(T(T(2)))) + (C(T(T(3)),T(5)))) \\ 53214 &:= -((T(T((T(4) - 1))) - (C(T(T(T(2))),T(3)) - T(5)))) \\ 53219 &:= -(((T(T(9)) + T((1 + T(2)))) - C(T(T(3)),T(5)))) \\ 53223 &:= ((C(T(T(3)),T(T(2))) - T(T(2))) - T((3 \times T(5)))) \\ 53224 &:= ((T((4^{T(2)})))/(-2) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))) \\ 53227 &:= -(((T(T((7 + 2))) + 2) - C(T(T(3)),T(5)))) \\ 53229 &:= (C(T((9 - T(2))),T(T(2))) - T((3 \times T(5)))) \\ 53232 &:= (T(2) + (C(T(T(3)),T(T(2))) - T((3 \times T(5)))))) \\ 53234 &:= ((T(4!) - C(T(T(3)),T(2))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))) \\ 53239 &:= -(((T(T(9)) - T((T(3) - 2))) - C(T(T(3)),T(5)))) \\ 53256 &:= (T(6) + (C(T(5),T(2)) \times (-3) + 5!)) \\ 53257 &:= ((T(7) - T((T(5) \times T(2)))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))) \\ 53259 &:= -(((T(T(9)) - (T(5) \times 2)) - C(T(T(3)),T(5)))) \\ 53264 &:= (-((T(4)^{6/2})) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))) \\ 53274 &:= (-4!) + (C(T(7),2) \times (T(T(3)) + 5!)) \\ 53294 &:= ((-4!) - T((T(9) - 2))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5)) \\ 53304 &:= (C(4!, -((0! - T(3)))) + ((T(3))! \times T(5))) \\ 53312 &:= -T(T(2))! - 1 - T(T(T(3))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5)) \\ 53313 &:= ((T(T(T(3))) \times (-1)) - (((T(3))! - C(T(T(3)),T(5)))))) \\ 53318 &:= -((T(((T(8) + 1) + T(3))) - C(T(T(3)),T(5)))) \\ 53319 &:= ((-T(9)) \times T(T((1 \times 3)))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5)) \\ 53326 &:= ((T(T(6))^2) - (C(T(3),3) + T(5))) \\ 53328 &:= (((-T(8)) \times T(T(2))) - (T(3))!) + C(T(T(3)),T(5)) \\ 53334 &:= ((-C(T(4),T(3))) - (T(3))!) + C(T(T(3)),T(5)) \\ 53336 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(3)))) - (C(T(3),3) + 5)) \\ 53354 &:= -(((T((4! - 5))) + (T(3))!) - C(T(T(3)),T(5))) \\ 53355 &:= (5! + (C(T(5),3) \times (-3) + 5!)) \\ 53358 &:= -(((T(T(8)) + 5!) - (C(T(T(3)),T(3)) - 5!)) \\ 53364 &:= ((T((4 \times 6)) \times (-3)) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))) \\ 53367 &:= (-((T((7 \times 6)) - T(3))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))) \\ 53374 &:= (((T(4!) + 7!)/(-T(3))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))) \\ 53429 &:= -T(T(9) - T(T(2))) - T(T(4)) + C(T(T(3)),T(5)) \\ 53437 &:= (((-7) + (T(3))!) - T(T(T(4)))) + (C(T(T(3)),T(5))) \\ 53439 &:= (((T(9)/(-3)) \times T(T(4))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))) \\ 53442 &:= ((-2) - T((T(4) \times 4))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5)) \\ 53444 &:= (-T((44 - 4))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5)) \\ 53449 &:= -(((T(T(9)) - (4 \times T(T(4)))) - C(T(T(3)),T(5))) \\ 53454 &:= (C(4!,5) + ((-T(4)) - (T(3))!) \times (-T(5))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 53478 &:= -((T(T(8)) - (C(T(T((7 - 4))), T(3)) - (5!)))) \\ 53487 &:= (((T(7) \times T(T(8)))/(-4!) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \\ 53489 &:= ((T(9) - T((T(8) + (4)))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \\ 53498 &:= -((((T(T(8)) + T(9)) + T(T(4))) - C(T(T(3)), T(5)))) \\ 53508 &:= ((-T(8)) \times T((0! + (5)))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)) \\ 53514 &:= ((T(T((T(4) + 1))) \times T(5)) + (C(T(T(3)), 5)) \\ 53519 &:= -((T((T(9) + 1)) - ((C(T(5), 3) \times 5!))) \\ 53523 &:= (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - T((53 - T(5)))) \\ 53528 &:= -(((T((T(8) + 2)) - 5) - C(T(T(3)), T(5)))) \\ 53529 &:= ((T(C(9, T(2))) \times T(5)) - (T(3) + T(5))) \\ 53532 &:= (T(2) + ((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - (T(3))!) - T(5))) \\ 53533 &:= (-T(3) + ((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - (T(3))!) - 5)) \\ 53534 &:= ((-T(4) - (T(3))!) + C((T(5) + T(3)), T(5))) \\ 53536 &:= (-6!) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - (3 + 5)) \\ 53537 &:= ((-7) - (T(3))!) + C((T(5) + T(3)), T(5)) \\ 53539 &:= (((T(C(9, 3)) \times T(5)) - T(3)) - (5)) \\ 53542 &:= -((((T(T(2)))! - ((T(4)/(-5) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)))))) \\ 53543 &:= -((((T(3))! - ((4 - 5))) - C(T(T(3)), T(5)))) \\ 53544 &:= (C(T((4!/4)), T(5)) - ((T(3) \times 5!)) \\ 53545 &:= ((T(5) \times T(C((4 + 5), 3))) - (5)) \\ 53546 &:= (-((6! - (T(4)/5))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \\ 53549 &:= ((C((T(9) - 4!), T(5)) - (T(3))!) + 5) \\ 53559 &:= ((C(T((-9) + T(5))), T(5)) - (T(3))!) + T(5)) \\ 53561 &:= -((T(((1 + T(6)) + T(5))) - C(T(T(3)), T(5)))) \\ 53564 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) + ((-C(T(6), T(5)) - (T(3))!) - (5!)))) \\ 53565 &:= ((T(5) \times T(C((-6) + T(5)), 3)) + T(5)) \\ 53567 &:= (((T(7) + C(T(6), T(5))) - (T(3))!) - 5) \\ 53583 &:= -(((T((-3) + T(8))) + (5!)) - C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \\ 53584 &:= ((T((4! - 8)) \times (-5)) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \\ 53589 &:= ((-9) - T(T(8))) + C((T(5) + T(3)), T(5)) \\ 53598 &:= -((T(T(8)) - (C((((9 - 5))! - 3), T(5)))) \\ 53618 &:= -(((T(T(8)) - (-1) + T(6))) - C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \\ 53619 &:= -(((T(T((9 - 1))) - T(6))) - C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \\ 53622 &:= (T((T(T(2)) + T(T(2)))) + (-6!) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \\ 53624 &:= ((T(4) \times (-2^6)) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \\ 53627 &:= (-T(T(7))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6) - T((T(3) + T(5)))) \\ 53632 &:= (-2) + (C(T(T(3)), 6) - (T(35))) \\ 53634 &:= (C((4! - 3), 6) - T(35)) \\ 53649 &:= ((-9) \times T(T(4))) + ((C(T(6), T(3)) - 5!)) \\ 53654 &:= (-(((T(4) - 5!) + 6!)) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))) \end{aligned}$$

- 53669 := ((T(C(9,6)))/(-6) + C(T(T(3)),T(5)))
53673 := ((-3) - (T(7) × T(6))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))
53676 := -(((T(6) × T(7)) - C(T(6),(3 × 5))))
53679 := ((T(9) × (-7 + 6))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))
53681 := -((T((1 + T(8))) - ((C(T(6),T(3)) + 5!)))
53694 := -(((T(4) × T(9)) - (C(T(6),T(3)) - 5!)))
53697 := (T(-((T(7) - T(9)))) + (-6! + C(T(T(3)),T(5))))
53703 := -((T(((T(3) - 0!) + T(7))) - C(T(T(3)),T(5))))
53718 := -((T(T(8)) - (C(T(-((1 - 7))),T(3)) + (5!))))
53722 := C(T(T(T(2))),T(T(2))) - T(T(7)) - T(T(T(3)) - 5)
53724 := T(T(4)) - T(T(T(2)) + (T(7))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))
53725 := (C(T(5),T(T(2))) - (T(T(7)) × (-T((3 × 5))))
53732 := (((-2) + T(T(3))) × (-T(7))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))
53738 := ((-(((8 - 3)!)) - T(T(7))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5)))
53742 := ((T(T(2)) - T((4 + T(7)))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))
53744 := (-((T(4) × (4! + T(7)))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))
53746 := (((T(T(6)) × (-4)) + T(T(7))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))
53753 := ((C(T(T(3)),T(5)) - T((T(7) + 3))) - T(5))
53763 := ((C(T(T(3)),6) - T((T(7) + 3))) - 5)
53767 := ((T(T(7)) + T(T(6))) + (C((T(7) - 3),5)))
53774 := ((T(4) × (-7 × 7))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))
53778 := -(((T(T(8)) - (7!/T(7))) - C(T(T(3)),T(5))))
53788 := (T(T(8)) - (8 - C((T(7) - 3),5)))
53792 := ((-T((2 + 9))) - T(T(7))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))
53796 := (-((6! + (-9) × T(7))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))
53814 := (-((T(4) × T((1 + 8)))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))
53822 := -T(T(T(T(T(2)))/T(2))) - T(8) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))
53825 := ((C(T(5),T(T(2))) - (-8) × (T(3)!)) × 5)
53827 := ((T(7) - T(-((T(T(2)) - T(8)))) + (C(T(T(3)),T(5))))
53832 := (((-2) × T(3)) × T(8)) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))
53837 := -(((T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) - C(T((T(8)/T(3))),T(5))))
53852 := ((-T(T(2))) - T(T((T(5) - 8)))) + (C(T(T(3)),T(5)))
53853 := ((C(T(T(3)),T(5)) - T(C(8,T(3)))) - 5)
53854 := ((T(4) × (-5) - T(8))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))
53858 := -((T(T((C(8,5)/8))) - C(T(T(3)),T(5))))
53863 := ((C(T(T(3)),6) - T(C(8,T(3)))) + 5)
53873 := -((((T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) - T(8)) - C(T(T(3)),T(5))))
53894 := (-((T(4) - (T(9) × (-8)))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))
53897 := ((-7) + (T(9) × (-8))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5))
53903 := (((T(3))! - T((0! + T(9)))) + C(T(T(3)),T(5)))

- 53904 := $(-((40 \times 9)) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)))$
 53922 := $((-2) \times T((2 \times 9))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))$
 53925 := $((5^2) + T(C(9, 3))) \times T(5)$
 53934 := $((T(T(4)) \times (-T(3))) + (C(T((9 - 3)), T(5))))$
 53939 := $-((T((9 + ((T(3))!/T(9)))) - (C(T(T(3)), T(5))))$
 53942 := $-((T(T(T(T(2)))) - (-T((4 + 9))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))))$
 53943 := $((C(T(T(3)), 4) \times 9) + T((-3) + T(5)))$
 53947 := $((T(7) - T(4!)) - T(9)) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))$
 53954 := $((-T(4) - T((T(5) + 9))) + C(T(T(3)), T(5)))$
 53964 := $-((T((4 \times 6)) - C(T((9 - 3)), T(5)))$
 54012 := $(C(T(T(T(2))), T(T((1 + 0!)))) - C(T(4), 5)$
 54032 := $((C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - 0!) - T(T(T(T((T(4)/5))))$
 54033 := $(C(T(T(3)), T(3)) - T((0! + ((4 \times 5))))$
 54043 := $(-((T(T(T(3))) - T(4))) + C(T(T(-((0! - (4))))), T(5)))$
 54044 := $((T(T(4)) \times (-4)) + C(T(T(-((0! - (4))))), T(5)))$
 54053 := $(C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - (0! + T((4 \times 5)))$
 54123 := $((C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - T(T(-((1 - 4)))) - (5!))$
 54128 := $(-T((8 \times 2))) + C(T(T(-((1 - 4))))), T(5))$
 54129 := $(-((T(9) \times T(2))) + C(T(T(-((1 - 4))))), T(5))$
 54133 := $(C(T(T(3)), T(3)) - ((1 + T(4)) + 5!))$
 54134 := $(-T(4) + (C(T(T(3)), T(-((1 - 4)))) - (5!)))$
 54137 := $(-7) + (C(T(T(3)), T(-((1 - 4)))) - (5!))$
 54144 := $(C(T((4!/4)), T(-((1 - 4)))) - (5!))$
 54153 := $(C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - ((1 - T(4)) + 5!))$
 54159 := $(-T((9 + 5))) + C(T(T(-((1 - 4))))), T(5))$
 54173 := $(-T((T(3) + 7))) + C(T(T(-((1 - 4))))), T(5))$
 54204 := $(C(T(T((4 - 0!))), T(T(2))) - (4 \times T(5)))$
 54209 := $-((T((9 + 0!)) - (C(T((2 + 4)), T(5))))$
 54214 := $(C(T(T((4 - 1))), T(T(2))) - (T(4) \times 5))$
 54219 := $((T(9) \times (-1)) + C(T((2 + 4)), T(5)))$
 54223 := $(C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - ((2 + 4!) + T(5)))$
 54224 := $((C(T(C(4, 2)), T(T(2))) - T(T(4))) + T(5))$
 54226 := $(C(T(6), T(T(2))) - (2 \times (4! - (5))))$
 54227 := $(-T(7) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(T(2))) - (4 + 5)))$
 54228 := $-((T(8) - C((T(2) \times (T(2) + 4))), T(5)))$
 54232 := $(-T(2) + (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - (4! + (5))))$
 54233 := $(C(T(T(3)), T(3)) - ((2^4) + T(5)))$
 54234 := $((T(4) \times (-3)) + C(T((2 + 4)), T(5)))$
 54235 := $(C((T(5) + T(3)), T(T(2))) - (4! + (5)))$
 54236 := $((C(T(6), T(3)) - T(2)) - T(4) - T(5))$

$$\begin{aligned} 54237 &:= (-T(7) + (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - ((4 - 5)))) \\ 54239 &:= (C(T((9 - 3)), T(T(2))) - (T(4) + T(5))) \\ 54252 &:= ((T(2) - T(5)) + C(T((2 + 4)), T(5))) \\ 54253 &:= -(((T(3) + 5) - C(T((2 + 4)), T(5)))) \\ 54254 &:= -((T(4) - C(((5^2) - 4), T(5)))) \\ 54256 &:= (((C(T(6), T(5)) - T(2)) - T(4)) + 5) \\ 54257 &:= (-7) + C(((5^2) - 4), T(5)) \\ 54258 &:= -((T((8 - 5)) - C(T((2 + 4)), T(5)))) \\ 54259 &:= (C(T((-9) + T(5)), T(T(2))) - (T(4) - 5)) \\ 54261 &:= (C(T((1 \times 6)), T(T(2))) - T((T(4)/5))) \\ 54263 &:= ((T(3)/(-6)) + C(T((2 + 4)), T(5))) \\ 54264 &:= C(T(C(4, ((6 + 2)/4)), T(5)) \\ 54265 &:= -((5 - 6) + C(T((2 + 4)), T(5))) \\ 54266 &:= (C(T(6), 6) - ((2 \times (4 - 5)))) \\ 54267 &:= (T(7) + (C(T(6), T(T(2))) - (T(4) + T(5)))) \\ 54268 &:= (-T(8) + ((C(T(6), T(T(2))) + T(T(4))) - T(5))) \\ 54269 &:= (C(T(T((9 - 6))), T(T(2))) + (T(4) - 5)) \\ 54271 &:= ((1 \times 7) + C(T((2 + 4)), T(5))) \\ 54273 &:= (C(T(T(3)), T((7 - 2))) + (4 + 5)) \\ 54274 &:= (T(4) + C(C(7, -((2 - 4))), T(5))) \\ 54279 &:= (C(T(T(T((9 - 7)))), T(T(2))) + (T(4) + 5)) \\ 54283 &:= (C(T(T(3)), (8 - 2)) + (4! - 5)) \\ 54284 &:= (C(T(T((4!/8))), T(T(2))) + (4 \times 5)) \\ 54285 &:= -(((T(5) - T(8)) - C(T((2 + 4)), T(5)))) \\ 54292 &:= (T(-((2 - 9))) + (C(T((2 + 4)), T(5)))) \\ 54293 &:= (C(T(T(3)), (9 - T(2))) + (4! + 5)) \\ 54303 &:= (C(T(T(3)), T(03)) + (4! + T(5))) \\ 54304 &:= (40 + C((-3) + 4!), T(5)) \\ 54309 &:= (T(9) + C(((0 - 3) + 4!), T(5))) \\ 54314 &:= (C(T(T((4 - 1))), T(3)) + (T(4) \times 5)) \\ 54315 &:= (51 + C((-3) + 4!), T(5)) \\ 54319 &:= (T((9 + 1)) + C((-3) + 4!), T(5)) \\ 54322 &:= (-2) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) + (4 \times T(5))) \\ 54323 &:= (((C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) - T(3)) - T(T(4))) + 5!) \\ 54324 &:= (C(T(C(4, 2)), T(3)) + (4 \times T(5))) \\ 54326 &:= (62 + C((-3) + 4!), T(5)) \\ 54328 &:= ((8^2) + C((-3) + 4!), T(5)) \\ 54329 &:= ((C(T((9 - T(2))), T(3)) - T(T(4))) + 5!) \\ 54342 &:= (T((2 + T(4))) + (C((-3) + 4!), T(5))) \\ 54347 &:= ((T(7) + T(T(4))) + (C((-3) + 4!), T(5))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54348 &:= (84 + C((-3) + 4!), T(5)) \\ 54353 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T(T(3))) - (T(4) - 5!)) \\ 54356 &:= ((C(T(6), T(5)) - T((3 + 4))) + 5!) \\ 54359 &:= (95 + C((-3) + 4!), T(5)) \\ 54374 &:= (C(T(T(-((4 - 7))))), T(3)) - ((T(4) - 5!)) \\ 54384 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (T(8) \times T(3))) + C(4!, 5)) \\ 54394 &:= (C(-((4! - T(9))), T(3)) + (T(4) + 5!)) \\ 54405 &:= (T(50) - (C(4!, 4) \times (-5))) \\ 54423 &:= (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) + ((T(T(T(4))))/T(4)) + 5)) \\ 54429 &:= (T(9) + (C(T(T(T(2))), (4!/4)) + (5!))) \\ 54432 &:= (((T(2) \times 3) \times 4!) \times C(T(4), 5)) \\ 54433 &:= (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + ((T(T(T(4))))/T(4)) + T(5)) \\ 54435 &:= ((T(C(5, 3)) \times T(44)) - T(5)) \\ 54439 &:= (((T(9) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(T(T(4)))) + C(4!, 5)) \\ 54463 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), 6) + T(T(4))) + (4! + 5!)) \\ 54467 &:= ((-T(7)) + T(T(6))) + C(T((4!/4)), T(5)) \\ 54516 &:= (C(T(6), (1 + 5)) + C(T(4), 5)) \\ 54524 &:= (-T(T(4))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + ((T(4!) + T(5)))) \\ 54533 &:= ((-T(3)) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))) - (T(T(4)) \times (-5)) \\ 54534 &:= -((T(T(4)) - (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) + T((T(4) + T(5)))))) \\ 54535 &:= (((C(T(5), 3) \times 5!) + T(T(4))) - (5!)) \\ 54537 &:= (7 \times ((T(3))^{C(5,4)} + T(5))) \\ 54539 &:= (C(T((9 - 3)), T(5)) - (T(T(4)) \times (-5))) \\ 54559 &:= ((C(T((-9) + T(5))), T(5)) + T(4!)) - 5) \\ 54563 &:= ((-((T(3) - C(T(6), T(5)))) + T(4!)) + 5) \\ 54564 &:= (T(4!) - (C(T(6), T(5)) \times (4 - 5))) \\ 54567 &:= ((T(7) + C(T(6), T(5))) - (T(T(4)) \times (-5))) \\ 54569 &:= ((C(T(T((9 - 6))), T(5)) + T(4!)) + 5) \\ 54595 &:= (((-5) + T(9)) \times C(T(5), 4)) - (5)) \\ 54622 &:= (-2) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6) + ((4! \times T(5)))) \\ 54634 &:= (T(4) + (C(T(T(3)), 6) + ((4! \times T(5)))) \\ 54642 &:= (T((T(2) + 4!)) + (C(T(6), (T(4) + (5)))))) \\ 54648 &:= (((8 \times (4!))/T(6)!)) - C(4!, 5) \\ 54663 &:= (C(T(T(3)), 6) + (C(T(6), 4)/T(5))) \\ 54664 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (-6) + C((T(6) + (4)), 5)) \\ 54667 &:= ((T(T(7)) + (C(T(6), 6))) - T((T(4)/5))) \\ 54669 &:= ((T(9) + C(T(6), 6)) + (4! \times T(5))) \\ 54726 &:= ((T(T(6)))^2 + ((C(T(7), 4!)/T(5))) \\ 54736 &:= ((C(T(6), T(3)) + T(T(7))) + T((-4) + T(5))) \\ 54744 &:= ((T(4!) \times 4!) + ((7! + C(4!, 5)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54753 &:= (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) + ((7!/T(4)) - T(5))) \\ 54763 &:= (C(T(T(3)), 6) + ((7!/T(4)) - (5))) \\ 54766 &:= ((C(T(6), 6) + T(T(7))) - (4! - 5!)) \\ 54798 &:= -((T(T(8)) - ((9!/T(7)) + C(4!, 5))) \\ 54824 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) + ((-8) \times T(T(4))) \times (-5!)) \\ 54844 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + ((T(4!) \times T(8)) + C(4!, 5))) \\ 54873 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (T((7!/C(8, 4))) - T(5))) \\ 54899 &:= (-C(9, 9) - (-T(8)) \times (T(T(T(4))) - T(5))) \\ 54924 &:= ((C(4!, 2) \times T(9)) + C(4!, 5)) \\ 54928 &:= (T(T(8)) - (2 - C((T(9) - 4!), T(5)))) \\ 54939 &:= ((-T(9)) + (T(3))!) + (C((T(9) - 4!), T(5))) \\ 54963 &:= ((T(3))! - (T(6) - C((T(9) - 4!), T(5)))) \\ 54993 &:= ((T(3))! - (-9 - C((T(9) - 4!), T(5)))) \\ 55029 &:= ((T(9) + (T(T(2))))!) + C(T((0! + (5))), T(5)) \\ 55084 &:= (T((4 + T(8))) + C(T((0! + (5))), T(5))) \\ 55167 &:= (T((7 \times 6)) + C(T((1 + 5))), T(5)) \\ 55179 &:= (T(T(9)) + ((C(T((7 - 1))), T(5)) - 5!)) \\ 55204 &:= (T(40) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + (5!))) \\ 55216 &:= (T(T((6 + 1))) \times C((2 + T(5)), T(5))) \\ 55248 &:= ((T(8) \times 4!) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + (5!))) \\ 55249 &:= ((T(T(9)) - T(T(4))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + 5)) \\ 55269 &:= (T(T(9)) + (C(T(6), T(T(2))) - (T(5) + T(5)))) \\ 55275 &:= (T(C((5 + 7), 2)) \times (5 \times 5)) \\ 55278 &:= (T(T(8)) \times ((T(7) \times T(2)) - C(5, 5))) \\ \\ 55287 &:= ((T(7) \times T(8)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + T(5))) \\ 55292 &:= ((-2) + T(T(9))) + (C(T((T(2))!), T(5)) - 5) \\ 55294 &:= ((-T(4) + T(T(9))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + 5)) \\ 55297 &:= ((-7) + T(T(9))) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + 5) \\ 55299 &:= (T(T(9)) + (C(C((9 - 2), 5), T(5)))) \\ 55304 &:= (T(T((T(4) - 0!))) + ((C(T(T(3))), T(5)) + 5)) \\ 55314 &:= (T(T((T(4) - 1))) + ((C(T(T(3))), T(5)) + T(5))) \\ 55325 &:= (((C(T(5), T(2)) + T(3)) \times 5!) + (5)) \\ 55329 &:= ((T(9) \times T(T(T(2)))) + ((C(T(T(3))), T(5)) + (5!))) \\ 55335 &:= (((C(T(5), 3) + T(3)) \times 5!) + T(5)) \\ 55349 &:= ((T(9) \times 4!) + (C(T(T(3))), T(5)) + 5) \\ 55359 &:= (9 \times 5!) + (C(T(T(3))), T(5)) + T(5)) \\ 55374 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times (7! - C(T(3), 5)))/5) \\ 55384 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(8)) - C((3 + 5), 5)) \\ 55392 &:= (T((2 + T(9))) + C((3! + T(5)), T(5))) \\ 55464 &:= (4! + (C((T(6) - T(4)), 5) \times 5!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}55468 &:= (C(8,6) - (T(T(T(4))) \times (-T((5!/T(5)))))) \\55473 &:= ((3 + 7!) \times (T(4) + C(5,5))) \\55479 &:= ((9!/T(7)) + (C(4!,5) + T(5))) \\55524 &:= (-(C(4!,2)) + (5! \times T((T(5) + T(5)))))) \\55539 &:= (T(T(9)) + (C(T(T(3)),T(5)) + ((5! + 5!)))) \\55642 &:= (T((-T(2)) + T(T(4))) + (C(T(C(6,5)),T(5)))) \\55647 &:= (T((T(7) + 4!)) + (C(T(6),T(5)) + (5))) \\55648 &:= ((-T(8)) + T(T(T(4)))) + ((C(T(6),T(5)) - 5!)) \\55659 &:= (T((T(9) + (5))) + ((C(T(6),T(5)) + 5!)) \\55692 &:= ((-C((2 \times 9),6)) \times T(5))/(-5) \\55795 &:= ((5! \times T((9 + C(7,5)))) - (5)) \\55804 &:= (T(T(T(4))) - (0 - C((T(8) - T(5)),T(5)))) \\55829 &:= ((C(9,T(2)) \times T(T(8))) + (5 - 5!)) \\55845 &:= ((C(T(5),4) \times (T(8) + (5))) - 5!) \\55847 &:= (T(T(7)) + ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(8)) + C(5,5))) \\55849 &:= ((T(9) + T(T(T(4)))) + (C((T(8) - T(5)),T(5)))) \\55869 &:= ((C(9,6) \times T(T(8))) + (-5 \times T(5))) \\55875 &:= (((5 \times 7) \times T(C(8,5))) + T(5)) \\55924 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (C(T(T(T(2))),(-9 + T(5))) + (5!))) \\55937 &:= ((T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times (C(9,5) + 5)) \\55944 &:= (T(T((4 + 4))) \times C(9,(T(5)/5))) \\55989 &:= (T(9) + (T(T(8)) \times C(9,(T(5)/5)))) \\56007 &:= (-7!) + (T((0! + 0!)) \times C(T(6),5)) \\56019 &:= ((T(T(9)) + (T(T((1 + 0!))))!) + (C(T(6),T(5)))) \\56034 &:= (T(((T(4) \times T(3)) - 0!)) + (C(T(6),T(5)))) \\56064 &:= ((T(4!) \times 6) - (0 - C(T(6),T(5)))) \\56094 &:= (T((4! + T((9 - 0!)))) + (C(T(6),T(5)))) \\56095 &:= (T((T(5) + T(9))) + ((0! + C(T(6),T(5)))))) \\56133 &:= ((3^{T(3)-1}) \times T(T(C(6,5)))) \\56214 &:= ((T((4! + 1)) \times T(T(2))) + (C(T(6),T(5)))) \\56224 &:= (T((4^{T(2)})) + (C(T(T(T(2))),6) - (5!))) \\56244 &:= ((T(44) \times 2) + C(T(6),T(5))) \\56259 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T(C(5,2))) - T((T(6) + T(5)))) \\56289 &:= ((T(C(9,8))^2) + C(T(6),T(5))) \\56292 &:= ((T(2) + (T(9)^2)) + C(T(6),T(5))) \\56294 &:= -((T(T(T(4))) - (T(C(9,T(2))) + (C(T(6),T(5)))))) \\56298 &:= (-T(8)) + ((T(T(9)) \times 2) + (C(T(6),T(5)))) \\56323 &:= -(((T(T(3)) - T((2^{T(3)}))) - (C(T(6),T(5)))))) \\56325 &:= ((T((5!/2)) + T(T(T(3)))) + (C(T(6),T(5)))) \\56329 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times 2) + (C(T(T(3)),6) - 5))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 56342 &:= ((-2) + T((4^3))) + C(T(6), T(5)) \\ 56344 &:= (T((4 + (T(4) \times T(3)))) + (C(T(6), T(5)))) \\ 56373 &:= ((T(37) \times 3) + C(T(6), T(5))) \\ 56409 &:= (T(((9 + 0!) + T(T(4)))) + (C(T(6), T(5)))) \\ 56433 &:= (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + (4! + T(65))) \\ 56435 &:= -((C(T(5), T(3)) + (-((4^6) \times T(5)))) \\ 56542 &:= (T(((T(2) \times 4!) - (5))) + (C(T(6), T(5)))) \\ 56559 &:= (T((T(T(9))/T(5)) - (5! - C(T(6), T(5)))) \\ 56574 &:= ((T(4) \times T(C(7, 5))) + C(T(6), T(5))) \\ 56624 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times 2) - (6! - C(T(6), T(5)))) \\ 56628 &:= (T((T(8)/T(2))) \times (6! + C(6, 5))) \\ 56634 &:= ((T(4) \times (T(3) + T(T(6)))) + (C(T(6), T(5)))) \\ 56637 &:= (C(T(7), 3) + (T(T(6)) \times T(T(C(6, 5))))) \\ 56679 &:= (T(((9 \times 7) + 6)) + C(T(6), T(5))) \\ 56724 &:= (4! + ((T(T(2)) \times T(T(7))) + (C(T(6), T(5))))) \\ 56739 &:= ((T(9) \times T((3 + 7))) + C(T(6), T(5))) \\ 56743 &:= ((-T(3)) + T((T(4) \times 7))) + (C(T(6), T(5))) \\ 56749 &:= (T(((T(9) - T(T(4))) \times 7)) + (C(T(6), T(5)))) \\ 56756 &:= (((T(6) \times 5!) - T(7)) + C(T(6), T(5))) \\ 56776 &:= (6! + (T(7) \times C((-7) + T(6), 5))) \\ 56791 &:= ((T(19) \times T(T(7))) - (C(T(6), 5))) \\ 56824 &:= ((T(4) \times (2^8)) + C(T(6), T(5))) \\ 56864 &:= ((T((4 + T(6))) \times 8) + (C(T(6), T(5)))) \\ 56891 &:= ((-1) + T((9 \times 8))) + C(T(6), T(5)) \\ 56892 &:= (T((((T(T(2)))! / 9) - 8)) + (C(T(6), T(5)))) \\ 56904 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(09))) - T(C(6, 5))) \\ 56919 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T((1 + 9))) - C(6, 5)) \\ 56925 &:= (((T(5)^2) + T(C(9, 6))) \times T(5)) \\ 56926 &:= ((T(T(6))^2) + ((T(C(9, 6)) - (5)))) \\ 56931 &:= ((T(T((1 + 3))) \times T(T(9))) + C(6, 5)) \\ 56934 &:= ((T(T(C(4, 3))) \times T(T(9))) + (-6 + T(5))) \\ 56936 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times T(T(T(3)))) + (T(C(9, 6)) + (5))) \\ 56943 &:= (-3) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(9))) + T(C(6, 5))) \\ 56946 &:= ((T((6 + 4)) \times T(T(9))) + T(C(6, 5))) \\ 56947 &:= (T(7) + ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(9))) - C(6, 5))) \\ 56949 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times T(T(4))) + (T(9) - T(C(6, 5)))) \\ 56964 &:= ((T((4 \times 6)) \times 9) + C(T(6), T(5))) \\ 56984 &:= ((-T(T(4))) + T((T(T(8))/9))) + (C(T(6), T(5))) \\ 57238 &:= ((-8!) - (T(3))!) - (2 - C(T(7), 5)) \\ 57256 &:= (T((6 + C(5, 2))) \times (T(T(7)) + T(5))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 57288 &:= (((-8!) - T(T(8))) - T(T(2))) + (C(T(7), 5))) \\ 57329 &:= (T(T(9)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), T(3)) - (T(T(7)) \times (-5)))) \\ 57345 &:= (((C(T(5), 4) \times T(3)) \times 7) + T(5)) \\ 57365 &:= ((C(T(5), 6) - (T(T(T(3))) \times (-T(7)))) \times 5) \\ 57384 &:= (((T(4) \times 8!) - C(T(T(3)), 7))/5) \\ 57431 &:= (T((1 + T(T(3)))) \times (-4 + T(C(7, 5)))) \\ 57464 &:= (((C(4!, T(6)) + 4!) \times T(7)) + 5!) \\ 57528 &:= (T(8) \times (2 + T(C((T(5) - 7), 5)))) \\ 57546 &:= ((T(T(6)) \times C(T(4), 5) - T(T((-7) + T(5)))) \\ 57582 &:= ((C(T((T(2))!), 8)/(-5)) + (C(T(7), 5))) \\ 57588 &:= ((T(8) \times (T(C(8, 5)) + 7)) - 5!) \\ 57622 &:= (-2) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6) + ((T(7) \times 5!))) \\ 57624 &:= ((C(4!, T(2)) + 6!) \times C(7, 5)) \\ 57634 &:= (T(4) + (C(T(T(3)), 6) + ((T(7) \times 5!))) \\ 57669 &:= ((T(9) + C(T(6), 6)) + (T(7) \times 5!)) \\ 57729 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times (2 \times T(7))) - T(C(7, 5))) \\ 57824 &:= -(((T((4^2)) + 8!) - C(T(7), 5))) \\ 57835 &:= ((-((5^3)) - 8!) + C(T(7), 5)) \\ 57855 &:= (((T(5) - 5!) - 8!) + C(T(7), 5)) \\ 57897 &:= ((-((7 \times 9)) - 8!) + C(T(7), 5)) \\ 57922 &:= (((T(T(2))!) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 9) - (7!)))/5) \\ 57923 &:= (C(T(T(3)), T(T(2))) + ((9 \times T(T(7))) + 5)) \\ 57933 &:= (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) + ((9 \times T(T(7))) + T(5))) \\ 57938 &:= ((C(8, 3) \times T(T(9))) - (7 + T(5))) \\ 57958 &:= ((C(8, 5) \times T(T(9))) - (7 - 5)) \\ 58066 &:= -((6! - (C(T(6), (0! + 8))/5)) \\ 58176 &:= (6! + (T((7 + 1)) \times T(C(8, 5)))) \\ 58184 &:= ((4 + T(T((8 + 1)))) \times C(8, 5)) \\ 58212 &:= (T(21) \times C((2 + 8), 5)) \\ 58233 &:= (T(T(3)) + (T(T(T(3))) \times C((2 + 8), 5))) \\ 58236 &:= ((T(T(6)) - C(T(3), T(2))) \times T((8 + T(5)))) \\ 58246 &:= ((C(T(6), T(4))/T(T(2))) - (T(8) \times T(5))) \\ 58248 &:= (T(8) \times ((4! - 2) + T(C(8, 5)))) \\ 58255 &:= ((5! \times C(T(5), T(2))) + T(85)) \\ 58293 &:= (-3) + ((T(T(9)) + T(T(2))) \times C(8, 5)) \\ 58353 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T(T(T(3)))) + (T(8) \times 5!)) \\ 58426 &:= ((C(T(6), T(T(2))) - (4!)) + T(T((8 + 5)))) \\ 58428 &:= (T(8) \times ((T(2) + 4!) + T(C(8, 5)))) \\ 58473 &:= (((T(3))! \times T(T(7))) + C(T(4), 8))/5 \\ 58539 &:= (-T(9)) + (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) + (T(8) \times 5!)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 58563 &:= -((T(T(3)) - ((C(T(6), T(5)) + (T(8) \times 5!)))) \\ 58629 &:= (T(T(9)) + (C(T(T(T(2))), 6) - (T(T(8)) \times (-5)))) \\ 58638 &:= -((T(T(8)) - (C(T(T(3)), 6) + ((-8) + T(5))!)) \\ 58693 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), 9) - T((-6) + T(8)))/5) \\ 58786 &:= (C(T(6), ((8 - 7) + 8))/5) \\ 58856 &:= ((T(T(6)) + T((5 \times 8))) \times C(8, 5)) \\ 58897 &:= ((T(T(7)) + T(T(9))) + (T(8) \times T(C(8, 5)))) \\ 58914 &:= ((T(T(4)) - 1) \times (T(T(9)) + C(8, 5))) \\ 58923 &:= -(((T(T(3)) \times T(T(2))) - ((C(9, 8)^5)))) \\ 58924 &:= ((4! + (C(T(T(T(2))), 9) + (T(T(8))))) / 5) \\ 58935 &:= -(((5! - T(3)) - (C(9, 8)^5))) \\ 58938 &:= ((T(T(8)) / (-T(3))) + ((C(9, 8)^5))) \\ 58949 &:= ((-T(9)) - T(T(4))) + ((C(9, 8)^5)) \\ 58957 &:= ((T(7) - 5!) + (C(9, 8)^5)) \\ 58958 &:= -((T((8 + 5)) - (C(9, 8)^5)) \\ 58983 &:= -((T((3 + 8)) - (C(9, 8)^5)) \\ 58993 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), 9) + T(T(C(9, 8)))) / 5) \\ 58994 &:= -(((T(4) + T(9)) - (C(9, 8)^5))) \\ 58997 &:= ((-7) - T(9)) + (C(9, 8)^5) \\ 59004 &:= -((C(T(4), (0! + 0!)) - (9^5))) \\ 59094 &:= (C(T(4), (9 - 0!)) + (9^5)) \\ 59214 &:= (C((T(4) + 1), T(2)) + (9^5)) \\ 59235 &:= -((T(C(5, 3)) \times (T(2) - (9 \times 5!))) \\ 59256 &:= (-C(T(6), T(5)) + (T((-2) + T(9)) \times 5!)) \\ 59269 &:= (C((-9) + T(6)), T(2)) + (9^5) \\ 59275 &:= ((-5) + T(C(7, 2))) + (9^5) \\ 59335 &:= ((T(C(5, 3)) + T(T(T(3)))) + (9^5)) \\ 59427 &:= (C(T(7), -(2 - 4)) + (9^5)) \\ 59428 &:= (C(8, 2) + (T(T(4)) \times (9 \times 5!))) \\ 59436 &:= (-6) \times ((T(3))! - C(4!, (9 - 5))) \\ 59506 &:= (6! - (C(T((0! + 5)), 9) / (-5))) \\ 59598 &:= ((8 + T((T(9) - T(5)))) \times C(9, 5)) \\ 59625 &:= (((C(T(5), T(2)) - 6!) \times T(9)) \times (-5)) \\ 59637 &:= ((T(C(7, T(3))) \times T(6)) + (9^5)) \\ 59643 &:= (((3^{T(4)} + 6!) - (C(9, 5))) \\ 59676 &:= (-6) + (T(T(7)) \times (T(6) + (C(9, 5)))) \\ 59682 &:= (T(28) \times (T(6) + (C(9, 5)))) \\ 59686 &:= (T(T(6)) + ((T(C(8, 6)) + (9^5)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 59835 &:= ((-C(T(5),3) \times T(T(8))) + ((9! - T(5)))) \\ 59934 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times 39) - C(9,5)) \\ 59976 &:= ((T(6) - T(7)) \times (-C((9+9),5))) \\ 60249 &:= ((9!/C(4,2)) - T(T(06))) \\ 60425 &:= (-T(C(5,2)) + (((T(4) - 0!)!)/6)) \\ 60438 &:= (8! + (C(T(T(3)), (4 + 0!)) - T(T(6)))) \\ 60935 &:= (C(T(5),3) + (9!/06)) \\ 61053 &:= ((C(T(T(3)),5) \times T((0! + 1))) + 6) \\ 61446 &:= (T(T(6)) \times (-T(4) - C(4!, (1 + T(6)))))) \\ 61455 &:= (T(5) + (T(5) \times (C(4,1)^6))) \\ 61464 &:= ((T(4) \times 6!) + C(T(T((4-1))),6)) \\ 61473 &:= (3 \times (C(T(7),4!) + (16))) \\ 61824 &:= ((C(4!,2) \times 8) \times T((1+6))) \\ 61845 &:= (C(T(5),4) + (((8+1)!)/6)) \\ 62245 &:= ((5 - T(4!)) \times (C(T(T(2)), T(2)) - T(T(6)))) \\ 62278 &:= (8! + ((T(7)^{C(T(2),2)}) + (6))) \\ 62334 &:= ((T(4!) \times T(C(T(3),3))) - T(T((2+6)))) \\ 62345 &:= ((C(T(5),T(4)) \times T(T(3))) + (2 - 6!)) \\ 62369 &:= (((T(9) \times T(T(6))) \times T(3)) - C(T(T(2)),6)) \\ 62377 &:= ((-7) - C(T(7),3)) \times (2 - T(6)) \\ 62464 &:= (((T(T(T(4))) - (6!)) \times T(4)) + C(T(T(T(2))),6)) \\ 62489 &:= (((T(T(9)) \times 8) - T(T(4))) + C(T(T(T(2))),6)) \\ 62532 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))),T(3)) + (T(52) \times 6)) \\ 62657 &:= -((T(T(7)) - ((C(T(5),T((6-2))) \times T(6)))) \\ 62724 &:= -((T((-T(4) + T(T(T(2)))))) + (C(T(7),T(T(2)))/(-6))) \\ 62727 &:= ((C(T(7),T(T(2))) - (C(T(7),2)))/6) \\ 62734 &:= -((T(T(4)) - ((T(3) - C(T(7),T(T(2)))))/(-6))) \\ 62735 &:= (-T(C(5,3)) - (C(T(7),T(T(2)))/(-6))) \\ 62736 &:= ((6! + C(T(T(3)),7)) - C(T(T(T(2))),6)) \\ 62739 &:= (-((T(9) + T(3))) - (C(T(7),T(T(2)))/(-6))) \\ 62755 &:= ((T((5+T(5))) - C(T(7),T(T(2))))/(-6)) \\ 62757 &:= (-((T(7) + (5))) - (C(T(7),T(T(2)))/(-6))) \\ 62763 &:= (-((T(3) + T(6))) - (C(T(7),T(T(2)))/(-6))) \\ 62766 &:= (66 \times (T(C(7,2)) + 6!)) \\ 62775 &:= ((C(T(5),7) - 7!) \times T((T(2) + (6)))) \\ 62776 &:= (-((T(6) - (7))) - (C(T(7),T(T(2)))/(-6))) \\ 62777 &:= -((T(77) - C((T(7) - 2), T(6)))) \\ 62781 &:= (-((1 + 8)) - (C(T(7),T(T(2)))/(-6))) \\ 62783 &:= ((-((T(3) + T(8))) + C(T(7),T(T(2))))/6) \\ 62788 &:= (-8) + ((-T(8)) - C(T(7),T(T(2))))/(-6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 62789 &:= (-(9-8) - (C(T(7), T(T(2)))/(-6))) \\ 62791 &:= ((1^9) - (C(T(7), T(T(2)))/(-6))) \\ 62792 &:= (((T(2)+9) + C(T(7), T(T(2))))/6) \\ 62795 &:= (((T(5)-T(9)) - C(T(7), T(T(2))))/(-6)) \\ 62799 &:= (((-9) - T(9)) - C(T(7), T(T(2))))/(-6)) \\ 62814 &:= (4! - (C(T(-(1-8)), T(T(2)))/(-6))) \\ 62827 &:= ((C(T(7), T(T(2))) + (T(T(8))/T(2)))/6) \\ 62868 &:= (((8+T(T(6))) \times T(8)) + C(T(T(T(2))), 6)) \\ 63063 &:= (T(T(3)) \times C((T(6)-0!) - T(3)), 6)) \\ 63145 &:= (5 \times (C((4!+1), T(T(3))) - (T(6)))) \\ 63231 &:= ((T(((1+3)!)) \times T(C(T(T(2)), 3))) + T(T(6))) \\ 63234 &:= (((T(4!) \times T(C(T(3), T(2)))) + 3) + T(T(6))) \\ 63308 &:= ((8-0!) \times (C(T(T(3)), T(3))/6)) \\ 63385 &:= (((T(5)-8)^{T(3)} - C(T(T(3)), 6)) \\ 63444 &:= (((C(4!, 4) - T(T(4))) + 3) \times 6) \\ 63459 &:= (9^5) + (C(T(4), T(3)) \times T(6)) \\ 63464 &:= (((T(4)+T(6)) \times C(4!, 3)) + 6!) \\ 63485 &:= (5 \times (-8) + (T(T(C(4, 3))) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 63494 &:= -(T(4) - ((9!/C(T(4), 3)) \times T(6))) \\ 63497 &:= (-7) + ((9!/C(T(4), 3)) \times T(6)) \\ 63524 &:= -T(T(T(4))) + T(T(2))! \times T(5) + C(T(T(3)), 6) \\ 63525 &:= ((T(C(5, 2))^{5-3}) \times T(6)) \\ 63545 &:= (5 \times (4 - (-T(C(5, 3))) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 63552 &:= ((T(T(2)))! + ((C(T(5), 5) \times T(T(3))) - T(T(6)))) \\ 63569 &:= -((T((T(9)+T(6))) - C((5+T(T(3))), T(6))) \\ 63588 &:= -(((T(T(8)) + (T(T(8)) \times (-T(5)))) - C(T(T(3)), 6))) \\ 63648 &:= (8 \times ((4 - C(T(6), 3)) \times (-6))) \\ 63756 &:= (-6) \times (C((-5) + T(7), 3) \times (-6)) \\ 63774 &:= ((C(4!, (T(7)/7)) + 3) \times 6) \\ 63789 &:= (T(T(9)) - (T(8) + (C(T(7), T(3))/(-6)))) \\ 63797 &:= ((-T(7) + T(T(9))) - (C(T(7), T(3))/(-6))) \\ 63822 &:= (((C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) \times 8) - 3) \times 6) \\ 63945 &:= (((C(T(5), T(4)) + T(9)) - 3) \times T(6)) \\ 63966 &:= (C(T(6), 6) + ((T(9) - 3) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 64058 &:= ((8 \times C((T(5)+0!), T(4))) - (6)) \\ 64124 &:= -((C(4!, T(T(2))) - (T((-1)+4!)) \times 6!)) \\ 64225 &:= -(C(T(5), T(2)) - ((2 \times T(T(T(4)))) \times (-T(6)))) \\ 64255 &:= (-5) + (C((T(5)+T(2)), 4) \times T(6)) \\ 64281 &:= ((1 + C((T(8)/2), 4)) \times T(6)) \\ 64284 &:= (4! + (C((T(8)/2), 4) \times T(6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 64295 &:= (-C(T(5), 9) - (-T(24) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 64323 &:= ((3 + C((T(2) \times T(3)), 4)) \times T(6)) \\ 64344 &:= ((4 + C((4! - T(3)), 4)) \times T(6)) \\ 64365 &:= ((5 + C((6 \times 3), 4)) \times T(6)) \\ 64405 &:= (5 \times (C((0! + 4!), 4) + T(T(6)))) \\ 64422 &:= (T(T((2^{T(2)}))) - (C(4!, 4) \times (-6))) \\ 64428 &:= ((T(T(8)) + T(T(2))) + (C(4!, 4) \times 6)) \\ 64449 &:= ((T(9) + (C(T(4), 4) + 4!)) \times T(T(6))) \\ 64476 &:= (6! - (C((T(7) - (4)), 4) \times (-6))) \\ 64497 &:= (T((-7) + T(9)) + (C(4!, 4) \times 6)) \\ 64525 &:= (C(T(5), T(T(2))) + (5! \times T((T(4) + T(6)))))) \\ 64569 &:= (((9 \times (C(6, 5)))! \times T(4)) - T(T(6))) \\ 64594 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + (-9) + (C(T(5), T(4)) \times T(6))) \\ 64625 &:= ((C(T(5), T(2)) + 6!) \times T((4 + 6))) \\ 64692 &:= (T(2) \times ((T(C(9, 6)) + 4!) \times 6)) \\ 64735 &:= (T(C(5, 3)) - (-((T(7) \times T(4)) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 64744 &:= -((4! - ((4 + T(7)) \times C(4!, T(6)))) \\ 64765 &:= (C(T(5), 6) - ((T(7) + T(T(4))) \times (-6!))) \\ 64828 &:= (C(8, 2) + ((T(8) \times T(4!)) \times 6)) \\ 64834 &:= -((T(43) - C((T(8) - T(4)), T(6)))) \\ 64854 &:= ((T(4) \times C(T(5), 8)) + (4! \times T(6))) \\ 64883 &:= -((T(T(T(3))) + (T(T(8)) - C((T(8) - T(4)), T(6)))) \\ 65052 &:= ((2 - T(5)) \times (0! - C(T(5), 6))) \\ 65063 &:= (C(T(T(3)), 6) - (0! - (T(5) \times 6!))) \\ 65085 &:= (T(5) \times ((T(T(8)) \times (-0!)) + (C(T(5), 6)))) \\ 65229 &:= ((T(9) \times (C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) + (5!))) - (T(6))) \\ 65338 &:= ((-8) + T(T(3))) \times (T(T(3)) + (C(T(5), 6))) \\ 65345 &:= -((T((5 + 4!)) - C((T(T(3)) + 5), T(6))) \\ 65352 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) + (((T(3))! / T(5)) \times T(T(6)))) \\ 65374 &:= (-T((4 \times 7)) + C((T(T(3)) + 5), T(6))) \\ 65485 &:= (((T(5) \times 8!) / T(4)) + C(T(5), 6)) \\ 65548 &:= (T(C(8, 4)) + (C(T(5), 5) \times T(6))) \\ 65549 &:= (C(((T(9) - 4!) + (5)), 5) - T(T(6))) \\ 65565 &:= ((5! + T(C(6, 5))) \times T((5 \times 6))) \\ 65594 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + ((9^5) + C(T(5), 6))) \\ 65625 &:= ((C(5, -(2 - 6))^5) \times T(6)) \\ 65644 &:= -((T((4 \times 4)) - C((T(6) + (5)), T(6))) \\ 65674 &:= ((T(4!) - T(T(7))) + C((T(6) + (5)), T(6))) \\ 65675 &:= ((T(5) \times (-7)) + C((T(6) + (5)), T(6))) \\ 65688 &:= (((8 \times T(C(8, 6))) - 5!) \times T(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 65699 &:= (-((9 \times 9) + C((T(6) + (5)), T(6)))) \\ 65729 &:= -((T(9) - (C((-2) + T(7)), 5) - (6))) \\ 65745 &:= ((T(5)^4) + (C(7, 5) \times 6!)) \\ 65759 &:= (C(-((9 - (5 \times 7))), 5) - T(6)) \\ 65765 &:= (-T(5) + C((T(T((T(6)/7))) + 5), T(6))) \\ 65775 &:= (-5) + C((T(7) - (7 - 5)), T(6)) \\ 65786 &:= (C(((6! + 8)/T(7)), 5) + (6)) \\ 65795 &:= (T(5) + C(-((9 - (7 \times 5))), T(6))) \\ 65801 &:= (C((-10) + T(8)), 5) + T(6) \\ 65808 &:= (T(8) \times ((0! + T(C(8, 5))) + T(T(6)))) \\ 65925 &:= -(((C(T(5), T(2)) \times T(9)) - (5! \times 6!))) \\ 65934 &:= (T((C(4, 3) \times 9)) \times (5! - T(6))) \\ 66045 &:= ((C(T(5), T(4)) \times (0! + T(6))) - T(6)) \\ 66235 &:= (C(T(5), 3) + C(26, T(6))) \\ 66276 &:= (T(6) \times (C(T(7), T(2)) + (6!/(-6)))) \\ 66279 &:= (((T(T(9)) - (7!)) \times (-T(2))) + (C(T(6), 6))) \\ 66292 &:= ((2^9) + C(26, T(6))) \\ 66464 &:= ((4 \times (C(T(6), T(4))/T(6))) - 6!) \\ 66495 &:= ((-C(T(5), 9) \times (T(4!) - (T(6))))/(-T(6))) \\ 66584 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times 8) + (C((T(5) + (6)), 6))) \\ 66639 &:= ((9! - C((T(3) + T(6)), T(6))) - T(T(6))) \\ 66724 &:= (((T(4!) - 2) \times T(T(7))) - (C(T(6), 6))) \\ 66738 &:= ((T(C(8, 3)) - (7)) \times (T(6) + T(6))) \\ 66786 &:= ((6 \times T(T(8))) - (C(T(7), 6)/(-6))) \\ 66864 &:= ((T(4!) \times T(T(6))) - (T(C(8, 6)) \times 6)) \\ 66918 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times 19) + (C(T(6), 6))) \\ 66939 &:= (((C(9, 3) + 9) \times 6!) - T(6)) \\ 67242 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times (C(4!, 2) + T(76))) \\ 67255 &:= (-5!) - (-T(C(5, 2)) \times T((T(7) + T(6)))) \\ 67264 &:= (((C(4!, 6)/2) - T(7)) - (6)) \\ 67284 &:= (((T(4!) \times 8) + T(2)) \times T(C(7, 6))) \\ 67456 &:= (T((T(6) - (5))) \times T((4! + C(7, 6)))) \\ 67655 &:= (5 \times (C(T(5), 6) - (T(T(7)) \times (-T(6)))) \\ 67823 &:= (((T(T(3)) - C(T(T(T(2))), 8)) \times (-7))/T(6)) \\ 67824 &:= ((C(4!, T(2)) \times T(8)) - (C(7, 6))!) \\ 67825 &:= (-5) - ((C(T(T(T(2))), 8) \times (-7))/T(6)) \\ 67904 &:= ((T((T(4) + 0!)) \times T(T(9))) - T(T(C(7, 6)))) \\ 68235 &:= ((-T(5) + C(T(T(3)), T(T(2)))) + (T(T(8)) \times T(6))) \\ 68252 &:= (C(T(T(T(2))), T(5)) - (-2 - (T(T(8)) \times T(6)))) \\ 68253 &:= ((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) + T(2)) + (T(T(8)) \times T(6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 68256 &:= ((C(T(6), T(5)) + T(T(2))) + (T(T(8)) \times T(6))) \\
 68355 &:= ((T(5) + T((C(5,3) \times 8))) \times T(6)) \\
 68376 &:= (((6 \times T(T(7))) + T(3)) \times C(8,6)) \\
 68445 &:= ((T(5) + 4!) \times (T(C(T(4),8)) + (6!))) \\
 68523 &:= ((C((T(3) \times T(2)),5) \times 8) - T(6)) \\
 68565 &:= (5 \times ((C(T(6), T(5)) - 8!) - T(T(6)))) \\
 68648 &:= (8 \times (T(T(4)) + (T(6) \times T(C(8,6))))) \\
 68733 &:= (T(T(3)) \times (-3 + C(T(7), T((8 - 6)))))) \\
 68894 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times T(9)) - T(C(8, (8 - 6)))) \\
 68925 &:= ((-C(5,2)) \times (T(T(9)) + 8!)) / (-6) \\
 68929 &:= (9! - (C(T(T(T(2))),9) + T((T(8)/6)))) \\
 68992 &:= -((C(T(T(T(2))),9) - ((9! + T(8)) + (6)))) \\
 69299 &:= (-C(9,9) + (T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))))) \\
 69306 &:= ((C((T(6) + 0!),3) \times T(9)) + (6)) \\
 69328 &:= (C(8,2) + (T(T(T(3))) \times T((T(9) - T(6)))))) \\
 69522 &:= (-2) - ((C(T(T(T(2))),T(5)) + 9!) / (-6)) \\
 69523 &:= ((-T(3) + (C(T(T(T(2))),T(5)) + 9!) / 6) \\
 69524 &:= ((C(T(C(4,2)),T(5)) + 9!) / 6) \\
 69534 &:= (T(4) - ((C(T(T(3)),T(5)) + 9!) / (-6)) \\
 69569 &:= (T(9) + ((C(T(6),T(5)) + 9!) / 6) \\
 69597 &:= (T((T(7) + 9)) \times (T(5) + (C(9,6)))) \\
 69694 &:= ((4! + 9!) - (C(T(6),9) - 6!)) \\
 69825 &:= (C(T(5),2) \times ((8!/T(9)) - T(T(6)))) \\
 69936 &:= (-C(T(6),T(3)) + (T(T(9)) \times T((9 + 6)))) \\
 70238 &:= (((-T(8)) + T(C(T(3),T(2))) - 0!) \times T(T(7))) \\
 70248 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times 4!) + C(T(T(T(2))), -((0! - (7)))))) \\
 70595 &:= -((C(T(5),9) - (T(5) \times (07!))) \\
 71435 &:= (C(T(5),3) \times (4 + T(17))) \\
 71456 &:= ((T(T(C(6,5))) - T(T(4))) \times T(T((1 \times 7)))) \\
 71589 &:= ((T(9) \times T(C(8,5))) - T(T(-((1 - 7)))))) \\
 71848 &:= ((T(C(8,4)) + (81)) \times T(7)) \\
 71928 &:= ((T(8) \times T(2)) \times T(C(C(9,1),7))) \\
 72325 &:= (T(C(5,2)) \times ((T(3))! + T((T(T(2)) + (T(7)))))) \\
 72338 &:= ((C((8 \times 3),T(3))/2) + 7!) \\
 72345 &:= (C(T(5),4) \times (-3) + (2 \times T(7))) \\
 72352 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))),T(5))/3) \times (-T(2) - (7))) \\
 72358 &:= (C((8 + 5),3) \times T(-((T(T(2)) - (T(7)))))) \\
 72359 &:= (((9!/5) - T(C(T(3),T(2)))) - 7) \\
 72384 &:= -((4! \times (C((8 \times 3),T(2)) - 7!)) \\
 72423 &:= (((C(T(T(3)),T(2)) \times T(T(4))) - (T(T(2)))!) - 7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}72445 &:= (-5) + ((T(4) \times T(C(T(4), 2))) \times 7)) \\72475 &:= ((-5) - 7!) + C((T(4) \times 2), 7) \\72589 &:= (((C(9, 8))! / 5) + T(T(2))) + 7 \\72738 &:= (T(T(8)) + (T(T(3)) \times C((7 \times 2), 7))) \\72793 &:= (((T(3))! - T(T(9))) \times (-T(C(7, 2)))) + (T(7))) \\72834 &:= (((C(4!, 3) \times T(8)) - 2) - T(7)) \\72863 &:= (((T(T(3)) - (C(T(6), 8))) / (-T(2))) + (7!)) \\72864 &:= (C(4!, T(6)) \times ((8^2) - T(7))) \\72865 &:= (-5) + ((C(T(6), 8) / T(2)) + 7!) \\72893 &:= (((T(3) \times T(C(9, 8)))^2) - (7)) \\73122 &:= ((C(T(T(T(2))), T(2)) \times T(T((1 + 3)))) - (T(7))) \\73227 &:= (T(C(7, 2)) \times ((T(2) + (T(3))! - T(T(7)))) \\73234 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times C(T(T(3)), T(2))) + (3 \times T(7))) \\73269 &:= (9 \times (T(6) + (C(T(T(2)), 3) \times T(T(7)))) \\73334 &:= -((T(T((T(4) + 3))) - (C(C(T(3), 3), 7)))) \\73535 &:= ((C(T(5), T(3)) \times T(5)) - T(T((3 + 7)))) \\73563 &:= -((T(T(3)) - (T((6! / C(5, 3))) \times T(7))) \\73584 &:= (T((4 \times (8 + C(5, 3)))) \times T(7)) \\73684 &:= (T(T(T(4))) + ((8! + C((6 \times 3), 7))) \\73942 &:= (-2) - (-4!) \times T(T((C(9, 3) / 7))) \\73969 &:= (((9! - C(T(6), 9)) - T(T(3))) + (7!)) \\73976 &:= (-((T(6) \times (T(7) - T(C(9, 3)))) - T(T(7))) \\73993 &:= -((C(T(T(3)), 9) - ((9! + 3) + 7!))) \\73996 &:= -((((C(T(6), 9) - 9!) - T(3)) - 7!)) \\74203 &:= (-((T(T(7)) + 4) + C((T(T(T(2))) + 0!), T(3))) \\74207 &:= -((T(T(7)) - C((4! - 2), -(0! - 7)))) \\74214 &:= (7 \times (C(4!, (T(2) + 1)) - 4!)) \\74228 &:= ((C((T(8) / 2), T(T(2))) \times 4) - (T(7))) \\74229 &:= ((T(C(9, T(2))) \times T(T(T(2)))) - T((T(4) + T(7)))) \\74244 &:= ((-7) + C(4!, 2)) \times (-4!) + T(4!)) \\74256 &:= ((T(7) - 4!) \times C((T(2) + T(5)), 6)) \\74258 &:= (8 + (T(5) \times T(-((T(T(T(2))) - C(T(4), 7)))))) \\74262 &:= ((C((-7) + 4!), T(T(2))) \times 6) + T(T(2)) \\74263 &:= (7 + (4 \times C((T(2) \times 6), T(3)))) \\74278 &:= (T(T(7)) + ((C(4!, T(2)) + T(7)) \times T(8))) \\74306 &:= ((-7) - T(4!)) + C((T(T(3)) + 0!), 6) \\74313 &:= -((T((T(7) - 4)) - C((T(T(3)) + 1), T(3))) \\74333 &:= (T(7) + (T(T(4)) \times (C(T(T(3)), 3) + T(T(3)))) \\74361 &:= (7! + ((T(4!) \times T(T(T(3)))) + T(C(6, 1))) \\74364 &:= (7! + ((T((C(4, 3))!) \times T(T(6))) + (4!)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}74368 &:= ((T(7) \times (C(4, 3)^6)) - 8!) \\74381 &:= ((7 \times C(4!, ((T(3)!/T(8)))) - 1) \\74402 &:= (((7 \times C(4!, 4)) - 0!) + T(T(T(2)))) \\74417 &:= (T(7) + ((C(4!, 4) + 1) \times 7)) \\74418 &:= ((7 \times C(4!, 4)) + T((1 \times 8))) \\74418 &:= (T(8) + (C(((1 \times 4)!, 4) \times 7)) \\74422 &:= ((7 \times (C(4!, 4) + T(T(2)))) - 2) \\74427 &:= ((7 \times C(4!, 4)) + T((2 + 7))) \\74429 &:= ((7 \times C(4!, 4)) + (2 + T(9))) \\74429 &:= ((T(9) + 2) + (C(4!, 4) \times 7)) \\74434 &:= ((7 \times (C(4!, 4) + T(3))) + T(4)) \\74437 &:= ((7 \times C(4!, 4)) + T((3 + 7))) \\74439 &:= -((T(T((9 + 3))) - (C((4! - (4)), 7)))) \\74442 &:= ((7 \times C(4!, 4)) + (T(4) \times T(T(2)))) \\74443 &:= (((7 \times C(4!, 4)) + T(T(4))) + T(3)) \\74446 &:= ((7 \times (C(4!, 4) + T(4))) - (6)) \\74463 &:= (-7) - (T(T(4)) \times (-4! + C(T(6), 3))) \\74469 &:= ((7 \times (C(4!, 4) + (6))) + T(9)) \\74469 &:= (T(9) + ((6 + C(4!, 4)) \times 7)) \\74473 &:= (7 \times ((C(4!, 4) + (7)) + T(3))) \\74519 &:= ((T(C(7, 4)) \times 5!) - T((1 + T(9)))) \\74574 &:= (T(C(7, 4)) + (T(T((5 + 7))) \times 4!)) \\74589 &:= ((9 - T(C(8, 5))) \times (-47)) \\74592 &:= ((7!/45) \times T(C(9, 2))) \\74595 &:= -((((T(7) + (4)) - C(T(5), 9)) \times T(5))) \\74602 &:= (-((7 + 4) + C((T(6) + 0!), T(T(2)))) \\74603 &:= -((T((T(7) - 4!)) - (C((T(6) + 0!), T(3)))) \\74606 &:= ((T(7)/(-4)) + C((T(6) + 0!), 6)) \\74613 &:= C(((7 \times 4) - 6), T((1 \times 3))) \\74616 &:= ((7 - 4) + C((T(6) + 1), 6)) \\74662 &:= (T(T(7)) + (C((-4) + T(6)), 6) \times T(T(2))) \\74755 &:= (((T(C(7, 4)) - (7)) \times 5!) - (5)) \\74766 &:= (T((-7) + 4!) + C((T(7) - (6)), 6)) \\74784 &:= ((C(7, 4) + T(78)) \times 4!) \\74808 &:= (T(8) \times (-((0! - T(C(8, 4)))) - T(T(7))) \\74851 &:= ((T(T(7)) - T(C(T(4), 8))) \times (-5! - 1)) \\74965 &:= ((T(T((7 - 4))) \times T(C(9, 6))) - 5) \\74966 &:= -((((T(7) - 4!) - (T(C(9, 6)) \times T(6)))) \\74970 &:= (T(T((7 - 4))) \times T(C(9, (7 - 0!)))) \\75048 &:= (T(T(8)) + (C(4!, -((0! - (5)))) \times 7))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 75145 &:= -((C(T(5), (4 - 1)) - (T(5) \times 7!))) \\ 75247 &:= (((T(C(7,4)) - T(2)) \times 5!) + (7)) \\ 75286 &:= -(((6! - T(C(8,2))) - (T(5) \times 7!))) \\ 75292 &:= ((T((T(2))!) \times (T(C(9,T(2))) + T(5))) + 7) \\ 75371 &:= ((1 + C(T(7),3)) \times (-5) + T(7)) \\ 75373 &:= (-3) + ((C(T(7),T(3))/5) + T(7)) \\ 75374 &:= (((T(4) - C(T(7),T(3)))/(-5)) + T(7)) \\ 75376 &:= ((C((T(6) + (7)),T(3))/5) + T(7)) \\ 75378 &:= ((T(T(C(8,7)))/(-3)) + ((T(5) \times 7!))) \\ 75526 &:= (C(6,T(T(2))) - (T(5) \times (5 - 7!))) \\ 75535 &:= ((T(C(5,3)) - 5!) + (T(5) \times 7!)) \\ 75544 &:= (-C((4 + 4),5) + (T(5) \times 7!)) \\ 75554 &:= (C((4! - 5), (5!/T(5))) - T(7)) \\ 75565 &:= (((T(5) \times (C(6,5))!) - 5) \times 7) \\ 75582 &:= C(((T(2) \times 8) - 5), (T(5) - 7)) \\ 75589 &:= ((T(9) - (C(8,5))) + (T(5) \times 7!)) \\ 75599 &:= (-C(9,9) + (5! \times T((5 \times 7)))) \\ 75612 &:= ((C(2,1) \times 6) + (T(5) \times 7!)) \\ 75626 &:= ((C(6,T(2)) + 6) + (T(5) \times 7!)) \\ 75627 &:= ((C(7,2) + 6) + (T(5) \times 7!)) \\ 75673 &:= (((3 + (C(7,6))!) \times T(5)) + T(7)) \\ 75677 &:= (((7! + C(7,6)) \times T(5)) - T(7)) \\ 75694 &:= ((T(4) + (C(9,6))) + (T(5) \times 7!)) \\ 75714 &:= (4! + (C((-1) + T(7)),5) - 7!) \\ 75742 &:= ((T(T(T(T(2)))) \times T(4!)) - (-7 - C(T(5),7))) \\ 75744 &:= ((4! + C(T(4),7)) + (T(5) \times 7!)) \\ 75754 &:= ((-C(T(4),5) + T(T(7))) + ((T(5) \times 7!))) \\ 75888 &:= (T(8) \times (T((8 + C(8,5))) + T(7))) \\ 75925 &:= (T(T(C(5,2))) + (T(9) \times T(57))) \\ 75978 &:= (T((T(C(8,7)) - 9)) + ((T(5) \times 7!))) \\ 76048 &:= ((T(C(8,4)) + T(T(06))) \times T(7)) \\ 76079 &:= -(((T(T(9)) + T(T(7))) - C(-((0! - T(6))),7))) \\ 76089 &:= -((T((T(9) + 8)) - C(-((0! - T(6))),7))) \\ 76142 &:= -((T((-T(2)) + T(T(4))) - (C((-1) + T(6)),7))) \\ 76188 &:= -(((T(T(8)) + T(T(8))) - (C((-1) + T(6)),7))) \\ 76328 &:= (((T(C(8,T(2)))/(-3)) + (6!)) \times T(T(7))) \\ 76338 &:= -(((8! - T((3^3))) - C(T(6),7)) \\ 76387 &:= (((T(T(7)) - 8!) + T(T(3))) + C(T(6),7)) \\ 76435 &:= (-5) + (T(C(T(3),4)) \times (T(T(6)) + T(T(7)))) \\ 76446 &:= -((C(T(6), (4 + 4)) - (6^7))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76488 &:= -(((8! - T((8 \times 4))) - C(T(6), 7))) \\
 76664 &:= (((C(4!, T(6)) + 6!) - (6)) \times T(7)) \\
 76832 &:= (((T(T(2)))! + C((3 \times 8), T(6))) \times T(7)) \\
 76845 &:= (T(5) \times (T(T(4)) + (C(8, 6) + 7!))) \\
 76863 &:= (T((T(T(3)) + (T(6)))) - ((8! - C(T(6), 7)))) \\
 76902 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times (T((0! + (C(9, 6)))) + 7)) \\
 77069 &:= (-((T(9) - C((T(6) - 0!), 7))) - T(T(7))) \\
 77114 &:= (C((T(4) \times (1 + 1)), 7) - T(T(7))) \\
 77124 &:= (T(4) + (C((T(T(T(2))) - 1), 7) - (T(T(7))))) \\
 77206 &:= (-6!) + (C((-0! + T(T(T(2)))), 7) + (T(T(7)))) \\
 77415 &:= (T(5) \times (1 + (C(T(4), 7) + 7!))) \\
 77428 &:= (((T(T(8)) - T(T(T(2)))) \times C(T(4), 7)) + (T(7))) \\
 77515 &:= (-5) + C((-1) + T(T(T(-(5 - 7))))), 7) \\
 77535 &:= (T(5) + C((-((3 + 5)) + T(7)), 7)) \\
 77542 &:= -((T(T(2)) - (C((4 \times 5), 7) + T(7))) \\
 77544 &:= (-((4 - C((4 \times 5), 7))) + T(7)) \\
 77548 &:= (C(((8 - 4) \times 5), 7) + T(7)) \\
 77595 &:= (T(5) \times ((C(9, 5) + 7) + 7!)) \\
 77616 &:= (C((T(6) + 1), 6) + T(7)) \\
 77624 &:= (C(4!, T(2)) + (6! \times T((7 + 7)))) \\
 77716 &:= (C((T(6) - 1), 7) - (-7) \times T(7)) \\
 77835 &:= ((T(5) \times T(T(3))) + (C((-8) + T(7)), 7)) \\
 77844 &:= (T(4!) + (4! + C((-8) + T(7)), 7)) \\
 77845 &:= (T((T(5) + T(4))) + (C((-8) + T(7)), 7)) \\
 77889 &:= ((T(T(9)) - T(T(8))) + (C((-8) + T(7)), 7)) \\
 77895 &:= (T(5) \times (T((9 + C(8, 7))) + 7!)) \\
 77898 &:= (T((T(8) - 9)) + (C((-8) + T(7)), 7)) \\
 77926 &:= (C(C(6, -((T(T(2)) - 9))), 7) + (T(T(7)))) \\
 78235 &:= ((-5) + (T(3))!) + C(((T(T(2)))! / T(8)), 7) \\
 78345 &:= ((T(5) \times T(T(4))) + C(((T(3))! / T(8)), 7)) \\
 78364 &:= (-C(4!, T(6))) - (T(T(3)) \times (-T(87))) \\
 78384 &:= ((4! \times T(8)) + C(((T(3))! / T(8)), 7)) \\
 78407 &:= ((C((T(7) + 0!), 4!) - 8!) - T(7)) \\
 78421 &:= ((-1) + T(C(T(T(2)), 4))) \times (T(T(8)) - 7) \\
 78456 &:= (C(T(6), T(5)) + ((4! \times T(8)) \times T(7))) \\
 78648 &:= (T((-8) + T(T(4)))) + C((6! / T(8)), 7) \\
 78726 &:= (-6) + ((T(2)⁷) \times T(C(8, 7))) \\
 78731 &:= (-1) - (-((3⁷) \times T(C(8, 7))) \\
 78732 &:= ((-((T(2) - T(3))⁷) \times T(C(8, 7))) \\
 78795 &:= (T((5 + T(9))) + (C((T(7) - 8), 7)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 78939 &:= (((T(T(9)) + (T(3))!) \times T(9)) - T(C(8,7))) \\
 78975 &:= (-((T(5) - T(7))) \times (T(T(C(9,8))) + (7!))) \\
 79044 &:= ((C(4!,4) + T(T(-(0! - 9)))) \times 7) \\
 79164 &:= (C(4!, T(6)) - (-T(19) \times T(T(7)))) \\
 79244 &:= ((T((T(T(4)) + C(4, T(2)))) \times T(9)) - (T(T(7)))) \\
 79252 &:= (-T(2) - (-T(C(5,2))) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(7)))) \\
 79254 &:= (((-4) + 5!) + T(2)) \times T(C(9,7)) \\
 79255 &:= (T(C(5, (5 - 2))) \times (T(T(9)) + T(T(7)))) \\
 79455 &:= (T(5) + (5! \times (-4) + T(C(9,7)))) \\
 79542 &:= -(T((T(2) + 4!) - (5! \times T(C(9,7)))) \\
 79548 &:= ((T((C(8,4) + 5)) - 9) \times T(7)) \\
 79625 &:= (-C(T(5), T(2)) \times (T(T(T(-(6 - 9)))) - (T(T(7)))) \\
 79674 &:= ((T(T(T(4))) \times (C(7,6) + T(9))) - (T(T(7)))) \\
 79765 &:= ((C((-5) + T(6)), 7) - T(9)) \times 7 \\
 79933 &:= ((T(T(3)) - C((T(3)!/T(9)), 9)) \times (-7)) \\
 79948 &:= ((T(T(8)) \times ((4 + C(9,9)))! + (T(7))) \\
 79974 &:= (((T(-(4! - T(7))))! / T(9)) - T(C(9,7))) \\
 79975 &:= ((T(5) - C((7 + 9), 9)) \times (-7)) \\
 80325 &:= (C(T(5), 2) \times ((T(3)! + T((0! + 8)))) \\
 80578 &:= ((T(T(C(8,7))) \times (5! + 0!)) - 8) \\
 82125 &:= (T((T(C(5,2)) - 1) + (2 \times 8!)) \\
 82134 &:= ((T(4!) \times C(((3 + 1)!, 2)) - T(T(8))) \\
 82238 &:= ((T(C(8,3)) + 2) + (2 \times 8!)) \\
 82278 &:= (8! + ((C(T(7), T(2))/2) + 8!)) \\
 82345 &:= (((-5) + C(T(4), T(3)))^2 + 8!) \\
 82643 &:= -((T(T(3)) - (C(4!, T(6)) + (2 \times 8!))) \\
 82664 &:= ((C(4!, T(6)) + ((6 + 2)!) + 8!) \\
 82674 &:= (-((4! \times (7! - (6)))) + C(T(T(T(2))), 8)) \\
 82678 &:= (T(T(8)) - (T(T(7)) \times (-C(T(6), 2) - 8))) \\
 82747 &:= (C(T(7), 4!) + ((T(7)^{T(2)} + 8!)) \\
 83054 &:= (((C(4!, 5) - 0!) + T(T(T(3)))) + 8!) \\
 83196 &:= (-6!) - (-C(9, (1 + 3)) \times T(T(8))) \\
 83302 &:= (2 \times (0! + (C(T(T(3)), 3) + 8!)) \\
 83324 &:= (4! - (-2) \times (C(T(T(3)), 3) + 8!)) \\
 83364 &:= -((T(4!) - (6 \times (C(T(T(3)), T(3)) - 8!))) \\
 83469 &:= ((T(C(9,6)) \times 4!) - T(T((3 + 8)))) \\
 83542 &:= (((-2) + C(4!, 5)) + (T(3))! + 8!) \\
 83544 &:= ((C(4!, (T(4) - 5)) + (T(3))! + 8!) \\
 83556 &:= ((T(6) + C((5 \times 5), 3)) \times T(8)) \\
 83622 &:= (T(T(T(2))) \times ((T(2) \times C(T(6), 3)) - 8))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}83768 &:= (8 \times (6 + (C(T(7), T(3))/T(8)))) \\83826 &:= (-6) - ((-2) \times (T(C(8, 3)) + 8!)) \\83832 &:= ((T(T(2))/3) \times (T(C(8, 3)) + 8!)) \\83847 &:= ((C((T(7) - T(4)), 8) - T(T(T(3)))) + 8!) \\83859 &:= (((C(9, 5) \times T(T(8))) - T(T(3))) - T(8)) \\83888 &:= (8! - ((-8) \times T(C(8, T(3)))) - 8!) \\83916 &:= ((6 + C((1 + 9), 3)) \times T(T(8))) \\84078 &:= (8! + C((T(7) - T(04)), 8)) \\84254 &:= (((4 + T(T(C(5, 2)))) \times T(T(4))) - T(T(8))) \\84525 &:= (C(T(5), 2) \times (-T(5) + T((4 + T(8)))))) \\84534 &:= (((-T(4)) + (T(3))!) \times (C(5, 4))! - T(T(8))) \\84535 &:= (T(C(5, 3)) \times ((5 + T(T(T(4)))) - 8)) \\84544 &:= ((T(T(4)) \times T(T(T(4)))) - ((C(5, 4))! + T(8))) \\84546 &:= (T(T(6)) \times (C((-4) + T(5)), 4) + T(8)) \\84636 &:= (6! - (-C((3 + 6), 4) \times T(T(8)))) \\84654 &:= ((C(4!, 5) + T((6 \times T(4)))) + 8!) \\84732 &:= ((T(C(T(T(2)), 3)) \times T(T(7))) - T((4 \times 8))) \\84979 &:= ((T(T(9)) + (T(7))) + (C(9, 4) \times T(T(8)))) \\84984 &:= (-4!) - (C(((T(8)/9))!, 4) \times (-8)) \\85184 &:= ((C(T(4), 8) - 1)^{-5+8}) \\85237 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times T(C(T(3), T(2)))) - (T(5) + 8)) \\85248 &:= (((T(C(8, 4)) + T(2)) - 5!) \times T(8)) \\85323 &:= -(((T(T(3))^{T(2)}) - (C(T(T(3)), T(5)) + 8!)) \\85365 &:= ((T(5) \times C((T(6) - T(3)), 5)) + 8!) \\85525 &:= (C(T(5), T(T(2))) - ((-5!) \times (5 + T(T(8)))))) \\85635 &:= -((T(5) \times ((T(3) + 6!) - C(T(5), 8)))) \\85674 &:= (((4!)! \times 7) / (T(C(6, 5))!) + T(T(8))) \\85744 &:= (((C(4!, 4) - T(7)) + 5!) \times 8) \\85893 &:= -((T(T(3)) + ((-C(9, 8) - 5!) \times T(T(8)))))) \\85914 &:= (((4 - 1) + C(9, 5)) \times T(T(8))) \\85924 &:= (T(4) - (-((T(2) + (C(9, 5)))) \times T(T(8)))) \\86292 &:= ((T((2 \times C(9, 2))) - T(T(6))) \times T(8)) \\86343 &:= (((T(3))! \times C(T(4), 3)) - (T(6) + T(8))) \\86346 &:= (((6! \times C(T(4), 3)) - 6!) + T(T(8))) \\86364 &:= ((C((4 + 6), 3) \times 6!) - T(8)) \\86428 &:= (C(8, 2) - ((T(4))! / (-6 - T(8)))) \\86433 &:= (-3) - ((T(C(T(3), 4)) \times (-6!)) - T(8)) \\86438 &:= ((-T(C(8, 3))) - (T(4))!) / (-6 - T(8)) \\86544 &:= (4! \times (T(C((4 + 5), 6)) + T(8))) \\86625 &:= ((C(T(5), 2) + 6!) \times T((6 + 8)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 86855 &:= ((C(T(5),5) - 8) \times (T(6) + 8)) \\
 86969 &:= ((C(9,6) \times T(T(9))) + (T(6) + 8)) \\
 87075 &:= ((C(T(5),7) + ((0! + (7)))!) + 8!) \\
 87216 &:= (6 \times (1 - (C(T(T(T(2))),7)/(-8)))) \\
 87222 &:= (T(T(2)) \times (2 - (C(T(T(T(2))),7)/(-8)))) \\
 87225 &:= (T(5) - (T(T(2)) \times (C(T(T(T(2))),7)/(-8)))) \\
 87298 &:= ((C((8 + 9),T(T(2))) \times 7) + T(T(8))) \\
 87336 &:= (6 \times (T(T(3)) - (C(T(T(3)),7)/(-8)))) \\
 87346 &:= ((6! \times C(T(4),3)) + T((7 + T(8)))) \\
 87426 &:= (((6! + T(2)) \times C(T(4),7)) + T(T(8))) \\
 87534 &:= (((C(T(4),T(3)) \times T(5)) \times T(7)) - T(T(8))) \\
 87668 &:= (-C(8,6) - ((-6) \times T(T(7))) \times T(8)) \\
 88424 &:= (C(4!,T(2)) - (T(4!) \times (-8) \times T(8))) \\
 88438 &:= (((T(C(8,3)) \times T(T(4))) + T(T(8))) - 8) \\
 88794 &:= ((T((C(T(4),9) \times 7)) \times T(8)) - T(T(8))) \\
 88932 &:= ((C((T(2) \times T(3)),9) - 8) + 8!) \\
 88938 &:= (((C(8,T(3)) + T(9)) \times T(T(8))) + 8!) \\
 88948 &:= ((C((8 + T(4)),9) + 8) + 8!) \\
 89064 &:= -(((C(4!,T(6)) \times (0! - T(9))) - 8)) \\
 89234 &:= ((C(4!,T(3)) - 2) - (9!/8)) \\
 89236 &:= (C((T(6) + 3),T(T(2))) - (9!/8)) \\
 89242 &:= (T(T(2)) + (C(4!,T(T(2))) - (9!/8))) \\
 89268 &:= (86 \times (T(2) + T(T(C(9,8)))))) \\
 89424 &:= ((C(4!, -((2 - 4))) \times 9) \times T(8)) \\
 89484 &:= -((T(4!) - (((T(C(8,4)) + 9) \times T(8)))))) \\
 89592 &:= (T(T(2)) - (C(9,5) \times (-T(9) - T(T(8)))))) \\
 89635 &:= (C(T(5),3) \times ((T(6) \times 9) + 8)) \\
 89649 &:= ((T(9) \times C(4!,T(6))) - T((T(9) + 8))) \\
 89667 &:= ((T(7) - C(6,6)) \times T((T(9) + T(8)))) \\
 89685 &:= (((5! \times T(8)) \times T(6)) - T(T(C(9,8)))) \\
 89775 &:= (T(5) \times C((-7) + T(7), (9 + 8))) \\
 90435 &:= (T(5) \times (C(T(T(3)),4) - ((0! - T(9)))))) \\
 90465 &:= (T(5) \times ((C(T(6),4) + 0!) + T(9))) \\
 91245 &:= (5! + ((C(4!,T(2)) + 1) \times T(9))) \\
 91565 &:= ((-5) \times (C(T(6),T(5)) - 1) + 9!) \\
 91568 &:= (8 \times (6 + C((T(5) + 1),9))) \\
 91727 &:= ((C(T(7),T(2)) \times T(7)) - (1^9)) \\
 91737 &:= ((C(T(7),3) \times T(7)) + (1 \times 9)) \\
 91756 &:= ((T(T(6)) - 5) \times T(T(C(7,(1^9)))))) \\
 91944 &:= -(((T(9) - C(19,4)) \times 4!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 92225 &:= (-T((T(5) + 2)) + C((T(T(T(2))) - 2), 9)) \\ 92234 &:= (-((4! \times T(3))) + C((T(T(T(2))) - 2), 9)) \\ 92252 &:= (-((T(T(2)) + (5!))) + C((T(T(T(2))) - 2), 9)) \\ 92254 &:= ((-4) - 5!) + C((T(T(T(2))) - 2), 9)) \\ 92258 &:= ((-8) \times T(5)) + C((T(T(T(2))) - 2), 9)) \\ 92259 &:= ((9!/5) + (C(T(2), 2)^9)) \\ 92273 &:= -((T((T(T(3)) - 7)) - C((T(T(T(2))) - 2), 9))) \\ 92323 &:= -((T(T((T(3) - 2))) - C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9))) \\ 92333 &:= (-T((3 \times 3))) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9)) \\ 92336 &:= ((-T(6) - T(T(3))) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9)) \\ 92339 &:= (-((T(9) - T(3))) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9)) \\ 92342 &:= (-T((2 \times 4))) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9)) \\ 92344 &:= (-((4! + T(4))) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9)) \\ 92347 &:= ((-7) - 4!) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9)) \\ 92352 &:= -((T(T(T(2))) + (5 - C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9)))) \\ 92354 &:= -((4! - C((T(5) + T(3)) - 2), 9))) \\ 92355 &:= (((-5!) \times T(T(C(5, 3)))) / (-2) - T(9)) \\ 92357 &:= -(C(7, 5) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9)) \\ 92363 &:= ((T(3) - T(6)) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9)) \\ 92366 &:= -((6 + 6) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9)) \\ 92369 &:= (-9) + C((T(6) - (T(3)/T(2))), 9)) \\ 92371 &:= (-((1 \times 7)) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9)) \\ 92375 &:= -((T(-(5 - 7)) - C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9))) \\ 92377 &:= -(C(7, 7) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9)) \\ 92378 &:= C(((-8) + T(7)) - (3 - 2), 9) \\ 92383 &:= -((3 - 8) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9)) \\ 92384 &:= (T((4!/8)) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9)) \\ 92393 &:= ((T(3) + 9) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9)) \\ 92397 &:= ((T(7) - 9) + C((T(T(3)) - 2), 9)) \\ 92423 &:= ((C(C(T(3), T(2)), T(4))/2) + T(9)) \\ 92426 &:= ((C((T(6) - 2), T(4)) + T(2)) + T(9)) \\ 92432 &:= (C((-2) + T(T(3))), T(4)) + (T(T(2)) \times 9)) \\ 92445 &:= (C(T(5), 4) + (C(4!, T(2)) \times T(9))) \\ 92466 &:= ((6 \times T(T(6))) + ((C(4!, T(2)) \times T(9)))) \\ 92575 &:= ((T(-(T(5) - T(7))) \times C(T(5), T(T(2)))) - 9!) \\ 92577 &:= ((T(T(7)) \times (T(C(7, 5)) - T(2))) + 9) \\ 92631 &:= (T((1 + T(T(3)))) + C((T(6) - 2), 9)) \\ 92664 &:= ((T(T(4)) + T(T(6))) + C((T(6) - 2), 9)) \\ 92693 &:= -((((T(3))! - T(T(9))) - C((T(6) - 2), 9))) \\ 92751 &:= ((T(T((1 + 5))) \times T(T(C(7, T(T(2))))) - T(T(9))) \end{aligned}$$

92757 := (((T(C(7,5)) × T(T(7))) + T(T(2))) - T(T(9)))
92997 := ((T(7) × T((T(9) + C(9,2)))) + 9)
93285 := ((5! + T((C(8,T(2)) + T(3)))) × T(9))
93288 := (-((T(8) + C(8,T(2)))) × (T(T(3)) - T(T(9))))
93435 := ((T(T(C(5,3))) × (T(4) × T(3))) + T(T(9)))
93599 := (-C(9,9) + (5! × T(39)))
93632 := ((C(((- 2) + T(3)))!, 6) × (T(3)!)/T(T(9)))
93756 := (((T(T(C(6,5))) × T(T(7))) - T(T(3))) - 9)
93776 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T(7))) - C((7 + 3), 9))
93831 := (((- 1) × T(T(T(3)))) × (-T(C(8, T(3)))) + T(9))
94269 := (C(9,6) + (T((T(2) + T(4))) × T(T(9))))
94368 := ((8! + C(T(6), T(3))) + (4! × (-9)))
94473 := ((- 3) + (C(7,4) × T(4!))) × 9
94489 := (-((9 - C(8,4))) × (T(T(T(4))) + 9))
94538 := (8! + ((C(T(T(3)), T(5)) - T(T(4))) + 9))
94584 := (T(T(T(4))) + (T(T(8)) + C((-5) + 4!), 9))
94599 := (9 × C(((9 - 5)!, 4)) - T(T(9)))
94608 := (T(8) × T(((06)!/C(T(4), 9)))
94776 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T(7))) + T((C(7,4) + 9)))
94822 := ((T(T(T(2))) × (C(T(T(T(2))), 8) - T(4!)))/T(9))
94867 := ((T(T(7)) × T(T(6))) + T((T(8) + C(T(4), 9))))
95095 := (C(T(5), 9) × (T(-((0! - 5)))) + 9))
95326 := (T(T(6)) - ((-2) + T(T(3))) × (-C(T(5), 9)))
95444 := -((T(T(4)) + ((C(4!, 4) - T(5)) × (-9)))
95618 := (((8! - 1) + C(T(6), T(5))) + T(T(9)))
95619 := (((9 - 1)!) + C(T(6), T(5))) + T(T(9)))
95704 := -((T(T(T(4))) + ((0! - C(T(7), 5)) + T(T(9))))
95705 := -((T(T(T((5 - 0!)))) + (-C(T(7), 5) + T(T(9))))
95725 := (((T(5) + T(2)) × 7!) + C(T(5), 9))
95745 := (((- 5) × T(4!)) + (C(T(7), 5))) - T(T(9)))
95886 := ((T(T(6)) × T(T(8))) - (C(8, 5) × T(T(9))))
96348 := ((- ((T(8) - C(4!, 3))) × T(T(6))) - 9!)
96535 := (T(C(5, 3)) - (5! × (T(T(6)) - T(T(9)))))
96756 := (T(T(6)) - (C(T(5), 7) × (-6 + 9)))
96768 := ((8 × 6) × T((C(7, 6) × 9)))
96936 := (T(T(6)) - (T(T(3)) × (-T(C(9, 6))) - T(T(9))))
97217 := (C(T(7), (-1) + T(T(2))) - (T(7) + T(T(9))))
97236 := ((C(T(6), 3) + 2) × (T(7) + T(9)))
97257 := (((T(C(7, 5)) + T(T(2))) × T(T(7))) + T(T(9)))
97263 := (((T(3))! × C(6, 2)) + 7) × 9

$$\begin{aligned}
 97325 &:= ((C(T(5), T(T(2))) + (T(3))!) \times (- (T(7) - T(9)))) \\
 97422 &:= (2 \times ((T(C(T(T(2)), 4)) \times T(T(7))) - 9)) \\
 97465 &:= (5 \times (C((T(6) - (4)), 7) + T(9))) \\
 97555 &:= ((- (5) + (T(5) \times C(T(5), 7))) + T(T(9))) \\
 97576 &:= -((6! - (C(T(7), 5) + ((7 + 9)))))) \\
 97577 &:= (C(T(7), (T(7) - (5))) - T((T(7) + 9))) \\
 97657 &:= (((C(T(7), 5) + (6)) + T(T(7))) - T(T(9))) \\
 97749 &:= (((C(9, 4) \times T(7)) \times T(7)) - T(T(9))) \\
 97825 &:= (C(T(5), T(2)) \times ((8 \times T(7)) - 9)) \\
 97846 &:= ((T(T(6)) + T(4)) \times T(C(8, -((7 - 9)))))) \\
 97857 &:= (((C(T(7), 5) - 8) - T(T(7))) - 9) \\
 98127 &:= (C(T(7), (T(T(2)) - 1)) - T((8 + 9))) \\
 98227 &:= (C(T(7), (2 + T(2))) - (8 + T(9))) \\
 98257 &:= ((C(T(7), 5) - T(T(2))) - (8 + 9)) \\
 98271 &:= (C(T((1 \times 7)), -((T(2) - 8))) - 9) \\
 98289 &:= ((T(T(9)) \times C(8, T(2))) + (8! + 9)) \\
 98307 &:= (C(T(7), -((0! - T(3)))) + (T(8) - 9)) \\
 98317 &:= (C(T(7), (- (1) + T(3))) - (8 - T(9))) \\
 98325 &:= (C(T((5 + 2)), -((3 - 8))) + T(9)) \\
 98343 &:= (((C(T(T(3)), T(4)) \times T(3)) / (-8)) + 9!) \\
 98357 &:= ((C(T(7), 5) + 3) - (T(T(8)) / (-9))) \\
 98457 &:= ((C(T(7), 5) + 4!) + T((8 + 9))) \\
 98637 &:= ((T(T(7)) + T(T(3))) \times T(C(T(6), -((8 - 9)))))) \\
 98857 &:= ((C(T(7), 5) + T(T(8))) - (89)) \\
 99245 &:= ((T(5)^4) + C((2 \times 9), 9)) \\
 99954 &:= (((T(4)^5) - T(9)) - C(9, 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

3 Summary: Selfie Numbers

The author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides of the expressions are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some operations. These types of numbers we call **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers** [2, 3, 4]. Friedmann [6, 7] also made some study in this direction. These numbers are represented by their own digits by use of certain operations. Following subsections give different ways of writing **selfie numbers**. Examples of selfie numbers are with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, **Quadratic numbers**, **Cubic numbers**, etc. In two variables, we obtained selfie numbers with **binomial coefficients**, **S-gonal numbers**, **centered polygonal numbers**, etc. The other way of writing **selfie numbers** is by use of **permutable powers**, where **bases** and **exponents** are of same digits. See the subsection below with some examples.

3.1 Permutable Powers

Below are some examples of **permutable power selfie numbers**. By **permutable powers**, we understand that bases and exponents are of same digits with different permutations. Some times we may call them as **flexible power selfie numbers**.

$1 := 1^1$	$3529 := -3^3 + 5^5 + 2^9 - 9^2$
$23 := -2^2 + 3^3$	$4316 := 4^6 + 3^1 + 1^4 + 6^3$
$1239 := 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^3$	$4355 := 4^5 + 3^4 + 5^3 + 5^5$
$1364 := 1^6 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 4^3$	$39339 := -3^3 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 9^3$
$1654 := -1^6 + 6^1 + 5^4 + 4^5$	$46350 := -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 0^4$
$1837 := 1^8 - 8^1 + 3^7 - 7^3$	$46360 := 4^0 + 6^6 - 3^4 - 6^3 + 0^6$
$2137 := -2^1 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 7^2$	$397612 := 3^2 + 9^1 + 7^6 + 6^7 + 1^9 + 2^3$
$2173 := -2^3 + 1^2 - 7^1 + 3^7$	$423858 := 4^3 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 8^2 + 5^8 + 8^5$
$2537 := 2^5 - 5^2 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$637395 := 6^5 + 3^3 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 9^6 + 5^7$
$3125 := -3^2 + 1^1 + 2^3 + 5^5$	$758014 := 7^7 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 0^5 + 1^4 - 4^8$
$3275 := -3^3 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 5^5$	$778530 := 7^7 + 7^3 + 8^5 - 5^7 + 3^0 + 0^8$
$3435 := 3^3 + 4^4 + 3^3 + 5^5$	$804637 := 8^0 + 0^4 - 4^8 + 6^6 - 3^3 + 7^7$

$15647982 := 1^5 - 5^9 + 6^2 + 4^4 + 7^7 - 9^1 + 8^8 + 2^6$
$17946238 := 1^6 + 7^8 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 6^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 8^7$
$57396108 := -5^6 + 7^9 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 6^7 + 1^1 + 0^0 + 8^8$
$134287690 := 1^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 2^4 + 8^9 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 0^1$
$387945261 := 3^3 + 8^2 + 7^6 + 9^9 + 4^7 + 5^8 + 2^4 + 6^1 + 1^5$
$392876054 := 3^0 + 9^9 - 2^2 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 + 0^3 - 5^4 + 4^6$
$392876540 := -3^0 + 9^9 - 2^4 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 - 5^3 + 4^6 + 0^2$

More details can be seen in author's work [20].

3.2 Basic Operations

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** by use of **basic operations**. See below some examples in both orders:

$13825 := 1 + (3 \times 8)^{-2+5}$	$= ((5 - 2) \times 8)^3 + 1$
$14641 := (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1$	$= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1$
$15552 := (1^5 + 5)^5 \times 2$	$= 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 1$
$16377 := (1 + 6 - 3)^7 - 7$	$= -7 + (7 - 3)^{6+1}$
$23328 := (2 \times 3^3)^2 \times 8$	$= (8 - 2)^{3+3} / 2$
$116565 := (-1 + 16) \times (-5 + 6^5)$	$= 5 \times (3 \times 6^{6-1} - 1)$
$131072 := (1 + 3)^{1+0+7} \times 2$	$= 2^{(7+0-1) \times 3-1}$

$$\begin{aligned} 147419 &:= -1 + (4^7 - 4) \times 1 \times 9 = 9 \times (1 \times 4^7 - 4) - 1 \\ 147429 &:= 1 + (4^7 - 4/2) \times 9 = 9 \times (2 + 4^7 - 4 - 1) \\ 147491 &:= 1 \times (4^7 + 4) \times 9 - 1 = 1 \times 9 \times (4^7 + 4) - 1 \\ 156252 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 2 = 2 \times (5^{2 \times 6 - 5} + 1) \end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and in reverse order of digits:

$$\begin{aligned} 656250 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 0 = 0 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ 656251 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 1 = 1 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ 656252 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 2 = 2 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ 656253 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 3 = 3 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ 656254 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 4 = 4 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ 656255 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 5 = 5 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ 656256 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 6 = 6 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ 656257 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 7 = 7 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ 656258 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 8 = 8 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ 656259 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 9 = 9 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6. \end{aligned}$$

The past work up to 6 digits numbers can be seen in [14, 15, 16, 30].

3.3 Factorial

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **factorial**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned} 145 &:= 1! + 4! + 5! & 361469 &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\ 733 &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! & 363239 &:= 36 + 323 + 9! \\ 1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & 363269 &:= 363 + 26 + 9! \\ 5177 &:= 5! + 17 + 7! & 364292 &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\ 10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! & 397584 &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\ 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! & 398173 &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \\ 80518 &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! & 403199 &:= 40319 + 9! \\ 317489 &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9! & 408937 &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\ 352797 &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! & 715799 &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9! \\ 357592 &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! & 720599 &:= -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9! \\ 357941 &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1! \end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and are only with positive and negative coefficients. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways:

$$\begin{aligned} 35280 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ 35281 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 35282 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35283 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35284 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35285 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35286 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35287 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35288 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35289 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [26, 27].

3.4 Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **square-root**. See below some examples in both orders, i.e., in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$1764 := 1 \times (7 \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}}$	$64 := \sqrt{4^6}$
$2378 := -23 + \sqrt{7^8}$	$1024 := \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 1}$
$19454 := 19 \times 4^5 - \sqrt{4}$	$1296 := 6^{\sqrt{9+2-1}}$
$19459 := 19 \times 4^5 + \sqrt{9}$	$2189 := \sqrt{9^{8-1}} + 2$
$19684 := 1 + \sqrt{9\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}/4}}$	$3867 := (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 3$
$839793 := (-8 + (-3 + 9)^7 + \sqrt{9}) \times 3$	$9375 := \sqrt{5^{7+3}} \times 9$
$839795 := -8 + (-3 + 9)^7 \times \sqrt{9} - 5$	$12289 := \sqrt{9} \times 8^{2 \times 2} + 1$
$839804 := (-8 + (3 - 9)^8 + 0) / \sqrt{4}$	$19693 := 3^9 + 6 + \sqrt{9} + 1$
$839816 := (8 + (3 - 9)^8) / \sqrt{\sqrt{16}}$	$42436 := (6 \times 34 + 2)^{\sqrt{4}}$
$995544 := ((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 54) \times 4$	$59051 := \sqrt{-1 + 5} + 0 + 9^5$
$999916 := -9 \times 9 - \sqrt{9} + (9 + 1)^6$	$999901 := (10^{9-\sqrt{9}}) - 99$
$999976 := -\sqrt{9} \times 9 + \sqrt{9} + (\sqrt{9} + 7)^6$	$999991 := (1^9 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9$

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details refer author's work [14, 15].

3.5 Factorial and Square-Root

Below are some examples with **factorial** and **square-root** written in both ways, i.e., in **digit's order** and its reverse

$$\begin{aligned}
 936 &:= (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6! &= 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 1296 &:= \sqrt{(1 + 2)!^9 / 6} &= 6^{(\sqrt{9}+2-1)} \\
 2896 &:= 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!) &= (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 331779 &:= 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}} &= \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3 \\
 342995 &:= (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 &= -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3 \\
 759375 &:= (-7 + 59 - 37)^5 &= (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9-5+7}}. \\
 759381 &:= 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1 &= -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5040 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 0 = 0 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5041 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 1 = 1 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5042 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 2 = 2 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5043 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 = 3 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5044 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 4 = 4 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5045 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 5 = 5 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5046 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 6 = 6 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5047 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 7 = 7 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5048 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 8 = 8 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5049 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 9 = 9 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!
 \end{aligned}$$

The following examples are in **digit's order** and its **reverse** separately:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 120 := ((1 + 2)! - 0!)! & 64 := \sqrt{4^6} \\
 127 := -1 + 2^7 & 289 := (9 + 8)^2 \\
 1673 := -1 - 6 + 7!/3 & 3894 := \left(\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{(\sqrt{9})!^8}\right) \times 3 \\
 1679 := 1 + (-6 + 7!)/\sqrt{9} & 4957 := 7! - 59 - 4! \\
 1680 := (1 + 6)!/\sqrt{8 + 0!} & 6992 := 2^9 + 9 \times 6! \\
 38970 := -3!! + 8! - 9 \times 70 & 26493 := (2 + 6)! - 4!^{\sqrt{9}} - 3 \\
 38986 := -3 + 8! - \sqrt{(\sqrt{9} + 8)^6} & 30792 := 3! \times ((0 + 7)! + 92) \\
 40310 := (\sqrt{4^{03}})! - 10 & 54476 := (5! + 4!^4 - 7!)/6 \\
 90894 := -(\sqrt{9})! + ((0! + 8)! + (\sqrt{9})!)/4 & 75989 := \sqrt{9} \times \left(8 - (\sqrt{9})!\right) + 5^7 \\
 91560 := ((\sqrt{9})! + 1)! + 5! \times (6! + 0!) & \\
 \\
 25 := 5^2 &
 \end{array}$$

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For details refer author's work [14, 15, 16].

3.6 Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence numbers are well known in literature. This sequence is defined as

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n + 1) = F(n) + F(n - 1), \quad n \geq 1.$$

Below are examples of **selfie numbers** by use of **Fibonacci sequence values**. This we have done in different situations, such as using $F(\cdot)$ and $F(F(\cdot))$ in separate works. See below examples:

$$\begin{aligned} 143 &:= -1 + F(4 \times 3) &&= F(3 \times 4) - 1 \\ 986 &:= F(9) \times (F(8) + F(6)) &&= (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) \\ 1178 &:= F(11) \times F(7) + F(8) &&= F(8) + F(7) \times F(11) \\ 2585 &:= F(2) + F(5 + 8 + 5) &&= F(5 + 8 + 5) + F(2) \\ 12819 &:= 1 + F(2 \times (8 - 1)) \times F(9) &&= F(9) \times F((-1 + 8) \times 2) + 1 \\ 24297 &:= F(2 \times 4) \times F(2 + 9) \times F(7) &&= F(7) \times F(9 + 2) \times F(4 \times 2) \\ 39394 &:= -3 + 93 + F(9)^{F(4)} &&= (-4 + F(9)) \times 3 + F(9)^3 \\ 74997 &:= -7 \times 4 + F(9 + 9 + 7) &&= F(7 + 9 + 9) - 4 \times 7 \\ 87937 &:= -8 + F(7) \times F(9 \times 3 - 7) &&= F(7) \times F(3 \times 9 - 7) - 8 \\ 98703 &:= 9 \times (F(8) + F(7 \times 03)) &&= (F(3 \times 07) + F(8)) \times 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34 &:= F(3 \times F(4)) &&36 &:= 6^{F(3)} \\ 233 &:= F(F(-2 + 3 \times 3)) &&143 &:= F(3 \times 4) - 1 \\ 630 &:= F(F(6)) \times 30 &&231 &:= F(13) - 2 \\ 1178 &:= F(11) \times F(7) + F(8) &&377 &:= F(-7 + 7 \times 3) \\ 2079 &:= (-2 + F(F(07))) \times 9 &&986 &:= (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) \\ 4864 &:= F(F(4))^8 \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(4))) &&1165 &:= 5 \times F(F(6 \times 1 + 1)) \\ 8759 &:= -F(9 - 5)^7 + F(F(8)) &&1596 &:= F(F(6) + 9) - F(F(F(5 - 1))) \\ 8849 &:= -9 \times F(F(F(F(F(4)))) - 8) + F(F(8)) &&2592 &:= F(2 \times 9) + F(5 + F(2)) \\ 9349 &:= -F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + F(F(F(-3 + 9))) &&9756 &:= F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times 7 \times F(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 834660 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 0 = 0 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\ 834661 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 1 = 1 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\ 834662 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 2 = 2 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\ 834663 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 3 = 3 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\ 834664 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 4 = 4 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\ 834665 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 5 = 5 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\ 834666 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 6 = 6 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\ 834667 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 7 = 7 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\ 834668 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 8 = 8 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\ 834669 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 9 = 9 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21960 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\ 21961 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\ 21962 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\ 21963 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21964 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\ 21965 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\ 21966 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\ 21967 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\ 21968 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\ 21969 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2. \end{aligned}$$

First three blocks are in both ways. In the last block the first column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [23, 24].

3.7 Triangular Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics. The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2).$$

The examples given in above subsections are with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence** numbers, etc. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Triangular numbers**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned} 1069 &:= T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9)) & 874 &:= T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) + 8) \\ 1081 &:= T(1 + T(08 + 1)) & 0105 &:= 50 + T(10) \\ 2887 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7) & 1155 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(51 - 1) \\ 4965 &:= T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5))) & 1224 &:= T(T(T(4) - T(T(2))) - 2 + 1) \\ 4999 &:= 49 + T(99) & 2418 &:= T(81) - T(42) \\ 99545 &:= T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 5 & 99632 &:= 2 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9) \\ 99546 &:= T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 6. & 99633 &:= 3 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9). \end{aligned}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{aligned} 2210 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 0 = 0 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 2211 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 1 = 1 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 2212 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 2 = 2 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 2213 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 3 = 3 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 2214 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 4 = 4 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 2215 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 5 = 5 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 2216 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 6 = 6 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 2217 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 7 = 7 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 2218 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 8 = 8 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\ 2219 &:= T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 9 = 9 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))). \end{aligned}$$

For more details see author's work [21, 31].

3.8 Binomial Coefficients

Binomial coefficients are well known in literature. They are given by

$$C(m, r) = \frac{m!}{r! \times (m - r)!}, \quad m \geq r \geq 0, \quad m, r \in \mathbb{N}.$$

In above subsections, we gave examples of selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, etc. Still, one can have similar kind results using **binomial coefficients**. See below some examples written in **both ways**, **digit's order** and **reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{6435} &:= C(C(6, 4), 3 + 5) &= C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4} + 6) \\ \mathbf{15504} &:= C(15 + 5, 0! + 4) &= C(4 \times 05, 5 \times 1) \\ \mathbf{42504} &:= C(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4}) &= C(4!, -05 + 24) \\ \mathbf{54264} &:= C(5 + 4^2, C(6, 4)) &= C(4! - 6/2, (\sqrt{4} + 5)!) \\ \mathbf{74613} &:= C(7 \times 4 - 6, 1 \times 3!) &= C(3! + 16, (-4 + 7)!). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{12650} &:= C(-1 + 26, 5 - 0!) & \mathbf{28} &:= C(8, 2) \\ \mathbf{12870} &:= C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7 + 0!) & \mathbf{792} &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7) \\ \mathbf{14950} &:= C(-1 + 4! + \sqrt{9}, 5 - 0!) & \mathbf{924} &:= C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!) \\ \mathbf{18564} &:= C(18, (5 - 6 + 4)!) & \mathbf{2024} &:= C(4!, 2 + (0 \times 2)!) \\ \mathbf{19448} &:= C(19 - \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4} + 8) & \mathbf{4845} &:= C(5 \times 4, 8 - 4) \\ \mathbf{26334} &:= C(2 + C(6, 3), 3 + \sqrt{4}) & \mathbf{00378} &:= C(C(8, \sqrt{7-3}), 0! + 0!) \\ \mathbf{43758} &:= C(4! - 3!, 7 - 5 + 8) & \mathbf{00792} &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7 - 0! - 0!) \\ \mathbf{53130} &:= C(5^{3-1}, 3! - 0!). & \mathbf{00924} &:= C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0! + 0!)). \end{aligned}$$

Consecutive sequential representations:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{25920} &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 0 & \mathbf{98280} &:= 0 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ \mathbf{25921} &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 1 & \mathbf{98281} &:= 1 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ \mathbf{25922} &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 2 & \mathbf{98282} &:= 2 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ \mathbf{25923} &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 3 & \mathbf{98283} &:= 3 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ \mathbf{25924} &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 4 & \mathbf{98284} &:= 4 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ \mathbf{25925} &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 5 & \mathbf{98285} &:= 5 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ \mathbf{25926} &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 6 & \mathbf{98286} &:= 6 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ \mathbf{25927} &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 7 & \mathbf{98287} &:= 7 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ \mathbf{25928} &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 8 & \mathbf{98288} &:= 8 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ \mathbf{25929} &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 9. & \mathbf{98289} &:= 9 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}). \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [22].

3.9 Binomial Coefficients and Triangular Numbers: Basic Operations

Below are some examples of selfie numbers written by use of **binomial coefficients and triangular numbers with basic operations** together.

$231 := T(T(C(2 \times 3, 1)))$	$286 := C(T(6) - 8, T(2))$
$241 := T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(C(4, 1))$	$0139 := C(9, 3) + T(10)$
$1535 := T(T(C(1 \times 5, 3))) - 5$	$1588 := -8 + T(C(8, 5) \times 1)$
$1561 := T(T(T(-1 + 5))) + T(C(6, 1))$	$5026 := C(T(5), T(T(02))) + T(6)$
$2922 := -T(2) + C(T(2) \times 9, T(2))$	$01754 := C(T(4), 5) \times 7 - 10$
$12256 := -T(T(-1 + T(T(2)))) + C(2 + T(5), 6)$	$01755 := T(5) \times C(T(5), 7) / T(10)$
$12339 := (C(-1 + T(T(T(2))), 3) + T(T(T(3)))) \times 9$	$13992 := T(T(2)) + T(T(9) - 9) \times T(T(C(3, 1)))$
$17432 := C(17, T(4)) - T(T(T(3)) \times T(2))$	$17155 := 5 \times (C(T(5) - 1, 7) - 1)$
$18647 := C(18, 6) + T(T(4)) + T(7)$	$22718 := T(8) \times (1 + T(C(7, T(2)))) + 2$
$28593 := (T(T(2)) \times T(C(8, 5)) - T(9)) \times 3$	$26943 := (C(T(T(3)), 4) \times 9 + T(6)) / 2$
$62397 := T(T(T(6)) / T(2)) \times T(T(3)) - T(C(9, 7))$	$46512 := C(T(T(T(2))) - 1, 5) \times T(6 - 4)$
$98752 := T(T(9) - 8) + C(T(7), 5) - T(T(T(T(2))))$	$52946 := T(T(6)) - T(T(T(4))) - 9 + C(T(T(T(2))), T(5))$
$99315 := T(T(9)) + C(9 \times 3 + 1, 5)$	$53484 := -T(4) \times T(8 + 4) + C(T(T(3)), T(5))$
$99945 := -T(C(9, 9) + 9) + T(4)^5$	$98317 := C(T(7), -1 + T(3)) - 8 + T(9)$

First column values are in digit's order and second column values are in reverse order of digits. Below are symmetric blocks of values in digit's order and reverse order of digit's.

$21420 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 0 = 0 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$
$21421 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 1 = 1 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$
$21422 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 2 = 2 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$
$21423 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 3 = 3 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$
$21424 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 4 = 4 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$
$21425 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 5 = 5 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$
$21426 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 6 = 6 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$
$21427 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 7 = 7 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$
$21428 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 8 = 8 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$
$21429 := T(T(2)) \times T(C(-1 + T(4), T(2))) + 9 = 9 + T(T(2)) \times T(C(T(4) - 1, T(2)))$

For more details refer author's work [34].

3.10 Binomial Coefficients and Triangular Numbers: Square-Root

Below are some examples of selfie numbers written by use of **binomial coefficients and triangular numbers with square-root** together.

3.10.1 Digit's Order

$$\begin{aligned}429 &:= - \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) - \left(T(29) \right) \right) \right) \\441 &:= \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{C(4,1)}} \\1329 &:= \left(- (1) + C \left(T((3 \times 2)), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\1491 &:= \left(T \left((-1) + T(T(4)) \right) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{C(9,1)} \right) \\1554 &:= \left((-1 + T(5)) + T \left(T \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\1585 &:= -\sqrt{1 + T(T(5))} + T(C(8,5)) \\4520 &:= \left(\left(T \left(T \left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) - 5 \right) \times 20 \\14399 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(C(T(4), 3) \times T \left(\left(T(9) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\14534 &:= \left(- (1) + \left(T \left(\sqrt{4} \right) \times C \left(\left(T(T(5)) / T(3) \right), 4 \right) \right) \right) \\39732 &:= \left(T(T(3)) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times T(C(7,3)) \right) + 2 \right) \right) \\48659 &:= - \left(\left(T(T(4)) + \left((- T(C(8,6))) \times T(T(5)) \right) + T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\53886 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T(5) + T(3) \right), \sqrt{T(8)} \right) - T \left(\left(\sqrt{T(8)} + T(6) \right) \right) \right) \\56349 &:= \left(5 + C(T(6), T(3)) \right) + T \left(\left(4^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \\74949 &:= \left(T(7) + T(T(4)) \right) \times T \left(\left(C(9,4) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\92973 &:= \left(C \left(\left(T \left(T \left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - 2 \right), 9 \right) + T \left(\left(T(7) + T(3) \right) \right) \right) \\98285 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - (8 + C(28,5)) \right) \right) \\ \\26460 &:= T(T(2)) \times C \left(T(6), \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(6) + 0 \\26461 &:= T(T(2)) \times C \left(T(6), \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(6) + 1 \\26462 &:= T(T(2)) \times C \left(T(6), \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(6) + 2 \\26463 &:= T(T(2)) \times C \left(T(6), \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(6) + 3 \\26464 &:= T(T(2)) \times C \left(T(6), \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(6) + 4 \\26465 &:= T(T(2)) \times C \left(T(6), \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(6) + 5 \\26466 &:= T(T(2)) \times C \left(T(6), \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(6) + 6 \\26467 &:= T(T(2)) \times C \left(T(6), \sqrt{4} \right) \times T(6) + 7\end{aligned}$$

$$26468 := T(T(2)) \times C(T(6), \sqrt{4}) \times T(6) + 8$$

$$26469 := T(T(2)) \times C(T(6), \sqrt{4}) \times T(6) + 9$$

3.10.2 Reverse Order of Digits

$$354 := \left((-\sqrt{4}) + T(T(5)) \right) \times 3$$

$$924 := C(4 \times T(2), T(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$0748 := T(T(8) + \sqrt{4}) + (7 + 0)$$

$$0945 := C(T(5), \sqrt{4}) \times (9 + 0)$$

$$1287 := C\left(7 + \sqrt{T(8)}, (T(T(2)) - 1)\right)$$

$$1329 := \left(C\left(T\left(\sqrt{C(9,2)}\right), 3\right) - 1 \right)$$

$$1344 := \left(4^{T(\sqrt{4})} \times T(T(C(3,1))) \right)$$

$$2648 := T(T(8) \times \sqrt{4}) + C(6, T(2))$$

$$02457 := \left((C(T(7), 5) / \sqrt{4}) / 20 \right)$$

$$13564 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times ((C(T(6), 5) / 3) - 1) \right)$$

$$17898 := \left(C\left(\sqrt{T(8) \times 9}, \sqrt{T(8)}\right) - T(T((7 + 1))) \right)$$

$$24992 := \left(2 - \left(T(C(9, \sqrt{9})) \times (-4 - T(2)) \right) \right)$$

$$33894 := \left(\left((\sqrt{4} \times 9) + T(C(8, 3)) \right) \times T(T(3)) \right)$$

$$53834 := \left(C\left(T(T(T(\sqrt{4}))), T(3)\right) - (T((8 + T(T(3)))) - 5) \right)$$

$$58993 := \left(\left((3^9) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - (C(8, 5)) \right)$$

$$93794 := \sqrt{C(4, \sqrt{9})} + T(T(7)) \times T(T(T(3))) + T(\sqrt{9})$$

$$24570 := 0 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2)$$

$$24571 := 1 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2)$$

$$24572 := 2 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2)$$

$$24573 := 3 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2)$$

$$24574 := 4 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2)$$

$$24575 := 5 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24576 &:= 6 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2) \\ 24577 &:= 7 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2) \\ 24578 &:= 8 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2) \\ 24579 &:= 9 + C(T(7), 5) / (\sqrt{4} \times 2) \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [35].

3.11 S-gonal numbers

The formula for **S-gonal numbers** is given by

$$P(n, s) := \frac{n(n-1)(s-2)}{2} + n, \quad s > 2.$$

This subsection brings some examples of selfie numbrs using **S-gonal numbers**. These examples are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned} 4992 &:= P(4!, 9 + 9 + 2) & 8967 &:= 7 \times P(P(6, \sqrt{9}), 8) \\ 7744 &:= (P(7, 7) - 4!)^{\sqrt{4}} & 9504 &:= 4! \times P(\sqrt{0! + 5!}, 9) \\ 7896 &:= 7 \times P(8 \times \sqrt{9}, 6) & 9744 &:= 4! \times P(4 \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \\ 65485 &:= -P(6, 5) + \sqrt{4} \times 8^5 & 49281 &:= 1 \times 8! + P(29, 4!) \\ 65943 &:= P(6, 5) \times ((\sqrt{9})!^4 - 3) & 49548 &:= -8! - P(4!, 5) + 9!/4 \\ 67977 &:= (6 + 7) \times (P(9, 7) + 7!) & 50424 &:= 4! \times P(-2 + 4!, \sqrt{0! + 5!}) \\ 72495 &:= -P(7 + 2, 4) + 9!/5 & 52895 &:= (5 + P(9, 8))^2 - 5 \\ 83544 &:= \sqrt{P(8, 3)} \times (5! - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}} & 53995 &:= (5! - P(9, \sqrt{9})) \times 3!! - 5. \end{aligned}$$

The consecutive sequential examples are given by

$$\begin{aligned} 86640 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 0 & 5640 &:= 0 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\ 86641 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 1 & 5641 &:= 1 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\ 86642 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 2 & 5642 &:= 2 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\ 86643 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 3 & 5643 &:= 3 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\ 86644 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 4 & 5644 &:= 4 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\ 86645 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 5 & 5645 &:= 5 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\ 86646 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 6 & 5646 &:= 6 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\ 86647 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 7 & 5647 &:= 7 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\ 86648 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 8 & 5648 &:= 8 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\ 86649 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 9 & 5649 &:= 9 + P(4!, 6) \times 5. \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [17].

3.12 Centered Polygonal Numbers

The formula for **centered polygonal numbers** is given by

$$K(n, t) := \frac{tn(n-1)}{2} + 1, \quad t > 2.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **centered polygonal numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inverse order of digits**:

<p>2883 := $K(2 \times 8, 8) \times 3$ 2888 := $K(2 + 8, 8) \times 8$ 3640 := $K(3!, 6) \times 40$ 14939 := $-1 + (K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 3) \times 9$ 14959 := $(-1 + K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 5) \times 9$ 15144 := $K(15, (-1 + 4)!) \times 4!$ 15347 := $(-1 + 5)! \times 3!! - K(4!, 7)$ 15399 := $K(1 \times 5!/3!, 9) \times 9$</p>	<p>00938 := $K(\sqrt{K(8, 3!)}, (\sqrt{9})!) \times (0! + 0!)$ 01051 := $K(15, 010)$ 01199 := $K(9, \sqrt{9}) \times (1 + 10)$ 59938 := $K(8, 3!) + (\sqrt{9})!! + 9^5$ 62424 := $4! \times K(2 + 4!, 2 + 6)$ 63384 := $4! + (K(8, 3) + 3) \times 6!$ 63744 := $4! \times (K(4!, 7) + 3 + 6!)$ 63973 := $K(3! + 7, 9) \times K(3!, 6)$.</p>
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The consecutive sequential examples are given by

99360 := $K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 0 = 0 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$
99361 := $K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 1 = 1 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$
99362 := $K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 2 = 2 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$
99363 := $K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 3 = 3 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$
99364 := $K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 4 = 4 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$
99365 := $K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 5 = 5 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$
99366 := $K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 6 = 6 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$
99367 := $K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 7 = 7 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$
99368 := $K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 8 = 8 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$
99369 := $K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 9 = 9 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$.

For more details refer author's work [17].

3.13 Quadratic-Type Selfies

The formula for **quadratic numbers** is given by

$$Q(n) := n^2, \quad n > 0, n \in \mathbf{N}.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **quadratic-type selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inverse order of digits**:

$48 := -Q(4) + Q(8)$ $81 := Q(8 + 1)$ $128 := 1 \times 2 \times Q(8)$ $292 := Q(Q(Q(2))) + 9 \times Q(2)$ $322 := Q(Q(3) \times 2) - 2$ $1036 := 10^3 + Q(6)$ $1125 := Q(11 + Q(2)) \times 5$ $1729 := 1 \times 7 \times (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 9)$ $9843 := (Q(-9 + Q(8)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 3$ $10025 := 100^2 + Q(5)$ $10384 := (-1 + Q(Q(03))) \times 8 \times Q(4)$ $99378 := 9 \times (Q(93) + Q(Q(7))) - 8$	$49 := Q(-9 + Q(4))$ $89 := Q(9) + 8$ $224 := (Q(4) - 2) \times Q(Q(2))$ $275 := Q(5) \times (7 + Q(2))$ $736 := Q(Q(6) - Q(3)) + 7$ $0107 := 7 + Q(010)$ $0231 := -Q(13) + Q(20)$ $1257 := 7 + Q(Q(5)) \times 2 \times 1$ $2239 := -Q(9) + Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(2))$ $08136 := Q(6) + Q(Q(3) + 1 + 80)$ $99712 := Q(Q(2)) \times 1 \times (Q(79) - 9)$ $37293 := -3 + (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(2)) - Q(Q(7))) \times Q(3).$
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First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 12680 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 0 = 0 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12681 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 1 = 1 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12682 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 2 = 2 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12683 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 3 = 3 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12684 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 4 = 4 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12685 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 5 = 5 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12686 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 6 = 6 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12687 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 7 = 7 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12688 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 8 = 8 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12689 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [25].

3.14 Cubic-Type Selfies

The formula for **cubic numbers** is given by

$$U(n) := n^3, \quad n > 0, n \in \mathbf{N}.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **cubic-type selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{array}{ll} \mathbf{125} := 1^2 \times U(5) & \mathbf{512} := U(2 + 1 + 5) \\ \mathbf{522} := 5 \times 2 + U(U(2)) & \mathbf{991} := (U(1 + 9) - 9) \\ \mathbf{991} := -9 + U(9 + 1) & \mathbf{0235} := 5 \times (U(3) + 20) \\ \mathbf{1371} := (1 + 3) \times U(7) - 1 & \mathbf{0263} := U(3) + U(6) + 20 \\ \mathbf{1715} := 1 \times U(7) \times 1 \times 5 & \mathbf{1735} := 5 \times (3 + U(7) + 1) \\ \mathbf{2587} := -U(2) + 5 \times (U(8) + 7) & \mathbf{5974} := -4 + 7 \times (U(9) + U(5)) \\ \mathbf{9945} := U(9) + 9 \times 4^5 & \mathbf{00157} := -U(7) + 5 \times 100 \\ \mathbf{10125} := (10 - 1)^2 \times U(5) & \mathbf{01928} := 8 \times (U(U(2)) + U(9) - U(10)) \\ \mathbf{16444} := U(16) \times 4 + U(4) - 4 & \mathbf{45194} := -4 + U(9) \times (1 + U(5) - U(4)) \\ \mathbf{30375} := U(30) + U(3 + 7 + 5) & \mathbf{99535} := 5 \times (U(U(3)) + U(5) + 99) \\ \mathbf{99873} := U(9) \times (9 + U(8)/(7 - 3)) & \end{array}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{array}{l} \mathbf{22950} := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 0 = 0 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2))) \\ \mathbf{22951} := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 1 = 1 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2))) \\ \mathbf{22952} := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 2 = 2 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2))) \\ \mathbf{22953} := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 3 = 3 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2))) \\ \mathbf{22954} := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 4 = 4 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2))) \\ \mathbf{22955} := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 5 = 5 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2))) \\ \mathbf{22956} := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 6 = 6 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2))) \\ \mathbf{22957} := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 7 = 7 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2))) \\ \mathbf{22958} := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 8 = 8 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2))) \\ \mathbf{22959} := (-2 + U(U(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 9 = 9 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + U(U(2))) \end{array}$$

For more details refer author's work [25].

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